

D 5.1

Stakeholder Reports

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| LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Full Text
GENERAL	
LC	Local Coalition
TFMUT	T-Factor Meanwhile Use Toolbox
WP	Work Package
AMSTERDAM Science Park	
ASP	Amsterdam Science Park
UvA	University of Amsterdam
NOW	National Research Organisation
BILBAO Zorrozaurre	
PEOU	Plan Especial de Ordenación Urbana
DUSI	Plan de Implementación del Desarrollo Urbano Sostenible e Integrado
KAUNAS Aleksotas	
AIIP	Aleksotas Innovation Industry Park
KTU	Kaunas University of Technology
VMU	Vytautas Magnus University
LISBON Trafaria	
CMA	Almada Municipality
EDA	Diálogos e Ensaios Associação
FCT	Faculdade de Ciências e Tecnologia
FCSH	Faculdade de Ciências Sociais e Humanas
IAT	Institute of Art & Technology
IAT@T	Institute of Art & Technology in Trafaria
UNL	NOVA University of Lisbon
LONDON Euston	
CC	Community Champions
CIG	Community Interest Group
CoP	Community of Practice

CSS	Citizen Social Scientists
EAP	Euston Area Plan
FYA	Fitzrovia Youth in Action
HS2	High Speed Rail 2
KQ	Knowledge Quarter
MDP	Master Development Planner
MUWG	Meanwhile Use Working Group
OSD	Over Station Development
RAG	Residents Advisory Group
STCA	Somers Town Community Association
STEAM	Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts & Maths
UAL	University of Arts London
MILAN MIND	
LL	Lendlease
OHM	Open House Milano
MIND	Milan Innovation District

| TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABOUT THIS DOCUMENT	6
INTRODUCTION	7
1. AMSTERDAM SCIENCE PARK	12
1.1. PILOT STARTING CONTEXT AND PRIORITIES	12
1.1.1. Issues	14
1.1.2. Challenges and Opportunities	15
1.1.3. Needs	20
1.2. MEANWHILE SPACES AND USES	20
1.2.1. Existing Meanwhile Spaces and Uses	20
1.2.2. Planned Meanwhile Spaces and Uses	25
1.3. ENGAGEMENT, EXPLORING AND INQUIRING, SUPPORT ACTIVITIES	26
1.3.1. Existing and Planned Engagement Activities	27
1.3.2. T-Factor Exploring and Inquiring Activities	32
1.3.3. Exploring and Inquiring Support Activities and T-Labs Probes	53
1.3.4. Overview of Stakeholders	64
1.4. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS	67
2. BILBAO ZORROZAURRE	71
2.1. PILOT STARTING CONTEXT AND PRIORITIES	71
2.1.1. Issues	72
2.1.2. Challenges and Opportunities	74
2.1.3. Needs	77
2.2. MEANWHILE SPACES AND USES	78
2.2.1. Existing Meanwhile Spaces and Uses	78
2.2.2. Planned Meanwhile Spaces and Uses	83
2.3. ENGAGEMENT, EXPLORING AND INQUIRING, SUPPORT ACTIVITIES	84
2.3.1. Existing and Planned Engagement Activities	84
2.3.2. T-Factor Exploring and Inquiring Activities	85
2.3.3. Exploring and Inquiring Support Activities and T-Labs probes	93
2.3.4. Overview of Stakeholders	98
2.4. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS	99
3. KAUNAS ALEKSOTAS	102
3.1. PILOT STARTING CONTEXT AND PRIORITIES	102
3.1.1. Issues	103
3.1.2. Challenges and Opportunities	105
3.1.3. Needs	106
3.2. MEANWHILE SPACES AND USES	106
3.2.1. Existing Meanwhile Spaces and Uses	107
3.2.2. Planned Meanwhile Spaces and Uses	111
3.3. ENGAGEMENT, EXPLORING & INQUIRING, SUPPORT ACTIVITIES	121
3.3.1. Existing and Planned Engagement Activities	122
3.3.2. T-Factor Exploring & Inquiring activities	125
3.3.3. Exploring and Inquiring Support Activities and T-Lab Probes	126
3.3.4. Overview of Stakeholders	135
3.4. CONCLUSIONS & NEXT STEPS	138

4. LISBON TRAFARIA	141
4.1. PILOT STARTING CONTEXT AND PRIORITIES	141
4.1.1. Issues	143
4.1.2. Challenges and Opportunities	144
4.1.3. Needs	145
4.2. MEANWHILE SPACES AND USES	145
4.2.1. Existing Meanwhile Spaces and Uses	146
4.2.2. Planned Meanwhile Spaces and Uses	148
4.3. ENGAGEMENT, EXPLORING AND INQUIRING, SUPPORT ACTIVITIES	149
4.3.1. Existing and Planned Engagement Activities	149
4.3.2. T-Factor Exploring and Inquiring Activities	150
4.3.3. Exploring and Inquiring Support Activities and T-Lab Probes	166
4.3.4. Overview of Stakeholders	169
4.4. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS	170
5. LONDON EUSTON	173
5.1. PILOT STARTING CONTEXT AND PRIORITIES	173
5.1.1. Issues	175
5.1.2. Challenges and Opportunities	179
5.1.3. Needs	182
5.2. MEANWHILE SPACES AND USES	183
5.2.1. Existing Meanwhile Spaces and Uses	184
5.2.2. Planned Meanwhile Spaces and Uses	188
5.3. ENGAGEMENT, EXPLORING & INQUIRING, SUPPORT ACTIVITIES	196
5.3.1. Existing and Planned Engagement Activities	197
5.3.2. T-Factor Exploring and Inquiring Activities	211
5.3.3. Exploring and Inquiring Support Activities and T-Lab Probes	228
5.3.4. Overview of Stakeholders	256
5.4. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS	258
6. MILAN MIND	262
6.1. PILOT STARTING CONTEXT AND PRIORITIES	262
6.1.1. Issues	263
6.1.2. Challenges and Opportunities	264
6.1.3. Needs	266
6.2. MEANWHILE SPACES AND USES	267
6.2.1. Existing Meanwhile Spaces and Uses	268
6.2.2. Planned Meanwhile Spaces and Uses	270
6.3. ENGAGEMENT, EXPLORING AND INQUIRING, SUPPORT ACTIVITIES	273
6.3.1. Existing and Planned Engagement Activities	273
6.3.2. T-Factor Exploring and Inquiring Activities	280
6.3.3. Exploring and Inquiring Support Activities and T-Labs Probes	280
6.3.4. Overview of Stakeholders	298
6.4. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS	300

ABOUT THE DOCUMENT

This document reports on the Exploring and Inquiring stage of the T-Factor Pilots: a programme of action research focused on the participatory planning and implementation of meanwhile uses in the context of six early-stage urban regeneration projects across different European cities. This report **describes the activities developed within this stage of the project and the findings surfaced through the implementation of these activities.**

A Stakeholder Report has been produced for each of the Pilots: Amsterdam Science Park (Amsterdam), Zorrozaurre (Bilbao), Aleksotas (Kaunas), Trafaria (Lisbon), Euston (London), MIND (Milan).

Each Stakeholder Report describes:

- the starting context and priorities of the Pilot, including the issues¹, challenges², opportunities³ and needs⁴ associated with each of the Pilot regeneration areas;
- the meanwhile spaces and uses that are already in existence, those that are planned and any further opportunities that exist for future meanwhile uses;
- the engagement activities associated with the regenerations that are already in existence, those that are planned and the actors that are engaged. It also identifies those stakeholders who are not yet engaged;
- the Pilot Support Plan activities that each Pilot has designed and delivered (in collaboration with Agency and T-Lab partners) to engage stakeholders in Exploring and Inquiring into the issues, challenges, opportunities and needs prioritised by each Pilots' local coalition (LC).
- the findings relating to the meanings, perceptions and values that different actors attribute to the area in relation to the issues, challenges, opportunities and needs identified.

These Stakeholder Reports are brought together within this document, in alphabetical order.

¹ Issues: Thematic topics of interest/concern that could be explored and addressed through various means (e.g. circular economy, healthy diets, green space, etc).

² Challenge: A concrete situation that requires effort in order to be addressed successfully and prevent a negative impact. In the context of T-Factor 'challenges' include barriers to the creation of enabling conditions for participatory meanwhile.

³ Opportunity: Potential to create positive impact by leveraging a set of circumstances. In the context of T-Factor 'opportunities' include factors that may contribute to the creation of enabling conditions for participatory meanwhile.

⁴ Needs: Defined requirements of actors within the regeneration area. In the context of T-Factor, Needs include requirements for the creation of enabling conditions for participatory meanwhile.

INTRODUCTION

The Exploring and Inquiring stage is the first step of the T-Factor transformative meanwhile approach. The intention of this stage is to support Local Coalitions' responsible for driving the T Factor approach in each of the six Pilots to:

- **Engage with the actors and themes already identified and mapped** within their regeneration area (see D.2.2. Pilots Reports, and D.2.3. Pilots Requirements). Through this engagement to **expand and enrich the understanding of the Pilots' context and the opportunities and needs** that exist for intervention through T-Factor meanwhile missions that address the challenges and goals of stakeholders.
- Develop and implement a range of activities that enable Local Coalitions (LCs) to assemble stakeholders around issues of concern, and to **explore the constellation of meanings, perceptions and values that different actors attribute to the regeneration area.**
- **Systematize findings as Stakeholder Reports** that provide inputs for the Scoping and Ideation of meanwhile missions that respond to the priorities of local actors.

Exploring and Inquiring Methodology

The Exploring and Inquiring stage is the inaugural stage of the T-Factor transformative meanwhile approach. It is a **divergent phase**, delivering an agile process that supports the Pilot Local Coalitions to uncover insights relating to stakeholder perspectives and values around the priorities defined by preceding research within the Pilots' regeneration areas.

The Exploring and Inquiring stage is **tailored to the local context of each Pilot**, responding to the contextual and processual differences between Pilots.

With support from T-Factor partners (especially those active within the projects' Agency and T-Labs⁵), each Pilots' LC has developed and implemented a **Support Plan** comprised of **Exploring and Inquiring 'activities'** (developed with support from Agency partners) and **'probes'**⁶ (developed with support from T-Labs). These activities and probes constitute a set of participatory research methods designed specifically to support Pilot LCs to dive deeper into local issues and challenges, by engaging with relevant stakeholders in ways that leverage local assets and meet local needs.

⁵ Agency & T Labs: The Transformation Agency (Agency) is a steering body and critical friend to the Pilots. It sets design-driven methods and processes that support the Pilots to implement the different phases of the T-Factor city-making process. Transformation Labs (T-Labs) provide thematic expertise to the pilots. Spanning multiple themes - arts, culture & creativity, industry 4.0, circular and collaborative economy, climate change, social innovation and inclusion, and more - the T-Labs aim to support and stimulate the Pilots towards 'meanwhile uses that are able to transform the trajectory of masterplans towards higher ambitions of sustainable, inclusive and thriving urban regeneration'.

⁶ Probes: T-Probes are exploratory activities that apply T-Labs expertise to Pilots' challenges. Within the Exploring and Inquiring stage implementing the Probes prototype the T-Labs' collaboration with the Pilots.

Key issues, challenges and opportunities formulated by Pilots' prior research within the regeneration areas provide the grounding and focus for Exploring and Inquiring.

The results of Exploring and Inquiring activities, whilst documented in diverse ways, are reported on in a common format within the Stakeholder Reports so as to enable them to be reviewed more easily. Activities are described in terms of their practical delivery. Findings relating to stakeholders' perceptions, perspectives and values are attributed to specific stakeholder groups to capture the diversity of views that may be held in relation to a specific issue. Insights regarding any enablers and barriers that are observed to affect stakeholders' ability to address goals and challenges are reported according to their contribution to relational, operational, and strategic infrastructuring⁷. In this way, Exploring and Inquiring 'activities' and 'probes' seek to uncover and build transformative potential in their means and ends, aligning with stakeholder agendas and priorities, assembling stakeholders into thematic coalitions around issues of interest and concern, and creating enabling conditions for participatory meanwhile uses within the Pilot areas.

Agency Workstream

Linked to D4.2. Exploring and Inquiring Tools, Agency partners reviewed the engagement activities described within the **Advance Cases Portfolio (D2.1)** and harvested those activities and tools that might be useful to Pilots for Exploring and Inquiring into the perceptions, meanings, and values attributed to the regeneration areas by local stakeholders. Agency partners also contributed relevant activities and tools developed through their own precedent practices and research activities. Lessons learnt about the strengths and weaknesses of different approaches to stakeholder engagement were also gathered from Agency partners and the wider T-Factor project and documented as stories. These stories, activities and tools were brought together to create the first iteration of the **T-Factor Meanwhile Use Toolbox**⁸.

Agency x Pilots Workstream

To enable the Agency to support the Pilots most effectively, each Pilot was assigned a member of the Agency team. This person is referred to as the '**Bridger**'. Their role is to 'bridge' between the Pilot they support and those within the T Factor consortium with knowledge and expertise that may be useful to the Pilot. Those with knowledge to share with Pilots are referred to as the '**Knowledge Bearers**'.

To familiarise themselves with the Pilots context the 'Bridgers' reviewed the findings of the **Pilot Diagnostic** interviews (delivered by the Agency lead), the **Pilots Report (D2.2)** which

⁷ The work of creating socio-technical resources that intentionally enable adoption and appropriation beyond the initial scope of the design, a process that might include participants not present during the initial design' (Le Dantec and DiSalvo, 2013).

Relational infrastructuring - these are actions and activities that create shared trust and value aimed at building generative networks and relationships between the range stakeholders within the development area.

Operational infrastructuring - these are actions and activities that develop and build capacity and where participation within the process develops knowledge and resource within the stakeholder network within the development area

Strategic infrastructuring - these are actions and activities that break institutional silos, align agendas and combine resources of stakeholders within the development area.

⁸ Available at: <https://hub.t-factor.eu/toolbox/>

summarises the research of WP2 into the six Pilots' contexts, and the **Pilots Requirements Report (D2.3)** which compliments D2.2 with a focused review of the essential regulatory, technical, legal and organisational requirements for the temporary use of the areas under regeneration. Next, 'Bridgers' visualised their understanding of the Pilots context with the use of **'Bridging Canvases'** – early iterations of the Exploring and Inquiring Tools developed within D4.2 Exploring and Inquiring Tools. Finally, the results of this validation were synthesised within Exploring and Inquiring Presentations to ensure a shared understanding of the Pilots' context between Pilot LCs, their 'Bridgers' and, through them, the relevant T-Labs and Agency 'Knowledge Bearers'. These results also provided inputs for the Agency to develop **'Kumu maps'** - visualisations of the starting context of each of the Pilots showing the connections between actors, issues, and activities within the six Pilot areas.

Having established a common understanding of the issues, challenges, opportunities and needs of the Pilots the 'Bridgers' identified which of the Toolbox activities may be of most interest to Pilots. 'Bridgers' worked with Pilots to select the activities that they felt might be useful to inspire and support Exploring and Inquiring activities within their Pilots context. These 'activities' of interest were brought together as a 'long list' of support activities for each Pilot. Each Pilots' long list of support activities formed the basis for discussion at the Pilots Kick off Workshop that marked the start of the Pilots actions.

For a more detailed description of the Bridging activities see **D4.2 Exploring and Inquiring Tools**.

T-Labs x Pilots Workstream

To connect the expertise of the seven T-Labs with the concrete challenges and goals faced by the Pilots, the T-Labs Lead attended the Pilot Diagnostic interviews delivered by the Agency, so as to identify the knowledge and expertise of most use to specific Pilots. Next, the T-Labs Lead surveyed the Pilots' LCs to gain an initial understanding of which T-Labs were of greatest interest to the Pilots to support them in addressing their local challenges and goals. The results were reviewed and discussed across the T-Labs, and the Pilots' challenges were arranged within six clusters, articulated as **'matters of concern'** so as to accommodate the plural, subjective, and context specific nature of Pilots' challenges.

Next, an online workshop was held that brought together Pilots' LCs with the seven T-Labs. Pilots were asked to draw on their local context to articulate and refine the 'matters of concern' as calls to action framed as 'How might we...?' questions. T-Labs were asked to respond to Pilots' 'How might we...?' questions with proposals for exploratory activities. In this way, T-Labs and their proposed activities were matched with specific Pilots. Following the workshop, the T-Labs developed the activities of interest to the Pilots as 'Probes' – activities and tools that could help the Pilots to Explore and Inquire into the specific 'issues' they faced. Supported by Agency Bridgers, the Pilots were able to identify which of the Probes they wanted to hear more about. The Probes of interest were added to the relevant Pilots 'long list' of support activities. Each Pilots' long list of support activities formed the basis for discussion at the Pilots Kick off Workshop that marked the start of the Pilots actions.

For a more detailed description of the T-Labs probe development see **D6.2 T-Labs Editorial Plan**.

Agency x T-Labs x Pilots Workstream

Each of the Pilots selected T-Lab Probes and Agency Activities that they felt most useful to them from their long list of support activities. For the most part Agency Activities are concerned with exploring the creation of 'enabling conditions' for participatory and transformative meanwhile uses within the regeneration areas. The Probes provide support to Pilots to explore issues that resonate with the themes of the T-Labs. The selected probes and activities explored through the Pilots Kick-off Workshop. Following the Pilots Kick-off Workshop, 'Bridgers' worked with the Pilots LCs and 'Knowledge Bearers' to further develop the Activities and Probes for use within the Exploring and Inquiring stage. Finally, each of the Agency Activities and Probes implemented within the Pilots will be documented within the T-Factor Meanwhile Use Toolbox v1. Lessons learnt from implementation will be documented as 'Toolbox stories' and shared in a similar fashion. In this way, the Exploring and Inquiring activities within the Pilots evolve and extend the T-Factor Meanwhile Use Toolbox for future users.

AMSTERDAM SCIENCE PARK

1. AMSTERDAM SCIENCE PARK

1.1. PILOT STARTING CONTEXT AND PRIORITIES

Regeneration Context and Vision

The Amsterdam Science Park (ASP) is situated in the Amsterdam Eastern district and finds itself surrounded by a park, waterside, highway and train track and the neighbourhoods Indische Buurt and Watergraafsmeer. The Amsterdam Science Park campus now has the highest concentration of university science education and research organisations in the Netherlands, and one of the highest in Europe. In addition, 170 knowledge-intensive companies, from promising start-ups to multinationals, make the park a hub for education, research, innovation and entrepreneurship in the field of ICT, life sciences, advanced instrumentation, high tech materials and sustainability. The development of the park in its current science-oriented function was initiated in 1946 and has been developed in earnest since the mid 80's, with the ASP masterplan being initiated in 2003 and revised in 2019. The latter 'Development Vision' report runs until 2028, demonstrating the advanced stage of this urban area in development and existence of established practices on site. The latest update to the masterplan subscribes to the following four strategic development goals:

- Colouring: a 'programmatically coloured' area, with a certain mix of functions, which creates an optimal interaction environment, with a rich palette of qualities and facilities.
- Densification: Adding a building programme to initiate the desired 'colouring', and to give certain functions 'critical mass' so that they can have even more impact nationally and internationally.
- Interweaving: Stronger internal and external relationships through better routes in public space and traffic connections with the city and region.
- Sustainability: Showcasing the top position in science with sustainable designs and techniques that also contribute to the liveability and environmental quality of the campus.

Ecological Relevance

While the area now consists predominantly of 'built' infrastructures, with clear and easily recognisable public spaces, the site is of ecological relevance to the rest of Amsterdam and the province of North Holland. Developed with the area's agricultural heritage, ASP rests on fertile land reclaimed from the sea, at 3,5m to 5m under sea level (NAP). This soggy ground forms the basis of the present and potential types of surrounding ecosystems. The surrounding natural edges - a former polder that over the years has transformed from peat meadows and allotments to reed marsh and scrubs - adds to the characteristics of the campus; of a smooth inter world contrasted by an unpolished natural outer barrier. A barrier that - under the Flora and Fauna act, must be strengthened to serve as compensation for the building activities in and around the current campus. And - apart from its formal obligation - offers an opportunity

for the ASP, with the rough vegetation, amphibian pools and natural banks forming an attractive setting for walks, educational and leisure activities.

It is through these edges and the adjacent ecological passageway that the ASP connects the biodiverse regions in the east and south of Amsterdam with the waterways and regions to the north of the city. As such the ASP and adjoining Flevopark form the north-western tip of the Diemer Scheg"; the "green lung" of the municipalities Amsterdam, Diemen, Weesp and Gooise Mere, and receive particular attention in terms of conservation efforts and in the development of ecological structures and niches in the urban environment. The passageway is subject to multi-level governance, as part of the Municipal structure vision 2040 and is part of the 'Nature Network Netherlands' under the direction of the province Noord Holland, where it is developed within the EU framework of Natura2000.

Top-down Green Policy

With the revision of the Masterplan in 2019 the ASP aims to further advance its goal to mirror its excellence in fundamental science with a sustainable design and management of the area. Sustainability as such has become an important development and thematic pillar for further developments of the park with the recent report; 'Amsterdam Science Park natuurinclusief en klimaatadaptief' contributing to this ambition. Underlining the notion that a sustainable park and increase in the environmental quality of the area will contribute positively to the wellbeing of its users and liveability of the campus.

'Dense' vs. 'Green'

Due to its very nature of being somewhat isolated from the city, having a strong work and educational orientation and being encapsulated by static infrastructural bodies, the area attracts mainly functional visitors and users (workers, students, and some nearby residents) and is 'forced' to develop in a vertical rather than horizontal matter. To the point that the 2019 revision of the Masterplan sees the need for 'interweaving' and 'densification' as two other strategic pillars for the further development of the park. However, despite the above-mentioned top-down green policy for the park and its thematic focus on 'Smart and Green', the strategic development goals of 'densification' and 'sustainable' are in tension with each other. The increase in people, buildings and activity places the natural environment and biodiversity of the area under pressure. And while there is a willingness - on paper - to showcase the top position in science with progressive sustainable designs and techniques that can contribute to the campus' liveability and environmental quality, in practice the thematic focus on 'green' is underdeveloped. And the fear of 'boxification' is growing amongst actors and stakeholders.

Complex Governance

The Amsterdam Science Park has a tripartite governance model, with UvA, NWO and the Amsterdam municipality all being owners of the area. A rather complicated governance structure that makes for slow and diffuse decision-making processes. There is a lack of clarity concerning the game rules for temporary and small-scale initiatives, partially due to the very little involvement of the ASP Consortium. Therefore, there is a lack of vision and sustainability plan of many of the temporary use activities that start without a business case and a clear strategy for contributing to the ASP.

This governing complexity stands in strong contrast with the transparency, agility and accessibility that is present in many of the strong meanwhile initiatives and small stakeholders that are on site. This poses an opportunity for the ASP. The flexible and experimental attitudes of both these actors and organisations could be leveraged for the realisation of the green and innovative ambitions of the park.

Focus on Ecological Meanwhile Uses

Due to the long arch of development with a high level of realised masterplan uses, the Amsterdam Local Coalition made the choice to focus on ecological meanwhile uses for the ASP pilot. The rationale for this choice is that successful meanwhile uses can extend beyond classical approaches that focus on cultural and economic activities in relation to the built environment, in particular where the space for such activities has become limited as the masterplan rollout continues. With growing urbanisation and rising challenges linked to environmental degradation, a clear distinction between built and natural environments is increasingly hard to make. If anything, Covid-19, as a zoonotic virus borne from environmental degradation and spread through modern logistics, has driven this point home. Cities face complex questions in the mitigation of and adaptation to impacts of climate change. And although these developments can be daunting, they also open spaces for new and lively perspectives.

Urban Ecology

Ecology rethinks the relations of people and environment within the city, now understood as a living place co-inhabited by human and non-human forms of life. Such a city operates not by building machines that control processes, but by the mutual adaptation of living systems. Such adaptivity allows for our recognition of mutual dependencies on which to build relationships of care within the city. This shift in perspective potentially has a far-reaching impact, moving urbanism away from building and logistics, beyond people and 'man-made' material streams, to manifold ecological flows including geological, biochemical, and living entities. From this follows an analysis of the city as a compound of flexible, nested realities, spanning ecological to technological agents. And city-making as something that can be done with and by non-human forms of life. In doing so Urban ecology reframes the everyday experience of urban environments. Rather than a world filled with distant and cold objects and their antecedent stressors (social pressures, noise, air and soil pollution, etc.), urban ecology emphasises a more intimate sense of place in which our environment is acknowledged as a living home that determines our wellbeing. Hence urban ecology is grounded in a physical, experiential and personal level, calling on the innate capacity of people to relate with the living world. In its aesthetics and economics, urban ecology departs from gentrification - the traditional perspective on the development of value in urban environments - articulating in its stead a notion of liveliness that arises from working with people and environment (and with all their surprises).

1.1.1. Issues

A number of key issues are to be addressed within the regeneration area, centred around quality of life for its human and non-human inhabitants. In this section, these issues are

elaborated in order of importance, and related to the 'impact domains' identified within the evaluation framework of T-Factor.

Renew the Relationship with Urban Nature

The primary issue focused on in this Urban Ecology Pilot is the question how we can renew the relationship with nature in the urban environment, specifically at Amsterdam Science Park and its direct surroundings. This issue revolves around the nexus of green spaces, wellbeing, care and health, including human communities and biodiverse inhabitants. This issue connects to the following impact domains:

- Improving Health & Wellbeing
- Attaining sustainability
- Making Places
- Building Communities

Rethink the Role of Public Space Post-Covid-19

The secondary issue being tackled by the Urban Ecology Pilot is how we can rethink the role of streets and squares post-Covid-19 to create thriving and inclusive neighbourhoods. This issue connects topics of heightened importance and interest in the post-Covid-19, surrounding inclusivity, (bio)Diversity, (multi-species) cohabitation, quality public space/green spaces, and production landscapes. The secondary issue connects to the following impact domains:

- Making Places
- Building Communities

1.1.2. Challenges and Opportunities

The following key challenges and opportunities will be addressed through the Urban Ecology Pilot within the regeneration area. Challenges are centred mainly around topics on governance and tensions between strategic greening and densification goals while the opportunities concern the existence of strong and diverse stakeholders and meanwhile initiative on site and broad support for urban ecology policies. The challenges and opportunities are listed in order of priority with the most relevant challenge/opportunity first.

Challenge 1 - Complex Governance Structure Among Large Institutional Actors

Rather than a central organisation, ASP has a tripartite governance model, with UVA, NWO and the Amsterdam Municipality all being owners of the area. The distribution of the ownership is unique in the Netherlands, with the National Research Council fulfilling a role at ASP that is far from its overall responsibility overseeing national science funding and national research institutes. Daily management is carried out by a group of delegates from the three landowners. Next to this, the Science and Business Organisation of ASP is in charge of managing the acquisition of tenants, bringing in new partnerships and opening up the park to interested parties, next to managing smaller projects, offering personal services to small teams, outreach and communication for the Science Park. Various organisations on the NWO and UvA plots come together in two different consortia that are involved in the decision making on the green management of the area. While needs and available budgets vary, both work with the same park management company adding to governance complexities on-site.

These complicated governance structures make for slow decision-making processes. Various boards and meeting structures are set up to enhance communication between stakeholders on site but many smaller initiatives are left out of this equation. There is a lack of clarity concerning the game rules for temporary initiatives: who and how to submit project requests? To whom? Partially due to the very little involvement of the ASP Consortium. Therefore, there is a lack of vision and sustainability plan of many of the temporary use activities that start without a business case and a clear strategy for contributing to the ASP. The governing complexity in the ASP Consortium stands in stark contrast with the transparency, agility and accessibility that is present in many of the meanwhile initiatives and small stakeholders. By being 'on the ground', open to the public and of small-scale initiatives such as Anna's Tuin & Ruyte created conditions by which they can be flexible, adaptive, move quickly and be in direct communication with their user groups.

Challenge 2 - Tension Between Two Strategic Priorities - Green vs. Dense

'Densification', 'colouring' and 'sustainability' are three strategic goals in the 2019 Development Vision for ASP. The creation of a dense 'interaction milieu' can give relevant functions a 'critical mass' so that they can have even more impact nationally and internationally. However, this increase in people, buildings and activity places the natural environment and biodiversity of the area under pressure. As such these strategic approaches are in tension. There is a willingness to showcase the top position in science with progressive sustainable designs and techniques that can contribute to the campus' liveability and environmental quality, but in practice the thematic focus on 'green' is underdeveloped. And the fear of boxification is growing amongst actors and stakeholders. This tension between the human-functional need versus sustainability and biodiversity goals is also reflected in the green management of the park. With its focus on shortly cut grasses, which are considered 'safe', 'clean' and 'functional', human use is preferred over biodiversity gains of a 'wilder' seed bedding. Further developing the wilder outskirts of the park as well as nature-inclusive building on campus is touched upon within the Development vision but a fear for ecological projects that will introduce rare species who in their place can block further building developments has proven to be too strong for any meanwhile initiatives to really gain ground. Recent reports such as 'Keen on Green' and "Eingraport Klimaatadaptatie" add to this 'sustainable' focus of the (green) development vision and provide suggestions and solutions for some of the issues raised, but this far it has been difficult to make these visions and advice actionable. A distinct gap can be seen between the vision on the area level, vs. the implementation on the parcel level. The developments of the 'kavel' need to be profitable due to the high level of investment and thus buildings are often prioritised over public space or green.

Challenge 3 - Lack of Diversity in Functions, Initiatives and Underused Public Space

In contrast to most areas in Amsterdam, the use of public space in the Science Park resembles that of a business district. While vibrant with student and work-life during daytime, the terrain is sparsely used after working hours and almost vacant in the weekends and holidays, except for Cafe Polder and the area of Spark Village. Furthermore, the locality hardly provides any shelter from sun or rain and half of the area (NWO) side is closed off with a fence after 18:00. While the 2019 Development Vision does speak of the opportunities for meanwhile use of underused spaces such as parking lots and main squares - which might contribute to a livelier environment - such as exhibition spaces, a tree nursery, mobile kitchens and markets stalls -

new initiatives are yet to be developed, probably due to the lack of definition on the 'where', 'how' and 'through whom' these plans can spring into being. Access to the terrain is granted through the one main road that divides the two parts of the Science Park. This sense of isolation and inaccessibility is enhanced by the unsafe feelings that seem to be present amongst inhabitants, which are most felt around the Flevopark and cyclepath on the north-west of the park and under the tunnel that connects the park with the train station in the south.

Challenge 4 - Lack of Support from Masterplan Consortium for Small-scale Activities

The ASP consortium (UVA, NWO and Amsterdam Municipality) tends to not be involved in smaller and/or temporary projects. The area development is currently in hands of the project management bureau of the Amsterdam Municipality (who work on behalf of both the UVA and A'dam) and while they do serve as a mediating partner between the various stakeholders on site, participatory processes involving and facilitating smaller initiatives are lacking. One could say that there even exists a certain degree of reluctance amongst large scale stakeholders in approving small and/or meanwhile projects as they are often seen as equally or more time, budget and effort consuming. The fact that ASP attracts mainly temporary residents (foreign students) contributes to this issue with the concern that short-term projects are 'left behind' when the given term is over. Meanwhile initiatives such as the permaculture project Anna's Tuin & Ruigte, the various sports facilities and Buurderij Polder do attract new audiences without a direct relationship with the campus and are considered to be beneficial for support of the facilities; however, they do not contribute to the 'innovation' climate. And while potential temporary functions such as theirs are listed within the 2019 Development vision, these are currently not prioritised in the development of the park and facilitation of meanwhile activities.

Challenge 5 - Complex Web of Funding Options

The funding ecosystem in Amsterdam provides ample options within the domain of culture, green and urban developments. However, there are not a lot of budgets allocated to meanwhile uses and precisely the initiatives that are in need of additional funds, do not always have enough capacity to dedicate to the complex web of funding options. Furthermore, the existence of other festivals, organisations and initiatives who combine green with cultural policies lead to a competitive funding field - which amplifies the need for a distinctive funding strategy and program.

Opportunity 1 - Diverse and Capable Stakeholders

The Amsterdam Science Park is densely populated by highly competent organisations with diverse international communities. Creating synergies between these is part of the strategic goal of 'programmatic colouring' of the area. By mixing functions, the 2019 Development vision seeks to create an optimal interaction environment with a rich palette of qualities and facilities to draw on. Firstly, the various National Science institutions; leading scientific institutes and highly regarded research facilities. Next to these professional organisations, UVA and Amsterdam University College have brought a lively international student community. Lastly, business entrepreneurship is embedded in the campus (Startup village, 7 Matrix), interacting strongly with the research institutions. The 'Science and Business' engagement is in the hands of the eponymous foundation. Their focus is mainly on connecting corporate actors with the (otherwise relatively closed) academic community. They have a community manager who is

also involved in meanwhile activities as these enhance the attractiveness of the area to businesses. The ambition to build a big Congress Centre to attract international scientific events and participants is also considered an activation strategy for the Science Park. Furthermore, Amsterdam itself has a strong heritage of citizen participation, on top of which a new national zoning law, the 'Omgevingswet', will obligate more intensive participatory processes in development and zoning projects and a stronger emphasis on these processes in early phases of development. Although it is yet unclear how this law will impact the development of the Amsterdam Science Park, both the civic tradition of the city and the national law support the inclusive and participatory character of the intended pilot.

Opportunity 2 - Strong Policy Support for Urban Ecology Agenda

Because of the Nature Conservation Act, building activities in and around the current campus must be compensated by strengthening the natural edges of the area. Other than that, the 2019 Development vision prioritised 'sustainability' as one of two thematic priorities for the international positioning of the science park, next to big data. In addition, sustainability is a strategic goal for the development of the physical park, not just for the sole purpose of improving the biodiversity on site, but also for recreational opportunities. From a management perspective the ecological pillar would add value to the campus. For ASP, this provides opportunities for wild growth, amphibian pools, natural shores, which make up an attractive area for recreational walks, educational activities and groups that like to help with the maintenance of the area. UvA already uses these areas for research and education for students. Strengthening flora and fauna in these margins creates an interesting connection in the ecological zone of the Diemerscheg, adjacent to the Science Park. The landscape design incorporates a walking path in the margins. While the interior of the campus will also benefit from a rough green outer edge. By constructing green roofs and facades and making green pocket parks in the 'eco corridors', rich flora and fauna can be pulled inwards. The outer edges then add to the ASP identity as a green campus in an urban area.

There are more policies and advises developed in recent years that contribute to this green agenda. There is the '*Eindrapport KlimaatAdaptatie Amsterdam Science Park*' (2020) [final report on Climate Adaptation] from Amsterdam Science & Business, which was commissioned by NWO, UvA and Amsterdam Municipality - outlining the measures that are needed for a nature-inclusive and climate adaptive Amsterdam Science Park. Next to this, 2020 saw the publication of the report 'Keen on Green', developed by Merel de Klerk and Karin de Vries under the guidance of Dr. Gerard Oostermeijer from the University of Amsterdam (IBED). This report combines advice on the development of a climate adaptive park, with a survey on the perspectives of its users. Amsterdam also recently published '[Groenvisie 2020-2050, een leefbare stad voor mens en dier](#)' in which the vision of the role of nature in the current and future city is laid out. With an ambition to improve the existing greenery of Amsterdam, make it more accessible, add new green areas and better interlink the green areas in and around the city.

From Report: *Keen on Green, Making the Amsterdam Science Park Climate Adaptive.*

Opportunity 3 - Existing Meanwhile Uses with Strong Potential

The strategic 'interweaving' goal of the 2019 ASP Development envisions stronger internal and external relationships through better public space and traffic connections with the city and region. Whereby interweaving is used as a metaphor for the development of strong internal and external relations. The strong meanwhile initiatives that are already present on site contribute to the strengthening of these relations. Through their lively functions - permaculture project Anna's Tuin & Ruigte, Science Donner, Startup Village, Spark Village, Planet B - stand in direct contact with their strong user base and visitors from the rest of Amsterdam. The permaculture project is always open and adds to the networking of the park, by adding an informal walking route, while the public programs of Anna's Tuin & Ruigte, Jeugdland, Buurderij Polder and Planet B attract new crowds with no relationships to the park and hold together a network of strong, intrinsically motivated volunteers and participants. Furthermore, Anna's Tuin & Ruigte is highly valued by the visitors and as such provides an example function for the park. Contributing to the potential of successful meanwhile uses having the chance to become permanent.

The Planet B functions as a co-creation space, makers workshop, exhibition space, and residency for guest artists and researchers to support the expeditions. An environment for communities and shareholders to discuss urgent and mutual topics from various perspectives and develop inclusive creative and cultural projects. The expected outcomes are divided into 'meanwhile uses' that contribute to a socio-technical (ecological) infrastructure, ranging from 'prompt' events to regular uses including training, incubation and workshops, to 'stable', potentially permanent uses as markets, artist and community spaces.

Opportunity 4 - Existing Budgets for Various Causes

Strong funding opportunities exist in the Netherlands and the city of Amsterdam. There are funds available based on outreach and communications budgets, but also funding for culture, science, and municipality budgets. Economic development subsidies are also available in relation to urban greening in times of Covid-19 from the Municipality while commercial funding from local enterprises (datacentres, tech-scale ups, biotech) could also be attracted. Smaller scale funds for volunteer initiatives or neighbourhood projects also exist in the region.

1.1.3. Needs

The Urban Ecology Pilot defined two requirements of actors within the regeneration area. Relating to the need for informal green and open spaces for daily use and the compensation for biodiversity loss due to building activities. The needs are listed in order of priority, with the most relevant need first.

Green and Open Spaces

A primary need of day-to-day users is maintaining a green and spacious Amsterdam Science Park. This is a 'soft' need that speaks equally to a need for greenery, open spaces and informal/sheltered meeting spaces for where various users of the park can mix. As the ASP is 'filled in' and the masterplan completed over the course of the 2020s, its qualities as a parkland are constrained and, in some instances, disappear. This process of 'boxification' -although partially inevitable- should be balanced with compensation of (informal) functions that are lost, enhancing the green quality and diverse functions available in remaining open spaces.

Increase Biodiversity

A secondary need is defined by national policy requirements of compensation for biodiversity loss due to building activities, which is applicable to the development at ASP in the coming years. Additionally, significant biodiversity and climate adaptation goals have been set for the ASP. This is a 'hard need' for spaces, designs and practices to situate and implement these policy requirements.

1.2. MEANWHILE SPACES AND USES

This section provides a thorough overview of existing, planned, and potential meanwhile spaces and uses within the regeneration area over the period of the T-Factor project.

1.2.1. Existing Meanwhile Spaces and Uses

An overview of the existing meanwhile spaces and uses within the regeneration area is provided in the map below.

1. Anna's Tuin & Ruigte
2. Startup Village
3. Spark Village
4. Experiment garden UVA
5. Science Döner

Map of Existing Meanwhile Uses at ASP, Own elaboration.

Anna's Tuin en Ruigte

Anna's Tuin en Ruigte (Anna's Garden and Wilderness) was founded in 2015 and is a permaculture project named after the historical Anna Hoeve, devised and managed by (biology) students and local residents. The garden is an attractive example of a semi-stable temporary initiative on the campus. Although the organisation struggles with the fact that they barely receive any funding, it nonetheless activates a lively community of +/90 volunteers, mostly from surrounding neighbourhoods, permaculture enthusiasts from across the city, as well as ASP students. It seeks to integrate in the park governance through its board, which contains diverse senior officials from park institutions. The area where Anna's Ruigte is located is characterized by its wide waterways, which are specially constructed to drain any excess water. This is important, given that the ASP is well below ANP. In addition, the area connects the ecological passages to the ASP. The principles of Permaculture assume that nature should be allowed to take its course as much as possible. According to these principles the garden is divided into several rings, whereby the outer rings have as little human interference as possible. As such a natural progression is developed to the ruggedness and passages. The park functions not only as a garden but also as a living lab - for research by biology students of the adjacent university - and as an educational platform. Through their network of affiliated experts and volunteers' events such as workshops and tours are hosted throughout the year and the garden and workshop area are frequently used by local residents and workers for leisure walks and small lunch gatherings.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Natural
Type of meanwhile use	Education & training; Green & garden; Health spot; Food & drink; Research
Stakeholders involved and roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Gardenoperator Anna's Tuin & Ruigte; maintaining garden, managing volunteers, hosting permaculture, events & tours, advice, guidance and knowledge exchange ● Volunteers; maintaining garden, assisting events & tours ● Inhabitants & Workers; visitors
Target groups	Researchers & Academics, Makers & Artisans, Children & Families, Young people, Older people, Migrants & Refugees; Students & Pupils
Temporality	2015 – ongoing, Stable
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Shared interest on the issue 'how to renew relationship to urban nature' offers opportunity for co-organising public events, such as walks, tours and workshops. Expertise on nature observation, conservation and regeneration can be leveraged for advisory purposes and volunteers could be activated as participants for public events. Events currently organised at location, could be brought into the wider locality of Amsterdam Science Park. Initiators of Anna's Tuin & Ruigte plus core volunteers can be invited for more dedicated stakeholder engagement

	activities in the E&I phase of the project. Location itself could be used for activities and workshops.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Startup Village

Startup Village was founded in 2016 and is currently a major stable temporary function on building field 18 at the ASP. It consists of a variety of temporary containers that function as offices, workshops, presentation and conference spaces. With a total of +450 workspaces, 35 containers for future-proof start-ups, 5 containers for meeting rooms, 1 venture studio with 5 spaces. co-work + coffee place, plus outdoor picnic tables, canopy and benches the village offers a variety of functions to its users. The open and playful structure of the place, with lots of glass windows, terraces and a roof garden contrast the fixed aesthetics of the rest of ASP. The flexibility and low threshold of Startup Village have proven a valuable addition to the campus; a number of start-ups are developing into serious scale-ups. For this reason, a study is being carried out into where such start-up concepts can be given a permanent place.

Startup Village opened in October 2016 and doubled its size in no less than three years time. The village now houses over 35 companies in the field of tech, AI and cryptocurrencies, as well as some initiatives who orient themselves toward green solutions - which is in line with their ambitions to increase the percentage of sustainable initiatives. Due to its location in proximity with research institutions and corporations the village attracts entrepreneurs from all parts of the Netherlands. Startup Founder Femmie Geradts also takes part in the 'holding' of the ASP - who regularly comes together to discuss the coherence and opportunities for the ASP and its businesses. As such the Startup Village now plays a vital role on site. During Covid vacant containers and workplaces were offered to students from the neighboring UVA. With the hiring of a new event manager, community events will be organised going forward.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Natural; Industrial
Type of meanwhile use	Workspace & co-working; Education & training; Job spot; Food & drink
Stakeholders involved and roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statutory Director; Daily management • Community & Event Manager • Startups; tech, Ai
Target groups	Startuppers and businesses, Researchers & Academics, Young people, Students & Pupils
Temporality	October 2016 – ongoing, Stable Use
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Outside terrain of Startup Village can be used as temporary public space for events and workshops, while meeting spaces, vacant containers, shared community space and conference rooms can be used for indoor events. The community of users can be activated for E&I activities, especially in the domain of AI and technology. Known plans for the

	improving of public space and entrance could form the basis for collaboration on for instance public greening and making of signage.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Spark Village

Spark Village was opened in 2018 with Rochdale housing corporation. Spark Village is a small and experimental residential neighbourhood format to locate recently arrived refugees together with Dutch residences, seeking to create a community in which mutual support and social resilience play an important role. It is located adjacent to the Startup Village, and similarly takes a container-style approach to temporary building, planned as a semi-permanent function until 2028. Spark Village holds 240 container homes, 80 of which are let to students, 120 to refugees with a residence permit, and 40 for youth housing (for young people with a declaration of urgency, such as teachers, nurses, etc.). Spark is actively supported by a number of organisations to support the residents, in particular those with complex migration histories, challenges of adapting to a new context and integrating in Dutch society. Most of these organisations have left now due to Covid-19. At the same time, a strong sense of community has developed, 'a bubble' surrounding the area that can be seen as a little neighbourhood in the middle of a park that, at the eastern side, otherwise does not have residents and therefore is faced with a different user group by day (work/study) and a sense of insecurity at night. In all, the project is developing well, it has regular interaction with the park management in a monthly 'security meeting' with a broad agenda. The main challenge facing the project is its resilience and support activities after the NGO and government agencies withdraw from what remains a fragile community. For its community building activities, the village works with Academie van de Stad to support residents with organising events and gatherings.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Natural; Industrial;
Type of meanwhile use	Housing & shelter
Stakeholders involved and roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community Builders Spark Village • Inhabitants
Target groups	Young people, Migrants & Refugees; + is missing; Students & Pupils
Temporality	2018 – ongoing, Stable
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Inhabitants could be activated in E&I activities and public events. Through their cooking club and public gardening activities thematic connection can be made on the issue of 'renew relationship with urban nature', while their use of public space for gardening, sports, bbq's offers connection to the issue of 'rethink the role of public space'. Community builders and inhabitants could be invited for dedicated stakeholder engagements.

Relation to T-Factor	Engaged
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Experiment garden - UvA

Since the beginning of February 2021, a plot of grassland, situated in between the UVA main building and parking lot (nr), has been used by PHD candidate Eileen Enderle and accompanying students from UVA as an experiment garden. Here four rows of black open containers with planted vegetation (mainly grasses) are placed underneath frameworks that serve to partly cover the plants. The experiment is meant for scientific research on the effect of drought on vegetation. The plot of land is normally used as a lawn and is enclosed in the front and one side by a pedestrian area and in the back by a row of trees that function as a barrier to the parking lot. One picnic table is also present in this area. It is unclear to us when the experiment stops or how it will be continued in the coming period. Both UVA, green management organisation Interglobe are aware of the governing arrangement, however the details are unknown to the Amsterdam Local Coalition.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Streets & squares
Type of meanwhile use	Education & training: Green & garden; Research
Stakeholders involved and roles	Students Research Groups
Target groups	Researchers & Academics: Students & Pupils
Temporality	2021 – ongoing, Stable
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	The experiment garden is at this moment the only meanwhile use of land on the Amsterdam Science Park for experimental purposes - that we know of. A better understanding of the arrangements, relating to governance and maintenance, would be helpful when wanting to attain land for similar meanwhile uses.
Relation to T-Factor	No relation yet

Science Dönner

The mobile food stand of Science Donner is located at the main road and entrance of the Amsterdam Science Park on the pedestrian area, right next to the entrance of Anna's Tuin & Ruigte. While mobile the truck is not moved from location and is only coupled with a car during opening hours. Their truck is then also coupled with one standing table. From 11:00 to 20:00 Science Donner serves a variety of snacks to their visitors - mainly students, construction workers, residents and workers. The menu is simple and popular due to its low prices. Science Donner is a stable meanwhile function that has been around for over 10 years and has seen

two other locations before it was placed here. The family who operates the truck - now a son and father, are well known to all. And the owner even has his portrait hung in the UvA main building. Their clientele queues up during lunch and dinner time, with lines of people surpassing the pedestrian area - thereby blocking not only the pedestrians coming in from / or walking towards the public transport, but also the bikes on the bike-lane. Seating facilities are limited there, as are garbage opportunities. Two metal benches are placed with a garbage bin in between, which is hardly enough for all their customers. Opening hours and marketing expressions are imprinted on the outside of the truck. When interviewed, the operator expressed their ambition to grow in scale - with a new truck, diversifying their menu with more vegetarian options and becoming more sustainable, through the placement of solar panels on the roof. They are also considering hyper-local food delivery by electric step; and as such hope to employ some young students. However, a new permit from the Amsterdam Municipality is needed before this plan can be taken into action. Vandalism is low in their experience, especially compared to their colleagues in the heart of Amsterdam. Right before opening, pigeons can be seen feeding on spent bread at the back side of the truck - this is their way to use wasted resources that they bring in from a befriended bakery.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Streets & squares
Type of meanwhile use	Food & drink; Pub, bar & restaurant
Stakeholders involved	Workers, students, inhabitants, visitors; customers
Target groups	Startuppers and businesses, Researchers & Academics, Young people, Migrants & Refugees; Students & Pupils.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Due to its large clientele the stall provides access to a variety of actors on site, who can be activated for E&I activities. Through their food activities thematic connection can be made on the issue of 'renew relationship with urban nature', - specifically on the topic of health, wellbeing and cohabitation, while the use of public space by their users (for queueing, sitting, parking bikes) offers connection to the issue of 'rethink the role of public space'. Initiator and customers could be invited for dedicated stakeholder engagements.
Relation to T-Factor	Informed

1.2.2. Planned Meanwhile Spaces and Uses

The Amsterdam Local Coalition is currently unaware of any planned meanwhile uses.

Additional Opportunities for Meanwhile Uses

The regeneration area offers additional opportunities for meanwhile uses that are not yet planned.

Informal Ecology Hub

The N-E quadrant of the ASP has several grassy fields that are poor in biodiversity and are occasionally used by actors (mainly students) to meet, have lunch or a barbeque. Although most of these fields are in open spaces with wide, pedestrian roads cutting past them amid large buildings, a few are more at the edges of the park and/or shaded by trees, being preferred by actors for prompt uses. One of these spaces can progressively be transformed into an 'informal ecology hub', where a temporary structure and welcoming environment allows a mix of recreational functions, (pop-up) art exhibitions, urban ecology activities and demonstrators.

For the curation of projects, a board for informal ecology could be set up, composed of some of the small scale meanwhile actors. The board could provide expertise on issues such as biodiversity, soil use, (organic) waste management and work together on public programs. Though this board - more direct, local and transparent governing could be achieved. Most of this land is owned by either UvA or the Municipality of Amsterdam and should allow for a license to occupy both bottom-up from the green maintenance services that will endorse alternative use of the space, and top-down through the 'testing ground' policy.

Wilderness Observation Post and Path

The south-eastern fringe of the Science Park is a major ecological passageway and the designated site for biodiversity compensation for building activities. The natural space is in a relatively wild and biodiverse corner of the park that will not be developed adjacent to an unused parking lot and a road. A wild corner of the park with a large body of water, with diverse landscapes and vegetation. While not advertised as a recreational area, the area is currently sparsely used for leisure walks and nature observations - both from people from outside of the region, as well as some of the researchers on site. Concretely establishing one or more observation posts and a wilderness walkway through the area. While most terrain in this region is owned by the Amsterdam Municipality, the opportunities for the placements of post lie also within the UVA owned area of the site and as such arrangements need to be made with the Project Bureau of the Amsterdam Municipality. Funding would be combined between municipal subsidies for biodiversity and 'adoption' by ASP institutions. Both post(s) and path would be publicly accessible and provide an additional use of the area, during 'dormant' hours of the park; on weekends and holidays.

1.3. ENGAGEMENT, EXPLORING AND INQUIRING, SUPPORT ACTIVITIES

This section describes engagement, exploring and inquiring, and support activities currently ongoing, recently delivered or planned for the near future. More in detail, content is articulated into the following sub-sections:

- 'Existing & Planned Engagement Activities' describes both existing and planned engagement activities in the area that are not initiated or directly supported by T-Factor.
- 'Exploring & Inquiring Activities' describes local exploration activities run by the Local Coalition in the context of T-Factor.

- ‘Support Activities & T-Labs Probes’ describes supporting activities that are developed by the Local Coalition in close collaboration with Agency members and relevant T-Labs.
- Lastly, the section provides a general overview of the relational ecosystem of stakeholders that characterises the pilot at the time of writing this report (November 2021).

1.3.1. Existing and Planned Engagement Activities

Timeline

The timeline underneath demonstrates the existing and planned engagement activities within the regeneration area over the period of the T-Factor project. Activities are thematically grouped.

	2021	2022	2023	2024
Existing				
Public Events - Anna’s Tuin & Ruigte - Jeugdland	■	■	■	■
Community / Network events - Spark Village - Startup Village	■	■	■	■
Food related events - Buurderij Polder	■	■	■	■
Introduction days Students - UVA - AUC		■		■
Sports activities - UCS - various sport groups	■	■	■	■
Planned				
Open Day Amsterdam Science Park		■	■	■
WAAG expeditions		■	■	■

‘Green’ Related Public Events

Impact Domains

- *Improving Health & Wellbeing*
- *Building Communities*
- *Making Places*
- *Attaining sustainability*

Both youth playground [Jeugdland Amsterdam](#), situated at the outskirts of the Amsterdam Science Park, and meanwhile initiative permaculture project [Anna's Tuin & Ruigte](#) offer a variety of public events for the general public - kids, local inhabitants, students & workers - and trainings for their volunteers - gardening, soil health, trees.

Jeugdland Amsterdam: Most of the events organised at Jeugdland are aimed at the younger generations; age 8 - 12. While the playground itself is open 6 days a week, free for all children on a walk-in-base, most organised events do need a registration due to limited availability. These events are also free of charge. On average, there are about 3 to 4 events organised per month, varying from a bee-keeping course to 'zaadje > maaltijd' (seed to meal), sports days, harvest events and nature drawing. Kids can also subscribe to longer programmes in the summer.

Anna's Tuin & Ruigte: The events and tours that are organised at Anna's Tuin & Ruigte have a strong educational component to them. The tours introduce the permaculture way of working to neighbours, school kids and others who are interested, while the events, in the form of workshops, serve as a deep dive into specific skills or knowledge. A lot of time and attention is given to training the group of +/- 90 volunteers, for which they regularly host extra training programs on the Sunday and organise a weekly study evening on Thursdays.

Highlights of the activity	
Stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jeugdland Amsterdam • Anna's Tuin & Ruigte 	Relation to T-Factor Engaged
Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities Both Anna's Tuin & Ruigte and Jeugdland already organise events that are strongly related to the Urban Ecology agenda of the Amsterdam local coalition at the Amsterdam Science Park, making them potential ambassadors for the local Pilot's initiatives. Due to their limited size, they might be more flexible in their ability to take part in / or co-organise any exploring and inquiring activities than the large-scale stakeholders - while their strong relationship with their public - which is activated through their outreach activities and communication channels - provide a potential pathway towards reaching out to and involving local communities. Conversations are already taking place between Pilot and Stakeholders.	

Community & Networking Events

Impact Domains

- *Improving Health & Wellbeing*
- *Building Communities*
- *Making Places*
- *Cultivating innovation*

Spark Village and [Startup Village](#) both emphasise 'building community' as the core of their role and function. Other than providing living space for migrants, students and starters on the job market (Spark Village) and office space startups in the Ai & Technology domain (Spark Village), both wish to connect their users with each other. However, mingling between the two different groups is limited.

Spark Village: The inhabitants of Spark mainly organise their own events, through their self-assigned ‘community builders’, who are assisted in these activities by the Amsterdam organisation Academie van de Stad. Through this institution financial means and funds are distributed to various initiatives on site; such as those involved in the community garden or public building. Activities such as a plastic-clean-up-day, neighbour-day or a fundraiser for the Afghan community, but also birthday parties are communicated through their What’s app channel and posters in the communal building.

Startup Village: As per September 2021 Spark Village employed an event and community manager for the sole purpose of organising events for their community of tenants as well as facilitating in the production and organisation of the many external events that take place in their three main event-locations. Due to Covid, the organisation of community building events has been limited in the past 2 years. The role of the new community manager will be to increase the quantity of networking events for and amongst the tenants and work on implementing a new software tool that should enable workers to find, interact and meet each other on and offline.

Highlights of the activity	
Stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spark Village • Startup Village 	Relation to T-Factor Engaged
Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities <p><u>Spark Village</u>: Spark Village provides the most direct access to inhabitants of the Amsterdam Science Park. However, engagement fatigue is mentioned while engaging with their community managers. Their community garden might be a point of entry for engagement activities, as is their communal kitchen and the surrounding green areas which are currently maintained by the Amsterdam Municipality.</p> <p><u>Startup Village</u>: Due to the very nature of the Startup Village terrain being less heavily ‘managed’ and more hidden from sight, more freedom might be attained for organising small-scale activities in the public space as well as in their communal area. Their capabilities as event location makes them a suitable partner for the organisation of events in the future, with WAAG receiving discounts on rental prices, due to their being a tenant there. These are commercial prices nonetheless, so a good relationship is needed to create leverage when partnering. Startup Village is also frequently asked to facilitate tours over the ASP, which might serve as a potential demonstrator activity later. Through the development of the networking app, future events of the local coalition might be shared through this channel. The app will also provide more insight into actors on site, leading to a better understanding of the playing field in this part of the ASP.</p>	

Various Sports and Embodiment Classes, Events and Courses

Impact Domains

- *Improving Health & Wellbeing*
- *Building Communities*

The ASP is frequently used by various sports groups. The main location is the sports facility [UCS](#) sports, which holds fitness spaces, classrooms and a boulder and climbing wall. Other than that, outside meanwhile facilities such as the volleyball fields next to the UVA and Spark Village

and boxing spot from [Boogieland](#) and the permanent outdoor boulder installation are frequently used. In the afternoons and weekends various running, boxing and fitness groups take their space in the area. Communication about the activities is shared through leaflets on the pinboards in UCS sports facilities, cafes and other public venues on site, as well as through their websites.

Highlights of the activity	
Stakeholders Activities are organised by a wide variety of stakeholders	Relation to T-Factor To be mapped more thoroughly
Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities Both the sports facility and individual groups provide access to specific actors at the Amsterdam Science Park; namely students, workers and local residents. Insights in their usage and needs of public space might provide valuable information for intervening purposes later in the project. Through their connection to the topic of health, wellbeing and care actors might be activated to join specific exploring and inquiring activities.	

Public Food Related Events

Impact Domains

- *Improving Health & Wellbeing*
- *Building Communities*

The Amsterdam Science Park is home to a variety of bars and cafes; such as [Cafe Polder](#) and [The Coffee Virus](#), as well as meanwhile initiative [Buurderij Polder](#). All organise a variety of food and community related events for the local community.

The Coffee Virus: The Coffee Virus' main focus for organising events is community related. Through their activities as a caterer and co-host of Startup Village they facilitate commercial and community related events at Startup Village. In the past they used to organise network lunches for stakeholders in the park.

Buurderij Polder: Farm to Fork initiative Buurderij Polder extends its direct sales from local farms in the region with seasonal events for which the partner with Cafe Polder, who provides the location and various farmers and partners. These small-scale festival / market like events are meant to celebrate the new harvests and serve as a meet-and-greet between local residents and farmers in the region.

Highlights of the activity	
Stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Coffee Virus • Buurderij Polder 	Relation to T-Factor Informed
Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities Both The Coffee Virus, Cafe Polder and Buurderij Polder will provide access to local communities of inhabitants, workers and students. Through its connection with food, environment, and health,	

the actors engaged through Buurderij Polder might be activated. Knowledge and experience from The Coffee Virus and Cafe Polder might provide insights in the usages and values of the park, while their locations might serve as promotional platforms for Exploring and Inquiring activities organised by the pilot.

Introduction Week Students UVA + Various Study-specific Student Groups

Impact Domains: *Building Communities*

Every year in September the beginning of the educational year is celebrated through a variety of activities and events. New students are engaged through 'introduction weeks' where they are introduced to the campus, their classes, sports facilities and the area. Students of 2nd+ years are enrolled as facilitators and co-organisers of these events. These events are mainly organised by dedicated study-groups, such as the [NSA Amsterdam](#), which is part of UVA.

Highlights of the activity	
Stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> NSA Amsterdam 	Relation to T-Factor Informed
Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities Student organisations can provide access to students and study groups. Both user groups can provide information on the use and value of the park and can be activated as participants for public events and exploring and activities. Peak activities during introduction week allow opportunities for co-organising events and offer opportunities for meanwhile initiatives to be included.	

Planned Engagement Activities

Open Day Amsterdam Science Park

Impact Domains

- Building Communities*
- Cultivating innovation*

Open doors and behind the scenes at various organisations and locations on the Amsterdam Science Park. Hybrid online and offline events, such as lectures, tours and visits as part of the larger event 'Weekend van de Wetenschap' (Science Weekend) that takes place in Amsterdam.

Stakeholders Amsterdam Science Park (stichting Science & Business), AMOLF, ARCNL, AUC, CWI, Netherlands eScience Center, Nikhef, SURF en UvA-FNWI, Weekend of the Science
Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities Meanwhile initiatives could be included in the program of the Amsterdam Science Park open day. Visitors to the open day can be activated for experiment and inquiry activities and provide insights into the values and meanings of the ASP for people coming from outside of the park.

Programmatic partnering, collaborations and public programs could be set up for experiment and inquiry purposes through thematic coupling with the open day theme of 'open science'.

Waag Future Lab – Expeditions

Impact Domains

- *Building communities*
- *Cultivating innovation*
- *Attaining sustainability*

As a Future Lab for technology and society, Waag is researching how to create an open, fair and inclusive future. To bring about a better world, Waag works to enact practical change in the present. One of the ways Waag does this is by envisioning an ideal place called planet B. Imagine what would happen if we were allowed to completely redesign a planet. How would we do that? What would we take with us? What would we leave behind? What social, environmental, and technological structures would we build to create an open, fair and inclusive world? To explore this idea, Waag will be organising four expeditions to planet B over the next years. Each expedition consists of different programs, for example walks, workshops, dinners, talks, (film) screenings and debates. Waag’s outpost - located at Startup Village - will be used as a location for related events.

Stakeholders

Waag Society, Ministry of Culture, Education and Science, Municipality of Amsterdam.

Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities

By linking the Expeditions to the themes and goals of the Urban Ecology Pilot, additional activities can be organised through the Expeditions. The Expeditions have a wide reach throughout the Netherlands and internationally, which helps the Pilot gain more awareness and participants. Due to many of the activities of the Planet B program taking place at Waag’s outpost at Startup Village, the program will generate traction to the Amsterdam Science Park, thereby enhancing the visibility of the area.

1.3.2. T-Factor Exploring and Inquiring Activities

Timeline

	2021	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep
Activity								
AI mapping prototype								
Building as being								
Walk & Talk								
Symposium								
Zoöp Curriculum								

One-day Walk: Amsterdam Science Park							
General public							
Waag staff							
Future Festival, i.c.m. exhibition 'Dear earth'							
Street Interviews							
Speculative Writing Workshop - How to fieldnote							
General public							
Students - KABK							
Students - Wdka							
Montessori							
AUC							
Rotterdam Academy - Urban Ecology Course							
Kids Workshop - Building like/for Animals							

AI Mapping Prototype with University of Applied Sciences (HvA)

Over a five-month period, the coordinator of the Urban Ecology Pilot supervised a group of students from the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences in developing a digital mapping tool for the Pilot. This involved a number of explorations of the ASP to understand the user experience, after which the students tested various machine learning models and developed a prototype application that will be used during the pilot.

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Building Communities</i> • <i>Making Places</i>
Activity Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a prototype biodiversity digital mapping tool that combines objective and subjective data points. • Support students in understanding the mapping methodology. • Emphasise '(non-)human in the loop' design principle for Artificial Intelligence.
When/Where	Project duration: 1-2-2021 until 15-7-2021. Expeditions ASP in March 2021.
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	Waag, collaborating with HvA and six students.
Participants	Participants – engaged <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students HvA, AI minor • High School pupils (see next activity box)

Insights	<p>Key insights</p> <p><u>Students</u>: working with a group of typical béta students, it was interesting to note how a mapping tool for biodiversity was initially hard to grasp for them. They did not identify with the ‘needs’ outlined by the pilot, to connect with nature. Based on the principle of ‘human in the loop’ processes in algorithm development, the students opened to the concept as the project progressed, learning to appreciate the combination of ‘hard’ data points and subjective labels to create a semantically rich system. This showed us how the ‘need’ for biodiversity and green spaces can develop in people during a project.</p> <p>Discoveries about enabling and prohibiting conditions</p> <p><u>Relational</u>: the activity showed how a careful process of introduction can make people that have no initial affinity with the topic of biodiversity and ecology grow to engage with this viewpoint, which opens space for the pilot to engage with the ‘opportunity’ of strong and diverse stakeholders.</p> <p><u>Operational</u>: the activity builds operational capacity by furnishing a first version of a mapping tool that combines geotagged observations of biodiversity with subjective labels. This allows us to combine offline walks with generating an online database.</p> <p><u>Strategic</u>: the activity supports the development of an alternative master plan, allowing the pilot to index the living environment and relations between it and human users of the park. This is a way to face the ‘challenge’ of complex governance; providing a single interface that can accommodate various perspectives.</p>
Outputs	<p>Software</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Prototype AI system ● User manual and GitHub repository
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Insights into engagement with low-affinity partners. ● Enhancing mapping capacity pilot.

Building as Being; Symposium + Walk & Talk

Together with Waag research fellow, artist, and earth scientist Esmee Geerken, the team of the Amsterdam Urban Ecology Pilot organised a three-part **online symposium and one hybrid walk & talk event, bringing together thinkers, scientists, and designers from the field of biology, material development and sociology to discuss ‘building’ on the scale of the city, the mind and matter**. Through the talks and physical exploration of the green corridors of the Amsterdam Science Park, experts and participants collectively explored new urban design strategies.

Impact domain(s)	<i>Building Communities</i>
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Activity Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduce the T-Factor project and Amsterdam Urban Ecology Pilot to the local ASP research groups and institutions and art/science Waag audiences. • Create conditions for strengthened collaborations between the local stakeholders.
When/Where	<p>28 March - Walk & Talk</p> <p>Hybrid; streamed online + in green corridors ASP on the east side of the park right behind Spark Village.</p> <p>1 April - Symposium part 1, The City. 15 April - Symposium part 2, The Mind. 22 April - Symposium part 3, Matter. Online, streamed through Waag channels.</p>
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	<p>Activity Provider - Waag, collaborating with local (stakeholder) artist & earth scientist Esmee Geerken.</p> <p>Speakers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders: Orion Maxted and the Interactions (IAS research fellow), Prof. Dr. Wim Noorduin (Self-Organizing Matter group AMOLF, NL), Esmee Geerken (research fellow WAAG and IAS), De onkruidenier. • Non-Stakeholders: Dr. Sharon Wohl (Architecture and Urban Design, Iowa State University, US), Dr. Marie-Eve Aubin-Tam (Bionanoscience department, TU Delft, NL), Prof. Dr. Brian Castellani (Sociology department, Durham University, UK and Psychiatry department, Northeast Ohio Medical University, US).
Participants	<p>Public – informed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waag audience [newsletter - 1267 recipients] • Local stakeholders <p>Participants – engaged</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art/Science experts • Waag audience <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Walk [43 participants] ○ Symposium day 1 [60 participants] ○ Symposium day 2 [74 participants] ○ Symposium day 3 [79 participants]
Insights	<p>The activity showed the extent of interdisciplinary interest in Urban Ecology as it relates to complex systems science and to artistic practice. This connects directly to the opportunities of policy support and diverse stakeholders, many of whom share a thematic interest with the pilot.</p>
Outputs	<p>Published events - WAAG website</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://waag.org/en/event/building-being-walk-esmee-geerken

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://waag.org/en/event/building-being-symposium-part-1-city <p>Published interview - WAAG website</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://waag.org/en/article/esmee-geerkens-research-building-funny-and-absurd-ways <p>Video registrations - WAAG Vimeo</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://vimeo.com/525783573 • https://vimeo.com/529965801 • https://vimeo.com/531956586 • https://vimeo.com/537423302 <p>Screenshots of Building as Being walk & talk.</p>
<p>Outcomes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement of Waag's general public in the T-Factor program. • Research groups located at ASP are aware of Waag's Art/Science program.

Zoöp Curriculum

Zoöp is the title of an organisational model for cooperation between humans and nonhuman life that safeguards the interests of all zoë (Greek for 'life'). The Zoöp model makes the interests of nonhuman life part of organisational decision making, by including a Zoöp representative part of the boards of directors of institutions and organisations. The Zoöp concept and its key methods were developed in a public research trajectory of Het Nieuwe Instituut over the past 3 years and the legal framework has recently been formalised. Together with other proto-zoöps, institutions and organisations with the ambition to become a Zoöp, the local coalition's lead of the Urban Ecology Pilot took part in the four-day Zoop curriculum as provided by the main initiator Het Nieuwe Instituut. Through its program participants were introduced to the key topics - via lectures -, collective mapping activities and group discussions.

<p>Impact domain(s)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Making places</i> • <i>Building communities</i>
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Activity Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To understand the Zoöp model and the potential for Pilot. • To learn from the mapping activities.
When/Where	Online sessions
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	Het Nieuwe Instituut.
Participants	Engaged <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 24 institutions [art/science/education/ecology]
Insights	<p>Key insights</p> <p><u>Organizer:</u> The activity demonstrated how participatory and iterative governance and curriculum design process, with contributions from early adopters, can contribute to the build of a solid legal framework. This framework would be easy to understand and apply, supported by the early adopters, and tested in real-world contexts, thereby providing a novel solution to the 'challenge' of complex (green) governance situations.</p> <p><u>Participants:</u> The high level of engagement by the participants in the activity and strong support of affiliated organisations operating at the intersection of culture, art and ecology made clear that the 'need' for an increase in (bio)diversity and shift in perspective towards a societal diversity that equalises the rights of human and non-human actors is supported throughout the creative sector.</p> <p>Discoveries about enabling and prohibiting conditions</p> <p><u>Relational:</u> Both participants and their affiliated organisations demonstrated a strong intrinsic motivation to work towards the 'issue' of renewing the relationship with urban nature. This became apparent not only through the high level of participation in the activity but especially thereafter, with the setting up of a support network, regular check-ins through email, and physical meetings at participants' locations all without additional financial support or incentives.</p> <p><u>Operational:</u> Through the activity, the Amsterdam Urban Ecology Pilot learned that their mapping activities thus far showed close resemblance to the four modes of inquiry that are proposed by the Zoöp Institute. The modes are: Demarcating, Observing/Sensing, Characterising and Intervening. Which could potentially benefit the ease at which a Zoöp at the ASP could be initiated, while the 'opportunity' of both strong existing meanwhiles and diverse stakeholders is an asset of the area which can greatly contribute to the inclusion of well thought (bio)diverse views.</p>

	<p><u>Strategic:</u> The discussion with the leading Proto-Zoöp made apparent that support from ground owners, or being ground owner, is of vital importance for the succeeding of the setting up of a Zoöp. Amplifying the 'challenge' of complex governance - and lack of a support masterplan consortium were the main barrier for the succeeding of Zoöp ASP.</p>
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recording sessions (private)
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insight into the feasibility of the Zoöp model for the ASP area. Connection to a network of affiliated organisations.

One-Day Walk

A one-day walk, co-created by WAAG and 3 local stakeholders (Anna's Tuin & Ruigte, Buurderij Polder, Jeugdland), where visitors were equipped with an exploration set (map, conversation cards, tasks) and mapping cards that would allow them to view the park through the perspective of the 'other'. The exploration served as a conversation starter introducing the participants to non-human perspectives and histories while the mapping cards were meant as a way to investigate the values and meanings of the area to the public. Both the narrative, route, and prompts were co-created by all 4 organisations with the intent for this walk-as-storytelling-format to be further developed in the future. Both by adjusting it to a DIY format and through the collaboration with and including more local initiatives, storylines, perspectives and prompts. The walk has been organised on various occasions with different groups of visitors and is also reworked to become a DIY walk. During one of the organised sessions, the walk was extended with an outdoor exhibition with selected 'field note' posters from the graphic design students from the KABK and coupled to the Waag's Future Lab Expedition program.

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Improving Quality of Life</i> <i>Building Communities</i>
Activity Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Generate insights and ideas around how the ASP is perceived by stakeholders and the public. Validate assumptions on the topic of 'green' between T-Factor Amsterdam Local Coalition and selected (meanwhile) stakeholders. Set up a collaborative environment between the local (meanwhile) stakeholders. Understand 'willingness to participate' from local residents and the general public as well as local stakeholders. Introduce terminologies on ecology and non-human perspectives present local stakeholders to WAAG general public

When/Where	<p>Amsterdam Science Park</p> <p>03 July - General public.</p> <p>13 August - Waag colleagues.</p> <p>24 September - General public, i.c.w. Exhibition Dear Earth as part of Waag's Future Festival.</p> <p>29 September onward - DIY version of the walk.</p>
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	<p>Activity Provider: Waag, in close collaboration with Stakeholders; Anna's Tuin & Ruigte, Jeugdland and Buurderij Polder.</p>
Participants	<p>Public - informed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waag audience [1307 recipients] <p>Participants - engaged</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Walk 1 [17 participants] • Walk 2 [20 participants registered] • Walk 3 [38 participants registered]
Insights	<p>Key insights</p> <p><u>Stakeholders:</u> Through the co-creation of the walk and accompanying narrative it was interesting to note how strong all parties feel their role as advocates for addressing the 'issue' of renewing the relationship with urban nature, which they all individually already take on in their programming. The ease at which the program was developed as well as the fitting characteristics of their included areas demonstrated that these meanwhile spaces are one of the great 'opportunities' of the area.</p> <p><u>Participants:</u> Through the activity, the 'challenge' of Green v.s. Dense was explored, with participants naming the Amsterdam Science Park as 'more green than expected' after having visited the Stakeholder locations and being invited to look with and from different non-human perspectives.</p> <p>Discoveries about enabling and prohibiting conditions</p> <p><u>Relational:</u> On the 'issue' of rethinking the role of public spaces participants shared the emphasis on minimising the building volume, creating more space for animals and keeping current green patches - all fitting the 'need' of more biodiversity on-site.</p> <p><u>Operational:</u> The success of the T-Factor project will depend on the ability of the Amsterdam Urban Ecology Pilot to unite diverse stakeholders facing challenges of 'complex governance' and 'funding issue'; with lots of expertise on ecological issues and local eco-stories</p>

	<p>present, a unifying topic might be found in the shared 'need' for more biodiversity on site.</p> <p><u>Strategic:</u> The activity brought forth a strong appreciation by the public for the current green-oriented meanwhile activities on-site, with the perception of the area shifting from 'built' to 'green'. Since this does correspond to the ambition of the Masterplan, addressing these values and perceptions from the audiences, might contribute to elevate the 'challenge' of lack of support from the masterplan consortium.</p>
<p>Outputs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Images of activities ● Value Mapping Cards responding to the following questions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Do you see the Science Park as a 'natural' or 'built' environment? Is there a difference? ○ Imagine that we were to rebuild the Science Park on another planet; what would you like to take with you, what would you like to leave behind. ○ Who did you meet on your walk? Think of animals, plants, humans, materials? ○ Consider the route you took, what/whom/which place stuck with you? - make a drawing <p><i>One day walk. Photo credits: Waag.</i></p>
<p>Outcomes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Better understanding of the collaborative potential between local stakeholders. ● Better understanding of existing public engagement processes.

- Insight into the values and meaning of the built and natural environment at ASP.

Speculative Writing Workshops: How to Field-Note

Scientists, botanists and biologists like Charles Darwin have always written and drawn field notes to capture their observations about a site or specimen. These notes provide important information, but many things are left out of this type of narration. Within this writing workshop, we will collectively expand on the idea of what a field note is. Who for example is the audience of the field note? Can a field note be directed towards nature itself? Is it possible to create field notes based on a more equal dialogue, that blurs the dichotomy between the human observer and objectified nature? We would like to widen the scope as to what a field note can be, as part of an artistic and explorative practice. We start by being with and among non-human entities such as microbes, plants or animals in the Amsterdam Science Park. From these encounters, we start to explore **how the entanglement of human and non-human entities might imagine this location to be.**

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Making Places</i> • <i>Attaining Sustainability</i>
Activity Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiment with speculative writing, field-note taking and 'arts of noticing' practices. • Bring together scientists, humanities scholars, artists and the general public. • Explore and map locality and its relation to non-human actors.
When/Where	<p>Starting location - outdoor at Waag's outpost at Startup Village. Fieldwork on various locations on and around Science Park</p> <p>10 July 2021 - General Public</p> <p>02 September 2021 - 1st year Master Students Industrial Design, KABK</p> <p>06 September 2021 - 4rth year Graduation Students Transformation Design - WDKA</p>
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	<p>Activity Provider: Waag in close collaboration with two local artists, Esmee Geerken and Adriana Knouf.</p> <p>Stakeholders involved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Startup Village - provider location outdoor session
Participants	<p>Informed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WAAG audience - newsletter [1307 recipients] <p>Engaged</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1st edition [8 participants] • 2nd edition [15 students Industrial Design KABK] • 3rd edition [6 students Transformation Design - WDKA]
Insights	Key insights

	<p>Participants: The activity demonstrated interest for Urban Ecological practices from an interdisciplinary group of professionals working in the domains of the arts, sciences and humanities as well as students. The practices offered within the workshop confirmed the hypothesis of the Amsterdam Urban Ecology pilot that the 'issue' of renewing the relationship with urban nature can be raised and addressed through art practices and arts of noticing prompts, such as fieldwork and speculative writing.</p> <p>Stakeholders: The activity demonstrated the added value of outdoor work. With one stakeholder sharing the ambition afterwards to improve the specific area for these purposes, thereby contributing to the 'issue' of rethinking the role of public space.</p> <p>Discoveries about enabling and prohibiting conditions</p> <p>Relational: The offered arts of noticing prompts during the activity, alongside the sharing of the practices of the co-hosting artists, contribute to the development of a multi-voiced perspective of the area. Through its end results, in the form of audio recordings, letters, poems and drawings a new imaginary for the 'issue' 'renew the relationship with urban nature' is being created.</p> <p>Operational: The activity builds on the operational capacities of both Waag, Stakeholders, participating artists and affiliated institutions. Through combining the capacities of 'opportunity', diverse stakeholders and existing meanwhile initiatives and high-quality events can be organised with limited resources and effort.</p> <p>Strategic: The activity and its output support the Amsterdam Urban Ecology Pilot's goal of alternative mapping, with which to mobilise the 'opportunity' of policy support for green practices at ASP, as well as connecting to diverse, strong stakeholders, specifically educational bodies; eco-practices are supported within higher education (art, academia).</p>
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Images activities ● Letters & drawing ● Audio recording collective fieldnote ● +40 entries for AI mapping prototype

Fieldnote Workshop. Photo credits: Florian Geerken.

Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Insights into non-human actors on-site ● Insights into engagement activities that correspond to issue 'how to connect with urban nature'
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Street Interviews

Facilitators of Waag conducted 2 street interview sessions on the regeneration site. Following a short introduction and recap of the aim of T-Factor, the Amsterdam Local Coalition and Urban Ecology, the facilitators went out onto the streets to conduct short interviews with local actors, using a map of the ASP as a guide for stirring the conversation. The mapping is inspired by the work of LAND Italia, lead of T-Lab4.

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Improving Health & Wellbeing</i> ● <i>Building Communities</i> ● <i>Making Places</i>
Activity Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Engage with actors of ASP ● Insights value & meaning ASP, green spaces, function ● Insights into use of public space
When/Where	<p>Amsterdam Science Park, South-Eastern part - 17 June Amsterdam Science Park, Northern part, in between Science Park and Flevopark - 01 July</p>
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	<p>Waag, with inputs provided by T-Lab 4 (LAND Italia).</p>

Participants	<p>Participants – engaged [24 interviews]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students & Workers • Inhabitants • Visitors / Recreation
Insights	<p>Key insights</p> <p><u>All actors:</u> On the challenge of 'diversity of function', we spoke to a variety of different actors, from students to workers, kids, visitors and sporters. While there is diversity of use amongst the group of actors, on an individual level their usages of the park are more homogenous. Most actors defined a strict effective use of the park, meaning that they did not visit, nor had an awareness of some of the other usages and meanwhile initiatives on site. A pragmatism that was also reflected in the used pathways and routes.</p> <p><u>All actors:</u> A fear for more boxification and the 'need' for more green spaces, both for recreational and sports efforts, were shared amongst students and inhabitants.</p> <p>Discoveries about enabling and prohibiting conditions</p> <p><u>Relational:</u> The effective use of the park by its users is contrasted with a high affection and appreciation for the area. Most of the actors expressed a high 'fondness' of the area, fitting to their personal needs.</p> <p><u>Operational:</u> In addition to the lack of awareness of other functions and stakeholders on site, wayfinding was named as contributing to this issue. Considering the 'issue' of rethinking the role of public spaces this could be something that can be improved. One can also imagine that the lack of mingling amongst the various types of actors, can be challenged through the redesign of public space in a way that exchange, and interaction and natural exploration of the area are better facilitated.</p> <p><u>Strategic:</u> Both Science Donner and Anna's Tuin and Ruigte were highly regarded and the only meanwhile initiatives that were known amongst most of the interviewees. This confirmed that the 'opportunity' of existing strong meanwhile initiatives on site is shared amongst the users of the park. However, both initiatives are dependent on either financial support or permissions from both the Amsterdam Municipality in general and the masterplan consortium. It demonstrates that the 'opportunity' of existing meanwhiles and 'challenge' or complex governance need for local budgets/funding and 'support of masterplan consortium' are heavily intertwined.</p>
Outputs	<p>Article</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fieldnote Published on Waag website

Street Interviews: Maps with Notes and Comments.

Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Insights into values & meanings ● Insights to be used as inputs for Probe 1 + 2
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Biomimicry and Design project with Montessori High School

Waag facilitates a design module with a local ‘Technasium’ high school, meant to introduce students to design thinking and specifically the concept of biomimicry, by applying this idea to the Amsterdam Science Park from the perspective of Urban Ecology. Thus, a number of perspectives are formulated from the young generation on the future of the park.

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Building Communities</i> ● <i>Making Places</i> ● <i>Attaining sustainability</i>
Activity Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Educate high school students in biomimicry and design ● Develop new perspectives on ASP as a green space ● Understand engagement of 12-14 yrs with Urban Ecology
When/Where	<p>September - November 2021. 1st week of September: Participation in on-site Probe by T-Lab 4 (LAND Italia). 2nd week of September: exploration (walk) of the park, using AI tools to map the area. Two presentation and feedback moments in October & November.</p>
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	<p>Waag, together with teachers of the Technasium, supporting 60 students (12-14 years old) in developing a design project for the ASP.</p>

Participants	Pupils
Insights	<p>Key insights <u>High School students (12-14)</u>. The key insight for both groups is the issue of renewing relationship with nature is a <i>highly attractive thematic way to bring together different stakeholder groups</i>, with particular strength among younger generations.</p> <p>Discoveries about enabling and prohibiting conditions <u>Relational</u>: topics surrounding biodiversity and green spaces create a sense of connection and intrinsic motivation among participants, supporting the goal of ‘building communities’ and the ‘opportunity’ of diverse stakeholders.</p> <p><u>Operational</u>: working from a grass-roots level to connect different stakeholders in urban ecology projects works well, as it provides a common, intrinsic interest beyond practical incentives for people to work together. Building on this grass-roots fabric should help in the ‘challenges’ of complex governance and funding, by making the needs and energy of the community as aligned with the pilot visible.</p> <p><u>Strategic</u>: the motivation of the students showed how much energy is present to develop community-based green projects and spaces at ASP, both for their intrinsic value as well as to increase social cohesion and wellbeing.</p>
Outputs	<p>Creative output developed by participants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design proposals for improving Amsterdam Science Park • 100+ entries in AI mapping system <p>Concepten: gebouw voor op het parkeerterrein</p> <p>Dit concept is een tunnelvormig concept het is hol van binnen, er zitten planten aan de zijkant zoals mos om het groener te maken.</p> <p>Er zit een rond raam op het dak, zonnepanelen met groene plastic folie om het meer in de natuur op te laten gaan. Iglvorm concept Meer planten zodat dieren een beter leefplaats kunnen hebben.</p> <p>Dit is het ronde concept waarvan de zonnepanelen alleen op het hoogste punt zitten.</p> <p><i>Biomimicry and Design Project with Montessori High School</i></p>
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping perspectives of a young generation (12-14yrs)

Design-a-thon with Amsterdam University College

Waag introduced and juried a design-a-thon organised by AUC students with high school students from the greater Amsterdam area. The high school students had indicated they wanted to work on sustainability and green city. Hence the topic of the two-day design session was “Moving beyond urban food gardens: ‘green’ production spaces in the magical city of Amsterdam what else is possible?”

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Improving Health & Wellbeing</i> • <i>Making Places</i> • <i>Attaining sustainability</i>
Activity Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage with actors of ASP • Insights value & meaning ASP, green spaces, function • Insights into the use of public space
When/Where	<p>18 October: introduction & exploration</p> <p>19 October: jury</p> <p>Amsterdam University College, Amsterdam Science Park</p>
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	Waag, with AUC staff, students, and high school students from the area
Participants	<p>Participants – engaged</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AUC students • High School students (and family & friends)
Insights	<p>Key insights</p> <p><u>AUC Students</u>: were engaged with the topic of Urban Ecology, and with the Local Coalition of T-Factor. This way, the ‘challenge’ of fragmentation of actors at ASP was countered by making connections that will be built upon during the prototyping phase of the pilot. This feeds the issue of renewing the relationship with urban nature.</p> <p><u>High School pupils (15-17)</u>: the issue of renewing a relationship with nature is a <i>highly attractive thematic way to bring together different stakeholder groups</i>, with strength among younger generations.</p> <p>Discoveries about enabling and prohibiting conditions</p> <p><u>Relational</u>: topics surrounding biodiversity and green spaces create a sense of connection and intrinsic motivation among participants, supporting the goal of ‘building communities’ and the ‘opportunity’ of diverse stakeholders.</p> <p><u>Operational</u>: working from a grass-roots level to connect different stakeholders in urban ecology projects works well, as it provides a common, intrinsic interest beyond practical incentives for people to</p>

	<p>work together. Building on this grass-roots fabric should help in the 'challenges' of complex governance and funding, by making the needs and energy of the community as aligned with the pilot visible.</p> <p><u>Strategic:</u> the motivation of the students showed how much energy is present to develop community-based green projects and spaces at ASP, both for their intrinsic value as well as to increase social cohesion and wellbeing.</p>
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Models, artistic propositions
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insights into shared values • Connections between ASP stakeholders • Validation of interest from focus group students/Gen Z

Rotterdam Bouwkunst - Urban Ecology Course

Waag, in collaboration with Esmee Geerken and the Rotterdam Academy of Architecture (RAVB) organised **a lecture series and design research program for the Master Students of RAVB**. The Urban Ecology series, a follow-up of our previous 'Building as Being' symposium, **explores the crossovers between ecology and architecture, looking at building in the broadest sense of the word:** shaping elements into structures, at various levels of complexity. The 7-part lecture series, accompanying work seminars and extended assignment explored the role of temporal spaces in the context of city developments. With an emphasis on the 'making public' of space for non-human and human actors alike, the invited lectures provided insights on self-organisation, complexity, biodiversity and systems thinking as a source of inspiration and starting principles for design research. While being embedded in architecture, urban planning, and landscape design disciplines the aim for the curriculum is not to bring forth new designs per se, but to evoke a new imaginary around the ASP. The course will be concluded with a public event wherein the students can present their works, maquettes, and designs to stakeholders on site.

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Improving Health & Wellbeing</i> • <i>Making Places</i> • <i>Attaining sustainability</i>
Activity Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build a repository of imaginaries i.r.t. potential landscape interventions at Amsterdam Science Park • Facilitate collaborative environment and exchange between local stakeholder and outside parties • Support local artist and stakeholder
When/Where	<p>Amsterdam Science Park, WAAG outpost at Startup Village, UVA</p> <p>Rotterdam, Academie Bouwkunst</p>

<p>Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved</p>	<p>Activity provider: Esmee Geerken, in assignment of Rotterdam Academy Bouwkunst, with support of Waag</p> <p>Stakeholders involved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutions; UVA, IAS • Professional architects
<p>Participants</p>	<p>Master students Architecture and Landscape design</p>
<p>Outputs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video Registrations lectures • Landscape, art and design proposals <div data-bbox="427 600 1388 1590"> <p>Het groene auditorium</p> <p>new topography + lush landscape</p> <p>+1.5m</p> <p>„proeftuin“ for new vegetation</p> <p>auditorium</p> </div> <p><i>Design By: Nancy Smolka.</i></p>

	<p>WILDGROEI (NAT EN DROOG GEBIED)</p> <p>Research By: Iris Bol.</p>
<p>Outcomes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repository of design proposals for Amsterdam Science Park • Validation of interest and design opportunities from focus group young architecture professionals

Kids Workshop - Building Like/For a Beast i.c.w. Esmee Geerken

Local artist Esmee Geerken, together with Jeugdland and Waag developed a 2-day workshop for young kids in the age of 8 - 11. Over the course of these days, the participants undertook a variety of field explorations, observations, drawings sessions, foraging exercises, lectures, conversations and imagination sessions where they were invited to consider what their ‘house’ of the future and the ‘Science Park’ of the future would look like. Taking inspiration from the practices of earth scientist and artist Esmee Geerken, zoo-designer Thijs de Zeeuw and a local beekeeper and beehive builder. The workshop concluded with the building of several animal/life-inspired enclosures and constructions in the outdoors on the Amsterdam Science Park, and a presentation for their parents with accompanying drinks.

<p>Impact domain(s)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Building Communities</i> • <i>Making Places</i>
<p>Activity Objectives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bring a future generation to Amsterdam Science Park. • Facilitate a collaborative environment for Stakeholders. • Involve kids in city planning/making, future thinking and urban ecological conversations. • Experiment with nature-based interventions on-site. • Experiment with embodied foraging and building practices and performing landscapes.

When/Where	<p>Amsterdam Science Park, WAAG outpost at Startup Village & public space - grass field in between the Equinox data centre and Spark Village, Jeugdland</p> <p>18 October: presentations, foraging, exploration</p> <p>19 October: building like a beast, demonstrations with parents</p>
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	<p>Activity provider: Waag, local Artist Esmee Geerken, Jeugdland</p> <p>Stakeholders involved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Local Beekeeper ● Local Artist - Thijs de Zeeuw ● Community builder Spark Village - fine-tuning arrangements use field ● Representative Project Bureau Amsterdam Municipality, on behalf of Masterplan Consortium - use of plot of land
Participants	<p>Audience - informed - newsletter [1307 recipients]</p> <p>Participants - engaged</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 13 kids + parents
Insights	<p>Key insights</p> <p><u>Kids:</u> The activity demonstrated that young kids are not only able to consider the meanwhile and urban ecology as conceptual framework, but also to think constructively about city making and urban development plans and its relevance to their future. The design thinking and imaginative exercises allowed them to consider the 'issue' of rethinking the role of public space effectively and made clear that younger generations can and should be included in city-making efforts, given that they are addressed as equal within the context of their personal future and living environment.</p> <p><u>Stakeholders:</u> The activity demonstrated that the 'opportunity' of diverse stakeholders and strong existing meanwhiles contribute to the development of enabling conditions for artists to work in and with. By combining the expertise, knowledge, facilities and capabilities through a shared affiliation on the 'issue' of renewing the relationship with urban nature, highly valued events with good communicative and promotional potential can be established.</p> <p>Discoveries about enabling and prohibiting conditions</p> <p><u>Relational:</u> the activity made it apparent that imagining and drawing 'what it is like' to be a non-human animal is much less effective when it comes to the 'issue' of renewing the relationship with nature, than through acts of embodiment. The organising artist shared with the local coalitions lead that relating seems to come about more through the ecosystem and environment that is shared by humans and non-</p>

humans alike. And that it is specifically embodied acts such as foraging, collecting, observing and the building of shelters, which are innate qualities of both humans and non-humans, that a deeper relating to nature comes about.

Operational: The activity took place at various locations at the Amsterdam Science Park, one of which was a public space. This was the first time that a prompt use by the Local Coalition of public space was granted by the project bureau of the Amsterdam Science Park, and as such the activity made way for future prompt usages. While permission was granted, the fact that the location was so close to the inhabitants made the artist feel somewhat of an intruder and questions were raised by passers-by about the approval of these acts. Amplifying the tensions that can arise when addressing the 'issue' of the role of public space. Other than that, the location was rather remote with limited traffic of 'natural' visitors, and less connection to the more science-oriented facilities on sights. A location more in the public eye would have helped with the strategic positioning of the Urban Ecology Pilot.

Strategic: The activity demonstrated that kids-events can be used as a strategic programming effort for reaching audiences that usually engage less with the Amsterdam Science Park. Since children of this age are too young to be visiting the location alone, parents are engaged in at least two moments, during delivery and pick up. The concluding event provided an opportunity for the parents to engage amongst each other and provided an opportunity for the Urban Ecology Pilot to bring forth its ambition for the area in terms of the 'needs' for green open spaces and increase in biodiversity. Ticket sales proved that events such as these are in demand by children, while comments made by the general public demonstrated that the event also has potential as an engagement strategy for working with adults. It would be interesting to reprogram the event for older generations and see whether the acts of embodiment as a strategy for renewing the relationship to nature are also effective in adults.

Outputs

- Kids' drawings

Kids' Drawing - Building Like a Beast Workshop

Kids Building Animal Houses - Building Like a Beast Workshop. Photo credits: Esmee Geerken

Outcomes

- Insight into capacity kids (8-11) for performing landscapes
- Insight into the potential of inclusion of future generations in urban development project
- Insight into needs and expectations of local inhabitants

1.3.3. Exploring and Inquiring Support Activities and T-Labs Probes

The following support activities have been implemented within the Exploring and Inquiring stage of the Pilot.

Timeline of Exploring & Inquiring Support Activities

September 2021	W35	W36	W37	W38
Support Agency Activities				
Coffee with Stakeholders				
Stakeholder Workshop				
Probe 1 + 2				
Co-creation of an alternative masterplan				

Coffee with Stakeholders

Informal discussion on the specific needs, challenges, opportunities of selected stakeholders.

Impact domain(s)	<i>Building Communities</i>
Activity Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for Amsterdam Local Coalition Lead before, during and after the conversations; providing strategic advice on how to scope the conversation, take note during and summarize after + conclude and next steps • Strategic; bringing Bridger as Consortium member to the conversation for extra weight. • Amsterdam Local Coalition Lead has not been personally in contact with identified stakeholders before
When / Where	08 September 2021 at The Coffee Virus and Startup Village
Activity Providers	Waag in close collaboration with Aalborg University (Agency member)
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amsterdam Science and Business • Startup Village
Insights	<p>Key insights</p> <p>Both Matrix Innovations Centre and Startup Village expressed the 'need' for Green Open Spaces, hinting at closing of the main road - for</p>

	<p>the purpose of making a public park, v.s. placing community garden beds for the Startup community as ways to do so.</p> <p>Discoveries about enabling and prohibiting conditions</p> <p><u>Relational</u>: 6 years ago, Amsterdam Science and Business placed picnic tables at various locations. Originally meant as both tracking devices for the movement of benches and people and places for social gathering, it quickly became apparent that they are used frequently by all stakeholders on site. Since then, the tracking has been stopped, but more benches have been placed and the method of placing shared benches has been adopted by other organisations on site. The benches are freely used and moved across the area, according to the needs of the users. Contributing to the potential of mobile furniture as a way to engage with the 'issue' of rethinking the role of public spaces.</p> <p><u>Operational</u>: On the 'issue' of rethinking the role of public space Matrix Innovation Centre expressed that the connecting of the park to the city (physically) is an issue, since it's blocked by roads, canals and rails. Potential solutions which are now in the process of planning: build two new bridges over the canal, create new walking paths and add more bus stops. There is also a plan for a new tunnel that will connect it to the city. Similarly, Startup Village also added to the same issue mentioning that wayfinding and accessibility of Startup Village is currently insufficient. Regular remarks are made by visitors that it was hard to find.</p> <p><u>Strategic</u>: On the 'issue' of rethinking the role of public space a potential was identified; namely that most of the Amsterdam Science Park is vacant during summer times and holidays, with plenty of space for the organisation of events in the public space.</p>
Outputs	Minutes of conversations
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Insights into needs, issues, challenges and opportunities of selected stakeholders ● Setting up of collaborative environment for future potential collaborative efforts ● Stakeholders are aware of upcoming Stakeholder Workshop

Stakeholder Workshop: Amsterdam Science Park Komt Samen (Amsterdam Science Park Comes Together)

Stakeholder workshop with selected invitees where the participants are led through several exercises meant to establish positive and collaborative relations amongst the stakeholders and validate the concerns identified by the Amsterdam Local Coalition. Structured as a meeting and exchange of relations, ideas, perspectives and concerns.

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Building Communities</i>
Activity Objectives	<p>The main goal of WAAG is to promote a green agenda in the regeneration project. However, this is not necessarily the case with other stakeholders who might have a different interest. Additionally, needs could vary also among those who share a similar agenda. Understanding and defining the motivations of each stakeholder when collaborating with others is a key for bringing them onboard. By identifying what could benefit the various actors, it will be easier to establish collaborations and create a win-win situation for everyone involved. The overall objective of this activity is to bring every relevant actor on board, and understand the interest of stakeholders to collaborate with each other and Waag and to validate and get insights into newly addressed issues, needs, concerns and challenges as identified by the Amsterdam Local Coalition and stakeholders</p>
When / Where	8 September 2021 Outpost Waag; Amsterdam Science Park 608, Startup Village, outdoor
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	Waag in close collaboration with Aalborg University (Agency member)
Participants / Beneficiaries	<p>9 people representative of different stakeholders, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Academie van de stad - Spark Village - Amsterdam Green Campus - UVA - Spark 904/Open Kitchen Lab - Anna's Tuin & Ruigte

Insights

Photo Credits: Waag

Key insights

Stakeholders involved: The UvA has a proposal under consideration that nominates the Pilot together with Anna's Tuin & Ruigte to start a 'proeftuin' ('experimental space') as part of their city-wide campus policy. Their election of Waag and AT&R shows how developing strong partnerships that are cooperative rather than collaborative (based on mutual capacities and trust rather than on any particular programmatic goal) is a strong basis for a meanwhile strategy.

Discoveries about enabling and prohibiting conditions

Relational: wilderness aspect was shown to be an important part of the 'need' for green open spaces. See conclusions (below) for elaboration.

Operational: there are numerous bird watchers informally active on the ASP, coming from various institutions. This deepens the 'opportunity' of diverse stakeholders and connects them to the opportunity of developing a watch post.

Strategic: having a coalition of the willing, with diverse and motivated grassroots stakeholders, sends a strong message to policy makers about the potential of eco-practices. This connects the 'opportunities' of diverse stakeholders and policy support.

Outputs

- Photos (introduction details + registration event)
- Map with potential locations for meanwhile interventions
- Persona cards

Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Insights into needs, challenges and opportunities of selected stakeholders ● Insight into potential thematic coalition partners ● Insight into direction innovation missions Amsterdam Local Coalition
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Co-creation of an Alternative Masterplan (T-Lab Probe)

The Probe consists of a tour around the eastern part of the area, stopping by 6 stations and is developed by Tlabs 3&4 together, thereby combining the two probes. With Tlab3 focussing on the ecology of attention, while the focus of the remainder of the stations was more focus on the sense of space and relationship to nature.

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Improving Health & Wellbeing</i> ● <i>Building Communities</i> ● <i>Making Places</i>
Activity Objectives	<p>Understanding community perspective about care and attractiveness of green areas, new uses, emotions and values associated with wilderness VS the digital landscape, perception of nature by different stakeholders and target groups.</p>

Activity Description

SENSEMAKING T-PROBE

1 During the workshops, participants received one card each, showing the tour on the front side and six boxes on the backside. Each box represents one station of the workshop, after each activity they were asked to write their thoughts, feelings, impressions inside the equivalent box. The gathered information was digitalized and specified, the answers of 6 different groups with a total of 67 participants were clustered.

2 The evaluation of the cluster contribution showed particularities of the different stops.

- EMOTION / IMPRESSION
- SILENCE
- VISION
- APPROPRIATION
- NATURE
- BUILDING
- SPACE / ENVIRONMENT

T			

3 A combination of the statements of the participants, the cluster contribution per station and the most frequent words used on the cards enabled the definition of the stations' "characters" by their physical state and the visitors perception.

1	DATA	
2	CLUSTER	
3	CHARACTER	
4	POTENTIAL	
5	PROPOSALS	

4 The participants visions for each station are displayed on different layers around the map and show the areas with more and less potential of transformation in the eyes of participants.

- LEGEND**
- Walking route with stops
 - SPACE** Most prevalent cluster of statements per stop
 - STOP** Stop number and name on the walking route
 - WORDS** The words most frequently used by the participants on the stop
 - VISION** Participants' statements expressing a vision about or desire for the future state of the space of the stop. Different shades of blue show dark to light show complexity of implementation in time.

The aim of the workshop was to gather data for the alternative mapping and opportunities of biodiversity education of ASP related to meanwhile uses and spaces together with local actors. Each station brought together storytelling - on the topics of 1. experience of space, 2. active observation, 3. moving through space, 4. making and imagination, 5. ecology of attention, 6. sharing and impressions - and specific experiential tasks and mapping activities.

Over the two days, there were 4 different groups performing the workshop. The event was conceived as a bottom-up mapping of the ASP open spaces through walking as a participatory method. This enabled participating local actors to get in touch with each other and share their impressions and visions about the spaces.

During the workshops, participants' expectations and impressions were collected on cards regarding:

- relationship with the urban nature (desired or imagined)
- perception of urban space (critical issues, ideas)
- use of public open spaces (desired or already done)
- perception of natural space

This data is to be transferred into different emotional maps of space. Thanks to this activity, it will be possible to generate relevant output for future temporary activities.

PARTICIPANTS' RESPONSES EXPRESSED THROUGH CLUSTERS - VIEW PER STOP - with Emotion / Impression (in absolute numbers)

PARTICIPANTS' RESPONSES EXPRESSED THROUGH CLUSTERS - VIEW PER CLUSTER - with Emotion / Impression (in absolute numbers)

Once removed from digital distractions and commitments, where does attention go? The attention inputs were objectified (nature, colours, people, sounds, buildings) or immaterial (feelings and reflections). The inputs can be classified into the six attention foci identified in the figure below.

When/Where	10 + 11 September 2021 Outdoor at various locations at ASP
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	LAND - Tlab 4, Futuribile - Tlab 3 and Waag
Participants & Beneficiaries	<p>Group 1: Students & Workers</p> <p>Group 2: Inhabitants</p> <p>Group 3: Students from abroad</p> <p>Group 4: Children</p>
Insights	<p>Key insights</p> <p>The range of different target groups who took part in the Probe delivered consistent feedback on expectations and potential uses on site. Active participation in exploring the site, testing nature and imagining spaces raised enthusiasm and curiosity among participants. With a shared understanding on how the ‘issue’ of rethinking the role of public space can be addressed.</p> <p>Discoveries about enabling and prohibiting conditions</p> <p>Tlab3</p> <p><u>Relational</u>: The activity demonstrated that the act of removing digital distraction can be used to adhere to the ‘issue’ of renewing the relationship to nature’. Removing the phone allowed focusing attention on the present moment in time and space: people experienced an</p>

	<p>enhanced presence, accompanied by a higher capability to be tuned with nature and other humans. The probe supported the deepening of the set of starting questions that informed the Data Nest building: how to create a sense of intimacy in public spaces? It emerged that restorative areas offering experiences of wellbeing and a break from the digitalised everyday would be an extremely valuable 'opportunity' for ASP users.</p> <p><u>Operational:</u> The usage of the Data Nest installation, as a communicative tool provided to be effective instrument to address the 'issue' on the our relationship to nature, by steering conversations about the false immateriality of our digital everyday and its impact on the environment</p> <p><u>Strategic:</u> At the beginning of the tour, participants were asked to share something that they wanted to leave behind. While anonymous, the similarities in the answers demonstrated that it might be beneficial to make these types of shared concerns public, as to create a sense of empathy and empowerment amongst the diverse visitors and stakeholders.</p> <p>Tlab4</p> <p><u>Relational:</u> Active participation in exploring the site, testing nature and imagining spaces raised enthusiasm and curiosity among participants.</p> <p><u>Operational:</u> The outreach and mobilisation of stakeholders was a critical issue to be improved and rethought in the future, both in terms of timing sessions correctly and building up engagement within the community as the project progresses.</p> <p><u>Strategic:</u> Working within the framework of the T-Factor project, the activity demonstrated that it is essential to approach future decisions with the help of those who live in the places, trying to incorporate ideas that respond to real needs and perceptions. The activity of data collection can therefore be considered both as a preparatory activity for the future development of the project but above all it can be the basis for a new knowledge of the place and its future vocations.</p>
Outputs	<p>Alternative map on open-source platform</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inputs for public space design 2. Users and future users are aware about the place - community building 3. Video/Photo report 4. Meaningful routes and insights connecting people's awareness to the built and wild environment <p>The following outputs are still in development:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Emotional mapping of each stakeholder group in response to the

	<p>activities carried out in the specific stations (ongoing);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial mapping of the site highlighting open space perception of local community and potential places for temporary uses and public space activation. <p><i>ASP Probe. Photo credits: Rosalie Bak.</i></p>
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insights into community perspectives i.r.t. public space, biodiversity, relationship urban nature. • Insights in the workings of the provided walk, for other localities connected to T-Factor.

1.3.4. Overview of Stakeholders

At the time of writing this report, the relational ecosystem surrounding the Amsterdam pilot comprises **around 30 different organisations** and a **much bigger number of individuals across scientific communities, resident communities, students' communities and other informal groups**. In this number, we consider both organisations that have been actively engaged so far (for example through collaboration during exploring & inquiring activities), and those that have been informed and reached out actively.

Below we provide a **preliminary** map of stakeholders and initiatives as it emerges from exploring and inquiring activities. This map is continuously evolving in sync with the progress of the activities at pilot site. The link below shall provide a dynamic overview of the evolution of the pilot as it progresses over time.

<https://kumu.io/tfactor/amsterdam-science-park>

Preliminary Map of ASP Relational Ecosystem.

Missing Stakeholders

The following stakeholders are currently not engaged in activities relating to the regeneration process.

1. Flevopark
2. Community garden Valentijn
3. Flevoparkschool
4. Basisschool de Waaier
5. Frankendaelschool
6. Basisschool Frankendael
7. Kunstmagneetschool de Kraal
8. 5e Montessori school Watergraafsmeer
9. College De Meer
10. Centre for Urban Studies

Map of Missing Stakeholders.

Flevopark & Community Garden Valentijn

Flevopark: The Flevopark is the park next to the Amsterdam Science Park, situated on the north side of the ASP. There is a high biodiversity, and the park is part of the eco corridor of Amsterdam. It's 15 hectares big.

Community Garden Valentijn: This community garden (Buurtuin Valentijn) is initiated and maintained by the neighbourhood (40 people). In the garden you will find vegetables, fruit trees, butterflies and herbs. It's supported by the municipality. The garden is situated next to the Flevopark. The Flevopark, the community garden Valentijn and ASP are divided by water, a road and high buildings. This makes it feel both are quite far away from each other, while the distance is only 1 kilometre.

The association of the Flevopark, the community garden and the Urban Ecology Pilot are focussing on similar goals and themes, this could motivate both parties to engage with us. There is an opportunity to share knowledge, activities, etc.

Elementary, High Schools and Universities Around the ASP

There are multiple elementary, high schools around the Amsterdam Science Park. A couple of these schools were invited to our ecology walks, in which the teachers were very interested. Ecology seems to be an appealing theme for schools to be involved in. Waag is not offering a program to these schools yet and most schools have their own programs for each year already.

- Elementary schools
Flevoparkschool
Basisschool de Waaier
Frankendaelschool
Basisschool Frankendael
Kunstmagneetschool de Kraal
- High Schools
5e Montessori school Watergraafsmeer
College De Meer
- Universities
Centre for Urban Studies

As a first step Waag would like to create a program for these schools. This would be a collaboration between the Urban Ecology Pilot and the LEARN research group of Waag, that focuses on contemporary education and experiential disciplines. With this program Waag can approach several schools and detail the program based on the needs and opportunities of the schools.

1.4. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

A number of new insights were gained during this phase, which underscore our core conclusions and at the same time allow us to refine our prototyping trajectory. Generally, the Urban Ecology Pilot has a clear vision on establishing eco-practices as a meanwhile strategy to influence the development of the regeneration area. This provides a clear context for our engagement with stakeholders and the conclusions below.

Core Conclusions

Core conclusions after this phase of stakeholder mapping are that (1) many local stakeholders share institutional support as well as intrinsic, personal motivation to participate in eco-practices; (2) ecology and biodiversity are excellent topics to engage with a diversity of stakeholders and can be implemented in a diversity of spatial and functional contexts; and that (3) ecology and biodiversity are a primary driver for engagement among young generations.

New Insight: Discovering Urban Wilderness

During stakeholder workshops, the wilderness areas of ASP featured prominently. Such areas apparently connect strongly to the 'need' for green open spaces. People are drawn to wilderness spaces. These spaces suggest their own set of eco-practices, ways of behaving and observing. The prominence of wilderness areas and its resonance with various stakeholder groups was a new insight for the pilot. This insight is integrated into the activity portfolio structure, which now anticipates two modalities of programmatic and/or operational deployment; in a 'garden' space and a 'wilderness space'.

The insight therefore creates a twofold geographic orientation of pilot activities at ASP; on garden spaces and a wilderness space. This enables agency towards the 'challenge' of Green vs. Dense, because it makes tangible the values of green open spaces in an area that is increasingly filled with large buildings. Delineating wild and garden spaces in the park provides different ways that people can connect with their green environment, which increases the levels of engagement with the opportunity of diverse, competent stakeholders in the park. Moreover, it provides a clear and strong relational opportunity, bringing together bird-watching enthusiasts from various institutions at the park, for example.

The value of engaging with 'wild' contexts was further enhanced by experimenting with 'no phone' walks as well as with explorative walks that make use of phone photography and digital apps to map the environment. Engaging with wilderness while consciously using or leaving aside digital technology (effectively creating white spots for participants), increased attention and appreciation of the material surroundings. On a strategic level, this insight can support urban planning by offering good practices in urban rewilding and bring together complex governance stakeholders based on shared intrinsic values as well as policy priorities.

New Insight: Uniting New Generations

During various activities with young children, high school students and university students, the level of engagement with 'more-than-human worlds' was striking. On the level of imagination, future aspirations and hands-on engagement, there was a clear, tacit agreement among participants that 'green practices' are of primary importance in their lives. On a relational level, this means the pilot may further engage the students and youth that are a large section of the actors at the ASP. It also means that eco-practices form a privileged thematic by which diverse groups can be brought together without needing to offer much context.

New Insight: The Living World as a Source of (Mental) Health

Conversations with stakeholders revealed what science has clearly shown in recent years: exposure to natural and green spaces has large well-being benefits, both in terms of physical and mental health. This relates to air quality, exposure to green environments and in particular trees, quietude, exercise, etc. Given the pressures to which young people and in particular students are exposed, with high levels of anxiety and stress, it was found to be an important opportunity to partially focus eco-practices on their wellbeing and incorporate mental wellbeing issues in the activity portfolio. These meanwhile animation should offer a collective dimension to enhance empathy and sociability, and a compulsory element creating an equal starting ground for participants. Finally, they should improve awareness of self, space and other beings as an antidote to anxiety and digital fatigue. Hence, our challenge for the T-cycle is to "optimise" wellbeing by reducing traditional technology optimisation practices (e.g. data extraction; connectivity everywhere) and creating restorative areas/experiences where nature and technology minimisation are merged.

New Insight: Performing Landscapes and Embodiment as an Effective Way to Renew Relationships to Nature and More-than-human World

Lastly the insights, coming from the Kids-workshop, brought forth that acts of embodiment and performing landscapes - engaging in acts of 'foraging', 'collecting' 'building shelters', 'observing', wherein both the body, once senses and the physical environment and its resources are incorporated, provide a additional way to renew the relationship with nature. Working with the children it was clear that acts such as 'imagining', 'drawing', 'talking' do have the potential to generate new imaginaries, but, given that they lean strongly on our cognition, the imagined did stay closer to the human perspective. Embodied acts offer a more visceral 'relating-to' where the submersion in non-human perspective seems to come more easily. It would be interesting to investigate whether this division is also applicable to adults.

Next Steps

- Following the first workshop during the E&I phase, where shared opportunities and concerns were brought forth, a second workshop will be organised. The premise here is to take the conclusions of the before mentioned opportunities and concerns, as well as a synthesis of the insights of all previous events organised by both T-Labs and Local Coalition, to instigate a design thinking session, where the focus will be on prototyping ideas for meanwhile activities that can take place in the following year. The invite list will be expanded to include newly engaged stakeholders, and will also include selected artists, designers, and eco-practitioners to enhance the creations.
- The local coalition will also publish an in-depth article about the activities of the E&I and S&I phase, which will be shared amongst all Stakeholders engaged thus far. The

Stakeholders will also receive a personal invite for the presentation of the Urban Ecology course in January, with the aim to provide inspiration for the activities to come and further the conversations about the local governance and use of meanwhile spaces for eco-practices.

BILBAO ZORROZAURRE

2. BILBAO ZORROZAURRE

2.1. PILOT STARTING CONTEXT AND PRIORITIES

Bilbao has a population of about 347,100 people and accounts for 40.4% of Greater Bilbao's population and 30.3% of the territory of Bizkaia region (1,142,853 inhabitants).

Zorrozaurre is one of the least populated neighbourhoods in the city with only 216 women and 209 men and it is home to a small population of homeless migrants who occasionally occupy uninhabited post-industrial spaces. It is also one of the neighbourhoods with the lowest individual and household income of 16,810 euros and 31,782 euros, respectively, in the city. Despite the small number of inhabitants, residents are quite well organised.

The emergence of “meanwhile” cultural and creative activities gave rise to actions that provided the island with social life and economic activity. In turn, these initiatives have been catalysts for attracting new projects to the island, contributing to its habitability and the creation and identification of opportunities. The relationship between the municipality and the neighbours and the actors involved in the “meanwhile” activities has gone through setbacks and conflicts. Nevertheless, it has many chapters of collaboration and mutual support to its credit.

The island of Zorrozaurre has a surface area of 838,781 m². More than half of the land belongs to public entities (Basque Government, Bilbao City Council and the Port Authority of Bilbao). The rest of the land is divided between several private owners.

In 2004 was approved the Master Plan for the regeneration of Zorrozaurre designed by the Anglo-Iraqi architect **Zahra Hadid** and it was revised in 2007. Zorrozaurre is currently the largest urban regeneration project in Bilbao. The regeneration, led by Bilbao City Council, will convert a semi-abandoned and decaying industrial area into a new mixed-used 24/7 business district that will have an impact on the entire city.

At present, Bilbao is facing new challenges that imply new urban renewal plans, as in the cases of the Zorrozaurre Island and Punta Zorroza, a section of the Zorroza neighbourhood. These projects will have a decisive influence on the economic and social development of Bilbao. Simultaneously, the city continues to generate solutions to the current situation where technological innovation is radically changing the way of understanding the world and facing and solving problems. For this reason, the metropolis is immersed in a second transformation to move from a friendly city to a smart city that continues to advance and innovate to build a more competitive and creative city.

Zorrozaurre has a **strong legacy of temporary uses and a long-standing involvement of several grassroots agents and new universities.** However, the pilot also faces many challenges that T-Factor will encounter, many of these related to the urban decay and isolation as well as the need to build a strong urban ecosystem for the future.

T-Factor may contribute to addressing many of the current challenges in Zorrozaurre, especially those related to the promotion of economic activity, collaboration between actors, and scaling-up of existing initiatives. At the same time, T-Factor can contribute to exploring legal frameworks for similar regeneration projects with temporary uses of space.

2.1.1. Issues

In the paragraphs that follow, we report on the main issues or problems identified thus far, through both research developed within work-package 2 and initial exploring and inquiring activities. Issues are grouped and briefly described according to the six core themes of the T-Factor's Theory of Change - i.e. Improving Health & Wellbeing, Attaining Sustainability, Making Places, Growing Prosperity, Cultivating Innovation, Building Communities.

Improving Health & Wellbeing

Ageing & Low Density

Following a trend from the previous years, the city continues to grow thanks to the positive migration balance (5,211 people in 2018) that surpasses the negative rate of natural population growth (-1,740 people in 2018). Bilbao's population is slowly ageing, reaching its highest index of 24.0% in 2019 and an average age of 46.4 years old. Foreign population represents 8.6% of the city's total population and it grew by 2,206 people in the last year, reaching a total of 29,815. Zorrozaurre is one of the least populated neighbourhoods in the city with only 216 women and 209 men and it is home to a small population of homeless migrants who occasionally occupy uninhabited post-industrial spaces. 23% of the population in the area is over 64 years old and there is a negative migration balance.

Safety and Security

There are perceptions and feelings of insecurity, mainly related to the lack of urban lighting in certain parts of the island and the presence of squatting groups that live in some of the vacant warehouses.

Rising Inequalities

Growing imbalances between neighbourhoods in terms of income, educational level, employment, social housing, accessibility to public facilities and services, and socio-cultural activities.

Lowering Living Standards

Living standards in the island have generally deteriorated over time, mainly as result of poor maintenance of aged buildings and public and private spaces.

Making Places

Heritage & Infrastructure Degradation

The decline in Zorrozaurre started with the 1970s economic crisis, along with the collapse of industrial activity in the Bilbao estuary, the progressive abandonment of buildings and infrastructure, and the loss of investment in the peninsula. The neighbourhood was a degraded

and isolated area of the city with certain industrial activities such as “Coromina Industrial”, “Metalduro Mefesa” or “Cromoduro”, whose buildings remain as good testimonies of what was once the skyline of Zorrozaurre. After decades of industrial and social decline, barely 500 people live in Zorrozaurre today and living standards have deteriorated as result of poor maintenance of aged buildings and public and private spaces.

Weak Connectivity

Despite its centrality, Zorrozaurre is very isolated from the rest of the city and it is perceived as a peripheral space because of its accessibility problems. Most of the people interviewed expressed the need for an improvement in the public transport infrastructure. Due to the increasing number of people traveling to the island, the city bus’s frequency that connects the island with the rest of the city is insufficient. Although the number of municipal bicycles has increased, more and more people are accessing the island by car, creating the need to increase the number of parking spaces.

Lack of green & open spaces

There is a general lack of green areas and spaces for pedestrians and bicycles to meet daily recreational needs.

Attaining Sustainability

Energy

High energy consumption in housing due to lack of energy efficiency measures.

Soil Pollution

Contaminated soils in historically industrial areas, subject to new transformation processes.

Waste & Recycling

The island generally shows low levels of recycling, mainly due to insufficient waste containers.

Environmental Risk

Zorrozaurre is particularly exposed to environmental risks such as flooding.

Growing Prosperity

Loss of Competitiveness & Unemployment

Post-industrial decline and relocation of the port has resulted in high loss of industry and employment opportunities. Much of the site is now empty, obsolete and unused, which led to a lack of identity and progressive loss of jobs.

Income

Zorrozaurre is one of the neighbourhoods with the lowest individual and household income of 16,810 euros and 31,782 euros, respectively, in the city.

Cultivating Innovation

Fragile Creative Economies

Zorrozaurre is already inhabited by many active and vibrant creative and cultural actors that work across several cultural and creative industries. However, many of these actors are relatively small and fragile, also due to the lack of innovation services and facilities in the island that may help them grow and thrive.

Lack of Innovation Facilities & Services

As mentioned above, the island generally lacks an 'innovation infrastructure' that can work as the backbone for reinforcing the existing actors and initiatives, while attracting new actors and investment.

Building Communities

Identity

Inhabitants of the island's historic communities are unwilling to let their past as the Deusto district's former waterfront and their post-industrial identity built up over decades of history be wiped out. They have the spirit of looking ahead and starting a new phase which adapts to new times, but they want to do so without great losses.

Mistrust & tensions

There are tensions related to conflicting expectations of the public, private actors and associations in Zorrozaurre that may hinder collaboration if not properly addressed. Visitors of the area are mostly people of Bilbao with social and cultural interests. Failing to meet their expectations might create a high level of disappointment and therefore, a decrease in public trust.

Poor Information

Despite the efforts of the city to widely communicate the redevelopment and actively engage with citizens throughout consultations processes, general awareness and information about the future of the island still appears to be weak and fragmented.

Lack of Meanwhile Regulatory Frameworks

Temporary uses in the city are not a new practice and Bilbao shows several examples of temporary initiatives that have been developing successfully over the years. However, there is no specific regulatory framework in place at city level, and this often creates many barriers to both existing and new meanwhile initiatives. Complying with safety, accessibility and licencing standards under the existing regulations may imply a huge financial investment that small actors and local communities can hardly afford.

2.1.2. Challenges and Opportunities

The regeneration of Zorrozaurre faces multiple challenges of different nature (urban, economic, social, environmental). Most of these challenges have a fundamental systemic

nature and can be therefore understood and addressed only through a long-term perspective and in sync with broader dynamics occurring at city and beyond city scale. Thus, not all these challenges can be addressed in the timeframe of T-Factor; however, the project can create some of the enabling conditions that may allow challenges such as economic development, social cohesion and innovation society to be 'infrastructured', especially by means of creating wide engagement, collaboration and trust-based dynamics that stand as the backbone of systems transformation.

In the paragraphs that follow, we provide an overview of the core challenges mapped to date and prioritised for address by the Local Coalition.

Challenge 1 - A Collaborative and Diverse Innovation Ecosystem

In Zorrozaurre, actors of different kinds coexist in the 'meantime', both in terms of the activity they carry out and whether they are temporary.

Higher Education Institutions

The Bilbao City Council is committed to turning Zorrozaurre into an island of knowledge, with the presence of universities offering degrees related to the sectors of activity considered strategic for the city: art and creativity, advanced services for industry - KIBs, technology and health. To this end, an effort has been made to attract universities to this area of the city and there are three universities currently operating in the island:

- Mondragon University. Bilbao As Fabrik
- IED Kunsthal. Design School.
- Digipen

In addition to these three universities, which have been established on the island in recent years, the other two universities operating in Bilbao have at least one of their campuses relatively close by:

- University of Deusto
- University of the Basque Country: Faculty of Business Administration

Creative, cultural, sport and leisure initiatives

- Espacio Open - Cultural association
- Pabellón 6 – Theatre company
- La Haceria Arteak (ZAWP Project) Cultural association
- Bilbao School of Cinematographic Creation (ECCBI)
- Zirkozaurre - Circus and performative arts
- Karola Zirko - Circus and performative arts
- Gure Txoko - School of skate
- Piugaz - Climbing school
- Artiatx – Cultural association
- Espacio 600 – Space for cultural and leisure events

Other actors in the island that are relevant to T-Factor

- Euskaldunako Zubia. Neighbourhood association
- Bizinahi - Neighbourhood association

- SMEs. Other companies currently based in Zorrozaurre

The main challenge to be addressed in the framework of T-Factor is to foster the collaboration among HEIs and local grassroots movements to create an innovation ecosystem that includes all the actors and stakeholders in the meanwhile and that enables students, entrepreneurs and citizens to set up their company in this area. Using spaces in the meanwhile can be a way to prototype innovative solutions addressing some of the problems faced by Zorrozaurre (such as lack of security and green areas, poor mobility system) with a user-centred and citizen-participation approach and the use of spaces in the meanwhile.

Challenge 2 - Boost Entrepreneurship and Economic Development

Zorrozaurre is planned to become a business district with an economic impact on the entire city. Its evolution will have a decisive influence on the economic and social development of Bilbao. Therefore, one of the main challenges is to boost the island's economic activity and its capacity to give birth to new businesses, while fostering entrepreneurship education and mindsets. To meet this challenge, the City Council has a long-term plan that includes, among other goals, attracting universities to the island and supporting the creation of an urban technology park. T-Factor can contribute to generate new business models in the meantime that can develop and establish in the future in the technology park and generate economic and social value. In any case, it must be considered that the activities that are already developing their activity in the meantime, generate economic value, have the capacity to attract other activities to the island and have made possible that some former industrial buildings are not abandoned. This value, although difficult to quantify, is very important and it would be interesting to analyse how to make this value visible and if there is the possibility of increasing it within the T-Factor framework.

Challenge 3 - A New, Post-industrial Identity

Zorrozaurre has a long industrial history and presents industrial assets and heritage with inestimable value. Yet, one key challenge is the creation of a new identity for the area that can project such heritage into the future, while preserving its memory. Knowledge economies, creative and cultural economies, circular and collaborative economies offer the opportunity to rethink existing assets, infrastructure and socio-cultural capital towards new services and business models that steer the economic development of the island and the broader city, while contributing to environmental and societal resilience. Meanwhile uses in T-Factor can be a way to explore this challenge, by prototyping new business ideas and solutions and by reinforcing cross-sectoral collaboration in the island.

Opportunity 1 - Innovative Arrangements for Collaborative Governance

The redevelopment of the island can create the conditions to explore and experiment with innovative forms and arrangements for collaborative and participatory governance. Through the prototyping and agile approach of temporary uses, T-Factor can offer the opportunity to co-design mechanisms for collaboration, development of joint projects and initiatives and for co-creating a shared and strong vision for the redevelopment.

Opportunity 2 - Enterprise Creation, Entrepreneurship Education and New Business Models

By supporting the collaboration between the different actors already existing in the island and prospective tenants, T-Factor can contribute to boost entrepreneurship education, the development of new business models and employment opportunities. One characteristic that defines the grassroots agents that develop their activity on the island is their capacity for entrepreneurship. These are agents who have high motivation, vocation and full confidence in their project and can develop it despite adverse circumstances. On the other hand, both these grassroots agents and the HEIs have a collaborative character and are interested in getting involved in collaborative activities beyond their activity. Zorrozaurre offers the opportunity to design and prototype meanwhile projects, as it is an extensive area undergoing regeneration that could be converted into a living lab. The island offers the possibility of being a testing ground for students and professionals in areas such as urban production, circular economy, urban production, culture and creativity.

Opportunity 3 - A Regulatory Framework for the Meanwhile

T-Factor may contribute to define and test a regulatory sandbox for temporary uses in the city. Exploring this opportunity is deemed key in order to be able to support both existing and new temporary initiatives, and allow them to develop in a clear, accountable and favourable legal and regulatory environment.

Opportunity 4 - Influencing Policies & Strategies

The City of Bilbao is committed to a number of strategic plans and roadmaps that aspire to support Bilbao in its transition towards a knowledge-based, climate friendly and socially cohesive city. One of the pillars in its urban development strategy is the shift from a smart to a creative and cultural city with highly specialized services. In this context, T-Factor may offer the opportunity to feed and even influence existing plans and strategies, leveraging temporary uses as possible testbeds for multiple innovations across placemaking, community engagement, entrepreneurship development, mobility and more.

2.1.3. Needs

Legal Framework

As mentioned above, the topic of the legal framework of temporary use appears to be critical for the success of the Zorrozaurre pilot within T-Factor. This topic is a priority in terms of support that the T-Factor project can provide.

Funding, Capital Deployment & Business Models for Temporary Uses

Defining business models and capital deployment mechanisms for temporary uses is also a need, in order to provide support to both existing and new temporary initiatives.

Governance Model

Although steps are being taken to build it, to date there is no governance model for Zorrozaurre. This is also where T-Factor can provide support, in the first instance by showcasing models and arrangements that have been adopted in other contexts.

Storytelling & Outreach

Lastly, a specific need is also identified around the design and development of engaging narratives and storytelling approaches that can support engagement and outreach.

2.2. MEANWHILE SPACES AND USES

Zorrozaurre has a relatively long history of temporary uses. These have taken the industrial spaces that became vacant with the deindustrialisation of the island. Some of these temporary uses are still in the location where they started, while others have already moved when the spaces they used to be in were developed into their final form. Most of these temporary activities are related to culture and creative industries. Below we provide a screenshot of some of the actors currently operating in the island, including through temporary initiatives. The full map can be accessed at this link:

<https://kumu.io/tfactor/zorotzaurre-bilbao#organisations>

2.2.1. Existing Meanwhile Spaces and Uses

Asociacion Haceria Arteak

Pioneers of the meanwhile in Bilbao and actively involved in the development of the island. The Hacería Arteak association works to ensure that art, culture and heritage strengthen, integrate and transform territories, communities and organisations with a clear neighbourhood vocation, promoting the attraction of activity to the area, facilitating work for entrepreneurs looking for a place to set up on the island, defending cultural heritage by maintaining abandoned facilities. They are today a consolidated movement of many people working for the social, economic and cultural revitalisation of the neighbourhood through the creation, intervention and enhancement of memory. The space has two areas: 1/ LA NAVE VA, the former headquarters of the company Kiperman, now a shared workspace or co-working space where residents' projects are housed. 2/ The Terminal, a former stamping and boiler factory, with more than 2,500 m², converted into a place for the exhibition and celebration of events, markets and urban festivals.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Industrial
Type of meanwhile use	Workspace & co-working; Education & training; Cultural activities.
Stakeholders involved and roles	Hacería Arteak association
Target Groups	Young people; Artists & Creatives; Makers & Artesans; Migrants & Refugees; Older People; Citizens at large.
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	Active since 2008 - in progress Stable Use
Relation to T-Factor	Informed

Espacio Open

Ecosystem of creative and social projects, which occupies the premises of a former biscuit factory in Bilbao (Artiach Factory) and to a large extent, thanks to their activity, they have helped to preserve one jewel of the island's historical heritage.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Industrial
Type of meanwhile use	Workspace & co-working; Education & training; Cultural activities
Stakeholders involved and roles	Espacio Open
Target Groups	Young people; Artists & Creatives; Makers & Artesans; Migrants & Refugees; Older People; Citizens at large.
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	Active since 2009 - in progress Stable Use
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Espacio Open is a full partner of the Local Coalition. It has settled in the area for years, having strongly contributed to create and support a creative community in the island. Thanks to the active engagement of EO, there are opportunities to reach out directly to other grassroots initiatives in Zorrozaurre, while also leveraging EO's expertise in creativity-led capacity building and programming in a range of topics, including urban manufacturing, digital tech, culture & arts.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged (Local Coalition Member)

Piugaz

Climbing school with a climbing wall that occupies a 2,000 square metre pavilion. It is one of the largest climbing walls in Europe for its size and for its European vision of the sport of climbing and for its training techniques for beginners, amateurs and high-level competition and performance on rock.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Industrial
Type of meanwhile use	Sport & Leisure
Stakeholders involved and roles	Piugaz (initiator and facility manager)
Target Groups	Young people; Children; Citizens at large.
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	Active since 2004 - in progress Stable Use
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Opportunity to reach out to young people and citizens at large, while exploring possibilities of temporary use programmes that revolve around active lifestyles, sports and leisure.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Gure Txoko

Non-profit skateboard school that occupies 2,000 square metres in the facilities of the old Artiach factory. Its goal is to promote skateboarding.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Industrial
Type of meanwhile use	Sport & Leisure
Stakeholders involved and roles	Gure Txoko (initiator and facility manager).
Target Groups	Young people; Children; Citizens at large.
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	Active since 2006 - in progress Stable Use
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Opportunity to reach out to young people, children, and citizens at large, while exploring possibilities of temporary use programmes that revolve around active lifestyles, sports and leisure.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Zirkozaurre

Centre of creation and exhibition of circus and performative arts. Its headquarters are now located on the first floor of the old Artiach factory after the building they used to be based at was demolished during the first phase of the project.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Industrial
Type of meanwhile use	Arts, Sport & Leisure
Stakeholders involved and roles	Zirkozaurre (initiator and facility manager).
Target Groups	Artists & Creatives; Young people; Children; Citizens at large.
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	Active since 2012 - in progress Stable Use
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Opportunity to reach out to young people, children, families and citizens at large, while exploring possibilities of temporary use programmes that revolve around performative arts.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Karola Zirko

Space for Basque, and Viscaian, professional circus and street theatre companies to develop their activities. Their goal is to disseminate circus and street theatre and offer a space designed by and for the companies.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Industrial
Type of meanwhile use	Arts, Sport & Leisure
Stakeholders involved and roles	Karola Zirko (initiator and facility manager)
Target Groups	Artists & Creatives; Young people; Children; Citizens at large.
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	Active since 2012 - in progress Stable Use
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Opportunity to reach out to young people, children, families and citizens at large, while exploring possibilities of temporary use programmes that revolve around performative arts.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Pabellón 6

Non-profit association of creators of Performing Arts established in Pabellón N°6. Their objectives are the organisation, generation, promotion and dissemination of different activities related to the Performing Arts in the Basque Country. In 2015, Pabellón 6 launched the first promotion of the Young Company, a pioneering performing arts project.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Industrial
Type of meanwhile use	Arts, Sport & Leisure
Stakeholders involved and roles	Pabellón 6 Association (initiator and facility manager)
Target Groups	Artists & Creatives; Young people; Children; Citizens at large.
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	Active since 2011 - in progress Stable Use
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Opportunity to reach out to young people, families and citizens at large, while exploring possibilities of temporary use programmes that revolve around performative arts.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Artiatx

Artiatx (from 2019) Project located in the Artiach Factory. It is an arts studio where independent artists offer their knowledge and resources to resident's projects. They also have an exhibition space.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Industrial
Type of meanwhile use	Arts, Sport & Leisure
Stakeholders involved and roles	Artiatx Cultural Association (initiator and facility manager)
Target Groups	Artists & Creatives; Young people; Children; Citizens at large.
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	Active since 2019 - in progress Stable Use
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Opportunity to reach out to young artists and citizens at large.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Espacio 600

A cultural space that occupies a two-storey warehouse that houses a mattress company. Espacio 600 hosts activities such as meetings, exhibitions, exhibitions, markets and all kinds of cultural events. They started their activity in December 2020.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Industrial
Type of meanwhile use	Arts, Sport & Leisure
Stakeholders involved and roles	A cultural association specialized in organizing cultural events (initiator and facility manager)
Target Groups	Artists & Creatives; Young people; Children; Citizens at large.
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	Active since 2020 - in progress Stable Use
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Opportunity to reach out to young people, artists, families and citizens at large.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Bilbao School of Cinematographic Creation

Small school that provides film courses and it is based at the former Artiach biscuit factory and that counts 60 students. In Zorrozaurre since 2020.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Industrial (It is located in the former offices of an industrial company)
Type of meanwhile use	Arts, Sport & Leisure
Stakeholders involved and roles	ECCBI Small Cooperative (initiator and facility manager)
Target Groups	Artists & Creatives; Young people; Citizens at large.
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	Active since 2020 - in progress Stable Use
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Opportunity to reach out to young people, artists, families and citizens at large.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

2.2.2. Planned Meanwhile Spaces and Uses

There is currently no plan for the temporary use of spaces in Zorrozaurre. It might be that new agents will rent private spaces that are available in the Phase 2 area, as has been the case with Espacio 600, which arrived on the island after the start of T-Factor, but there is no plan for this. What could also happen is that, driven by the T-Factor project, new temporary spaces could emerge through collaborations between agents, but we are at a stage of the project where this has not yet happened.

On the other hand, our intention is to make use of the meanwhile spaces mentioned above, as well as the public space, to develop some of the activities carried out in the framework of T-Factor. Likewise, it is in these spaces where the temporary solutions that arise from the collaboration between agents to face the challenges of the island that are susceptible to be addressed from T-Factor can also be prototyped. This fits with the interest that exists in the Economic Promotion Area of Bilbao Ekintza in turning Zorrozaurre into a testing ground or living lab, giving the opportunity to try out new solutions.

2.3. ENGAGEMENT, EXPLORING AND INQUIRING, SUPPORT ACTIVITIES

This section describes engagement, exploring and inquiring, and support activities currently ongoing, recently delivered or planned for the near future. More in detail, content is articulated into the following sub-sections:

- **‘Existing & Planned Engagement Activities’** describes both existing and planned engagement activities in the area that are **not initiated or directly supported by T-Factor**.
- **‘Exploring & Inquiring Activities’** describes local exploration activities run by the Local Coalition **in the context of T-Factor**.
- **‘Support Activities & T-Labs Probes’** describes supporting activities that are developed by the Local Coalition in close collaboration **with Agency members and relevant T-Labs**.
- Lastly, the section provides a general overview of the **relational ecosystem of stakeholders** that characterises the pilot at the time of writing this report (November 2021).

2.3.1. Existing and Planned Engagement Activities

Timeline

	2021	2022	2023	2024
Bilbao AS Fabrik				

Bilbao As Fabrik

Impact Domains

- *Cultivating Innovation*
- *Growing Prosperity*

Bilbao As Fabrik is a project promoted and led by Bilbao City Council, through the Bilbao Ekintza Municipal Society, and co-funded by the European Commission through the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), after being selected as a UIA (Urban Innovative Actions) project. The aim of the project is to promote advanced services for Industry 4.0 and the digital economy based on the consolidation of the Isle of Zorrozaurre as an innovative ecosystem. Participants of the Bilbao As Fabrik project, alongside Bilbao City Council, are strategic partners including the Mondragón Corporation, the University of Mondragón, MIK, Orkestra, GAIA, IDOM and EIKEN. This serves to highlight the importance of public and private collaboration in the promotion of major initiatives which contribute to the sustainable economic development of the city. The project aims to improve the competitiveness of local businesses in the KIBS (Knowledge Intensive Business Services) sector, through a collaborative capacity building process. This allows a suitable response to be offered to the challenges associated with the digital transformation of the industrial sector, consolidating the Isle of Zorrozaurre, where it is located, as an innovative ecosystem of reference in the area of advanced services for Industry 4.0 and the digital economy. The epicentre of the project is the Beta 2 Building, which has been fitted out as a centre of reference for the project and a meeting point for the proposed activities.

Highlights of the activity	
Stakeholders Bilbao City Council, Mondragón Corporation, the University of Mondragón, MIK, Orkestra, GAIA, IDOM and EIKEN	Relation to T-Factor Engaged
Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities Synergies between T-Factor and Bilbao AS Fabrik are already under exploration and discussion and will be further elaborated during a workshop planned for early November 2021, which shall also kickstart the scoping & ideation stage in the Zorrozaurre pilot.	

Planned Engagement Activities

At the time of writing this report, the Local Coalition is not aware of already planned engagement and consultation activities that will be run in the island, apart from those daily engagement activities that many actors already active in Zorrozaurre may run as part of their specific missions.

2.3.2. T-Factor Exploring and Inquiring Activities

Timeline of E&I Activities

	Jul 21			Sept 21			Oct 21			Nov 21	
Stakeholder KoM Meeting	X										

Guided Tour		X											
Mapping & Scoping Workshop										X			
EZZ Festival										X			

KoM Zorrozaurre Stakeholders

On June 30, 2021, a virtual meeting was held between the grassroots agents and the universities currently operating on the island of Zorrozaurre. The aims of this meeting were:

- Share the progress of T-Factor.
- Allow the agents to get to know each other and reinforce connections.

This was a first step towards building community among the agents, aligned with the impact domain “*Building Communities*”. This activity was needed in order to activate connections across these different actors, as a preliminary step in addressing the key challenge of *creating an innovation ecosystem*. The Programme for this activity included a broad presentation of T-Factor and its key challenges at pilot level, as well as a discussion on possible paths and ideas for collaboration.

Impact domain(s)	N/A
Activity Objectives	This activity aimed at gathering key stakeholders of the island together, in order to duly inform them about the project, understand interest and kickstart the engagement process.
When/Where	June 30, 2021 - Online meeting
Activity Providers	Bilbao Ekintza in close collaboration with Tecnalia and Espacio Open
Participants & Beneficiaries	11 participants representatives of different organisations
Insights	The level of participation in this activity was high and its objectives were achieved as it served not only to allow the attendees to get in contact with each other, but also to create the starting conditions for trust and collaboration. This virtual meeting also confirmed the agents' need to learn more about each other's activities, as well as the spaces where each of them carries out their activities. Thanks to the ideas that arose, we were able to give greater concreteness to the idea of visits to spaces that we had already been preparing.
Outputs	N/A
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced awareness and information about the T-Factor project

- Created a first dialogue with key stakeholders in the island as a basis for engagement and co-creation of meanwhile activities.

Meet your Neighbours

A 2-day collective visit on the island (12/13 July, 2021), organised to create closer contacts and allow the participants to better know the spaces and activities of the various agents active in Zorrozaurre.

Impact domain(s)	Building Communities
Activity Objectives	This activity aimed at convening local actors in the island through a guided tour in Zorrozaurre, in order to facilitate 'get to know each other's projects and initiatives.
Activity Description	<p>After the virtual meeting described above, the Local Coalition organised a 2-day collective visit on the island (12/13 July, 2021), in order to create closer contacts and allow the participants to better know the spaces and activities of the various agents active in Zorrozaurre. The Local Coalition supported the organisation and follow up of the visit, with great collaboration from all the actors directly involved in the tour.</p>

Photo credits: Tecnalía

When/Where	12/13 July 2021
Activity Providers	Bilbao Ekintza, Tecnalía and Espacio Open. All actors mentioned above actively collaborated in the organisation of the tour.
Participants & Beneficiaries	Overall, the visit included 12 sites across the island, and involved around 15 participants.
Insights	The feedback gathered during and after the activity were positive. The visit has been perceived to be useful, especially in terms of better knowing the different activities and organisations already existing and operating in the island, as well as to foster a good climate of trust needed for future collaborations. Although the University of the Basque Country and the University of Deusto aren't located in the area, they were invited. We consider their involvement in the organisation of the activities planned in the Bilbao pilot is crucial. In addition, both universities plan to be located on the island in the medium to long term as part of their strategy.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Photos • Collection of feedback cards
Outcomes	From a strategic perspective, this activity helped achieve a more direct and better understanding of the various initiatives and actors already active in the island. It also confirmed the opportunity for T-Factor to work as a 'connection' platform, particularly between Universities and grassroots initiatives. This guided tour also added a 'relational' contribution - i.e. activating more direct and horizontal relationships between actors in Zorrozaurre, which is a pre-

condition for the project to ignite and sustain collaborative ‘meanwhile’ projects.

Mapping & Scoping Workshop

Half-day workshop facilitated by LAMA and ANCI, which made use of the T-Factor Theory of Change and a canvas designed for this purpose. The methodology has been loosely built on backcasting dynamics, which usually start from inquiring into a desired future to then ‘reverse engineer’ the process to the ‘what can be done now’ in response to this future.

Impact domain(s)	All
Activity Objectives	The key objective of this Activity was to engage the local actors in a shared yet guided discussion about the desired futures, perceived issues and barriers and opportunities for collaboration in the framework of T-Factor. It built on the insights already emerged through previous research in T-Factor (ref. D2.2) to further enrich and expand the constellation of issues, challenges and opportunities already mapped, by including new perspectives and points of view from different actors in Zorrozaurre. It is worth highlighting that the insights of the workshop helped develop further the preliminary maps built for Zorrozaurre as a part of the support activities delivered by the Agency.
When/Where	Espacio Open, Zorrozaurre Bilbao, 28 October 2021
Activity Providers	LAMA Agency & ANCI Toscana, in close collaboration with Bilbao Ekintza, Tecnalía, Espacio Open and the University of the Arts London
Participants & Beneficiaries	23 Participants from the following organisations: Artiatx Bilbao Ekintza Bobo Espazioa Digipen Espacio 600 Espacio Open Herrizikleta Piugaz Pabellon nº6 ECCB - Escuela de Creacion Cinematografica de Bilbao Agirre Lehendakaria Center University of the Arts London Zirkozaurre
Insights	This activity has produced an extensive visual report, which can be found here:

	https://tfactor.kumu.io/zz-as-a-creative-hub?token=1qmQAIPxqnEREIHx
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zorrozaurre Dynamic Maps: https://kumu.io/tfactor/Zorrozaurre-bilbao • Report mentioned above
Outcomes	This activity contributed to create a collaborative environment of discussion between the various actors involved, as well as to define preliminary opportunities for intervention that T-Factor can support.

EZZ - Festival de Puertas Abiertas Erribera Zorrozaurre Zabalik (Open Day)

The Open Day - organised on October 29 and 30 - has been conceived as **a large call to citizens to come and visit the area**. It has been organised in close collaboration with some of the organisations and actors engaged so far. In the context of this event, the Local Coalition has also established strategic synergies with the Erasmus+ Eureka project, which seeks to create an international profile and curriculum for training urban professionals to become urban managers.

Impact domain(s)	Building Communities Making Places Cultivating Innovation
Activity Objectives	The key objective of the Open Day was to actively engage stakeholders in the island in the co-creation of a joint event that would create high visibility and information about the Zorrozaurre redevelopment, as well as about the already existing actors and initiatives operating in the island. The event also aimed at building trust among existing actors by collaborating in the organisation of a neighbourhood initiative and gaining media visibility for the whole island as a creative ecosystem that complements the existing cultural, creative and sports agenda in the city.
When/Where	Zorrozaurre Bilbao, 29/30 October 2021
Activity Providers	Bilbao Ekintza, Espacio Open, Tecnalía supervising the organisation of the event. The Open Day has seen the active contribution of the following organisations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ECCBI • Bobo Espazioa • Zirkozaurre • Artiatx • Gure Txoko • Pabellon n.6 • Piugaz • HerrizikletaBilbao

Participants & Beneficiaries

The participants in the event were mainly young people from the area and students studying in the HEIs operating in Zorrozaurre. In the age range of 10-30 years old in the majority. We had 191 registered participants in the event even though thanks to the public approach to it, more people came in. Here some figures of the registered participants:

In addition to those who registered the activities, about 100 others participated in activities for which registration was not required, bringing the total number of participants to **about 300 people**.

Photo credits: Espacio Open.

Insights

This Erribera Zorrozaurre Zabalik event was a continuation of the Know your Neighbours event in which the main objective was similar. Both events were focused on building community in Zorrozaurre among the agents that operate on the island, although it is true that this second event aimed to provide the students of the HEIs that operate on the island with a deeper vision of Zorrozaurre and what is happening there. The students (and other participants) have been able to discover a creative, artistic Zorrozaurre that may have been unknown to them previously, and this is a very important insight for the project as we have seen how activities of this style help to make visible the nature of the agents that operate in the meanwhile of the island and provide context for the students as to what the island was and what is currently happening on it.

Outputs

<https://www.elcorreo.com/bizkaia/industria-creativa-zorrozaurre-20211030180438-nt.html>
<https://play.cadenaser.com/audio/1635428548588/?ssm=whatsapp>
<https://www.t-factor.eu/es/ezz-festival-de-puertas-abiertas-erribera-zorrozaurre-zabalik-eng/>
<https://www.tecnalia.com/sala-de-prensa/bilbao-celebra-el-primer-festival-erribera-Zorrozaurre-zabalik>

Outcomes

The active participation of the HEIs in the event and the involvement of their students in the activity has created an inertia that we can build on for future activities (such as a pilot project with students in the framework of the Innovation Missions, for example). The EZZ Fest has also created momentum among the grassroots organisations to look forward for more collaboration

in the island to achieve collective objectives. In terms of capacity building, it has certainly created a very good starting point to enhance collective initiatives in the near future.

2.3.3. Exploring and Inquiring Support Activities and T-Labs probes

The following support activities have been implemented within the Exploring and Inquiring stage of the Pilot.

Timeline of E&I Support Activities

The following GANTT summarizes the support activities for the Zorrozaurre pilot, including in terms of support from the Agency and the T-Labs selected at this stage.

Activities	Explanation	Provider	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
Kumu Mapping	Definition of Maps and categories	Agency						
	Maps implementation	Agency						
	Map check & refinement including translation	Agency						
	Training on how to further develop the map through mapping tools	Agency						
Storytelling	Storyboard	Agency						
	Story implementation	Agency						
	Website integration and launch	Agency						
Probes								
CoP	TBD	T-Lab 1						
Governance of Innovation ecosystems	Concept	T-Lab 6						
	Case Study Report "Collaborative Governance Models"	T-Lab 6						
	Workshop, online	T-Lab 6					mid Nov	

Kumu Maps (Agency Activity)

A Kumu-based mapping and visualisations that allow the Local Coalition to keep track of:

- Core challenges, problems and opportunities that emerge over time in the development of the pilot;
- Actors that are mapped, informed and engaged over time;
- Initiatives in the area that are relevant to the scope and themes addressed by the pilot, and that can be either T-Factor or non T-Factor driven.

Impact domain(s)	All
Activity Objectives	This activity aimed to provide the Local Coalition with an easy-to-use tool to visualise the complex ecosystem of challenges, opportunities, actors and initiatives connected to the Zorrozaurre site, with key attention on the topic of cultural and creativity-led innovation . Such an activity is a key step in understanding and representing the complex dynamics that surround the pilot initiatives, while also producing content and insights that can inform an engaging storytelling strategy.
Activity Description	<p>These maps are meant as a tool to capture and navigate complexity, in order to support the Local Coalition in reflective and self-assessment processes that can help strategic decision-making. The insights of the maps shall also inform both the CoP and Governance of Innovation Ecosystem probes, by means of data and insights about the starting ecosystem of challenges, opportunities, actors and initiatives mapped in the area to date.</p> <p>A second iteration of this activity - particularly in sync with the CoP probe described later in this document - might explore new mapping and conversation tools (e.g. open survey, self-mapping tools, canvases) that the Local Coalition may adopt to further expand and enrich the mapping, therefore making it a dynamic tool to observe the progress of the local T-Factor activities over time.</p> <p>This activity runs through 4 main stages:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Definition of maps typologies and mapping categories; 2. Development of the maps by means of data stemming from the pilot report (D2.2), the bridging and validation stages which took place in spring 2021, and desk research activities performed by the knowledge bearer. 3. Map check and refinement, including translation in Spanish and Basque (TBC). 4. Training and coaching the LC members on how to use the maps and further develop them through participatory mapping methods.
When/Where	July/November 2021
Activity Providers	Agency, LAMA

Participants & Beneficiaries	<p>Participants: In its first iteration, this activity is participated and developed in collaboration with the members of the Local Coalition, therefore with a restricted group of people. This is needed to create the starting structure of the mapping, building on the direct knowledge that the local team holds in relation to the redevelopment, ongoing dynamics, challenges and issues in the area, as well as in terms of existing temporary and non-temporary initiatives.</p> <p>In a second iteration, particularly within the scope of the Scoping & Ideation stage, the mapping is meant to be opened to all the different organisations and actors with whom T-Factor will be engaging with over time.</p>
Insights	<p>This type of mapping process and the tool used seems to play an important role in understanding and managing complexity for the pilot, and it also facilitates ongoing conversation and discussion of progress between the pilot team and the various experts (for example across the Agency and T-Labs) that are following the evolution of the pilot. The preliminary insights of the map also point to the need of going deeper when it comes to existing initiatives, projects and assets that are already at stake in the island, in order to maximise the possibility for T-Factor to play a supporting role, and avoid it to be perceived as an additional layer of activities and propositions that is detached from the current reality.</p>
Outputs	3 visual maps
Outcomes	In depth representation of challenges, opportunities, actors and initiatives which can better inform the design of the strategy during the Scoping & Ideation stage.

Storytelling (Agency Activity)

This activity builds on the previously described Kumu Mapping. It uses the maps developed and translates them into an overall story that can be displayed and/or shared via different channels, including via integration with the T-Factor local website of the pilot. It is meant as a way to help the users navigate the maps and better understand the insights and data provided onto them, while creating a simple yet engaging narrative about the creative and collaborative evolution that the Local Coalition is aiming to trigger in the site.

Impact domain(s)	<p><i>Building Communities</i></p> <p><i>Making Places</i></p> <p><i>Cultivating innovation</i></p>
Activity Objectives	<p>This activity aims at providing the Local Coalition with a communication tool that can better serve the engagement process at pilot site. The institutional website of the Zorrozaurre regeneration project is indeed an important resource in this respect; however, the Local Coalition may need additional communication resources that adopt a fresher</p>

	approach and a type of language that can be closer to citizens and grassroots organisations. As for the previous activity, we are not targeting specific ToC themes, but rather addressing them all as an overarching narrative about the site, the regeneration project and what T-Factor aims to achieve.
When/Where	September - October 2021
Activity Providers	Knowledge bearer: Agency, LAMA Providers: Agency, LAMA & ANCI Toscana, Espacio Open
Participants & Beneficiaries	Participants: this activity is developed in close collaboration with the members of the Local Coalition, particularly in terms of identifying and conveying the proper narrative, key messages and approaches to storytelling.
Insights	N/A
Outputs	A full story which can be integrated in the website or shared as a presentation.
Outcomes	More effective outreach and raised interest in the project across a plethora of different local actors. Appreciation of the story by different actors and stakeholders and of its capacity to convey the complexity of the redevelopment, its challenges and aspirations.

Collaborative Governance Models for District Management – Building Local Innovation Ecosystems (T-Lab Probe)

Providing the pilot with a short case study report and workshop where different governance configurations for neighbourhood and district management models are presented and discussed. Public collaboration labs, platform-based models, community trusts, pacts of collaboration are some examples of governance arrangements that can trigger local innovation ecosystems, and be 'tested' through meanwhile activities aimed at engaging and empowering different audiences in the reactivation and management of urban assets.

Impact domain(s)	<i>Building Communities</i> <i>Cultivating innovation</i> <i>Growing prosperity</i>
Activity Objectives	This probe aims at providing the Local Coalition with starting inspiration and knowledge about possible paths of innovations for district and territorial governance. More in particular, the probe aims to offer an overview on collaborative governance forms and cases that embed principles and mechanisms of distributed and peer to peer collaboration,

	as a way to create more active, participatory, accountable and resilient "innovation ecosystems".
Activity Description	<p>This probe runs through 2 main stages and transitions into a T-Cycle activity in 2022:</p> <p>Brief case-study report with inspirational cases (Sept-Nov 21): TUDO develops a short case study report about different collaborative governance models for districts/quarter management; including different legal forms and business models (municipality-owned, for-profit, associations/NGOs), e.g. 22@Poblenou Barcelona, InWest Dortmund. The report will include recommendations for building local innovation ecosystems. Here, emphasis is put on the relation between the governance model and the innovation model of the district. This includes investigating the role of transformative urban governance and transformative innovation policies on a local level.</p> <p>Online-Workshop (Nov 21) to share the insights of the report and identify and discuss possible ways forward with the Local Coalition and key stakeholders.</p> <p>Outlook: Workshop in Bilbao (March 2022) as a T-Cycle activity for an in-depth exploration of collaborative governance models for Zorrozaurre.</p>
When/Where	September - November 2021
Activity Providers	T-Lab 6, TUDO and City of Dortmund
Participants & Beneficiaries	<p>Probe: Local Coalition Members and representatives from Bilbao City, Urban Development.</p> <p>Outlook T-Cycle: Local Coalition and key stakeholders, including local universities, grassroots organisations already active in the island, prospective tenants and representatives from Bilbao City Council as target-groups for discussing the insights and discoveries of the probe and understanding the viability in the context of Zorotzaurre's redevelopment.</p>
Insights	Collaborative governance models for district management can provide a (more or less) formalised organisational model for long-term cooperation between many different actors with the aim of placemaking at a specific site in the city. The legal statute, terms of references or articles of association of these models determine to a great extent the purpose, tasks, participation, decision-making procedures, and funding structures of the organisation. Structures can be developed that put

	collaboration as a defining principle in all these dimensions (purpose, tasks, participation, decision-making procedures and funding).
Outputs	Case study report Online workshop discussing insights and possible ways forward
Outcomes	Increased knowledge on the topic of collaborative governance models for district management and on existing frameworks, arrangements and tools by the local coalition and invited stakeholders. Increased alignment and consensus on the need to further develop and experiment with this topic across different stakeholders.

Communities of Practice (CoP) T-Lab Probe

Impact domain(s)	<i>Building Communities</i> <i>Cultivating innovation</i>
Activity Description	At the time of writing this report, this probe is still under definition. The CoP Probe initially entailed a conversation about the specific context of Zorrozaurre. Documentation from the Euston Pilot was shared, and the interview canvas was discussed and seemed to offer some initial ideas for Zorrozaurre. It was decided that after the 'Open Day' the relationship to the Probe would be reviewed. A meeting about Euston's Eols might be interesting in terms of identifying opportunities for activities, communities and practitioners who can be involved. The Euston CoP has been doing this type of work and is aware of a number of particular challenges that may be of interest for Bilbao. A discussion about the relationship to the Bilbao HEI is a possibility. What the probe is offering is the possibility of collaboration with the project, something that is of great value, pedagogically to HEIs (as practice based pedagogical material).

2.3.4. Overview of Stakeholders

At the time of writing this report (November 2021), the relational ecosystem of the Zorrozaurre pilot comprises **25 different organisations**, with the following characteristics:

- 6 are Universities;
- 2 are R&I Institutions;
- 2 are local public authorities;
- 15 are local associations, mostly cultural and social-type.

Out of these 25 organisations, **20 have been already actively involved** through preliminary meetings and conversations, as well as through activities organised by the Local Coalition. There is huge diversity and richness in terms of topics addressed by these various actors (ex.

Health, wellbeing, skills, creativity, making, etc.), as well as in terms of already existing assets across funding, spaces, training & capacity building programmes, communities, etc.

The map of all stakeholders is provided in the Figure below and it can be accessed [here](#) in its dynamic fashion.

Stakeholders Map in Zorrozaurre, own elaboration.

2.4. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

The Exploring and inquiring (E&I) phase has reaffirmed the conclusions of the pilot analysis report (D2.2. Pilot report). In this regard, several challenges were identified thanks to the collaboration established with the agents involved in the meanwhile of the island. These challenges set the framework for the next steps to be taken.

The main goal in Bilbao's pilot is the creation of a community of practice (CoP) which gives answers to the challenges raised in the T-Factor framework. For this, it is planned to design and organise activities that deepen the collaboration between stakeholders operating on the island to create a collaborative ecosystem that could be the seed of future collaborative innovation systems on the island.

For the engagement of stakeholders is foreseen the organisation of working meetings, workshops and/or encounters with specific issues that are of interest to them. Bilbao Ekintza

has a long-standing relationship with most of the organisations it wants to involve in the development of the project. With those agents with whom this relationship does not yet exist, it is understood that their commitment will be achieved through participative and inclusive activities. The design of these activities is yet to be specified because the aim is to design them through co-creation with the agents to be involved.

Regarding the financing of the activities, Bilbao Ekintza, as the city's economic development agency, has the resources to co-finance them. This funding can be in the form of grants or by integrating actions from other strategic projects of the city in T-Factor.

KAUNAS ALEKSOTAS

3. KAUNAS ALEKSOTAS

3.1. PILOT STARTING CONTEXT AND PRIORITIES

Kaunas is the second biggest city in Lithuania. It is located at the intersection of the two longest rivers of the country, Nemunas and Neris. The landscape of Kaunas is quite special; driving across city districts, one may experience rivers' valleys, green slopes, and curvy riverbanks. Aleksotas district is in the Southern part of the city, on the upper terrace of the Nemunas river. Aleksotas district used to be a quiet separated area from the rest of the city, therefore its urban morphology consists mainly of low rise monofunctional buildings, mostly residential. The situation changed in 2002, once the second bridge construction (M.K.Ciurlionis bridge) crossing the Nemunas River was completed. This new connection brought Aleksotas closer to the city. The convenient geographical location ensures good accessibility for both foreign and local markets' businesses. Since 2015 the city of Kaunas has been putting a great effort and investment into upgrading this neighbourhood. In general, Aleksotas is undergoing an increasing attention for urban redevelopment. Many new housing projects are taking place along the river Nemunas in Freda district as well as in the outskirts of Aleksotas district.

In order to attract investments and investors, **Kaunas needs to create appealing conditions for them and their businesses.** One of the methods to achieve that is by creating non-polluting industry parks. The establishment of the **Aleksotas Innovation Industry Park** is an important project throughout the country, as it can contribute to the implementation of the national strategic goals and objectives of the Republic of Lithuania.

The territory of the Aleksotas Innovation Industry Park location is known for being used as a testing site for helicopters. Moreover, its surroundings preserve the history of the Kaunas Fortress. The Kaunas Fortress is a fortress complex that was constructed between 1882 and 1915 to protect the Russian Empire's western borders. Later, during the period of the First Republic of Lithuania, the military warehouses became a garage, where the tanks were parked. Ammunition and gunpowder warehouses that are located on the North side of the site, remain. The main warehouse is transformed into the workshop space and the headquarters office of the "Kaunas Fortress". Some other warehouses and artillery batteries are abandoned; however, they have a great potential to be transformed and adopted for public needs. This Fortress complex in combination with the AIIP development could create a significant recreational area not only for the future AIIP talents but also for the citizens of the whole city. Regarding potential spaces for meanwhile uses, the surrounding area contains various warehouses, sheds and abandoned buildings that might also have a chance to be transformed to adopt creative temporary uses.

The goal of the AIIP development is to convert the former military base into an industrial innovation area designated to low carbon companies that create high intellectual value through scientific research and experimental projects. Three main directions are drafted: biomed, biopharma and bio-food. The AIIP has the potential to create a strong link between research institutions and local business. By facilitating a closer exchange between University

& Research and Industry it will increase national competitiveness and create added social and economic value. The main document that will define the guidelines for the developers and investors coming into the AIIP is the Development Plan. It will contain various development guidelines and KPI's, including the territory's urban development vision and its potential application for meanwhile uses during the waiting time. This document is expected to be prepared in the first quarter of 2022.

3.1.1. Issues

A number of key issues are to be addressed within the Aleksotas regeneration. In this section, these issues are elaborated in order of importance, and related to the 'impact domains' identified within the evaluation framework of T-Factor.

Identity

Impact Domains

- *Cultivating innovation*
- *Building Communities*
- *Making Places*

The AIIP territory has been closed to the public for years, thus is perceived as an unknown and undiscovered territory to many. Citizens are not used to exploring and accessing the territory. Until today the identity of the area relates to 'military' and 'aircraft' industry, as it is a former military base located next to the Aleksotas sports airport and historically was used as a helicopter base. Kaunas municipality aims to convert the territory to the innovation industry park, meaning the identity of the area should shift from the present (military aircraft industry) to the future one related to R&D. This means also building the R&D and innovative enterprise communities around the site; bringing in the 'ambassadors' to drive wider communities around the chosen R&D thematic topics. Although the main theme of the AIIP is more or less set, there is a need and potential to create a vision for the territory for the waiting time.

Access to Meanwhile and Awareness

Impact Domains

- *Cultivating innovation*
- *Making Places*
- *Growing prosperity*

In Lithuania and Kaunas region there is no diffused culture and practice on innovative city making methods through meanwhile uses. There are two main sub-issues: 1) lack of awareness on meanwhile and its potential values, impedance the decision makers to favour and introduce it to the process of the regeneration projects and the stakeholders/regeneration actors to take part in the meanwhile use projects; 2) the present legal framework does not support the access to meanwhile spaces. Moreover, the AIIP territory lacks meanwhile spaces, as it is mainly an open field with newly built road infrastructure. Two buildings present in the area have limited access - a) the former Helicopter hangar is in reconstruction during the time of the project, b) the former Train station is not included in the regeneration project, and the access is limited by the legal framework. The vacant territory and limited access to meanwhile make it difficult

to attract and grow new enterprises within the site as there is limited space for temporary start-up activities at the moment.

Engagement & Participation

Impact Domain

- *Building Communities*

Engagement & Participation in urban regeneration is one of the most discussed issues in Kaunas. In the past few years Kaunas municipality has delivered numerous infrastructural projects, a number of projects are undergoing at the moment. The engagement of stakeholders and local people require additional effort, specific capabilities and diffused engaging culture; lack of capability to effectively engage can lead to the unmet expectations from those being engaged, and the city is focused on the development of 'hard' infrastructure, thus engagement has not been widely practiced. Many local people and businesses want to have their voices heard; therefore, often conflictual situations arise because of a lack of engagement. On the other hand, the city needs a constructive dialog and active participation to make decisions in time, but not everyone is interested or able to do it in a constructive way.

Services, Amenities & Cultural Life

Impact Domains

- *Cultivating innovation*
- *Making Places*
- *Improving Health & Wellbeing*

The AIIP territory is a 30ha vacant territory with a newly implemented road infrastructure, where no services, amenities or cultural life exist at the moment. The territory surroundings are industrial-residential i.e. quite fragmented with little or almost none of the daily services or culture. Kaunas Municipality aims to convert the territory to the R&D area - innovation and industry park, hosting R&D workers with higher incomes; these workers will require the environments fitting to their lifestyle and quality of life i.e. work-life balance, meaning that all the daily services & cultural life should be in place, easy reachable by foot or bicycle.

R&D

Impact Domains

- *Cultivating innovation*
- *Growing prosperity*
- *Attaining sustainability*

Kaunas municipality aims to convert the territory to an innovation industry park that can become a landmark in Lithuania for academic and innovation research and development, attracting inhabitants creating added value and sustainable technologies and solutions. The city is trying to mitigate the main risk of this project which is a risk to become the second free economic zone in Kaunas which is concentrated mainly on production rather than creating higher added value. Therefore, one of the core issues is attracting and building the R&D potential within the territory.

3.1.2. Challenges and Opportunities

The following challenges and opportunities are to be addressed within the Aleksotas regeneration area.

Challenge 1 - Building Identity & Communication

Area is unknown and undiscovered by many. There is a need to develop and communicate the identity of the AIIIP. The site may be open and abandoned outside work hours and so early adopting businesses may not feel secure or comfortable.

Challenge 2 - Lack of Meanwhile Infrastructure

Lack of both 'operational' (buildings) and 'strategic' (legislation) meanwhile infrastructure on the site. The site is open ground and offers no buildings for meanwhile use during the term of the T Factor project. There is no legislation supporting meanwhile spaces, governance or use on the site beyond licensing for events. This is typical of Kaunas, as 'meanwhile use' is a new concept in the region and is as yet unsupported by legislative models and tools.

Challenge 3 - Connecting with Local Communities

So far, there has been little engagement and involvement of local communities and little consultation around the current and future plans for the site. Perhaps as a consequence of this there is some concern about gentrification and displacement amongst neighbouring residents.

Challenge 4 - Open vs Closed

There are concerns in the medium term that the site may not be attractive to early adopting businesses due to the fact that there is a lack of amenities for workers. The site may be open and abandoned outside work hours and so early adopting businesses may not feel secure. There is a challenge regarding the AIIIP territory's sustainable integration in the existing city's urban domain.

Opportunity 1- Cultural & Heritage Assets

Rich and diverse cultural heritage on and around the site. Kaunas Fortress, Glass Factory, green space, old railway tracks. Aleksotas marketplace is nearby. All provide opportunities for attracting residents of the nearby city centre. Some groups are already using the site for leisure activities e.g. roller-skating, walking. These groups could be engaged and supported. There is a two-stage plan for the development of the area's identity. Firstly, as a destination for cultural and leisure activities (short – medium term) and secondly as a destination for innovation and R&D (medium-long term).

Opportunity 2- Meanwhile as Experimentation Zone

Sandbox for R&D. Architects, designers, artists may be interested in experimenting with the meanwhile structures.

- There is an opportunity to use the AIIIP's as an experimental zone for exploration of meanwhile use and development of supporting strategic infrastructure.
- Post-Covid lifestyle. There is a need and appreciation for outdoor/Covid friendly venues. There is a proposal for a Covid-friendly pavilion on the site to support new uses by local people.

- There are opportunities to experiment with meanwhile provisions that support cultural and leisure activities – contributing to the development of AIIIP as a site for leisure and cultural activity.
- There is a significant space within the development – a helicopter hangar that is being transformed for use by start-ups from 2023. There might be a possibility to use some spaces for the meanwhile activities.

Opportunity 3 - Working with Existing Community, Cultural and Heritage Actors

There are a number of arts and cultural groups nearby that could be engaged in developing a cultural identity for the site. There are opportunities to engage with local communities to exchange visions of the site for the short, medium and long term.

Opportunity 4 - Cultural and Leisure Amenities

There is opportunity to find synergy between daytime and evening use of workers and evening and night time use of local communities. Such uses will provide opportunities for connection between new arrivals and local communities – ensuring a more inclusive meanwhile.

3.1.3. Needs

Communicate the Opportunity for Participation to Local Actors

How to engage local groups in the redefinition of the site and its future potential. Support residents to contribute ideas to the development plan.

Identity Co-creation

How can diverse stakeholders in the regeneration be brought together to share ideas and future visions.

Guidance and Methodology on Meanwhile Strategy

How to engage local actors in the shaping of meanwhile activities that meet their needs and promote the area to the city and business

Meanwhile Governance

Legislation and management plan to be able to access and govern meanwhile uses.

Attracting Start-ups

Make the site attractive to start-ups and their employees.

Strengthening Biotech R&I Identity

Meanwhile activation needs to consider how it might contribute to future bio tech innovation identity.

3.2. MEANWHILE SPACES AND USES

The map shows the location of existing, planned and potential meanwhile spaces and uses within the Aleksotas regeneration area over the period of the T-Factor project.

3.2.1. Existing Meanwhile Spaces and Uses

Street Race Championship

The race championship event was held around AIPP territory, using the newly established street infrastructure as a championship racetrack. The race took place on the 19th of June, 2021. The meanwhile use is Prompt. The space is an open airfield with newly built street infrastructure. Lithuania's Street race Championship is an annual auto sport event, first time established in AIPP territory. The aim of this event was to promote auto sport in Lithuania and to create an additional value to the AIPP territory. The land is owned by the Government of Lithuania. Kaunas City Municipality has the 'use right'. The LASF received permission from the municipality to organise this event. It went through a regular procedure which is required for any events in the city. Once the permission is granted, the land is being leased to the time of the event.

<https://www.lasf.lt/lt/sportas/kitos-sakos/2021-m-lietuvos-street-race-cempionato-iii-etapas/>

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Street
Type of meanwhile use	Leisure & sport
Stakeholders involved and roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LASF - Lithuania's auto sport federation. Organiser of the event • Kaunas Municipality - Mecenat & land operators under the trust right

Target groups	Children & Families, Young people
Temporality	The race took place on the 19th of June, 2021; Prompt
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring	Opportunity to initiate similar temporary use i.e. auto events organized by stakeholders and other relevant organizations.
Relation to T-Factor	Mapped

Skating, Rollerblading and Walking

Newly constructed streets are used by locals living around the AIIP Territory for sports & leisure activities like rollerblading, scooter riding, walking, etc. It could attract more healthy lifestyle promoters if some amenities are provided. The land is owned by the Government of Lithuania. Kaunas City Municipality has the 'use right'. This type of temporary use occurred naturally, without any specific pre-planning. The locals saw the potential of freshly laid streets and started using them. Streets are perfectly suitable for skating and rollerblading and being free of traffic ensures safety. Community, young people living around the area could be engaged in using infrastructure more often, if more amenities offered. Further funding could be obtained from public investors.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Streets
Type of meanwhile use	Leisure & sport
Stakeholders involved and roles	Local community, young people
Target groups	Children & Families, Young people
Temporality	Use is stable, seasonal, occurring in spring, and ends at the end of autumn.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	A discussion with local inhabitants and other stakeholders (e.g. skater's communities, skating championship organisers, makers) could be held on the skatepark infrastructure establishment as a meanwhile space in the territory.
Relation to T-Factor	Mapped

Collecting Flowers (fields of natural flowers)

At the moment, the territory of the AIIP is an open field crossed by a newly built infrastructure network. Naturally, the unused land is perfect for wild flowers and weeds to grow. Aleksotas inhabitants living around the area are coming here to have a walk and eventually started collecting the found flora according to their needs. This activity emerged organically.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Existing street network. Military aerodrome.
Type of meanwhile use	Green & garden; Health spot
Stakeholders involved and roles	Locals - engaging with the territory after it became open to the public.
Target groups	Local tenants (women and kids)
Temporality	Regular, every summer season.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	A discussion with local inhabitants and other stakeholders (e.g. gardeners, botanics) could be held in the public garden for planting vegetables or herbs during the waiting time of the AIP development
Relation to T-Factor	Mapped

Urban Gardening in Workspace of Kaunas Fortress Park

On September 19th of 2021, the project “Šilainiai project” together with Kaunas Fortress Park tried to share experience about composting in the city, raising questions from sustainability to climate change. The project was held in one of the warehouses, which is now the administrative office of Kaunas Fortress Park. The workspace is a former military warehouse of ammunition, built in the late XIX c. Later, in the period of the First Republic of Lithuania the military warehouse became a garage, where the military tanks were parked. Today, the workspace is an office of Kaunas Fortress Park and workshop space for a reconstruction of military items, which are found in fortress buildings around Kaunas. The workspace of Kaunas Fortress Park is next to the AIP territory and it is easy to access through newly built infrastructure. “Šilainiai project” is a creative platform for the community residents to participate in a variety of cultural events. Project created by a local artist Evelina Šimkutė, who is focusing on biodiversity of the neighbourhood, urban gardening and long-term strategy for VIII fort of Kaunas fortification system. Urban gardening workshop and practical implementation of the composting site together with a local community was held in the backyard of the Kaunas Fortress Park administrative office. The project aims to show people how they can make composting sites near their home and adopt sustainable ways of living. The project is funded by the Nordic Council of Ministers Office in Lithuania. The land is owned by the Kaunas City Municipality. The Kaunas Fortress Park has the ‘trust right’.

<https://silainiaiproject.com/>

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Natural; Military
Type of meanwhile use	Green & garden; Health spot
Stakeholders involved and roles	“Šilainiai project” Kaunas Fortress Park

Target groups	Children & Families, Young people, Older people
Temporality	The meanwhile activity is prompt.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	A discussion with local inhabitants and other stakeholders (e.g. gardeners, botanics) could be held in the public garden for composting sites during the waiting time of the AIPP development
Relation to T-Factor	No relation yet

Lecture Series (history of Kaunas military fortress)

The series of six lectures “The Influence of Kaunas Military Fortress in Kaunas modernism” took place in the workspace of Kaunas Fortress Park (September - November, 2021). The aim of this project is to present research and new findings on the history of Kaunas Fortress and how it influences the urban planning and social life of the First Republic of Lithuania. The influence of the former military fortress of Kaunas on the modern city is especially relevant in presenting a different approach to the former military cultural heritage objects, their significance and influence in the “interwar” and modern city infrastructure.

<https://youtu.be/Ole5VS3qVjE>

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Heritage, Military, Cultural
Type of meanwhile use	Workspace, Education, Researchers & Academics
Stakeholders involved and roles	The Kaunas Fortress Park.
Target groups	Researchers & Academics
Temporality	The meanwhile use is prompt.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	This is an opportunity to get to know better the history of Kaunas fortification and its impact on the modernization of Kaunas during the First Republic of Lithuania. Since there are a number of fortification buildings near the AIPP site, we can better understand the AIPP location and how it has been influenced by the fortification buildings.
Relation to T-Factor	No relation yet

Remote Tour and Photography Exhibition - former tank garage

On 2020 December 30 a remote presentation and a photography exhibition about the Tank Garage took place in the Kaunas Park Fortress workspace. The aim of this project is to present research and a collection of photographs of the former tanks garage. Large format photos are presented on the outdoors walls of Kaunas Park Fortress workshop space.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Heritage, Military, Cultural
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Type of meanwhile use	Workspace, Education, Researchers & Academics
Stakeholders involved and roles	The Kaunas Fortress Park.
Target groups	Young people, Older People, Researchers & Academics
Temporality	The meanwhile activity is prompt.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	This is an opportunity to get to know better the history of Kaunas fortification and its impact on the modernization of Kaunas during the First Republic of Lithuania.
Relation to T-Factor	No relation yet

3.2.2. Planned Meanwhile Spaces and Uses

Kaunas SandBox - R&D Test Area (smart city, green tech)

The aim of the project is to create conditions for testing innovative technologies and R&D solutions in the areas of smart city and green tech, which are complicated to test in the common public spaces because of the safety and specific infrastructural requirements. The land within the AIIIP territory is owned by the government of Lithuania and Kaunas city municipality currently manages this land on the 'use right'. The 'use right' does not allow leasing the land, therefore Kaunas city is seeking for a 'trust right', which allows land leasing (expected in 2022). In this case Kaunas municipality will be able to lease the land or agree on its temporary tenure. Nevertheless, legal framework restrictions remain regarding the land lease, which is not designed to support meanwhile uses as a strategic temporary use for the development of the specific area under regeneration. But former military warehouses bordering the AIIIP territory might be used as they are managed by Kaunas Fortress Park which has more flexibility in leasing or giving for a temporary use the warehouses to third parties. Therefore, the sandbox activities might start in the warehouses managed by Kaunas Fortress as it is way easier from the legal point of view, and then later expand to AIIIP territory if possible. By now prompt technology testing events might be organised within the AIIIP territory, and permanent sandbox activities within the Kaunas Fortress managed territory and infrastructure.

<https://kaunomtp.lt/en>

<https://niec.ktu.edu/>

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Natural; Military; Streets;
Type of meanwhile use	R&D
Stakeholders involved and roles	Kaunas Science and Technology Park (Kaunas STP) - mediator and organiser of R&D testing activities. KTU National Innovation and Business Centre (KTU NIEC) - potential mediator no.: 2. KTU NIEC is a link between science and business, ensuring a smooth mutual cooperation, commercialisation of the latest innovations

	developed at the Kaunas University, protection of intellectual property and development of newly established enterprises. - mediator and organiser of R&D testing activities.
Target groups	Startuppers and businesses, Researchers & Academics
Temporality	The project ideally could be initiated as of 2022 spring for at least 6 months and ideally could continue until the development of the site. Regular.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	The opportunity for E&I is to discuss with the Lithuanian Ministry of Innovation about the meanwhile use of the territories in urban regeneration as R&D testing areas and legal framework barriers for their implementation. The Kaunas case could be the first Lithuanian case where a testing area would strategically link the territory to the specific R&D topics aimed to be hosted there after regeneration. The Ministry could support/initiate the required actions related to the legal framework for land use, which could favor the establishment of the testing area in the AIIP territory, thus building practice on innovation testing areas as meanwhile spaces in Lithuania. The same ministry is also the decision maker regarding the promotion of the 'trust right' land licence to Kaunas municipality.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Space Syntax - Modelling of Meanwhile Uses Effects the Development of the AIIP

The aim of this project is to demonstrate the possible effects of meanwhile uses on the development and the gentrification of the territory. Space Syntax modelling software will be used to create a digital model of the AIIP territory and calculate the possible effects of meanwhile uses to the future development of the territory. Project is going to be held in digital space. AIIP territory streets, vacant land plots, former helicopter hangar is owned by Lithuanian government, and used by Kaunas city. The digital model will be owned by KTU. The event to present the digital model will be arranged in the AIIP territory according to the general requirements for organising events in public spaces in Kaunas city. Project supported by KTU internal resources, presently owned equipment will be used for modelling; data for modelling is collected from Kaunas register.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Natural; Military; Streets;
Type of meanwhile use	Research, future vision modelling, communication
Stakeholders involved and roles	KTU, Faculty of Civil Engineering and Architecture. Civil Engineering and Architecture Competence Centre (role - delivery of the model) Lithuanian Architects Union, Kaunas department (role - communication and dissemination, hosting the presentation event on the model i.e. during the architects day on July 1. 2022/2023)

Target groups	Startuppers and businesses, Researchers & Academic
Temporality	Prompt use - 2022-2023
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	The modelling can show various scenarios of the AIIP development thanks to meanwhile uses/spaces. It can help to get into constructive conversation with the decision makers and represent possible future development scenarios to the stakeholders and local inhabitants and regeneration actors involved in the delivery of the meanwhile use activities.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Circular Design Training & Acceleration Program

The aim is to build knowledge and capability in designing products based on the Circular Economy model around the territory. CD training and a product development program (CD acceleration pilot) is planned to be delivered partially online, partially within the spaces provided by the University of Applied Social Sciences and Kaunas Fortress suitable for experimentation and prototyping. The spaces are situated next to the AIIP territory. The spaces are owned by the stakeholders (University of Applied Social Sciences, Kaunas Fortress) which provide the permission to use spaces free of charge. The activity is part of the ongoing project of KTU Design Centre "Circular Design (CD) TOOLS for product integrity", which aims to develop CD TOOLS suited for the innovators from any discipline to embrace CE in product development. The project will create and test CD TOOLS and its supporting digital platform. The meanwhile activity will be the piloting of the tools. The aim is to build knowledge and capability in designing products based on the Circular Economy model around the territory. Participants will be engaged by Open call for individual innovators, entrepreneurs and SMEs to enrol to the pilot. Implemented by World-class Researcher Groups to develop R&D activities relevant to economic sectors, which can be later commercialized".

<https://en.ktu.edu/projects/cd-tools-circular-design-tools-for-product-integrity/>

<https://wearecritical.com/>

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Natural; Military; Streets;
Type of meanwhile use	Research, modelling, design, education & training
Stakeholders involved and roles	KTU Design Centre (project coordinator) Critical - service design company (partner of the CD TOOLS project) University of Applied Social Sciences (host of the training sessions) Kaunas Fortress (host of the training sessions)
Target groups	Startuppers and businesses, Researchers & Academics, Artists & Creatives, Makers & Artisans.

Temporality	Regular.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	The activity is part of the ongoing project of KTU Design Centre “Circular Design (CD) TOOLS for product integrity” Project no.: 01.2.2-LMT-K-718-03-0104, funded by the European Regional Development Fund according to the 2014–2020 Operational Programme for the European Union Funds’ Investments, under measure’s No. 01.2.2-LMT-K-718 activity “Research Projects Implemented by World-class Researcher Groups to develop R&D activities relevant to economic sectors, which could later be commercialized”. The spaces are owned by the stakeholders (University of Applied Social Sciences, Kaunas Fortress) which provide the permission to use spaces free of charge.
Relation to T-Factor	Mapped

Interdisciplinary Art Performance [VMU: International Congress on Happiness 2022]

Performative event is planned to be held around AIPP territory, close to Kaunas Fortress premises and Lakūnų street. Open air event is planned at the intersection of Kaunas Tvirtovė, Lakūnų street and AIPP territory in the public space. It is organised by Vytautas Magnus university as part of the International Congress on Happiness. The congress focuses on happiness and communities. The main aim is to merge different fields of science, culture and art in order to get closer to the difficult-to-reach and often confusing theme of happiness. During the congress, the social, philosophical, psychological, and economic aspects of the concept of happiness, their connection with community - more exactly communities that are formed by man and other forms of live species as well as artificial intelligence - will be discussed and performed. The congress will cover several different ways of articulation: scientific discussions, individual artistic creation, and elements of community art and other community activism.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Industrial; Military; Residential
Type of meanwhile use	Performative / sensoric experience of space(s)
Stakeholders involved and roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vytautas Magnus University - event organiser. • Kaunas European Capital of Culture 2022 - the event is part of the Kaunas 2022 programme. • Various surrounding communities as well as public / private organisations will be included in the performative event.
Target groups	Researchers & Academics, Artists & Creatives, Children & Families, Young people.
Temporality	Prompt, one-day event between March 17-19, 2022.

Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Opportunity to reach a wide audience of neighbouring communities, artists, press, academics, and the general public. Various surrounding communities as well as public / private organisations will be included in the performative event. The event is an opportunity to provoke a native mindset towards more inclusive (not only humans but also other species of lives) critical ecological thinking and possibly acting, this way 'losing the ground' for future identity of the AIP territory and possible innovation led mindset.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Community Event (Kaunas 2022 Programme)

The aim of the event is to bring the community of Aleksotas together and to announce that Kaunas has become the European Capital of Culture. The event will take place in one of the remnants of the helicopter landing base. The main aspect of the event will be a burning sculpture. The lights in the AIP area will be turned off and the performance of fire and lights in an open space will give an exceptional impression. Light artistic performances are one of the possible ways to operate in the territory of AIP. The light and fire performances are organized by fluxusLabas program under the project Kaunas 2022. The aim of the fluxLabas is to increase the community spirit of the people of Kaunas and the Kaunas District through cultural activities. Residents are encouraged to form resilient and creative communities through joint activities.

<https://kaunas2022.eu/>

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Streets & Squares, Military
Type of meanwhile use	Cultural, Leisure
Stakeholders involved and roles	The FluxusLabas program under the project Kaunas 2022.
Target groups	Children & Families, People
Temporality	The meanwhile use is prompt, the event will be held on January 21st, 2022.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	The opportunity to present AIP territory for a wide public audience of Kaunas residents.
Relation to T-Factor	Mapped

Mnemosyne (Kaunas 2022 Programme)

Mnemosyne project will be held in the workspace of Kaunas Fortress Park in June, 2022. Mnemosyne is a project about emotional memories and developed by a group of artists called Effetto Larsen, Italy. The meanwhile use is prompt. The project aims to create an emotional map of a place, starting from memories and experiences of people living around the territory. Starting from workshops and interviews, Effetto Larsen maps an area based on the emotional experience of those who live it, identifying and connecting spaces through the emotions they

have aroused in people. The result is a map installation. The Effetto Larsen performance is organized by fluxusLabas program under the project Kaunas 2022.

<https://kaunas2022.eu/>

<https://effettolarsen.it/>

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Heritage, Military, Cultural
Type of meanwhile use	Workspace, Artistic residency
Stakeholders involved and roles	The FluxusLabas program under the project Kaunas 2022 Effetto Larsen
Target Groups	Older people, Children & Families, Artists & Creatives
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	The meanwhile use is prompt, the event will be held on January 21th, 2022.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	The opportunity to gather life stories and information from those who live in the surroundings of AIPP territory and thus better understand their needs and expectations.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Additional Opportunities for Meanwhile Uses

Kaunas Fortress Digital Makerspace

Conversion proposal of the Kaunas Fortress Park Workshop (KFPW) into a digital hub, based on the Precious Plastic project, to raise community awareness on environmental sustainability regarding plastic recycling. The aim of the project is to make the community aware of the concept of environmental sustainability in the field of plastics, through practical activities, with high social impact and pragmatic implications in everyday life. As for the external participants, the added value of their experience will be to see first-hand the fruit of their recycling policies, as well as the possibility of sharing and expanding a new community.

<https://preciousplastic.com/index.html>

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Indoor: Industrial, Historical and former Military open spaces Outdoor: roads into and around the whole Aleksotas Innovation Park area.
Type of meanwhile use	Makerspace; Artisan, Crafts. Indoor: KFPW will be used as a makerspace - for designing and building the machinery and as a craft shop to sell all the semi-finished and finished products

	Outdoor: roads will be used as collection points to channel all the plastic waste.
Stakeholders involved and roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KTU Design Centre: Create and manage the Precious Plastic Community point, Collection point and Workspace point; • KFPW: Build and host the Precious Plastic Machine shop, Involve students and all the people interested in the Precious Plastic mission to the manufacturing process related to the plastic recycling; • KTU faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Design: Involve students in activities related to the manufacture of plastic, as well as the design of products based on the use of recycled plastic; • University of Applied Social Sciences: Involve students in activities related to the manufacture of plastic, as well as the design of products based on the use of recycled plastic; • Precious Plastic Lithuania: Train Kaunas Fortress staff and all stakeholders involved in the project on how to create a Precious Plastic pole in Kaunas. • Type of target groups: Artists & Creatives, Young people. Students, makers, artisans, volunteers, inhabitants.
Target Groups	Artists & Creatives, Young people. Students, makers, artisans, volunteers, inhabitants.
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	Stable, possible launch - 2022.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Access to the workshop and the use of the same will be free for all KTU students in possession of documentation for access to university laboratories, as well as for all employees of the KFPW. Visitors will be allowed access (for educational purposes or for the purchase of machinery/ products) but not the use of equipment. In this vision, Stakeholders and external participants are not separated but will form a single group of people who share knowledge and experience. The added value that the project aims to give to stakeholders is building places and capabilities for the development of a production reality based on recycling.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Biodivercities: Urban Wild Environments I - EDU

The project will develop on a green area not built and specifically dedicated to the development of a flora able to accommodate wild insects. The project aims to explore and encourage citizens to create more biodiverse habitats to tackle a severe ecological problem all over the world: pollinators decline. Due to high urbanisation rates and extensive landscape homogenisation for agricultural use, many insect species are experiencing massive habitat loss, and decreased floral and nesting material supply as the main factors of pollinators decline.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Natural; Military.
Type of meanwhile use	Green & garden
Stakeholders involved and roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KTU Design Centre & Delft University of Technology - Industrial Design Engineering Faculty, Sustainable Design Engineering department; toolkit developers and content creator • Kaunas Fortress & Kaunas Beekeeper Association: owners of hives on the ground of the Fortress and main users, as well as maintainers, the insect hotel and the ground unit
Target Groups	Researchers & Academics, Children & Families, Young people, Older People, Beekeepers, Farmers
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	Stable (2022-2023).
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Opportunity to reach a wide audience of neighbouring communities, press, academics, and the general public. Knowledge exchange with foreign partners could be initiated.
Relation to T-Factor	Mapped

Biodiversities: Urban Wild Environments II - TECH

This activity is part of Biodiversities project, which is aimed to deliver technological solutions, while the EDU is dedicated to educational purposes. The project aims to design a mid-tech solution where the toolkit elements equipped with sensors could measure the status of biodiversity where they are installed. Gathering data about wild pollinators and status of biodiversity through these sensing tools would also support a more scientific approach and so, hybrid outcomes: by mapping out status of biodiversity in different locations, recording taxonomic status of species, showing effects of environmental changes on species richness and abundance.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Natural; Military.
Type of meanwhile use	Green & garden
Stakeholders involved and roles	KTU Design Centre & Delft University of Technology - Industrial Design Engineering Faculty, Sustainable Design Engineering department: toolkit developers and content creator Kaunas Fortress & Kaunas Beekeeper Association: owners of hives on the ground of the Fortress and main users, as well as maintainers, the insect hotel and the ground unit
Target Groups	Researchers & Academics, Children & Families, Young People, Older people, Beekeepers, Farmers
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	The project is Regular, Stable – 2022-2023.

Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Opportunity to reach a wide audience of neighbouring communities, press, academics, and the general public. Knowledge exchange with foreign partners could be initiated.
Relation to T-Factor	Mapped

Architectural Route from City Centre to the AIP

The AIP territory is surrounded by few historical spots of Kaunas Fortress that are still undiscovered by many. Panoramic views from Kaunas Fortress community space roofs propose a completely different view to Kaunas city, compared to other available panoramic spots in Kaunas, which might become a popular place to visit and observe Kaunas from a different angle. The activity aims to attract visitors from the city centre showing the proximity of the area to the city centre. There is the possibility to use the old railway track which connects the Kaunas railway station and the AIP territory, as the means of transport - a unique experience.

<http://marsrutai.autc.lt/en/route-list>

<https://visit.kaunas.lt/en/see-and-do/tours/>

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Natural; Industrial; Military; Streets & squares.
Type of meanwhile use	Festival, interdisciplinary event, Culture & Tech.
Stakeholders involved and roles	Kaunas Fortress Park - possible key organizer Ekskursas - hospitalities Kaunas aviation museum Kaunas Artist House - education program Kaunas Municipality - landlord Kaunas Artists' House
Target Groups	Children & Families, Young people, Older people
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	The project is a Prompt, Regular with potential to become Stable - 2022 autumn-2023 spring.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	There is the opportunity to use an old railway track which connects the central train station of Kaunas to the AIP territory. Once similar initiative was delivered as a prompt activity by few architects. Opportunity to discuss the initiative with Lithuanian Railways and Architect's union, Kaunas division. Opportunity to discuss collaboration with Kaunas aviation museum and sport airport, as they can be motivated to include their offered services to the route.
Relation to T-Factor	Mapped

Multifunctional HUB

Possibility to establish a Multifunctional HUB for interdisciplinary facilities related to the needs of the AIP territory. A former train station is located next to the helicopter hangar, which will become a 'flex start' space. The former train station is a heritage building that is currently abandoned and there is no plan to renovate it by now, as it requires significant investment due to the heritage requirements. The building is owned by Kaunas city and it might be leased for up to 10 years. As it is not in use at the moment, a City council decision should be made to lease it and it is not an easy procedure. Still, this Building needs to be preserved on the other hand the AIP and the surrounding areas need basic services and a space to gather. While the Industry park's territory is being developed, this heritage object could enrich the landscape by support collaborations between arts, design & innovation, sheltering hospitality, food or other basic services missing in the AIP area at this moment. It might become a place to kick start initiatives designed to respond to the changing needs of developing AIP. As the first step at the beginning it might become an object for street art - a landmark for the AIP to attract initial interest and communicate the site, as today the site is still undiscovered by many.

<http://www.nykoka.lt/>

<https://visit.kaunas.lt/en/see-and-do/sights/street-art/>

<https://farmerscircle.lt/>

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Heritage & conservation areas; Industrial; Military; Mobility
Type of meanwhile use	Multifunctional HUB for interdisciplinary facilities related to the needs of the city.
Stakeholders involved and roles	Festival "Nykoka" or other street art initiatives Kaunas In Kaunas Artist Home Lithuanian Artist Association KTU, VMU, University of Applied Social Sciences; YURY; BAZOOKA (Restaurant)
Target Groups	Startupperes and Businesses, Researchers & Academics, Young People, Students & Pupils
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	Stable
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Exploration and inquiring tools are needed to set a start for this project. A few stakeholders may be involved in further developments, as well as the University of Applied Social Sciences located next to the territory, KTU and VMU. After defining the core goals from mentioned stakeholders, it is possible to involve public funds or private investors. The nearest opportunity is to collaborate with a street art festival for the exterior project.
Relation to T-Factor	Informed

Techno Festival (innovation, arts and tech)

AIP territory, Kaunas fortress, new urban district. Prompt, one day event in summer 2022.

Open air AIP territory with newly built street infrastructure, other industrial, military heritage infrastructure - former Kaunas Fortress warehouses; private ownership vacant industrial and military buildings surrounding the territory. Strategic space, easy to access from other cities also. The aim of this festival is to attract attention to the abandoned AIP location, communicate to citizens of Aleksotas and Kaunas the potential of the territory to expand the city centre, becoming a vibrant area where innovation, art and technology meets and co-live.. The goal is to hold a high-quality TECHNO fest with a contemporary program starting from Tech, Arts & Science achievements showcase to a full program of Techno music. A tiny version of “burning man” in Aleksotas. The land is owned by the government of Lithuania and Kaunas city municipality currently manages the land on “use right”, this means Kaunas city can allow the delivery of prompt events within the territory. Other private vacant infrastructure was identified bordering the territory, which might have the potential application for this activity. Kaunas Fortress warehouses might be used as well.

Many ways to participate for artists, musicians, entrepreneurs, city guests and others. They might be engaged via Open calls, media, stakeholders channels.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Natural; Industrial; Military; Streets & squares
Type of meanwhile use	Festival, interdisciplinary event, Culture & Tech.
Stakeholders involved and roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lizdas Club - possible key organizer • GODO Bar - hospitalities • Kaunas Artist House - education program • Kaunas Municipality - landlord
Target Groups	Artists & Creatives, Young people.
Temporality – Prompt, Regular, Stable	Prompt, one day event in summer 2022.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Possibility to experiment in space, to model its identity, involve new stakeholders, to catch the eye of investors and international media.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

3.3. ENGAGEMENT, EXPLORING & INQUIRING, SUPPORT ACTIVITIES

This section describes engagement, exploring and inquiring, and support activities currently ongoing, recently delivered or planned for the near future. More in detail, content is articulated into the following sub-sections:

- **‘Existing & Planned Engagement Activities’** describes both existing and planned engagement activities in the area that are **not initiated or directly supported by T-Factor**.
- **‘Exploring & Inquiring Activities’** describes local exploration activities run by the Local Coalition **in the context of T-Factor**.

- **'Support Activities & T-Labs Probes'** describes supporting activities that are developed by the Local Coalition in close collaboration **with Agency members and relevant T-Labs**.
- Lastly, the section provides a general overview of the **relational ecosystem of stakeholders** that characterises the pilot at the time of writing this report (November 2021).

3.3.1. Existing and Planned Engagement Activities

Timeline

The below timeline shows the existing and planned engagement activities and meanwhile uses within the Aleksotas regeneration area over the period of the T-Factor project.

	2021	2022	2023	2024
Existing				
Public discussion "Kurkime Kauną kartu" (<i>en. Let's create Kaunas together</i>) (2021-02-18)				
Deus Living Lab Workshop (2021-07-15)				
Conference "SMARTIES: technologijos, keičiančios miestą." Presentation "MIESTO ORIGAMIS - įtraukus miestų regeneravimas pasitelkiant laikinąsias infrastruktūros panaudojimo veiklas" (<i>en. "SMARTIES: changing the city's technologies." Presentation "URBAN ORIGAMIS - participatory urban regeneration through meanwhile uses"</i>) (2021-09-07)				
Planned				
N/A				

Public Discussion "Kurkime Kauną Kartu" (Let's Create Kaunas Together)

Impact Domains

- *Building Communities*
- *Improving Health & Wellbeing*

Public discussion is led by the University of Applied Social Sciences, which is currently building and setting up its Kaunas Branch near the AIIP territory. Public discussion attendees were

informed about development of the AIP and the future development of Aleksotas district. The main goal of public discussion is to facilitate the collaboration between universities, communities, Kaunas city municipality regarding Aleksotas district identity and the AIP development.

<https://kaunas.kasvyksta.lt/2021/02/22/mokslas-ir-it/diskusijoje-kurkime-kauna-kartu-socialiniu-mokslu-kolegijos-idejos-aleksoto-augimui/>

Highlights of the activity	
Stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University of Applied Social Sciences, Kaunas Branch • Kaunas City municipality • Aleksotas community • Urban researchers 	Relation to T-Factor Informed/engaged
Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities The mentioned stakeholders could be involved in collaboration and participation of AIP meanwhile or temporary uses. They also could be the active partners of dissemination and publicity about AIP development and T-Factor project. This activity expands the network that is needed to implement potential meanwhile uses.	

Deus Living Lab Workshop

Impact Domains

- *Cultivating innovation*
- *Building Communities*

DeuS Stands for the European Open Design School for Sustainable Regional Development. It aims at developing a participating, innovative, and sustainable cooperation model, facilitating professional skills development and promoting sustainability. The goal of Kaunas Living Lab is to *Prototype AIP futures* to unlock the multitude of innovative cultural, social and entrepreneurial activities. The Living Lab workshop focuses on the involvement of local stakeholders and formation of Local Coalition to create enough room for various interested groups to discover and participate in the regeneration project. For the project to be fully integrated into the Kaunas City's life, it must involve local businesses and universities from the first development stages. The workshop was divided into two round tables. The first one focused on the "Identity" and the second one on the "Meanwhile uses". This activity responds to the need for closer collaboration among various stakeholders and hearing their voices. Additionally, it provides space for different groups to share their thoughts and relative needs that have the potential to materialize in the AIP territory.

Highlights of the activity	
Stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kaunas University of technology • Aleksotas Community • Kaunas Fortress (<i>lt. Kaunas Tvirtovė</i>) • Kaunas Artists' House (<i>lt. Kauno menininkų namai, KMN</i>) 	Relation to T-Factor Informed/engaged

- | | |
|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kaunas IN • Kaunas Chamber of Commerce, Industry and Crafts (<i>lt. Kauno prekybos, pramonės ir amatų rūmai</i>) • Kaunas Science and Technology Park - Kaunas STP (<i>Kauno mokslo ir technologijų parkas, MTP</i>) | |
|--|--|

Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities

New stakeholders and potential partners for the meanwhile uses were activated and new ideas generated.

Conference “SMARTIES: Technologies That are Changing the Cities” Presentation “URBAN ORIGAMIS - Participatory Urban Regeneration Through Meanwhile Uses”

Impact Domain

- *Building Communities*

The main goal of the conference is to share the results of the SMARTIES Erasmus + project and spread the concept of smart cities. To attract partners and stakeholders, Kaunas pilot needs to spread the word about the project and the concept of meanwhile uses / temporary urbanism. This conference was a great opportunity to present the T-Factor, the concept of temporary urbanism, and Kaunas pilot.

Kaunas STP helps startups and already growing tech companies to increase transnational competitiveness, consults companies on business development issues, provides innovation support services, develops innovation communities, and fosters innovation culture in Kaunas region. As a member of Integrated Science, Studies and Business Centre (Valley) “Santaka” Kaunas STP stimulates science and business collaboration. The Park runs business pre-acceleration program “Evolut 4.0”, designed for early stage startups to develop an innovative product, increase sales and prepare for investment phase. At present, it hosts more than 100 companies operating in the fields of IT, engineering, health technologies, social innovation, future energy, and sustainable chemistry. More than 100 professionals from Kaunas STP ICT cluster “Digital Rocket LT” are providing ICT services for local and international customers. Since 2019 Kaunas STP is a part of CERN Business Incubation Centre in Lithuania and supports development and application of innovative ideas outside the field of high energy physics.

Kaunas STP is one of the potential partners for the delivery of the R&I related activities within the territory of AIIP. The Park is working on 2 projects which will need an open-air infrastructure area “sandbox” where to test green technologies, an open call for companies hosted in the park could be launched to test their technologies in the area as well. Kaunas STP is one of the actors of Kaunas innovation ecosystem, therefore is highly interested in the development of the AIIP.

<https://kaunomtp.lt/konferencija-smarties>

Highlights of the activity

Stakeholders	Relation to T-Factor
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kaunas Science and Technology Park (Kaunas STP) - conference organiser. 	Engaged

Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities

This conference was a great opportunity to present the T-Factor, the concept of meanwhile uses / temporary urbanism, and Kaunas pilot. It helped to expand the network needed for the meanwhile uses implementation. Grounding the term increases the awareness and helps to facilitate more potential activities.

Planned Engagement Activities

At the moment of writing this report, there are no planned activities.

3.3.2. T-Factor Exploring & Inquiring activities

Timeline of Local E&I Activities

	2021	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct
Activity								
“Kaunas Fortress” makerspace visit								

“Kaunas Fortress” Makerspace Visit

Impact domain(s)	1. Cultivating innovation 3. Building Communities 5. Making Places
Activity Objectives	This activity responds to the overall challenge and the need to connect to the local community, to create a place, where meanwhile could happen and create a future identity.
Activity Description	Currently the AIPP territory has no covered space to host any activities. Initiating a temporary building construction would require much time and effort, which might exceed the T-Factor project timeline. Therefore, it is essential to find a covered space where some small-scale activities could take place. Additionally, the fortress complex is a unique feature of the AIPP surroundings. Being merged into the natural valley covered in greenery, it is a highly potential recreational area for the future AIPP employees, Aleksotas district and the whole city. Due to its proximity and characteristics, Kaunas Fortress can facilitate the need for leisure, culture, and recreation regarding urban regeneration of this site.
When/Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When - 2021-04-22 • Where - Kaunas Fortress makerspace

Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	Provided by Kaunas Fortress director Stakeholders involved: Kaunas university of Technology
Participants & Beneficiaries	Kaunas Fortress and local coalition members from KTU and VMU.
Insights	<p>Kaunas Fortress workshop seems to be a suitable location to host small scale events. In general, Kaunas Fortress has a wide network of activists, organisations and artists. It is very much familiar with the local context and has a strong connection with the local community.</p> <p>Kaunas Fortress is very keen on collaboration with the project and sharing their knowledge, and their network. Kaunas Fortress has facilities and the network that could be very helpful for the T-Factor agenda implementation during the prototyping phase.</p>
Outputs	N/A
Outcomes	An important outcome is contribution to building up the network. Kaunas Fortress is keen to collaborate and provide the makerspace if needed to implement some of the T-Factor activities.

3.3.3. Exploring and Inquiring Support Activities and T-Lab Probes

Timeline of Exploring and Inquiring Support Activities

Name	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
<u>TLab 6</u> Review of Public Participation and Multi-Stakeholder Collaborations in AIPP			11th*	
<u>TLab 3</u> Digital Placemaking			10th	
<u>Act.1</u> Access To Meanwhile Forum / Business Models			11th	
<u>Act. 2</u> Future Identity Co-Creation		6th		

*T-Lab 6 activity is divided into two parts: the report presentation and the workshop. As a result, on the 11th of November, during the Forum (Support Plan activity), TUDO+Lodz report is going to be presented and once the service provider for the Development Plan of the AIPP is set, the workshop will take place.

“Urban Origami: Innovative City Making Strategies”

Impact domain(s)	Making Places
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Activity Objectives	It is necessary to improve the knowledge and understand the benefits of meanwhile uses and approach decision makers to support these activities. If meanwhile spaces are positioned as public/civic assets, then there needs to be a public/civic service that supports equitable and inclusive access to these spaces.
Activity Description	The aim of this event is to present the significance of temporary infrastructure use (meanwhile uses/temporary urbanization) in the development process of long-term urban areas and to discuss the possibilities of applying this method in Kaunas Aleksotas Innovation Industry Park (AIIP). During the project, this area and its surroundings become a site for temporary activities, inviting cultural, artistic, sports, community or business and innovation initiatives, and presenting scientific-artistic and technological achievements. During the forum, foreign experts and various AIIP stakeholders are to exchange knowledge, experience and ideas on the topic of temporary urbanism.
When/Where	When 11th of November 2021 Where blended event (the forum location is KTU Santaka Valley - Science, Technology and Business Centre, and partly online)
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	Providers KTU Stakeholders involved VMU, KMSA, T-Factor partners, Design agency CRITICAL
Participants & Beneficiaries	Ministry of the Environment of the Republic of Lithuania KTU KMSA Kaunas IN Kaunas Fortress Park VMU Vilnius Art Academy, Kaunas Faculty Politecnico di Milano Kaunas Science and Technology Park Kaunas architects' experts council Government Strategic Analysis Centre Euromonitor International Performative design agency Decreo – a professional management consultancy and training company Architects Citanos Sukaitytes architecture buro MB “Rigeto Studija” Kund studio MB “Rigeto studija” MB “Pastatu projektai” MB “Jurmata” Balinida - interior design studio 36 participants registered in total, 20 people showed up live, 10 people were watching YouTube streaming.

Insights	<p>Partners from the T-Factor contributed greatly to the Forum program implementation. There were several online presentations and a couple of recorded videos from the consortium's repository. Their presentations played an important role in filling in the lack of understanding what are meanwhile spaces and temporary urbanism. In many cases there is a need to get the insights from non-local networks and professionals working abroad to reach out the audience and make it listen more carefully. There is a challenge of how to apply the lessons learned in other countries to the local context, however, the rising awareness of meanwhile uses as a method that contributes to urban regeneration can facilitate the discussion and locally innovative solutions. The forum was a great opportunity to make the connection between the experts and the local stakeholders/decision makers.</p>
Outputs	<p><i>Ideation workshop.</i></p>

Forum audience. Image credits: KTU

<p>Outcomes</p>	<p>This activity contributed to expanding the network and increasing the awareness of meanwhile uses. Sharing cases from other pilots and raising sensitive topics like funding and benefits that meanwhile uses can obtain, helped to build more trust regarding positive influence of temporary urbanism. A possibility for collaboration with the Government Strategic Analysis Centre was identified for dedicated research on the Public Participation and Engagement in Multi-Stakeholder Collaborations.</p>
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Future Identity Co-Creation

<p>Impact domain(s)</p>	<p>All</p>
<p>Activity Objectives</p>	<p>To create a shared vision for the AIIIP.</p>
<p>Activity Description</p>	<p>Workshop “T-Factor Deus KAUNAS Living Lab II” This workshop is a result of collaboration between the Deus project, T-Factor, KTU and Kaunas Fortress. It consists of two parts: Kaunas Fortress makerspace and its surroundings visit and the workshop. The workshop is moderated by the Design agency “We Are Critical”.</p> <p>This activity gives space for various stakeholders to share their future vision of the AIIIP. It also invites people to get familiar with the Kaunas Fortress part, which is going to have the closest proximity to the AIIIP. Different actors have different visions of the future of a place. The co-creation of place-based identities/communications provides a context for exploration and exchange of the different perceptions, meanings and values attributed to regeneration</p>

	<p>sites. This workshop used creative brainstorming methods that helped to think along and bring diverse interest groups to collaborate.</p>
<p>When/Where</p>	<p>When 6th of October, 2021 Where Kaunas Fortress makerspace, 5th warehouse</p>
<p>Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved</p>	<p>Activity Providers Kaunas LC, Kaunas Fortress</p>
<p>Participants & Beneficiaries</p>	<p>15 participants.</p>
<p>Insights</p>	<p>The activity revealed that common ground is slowly being reached among various stakeholders and their interests and understanding regarding the meanwhile uses are aligning.</p>
<p>Outputs</p>	<p>Photos</p> <p><i>Image credits: Aiste Eidukeviciute</i></p>
<p>Outcomes</p>	<p>Convening various stakeholders for discussion helped to build stronger connections and improve the understanding of different perspectives. As an important outcome of this workshop, it was noticed that the participants generated relatively similar ideas. This suggests that a holistic vision of how</p>

the area could be used during the waiting time is emerging. As a result, this commonality and shared vision could satisfy a wide range of stakeholders.

Public Participation and Engagement in Multi-Stakeholder Collaborations

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Cultivating innovation</i> • <i>Growing prosperity</i> • <i>Building Communities</i>
Activity Objectives	<p>The probe tries to assess the possibilities of participation during the regeneration process of AIIP and suggests the possibilities of participation during the lifetime of Aleksotas Innovation Industry Park development (innovation model) as both are outlined in the planning documents for the innovation area.</p>
Activity Description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The T-Factor Local Coalition provided relevant public documents about the establishment of AIIP, including the Procurement Procedure for the Service Provider which is the company that is going to outline the AIIP Development Plan until spring 2022. 2. The team from City & University of Lodz as well as Dortmund University have translated all documents from Lithuanian to English with a licenced translation tool. 3. Furthermore, the team created a review model with basic guidelines in order to create an analysis according to the relevance of civic engagement, participation and the long-term goal of establishing multi-sectoral, multi-stakeholder innovation ecosystems for Kaunas Innovation Park. 4. The translated texts were the basis for a qualitative content analysis based on the review model. 5. The review is a proposal to the Local Coalition based on the author's suggestions that are grounded in a literature review of the topic and the authors' practical experience in the field of public participation. This is one of the approaches that can be taken, but each time local solutions and good practices should be considered, which can enrich participatory processes and make it more feasible to carry out. <p>Following the written review (report), the team organises two presentations about the review results. First, the team presented results at the Meanwhile Forum on 11th November. Second, the team will conduct a meeting with the Service Provider (Development Plan provider) on December '21 or January '22.</p>

When/Where	<p><u>Part1. Report presentation provided by TUDO and Lodz.</u> When 11th of November, 2021 Where Santaka Valley KTU Science, Technology and Business Centre (hybrid event)</p> <p><u>Part2. Workshop.</u> When TBD (once the Development Plan service provider is selected) Where online</p>
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	<p>Activity providers TUDO, City of Lodz Stakeholders involved Kaunas Local Coalition and Service Provider</p>
Participants & Beneficiaries	<p>1st presentation at Urban Origami (Kaunas Meanwhile Forum) on 11th November with several persons from the Local Coalition.</p>
Insights	<p>Preparation of the Development Plan as described in the Specification for the Purchase Technology for the Development of the Kaunas Aleksotas Innovation Industry Park Plan (Kaunas Municipality, 2021) depends heavily on the Service Provider's interpretation and willingness to act. Therefore, the quality of participation depends mostly on how specific tasks and activities will be carried out.</p> <p>The potential to include local perspective in the process of the AIIIP development plan: According to the Specification (Kaunas Municipality, 2021) the Service Provider shall schedule at least 12 meetings with the Service Recipient (at least once every 2 weeks). There is no mention of including members of the Local Coalition as participants of such meetings. It would be advisable to open some of the meetings to a wider audience and hence start an open dialogue during the Development plan preparation regarding problems encountered in the process, proposed solutions, amendments etc, especially regarding meanwhile uses. This would be a good basis and introduction to the public consultation - one of the activities that the Service Provider is responsible for. In addition, including local community representatives at early stages of the preparation of a planned investment in the discussion about it may increase the level of acceptance during its implementation.</p> <p>The technical specification are a good starting point for organising broader information meetings for the general public in addition to the consultation meeting. already stipulated in the Service Provider tasks. Comprehensive and understandable information on the underlying concepts, objectives, challenges of the whole project is a necessary precondition for successful consultation and wider participation of the local community.</p>

Outputs	<p>Review of Procurement Documents with technical specificities as well as review of the planning documents for AAIP regarding Creative Placemaking and Civic Engagement.</p> <p>Development of guidelines / objectives for future meanwhile uses as a part of development plan / masterplan.</p> <p>Workshops with service provider (developing the masterplan / development plan) - TBC</p>
Outcomes	<p>The most important outcome would be an ongoing conversation and collaboration with the service provider through the whole Development Plan preparation process that would result in the guidelines for the meanwhile use.</p>

Digital Placemaking. Extremely Vast and Incredibly Close Future Workshop (T-Lab Probe)

Impact domain(s)	All
Activity Objectives	<p>Specific objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking with local coalition and stakeholders; • Collecting expectations and ideas of the participants regarding the near future meanwhile activities to be used in digital modelling. <p>General objectives: generating knowledge on how to use technology in urban regeneration for digital place-making.</p>
Activity Description	<p>The probe was the first excursion by T-Lab 3 to touch base in Kaunas and start collecting inputs to feed the digital modelling platform. The probe was designed and facilitated by Futuribile, T-Lab 3. As a curatorial choice, the workshop focused on the near future, since because of their disconnection with the immediate reality, speculative futures can lead to engagement fatigue. Moreover, the local coalition is seeking support for organising real activities as soon as possible. Considering this, the second curatorial choice was to provide an experience and not only an ideation workshop. In this way, the probe could contribute to building the aesthetics of the site and lead participants to appropriate it.</p> <p>The probe took place on Thursday 10th afternoon. It was titled “Extremely Vast and Incredibly Close Future”, referring to the vastness of the regeneration site and the intention to activate meanwhile uses in a near future and not in a speculative one. The probe was made of three parts:</p> <p>Site visit Dream Room to spark imagination and reflection Brainstorming workshop</p>

When/Where	When 10th November 2021 Where Kaunas, AIIP and Kaunas Fortress
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	Activity providers Futuribile Stakeholders involved KTU & Kaunas Fortress
Participants & Beneficiaries	KTU students and staff; municipality; Kaunas fortresses association; Aleksotas residents/landowners. 13 participants.
Insights	<p>The probe led to identifying possible ways ahead for placemaking and the role of technology in it. Although one-time events emerged as the easiest and most engaging way to activate the space and open it to citizens, space accessibility and safety hurdles (which were raised by the municipality representative) make digital and hybrid activities a promising route for animating the meanwhile. From the final discussion, it emerged how physical and digital activities must be complementary and not mutually exclusive. Indeed, any digitally-enabled experience should be seen as a way to augment possibilities and not as a parallel alternative world. We sketched how gaming could lead to experiencing the site through somebody else's eyes (e.g. of another gender, historical period, profession) and hence enhance social inclusion. Another possibility is to create an economy around the place that connects it with the rest of the city (e.g. virtuous actions compensated with tokens to be spent in public services). Finally, digital modelling could be a way to open up imagination (e.g. with Space Syntax modelling infrastructures and activities, their requirements and impacts).</p> <p>Concerning engagement, efforts should be concentrated in finding the right channels, incentives and storytelling to involve citizens, especially those located at the outskirts of AIIP. The immediate workshop follow-up by KTU is the modelling in Space Syntax of some of the uses that emerged.</p>
Outputs	<p>Workshop methodology and materials Workshop report (includes pictures) Scenarios for Space Syntax modelling (for each, it is reasonably possible to model people's fluxes, infrastructures, and public transports)</p>

Image credits: Marta Arniani

Outcomes

The probe contributed to engage with new stakeholders from Aleksotas and unveiled how digitally-mediated meanwhile activities could be a sandbox for KTU to involve students in innovative and creative projects. Moreover, hybrid activities would help animating AIP regardless of security/accessibility constraints. Digital placemaking would help building a participatory identity of the place in coherence with its final use.

3.3.4 Overview of Stakeholders

The following map provides an overview of key stakeholders.

A dynamic Kumu map of all stakeholders can also be accessed [here](#).

Missing Stakeholders

The following stakeholders are currently not engaged in activities relating to the regeneration process.

- **Ministry of the Economy and Innovation of the Republic of Lithuania:** The ministry is one of the key decision makers for the development of the AIIP and the decision upon the “right of trust” of the AIIP land that Kaunas city is seeking for in order to manage the territory and lease land to third parties.
- **Real estate agencies and developers:** The development of the AIIP will attract many professionals and specialists who are going to be in need of housing. Work proximity is important to employees' well-being. It would be valuable to understand if there is an uprising pressure for the housing market regarding the newly created working places in the near future; what is the supply at the moment; what is the position from the municipality regarding the accommodation provision for the foreseen increase of Aleksotas population. As a result, the demand for other facilities will increase as well.
- **VMU Botanical Garden:** VMU Botanical Garden is relatively near the future AIIP, however, it is not successfully engaged as a stakeholder yet.
- **S. Darius and S. Girenas airport (also known as Aleksotas airport):** Open-air field as the AIIP territory at the moment is, could be interesting for some of the recreational airport activities.
- **Sports communities:** The territory of the AIIP and its current infrastructure is already being used by local skaters, it might be interesting for various sports communities (e.g. skiing in the wintertime) however, the sports communities have not been engaged yet.
- **University of Applied Social Sciences:** This university is currently building their brand new branch with design and tech laboratories just on the other side of the street

(Europos avenue). It might involve students in various educational or other activities. The newly built infrastructure could also become part of meanwhile-space's portfolio of the Kaunas pilot and invite other potential meanwhile-use partners to use it. The laboratories might be useful for artists, architects or designers, which might deliver their work in the territory. Potential collaborator for art residence.

- **Art communities from specific fields appropriate to the territory:** Performance art, Light and sound arts, Music, Land art, Street art, Sculpture, Installation, site specific artists, landscape design - these are the types of art and culture fields that are most potential for the use of available infrastructure in the AIIP territory.
- **Kaunas City Museum:** it could collaborate by co-organising some events as exhibitions, excursions and deepening the knowledge about the AIIP territory's history.
- **Pupils' technical creation center (Moksleiviu technines kurybos centras):** Their activities include technical creativity development workshops (initial technical modeling, aeronautical modeling, rocket modeling, track automotive modeling), robotics and information technology direction activities (engineering and physics circles (photonics (light science), radio electronics, spatial construction), creative constructors'), media related workshops (photography, Kadras film studio, animation, media and communication). Mentioned activities and expertise could help to brainstorm and build the potential AIIP's development direction related meanwhile uses.
- **Create Lithuania:** It is a unique program for professional development and enhancement of national competitiveness. Collaboration with the AIIP could help to attract talents and various highly skilled professionals.
- **Tech Zity:** Real estate projects through the development of coworking spaces & startup community. Might be interested in the AIIP, Flex-start space and Sandbox.
- **Lithuanian Geographical Society:** Possible collaborator for the Biodivercities project.
- **Cabbage Field (initiative):** One of the meanwhile uses implementation examples in Kaunas, which could be applied for the territory of the AIIP.
- **Šilainiai project:** Urban gardening project in one of the densely populated residential areas in Kaunas. Opportunity to replicate the same idea in Aleksotas.
- **Kaunas Architecture Festival (KAFe).** Kaunas Architecture Festival (KAFe) is an international project, taking place in Kaunas every 3 years and inviting architectural professionals and guests of the town to take part in an almost 2-month long experiment promoting architecture, creativity and education, which emphasizes the impact that architecture has on our lives, its importance to creation of public well-being and harmonious environment.
- **LUIT - Lithuanian Urban Innovation Network.** It is a network of urban planning practices seeking to promote innovative urban development strategies, processes and culture in Lithuania. The Association is actively involved in the formation of strategic and spatial planning, organization of planning processes and urban planning policy in Lithuania and abroad. Collaboration with LUIT could contribute to building up the local knowledge of temporary urbanism and its application to the local context.
- **Kaunas Extreme Sport Club.** Association promoting extreme sports, youth employment and street culture in Kaunas.
- **Kaunas Marathon.** Potential route through the AIIP.

- **Ekskursas.** Potential guided city sightseeing routes going through the AIIP and Kaunas Fortress.
- **Project “Upynes”.** They organize "river tours" to discover Kaunas' small rivers. SVIRBĖ, which runs in Aleksotas nearby the AIIP.
- **Open Kitchen Kaunas.** Potential open kitchen event on the site of the AIIP.
- **Public entity “Science and innovation for the society”.** Potential collaboration preparing thematic meanwhile uses.
- **Ezerelis center of culture.** Their Kites' festival could be relocated to the AIIP territory.
- **Cosmos Theater.** Potential partner for the continuing activities of the Digital Placemaking probe.

3.4. CONCLUSIONS & NEXT STEPS

Temporary urbanism is a relatively new practice in Lithuania and Kaunas. Good practices of citizen engagement through meanwhile uses can be found; nevertheless, a meanwhile approach has not been used as a strategic asset for urban development on a bigger scale. Engagement activities have demonstrated the general interest on the topic and generated the initial stakeholder coalition. Actions should be made in micro, meso and macro scale willing to forge the meanwhile culture locally: from small exemplary meanwhile initiatives, active communication on temporary urbanism and 'open call for meanwhile uses' to engaging important local businesses as well as forming a “meanwhile council” from representatives of main stakeholders and decision makers to work on legal framework and positioning of temporary urbanism practices as a mean for participatory city making within the local policies.

Few ongoing financed projects which can bring their initiatives into the territory were identified. Other ideas for meanwhile uses coming from small initiatives and artists should need additional funding, therefore it is possible to collaborate in applying for additional funding through the Lithuanian Culture Council (calls to be opened in spring 2022). Individual enterprises might be also interested to use the territory for their activities or contribute to the cultural events.

The lack of operative infrastructure for meanwhile in the AIIP territory posed some barriers for the engagement of the potential partners for meanwhile uses. Therefore, a list of private abandoned infrastructure including the warehouses of Kaunas Fortress was made. Contacts of the private buildings' owners were gathered in order to offer them collaboration with the project by providing access to their ownership as meanwhile spaces. A meanwhile-space map and portfolio collecting the available infrastructure of AIIP territory and around its borders is being prepared. It will be a useful document while defining meanwhile uses and delivering further engagement.

To ensure engagement of a wider cultural and arts community an initiative with Kaunas2022 and Kaunas artist home was discussed. Several dedicated meetings are planned where various cultural activity organisers will be informed on the existing infrastructure and the possibilities to use it for various initiatives. They will be provided with the meanwhile spaces map; guided tours on site are foreseen as well. The same counts for other formal and informal communities (such as extreme sports) that were mapped but still weren't engaged. One of the most

important issues is to communicate the project, the territory, and the possibility for meanwhile activities there.

The legal framework for land use is also one of the most important issues for the Kaunas pilot. It is important to keep on track the process of the political decisions on the framework reform, and its operative stage.

From the experience of the engagement activities delivered we note that it is important to work with smaller stakeholder groups in detailing and planning specific meanwhile activities that they could deliver. Working with wide stakeholder groups for a longer time tends to lower interest and motivation as they are directed to practical implementation of concrete activities they might deliver. The situation regarding the land use and the lack of infrastructure has remained the same, but we are extending our network with private infrastructure owners which gives an additional opportunity for meanwhile uses. The additional infrastructure discovered forms an inspirational territory for artists and other potential activities (e.g., street art).

Engagement activities showed that many stakeholders agree on the activities that the territory could host, which could contribute strategically to forming a new identity of the place but keep its historical background. The discovery of the undergoing political discussion on the land law reform could provide new opportunities for Kaunas pilot as well.

Next Steps

Scoping and Ideating is planned in main 3 steps: (1) TOC1 to be filled within the main Local coalition members by bringing in the ideas which came out from engagement activities; (2) ideation workshop with wider stakeholder group (3) TOC2 and the matrix to be filled within the main Local coalition members by bringing in the ideas from the ideation phase.

Key actions planned: the preparation of the Kaunas meanwhile portfolio which includes the vacant infrastructure and its use conditions of (1) AIIP, (2) Kaunas Fortress Park, (3) private owners. After preparing the portfolio, additional meetings with specific communities will be organised to identify potential meanwhile uses (in collaboration with Kaunas2022, Kaunas Artists' Home, Kaunas Aleksotas Community and others). Visits to the site are planned with those interested as well. We are also validating the possibility to establish a "meanwhile council" inviting the main stakeholders and decision makers to join. The council would be aimed to promote and create favourable conditions for meanwhile spaces in AIIP.

LISBON TRAFARIA

4. LISBON TRAFARIA

4.1. PILOT STARTING CONTEXT AND PRIORITIES

In the Greater Lisbon region there is no centre of artistic creation dedicated to both valorization and transfer of technology linked to the Arts. In Portugal there are other art-related research centres, with no solid technology base or international dimension. The **NOVA Institute for Art & Technology (NOVA IA&T)** will address this gap by presenting its own scientific and pedagogical program, guided by the great issues of the 21st century and their connection to art and technology.

Located in the former Trafaria Prison, which will be completely remodelled and adapted for this purpose, NOVA IA&T will have its initiatives in close and permanent interaction with the population of Trafaria and Almada, and in alignment with the objectives of the Almada municipal government. It will be a space open for the **inclusion of the various local communities and an ecosystem for the qualification of the population and of the surrounding area, capable of driving the social development and the economy of the region, and a catalyst for development in Trafaria. Meanwhile uses in Trafaria will be key in achieving this second goal.** They will also be a tool for NOVA University to establish relationships and communicate the masterplan project and engage with the local population.

Trafaria is an old fishermen's village located in the South bank of the Tagus River, opposite to the City of Lisbon. The origins of Trafaria date back to 1565. Trafaria's identity is strongly linked to its military function. Its strategic location at the river mouth converted Trafaria into a surveillance point of the Tagus River navigation channel. This strategic location also converted Trafaria into a beach resort. Its water was known for its therapeutic properties that gave the town a reputation for its curative powers, turning the village into an attractive tourist destination. Possibly because of the lack of readiness of the village to absorb these types of activities and Portugal's central government policies that favoured other tourist locations, such as the nearby Costa de Caparica, Trafaria lost its importance as a tourist destination.

Trafaria is a village of 5,696 people (2011 census) that belongs to the municipality of Almada and to the Lisbon Metropolitan Area (L.M.A) on a larger scale. At an administrative level, Trafaria is part of a union of parishes called União das Freguesias da Caparica e Trafaria that was established in 2013. The village is delimited by the Tagus River on its northern bank, the Atlantic Ocean on the West and a mountain ridge that separates Trafaria from Almada city centre on the East. Despite its proximity to Lisbon, the town is quite isolated from the capital and the commute is only possible with public transport (ferry or bus) or private car. Trafaria is located about twenty-two minutes by car from Lisbon city centre with no traffic conditions and it takes only twenty minutes for the ferry to cross the Tagus River from Trafaria station to Belém, at the outskirts of Lisbon. However, the ferry service has a limited schedule and frequency and the commute from Belém to the centre of Lisbon adds about an hour to the trip by public transport.

The connection between Almada and Lisbon is much stronger and appears to confirm that the two municipalities work as a consolidated metropolitan region. According to a 2008 study entitled “comparative evaluation of the existing alternatives for the third crossing of the Tagus River in the metropolitan area of Lisbon” there is a daily commute from Lisbon to Almada of about 156.000 people (estimated data based on a survey applied to 46.000 people in 2007). Trafaria is however near the current NOVA University’s Faculty of Science and Technology, which is located at the Southwest of Almada’s City Centre.

Its geographical location, in close proximity to the country’s capital, has been at the centre of the debates around the development of the town. Trafaria has often been described as a “deposit of those condemned to exile” (Leal, 2014) and there is a concern that Trafaria may become a repository for the capital, forging a duality that could harm the village’s identity and negatively impact the life of its citizens.

On the westernmost point of Trafaria there is one of the largest informal settlements in the country, the Segundo Torrão neighbourhood. This concentrates high levels of poverty and population with a migrant background. The Bairro dos Pescadores (Fishermen’s Neighbourhood) also concentrates high levels of poverty as it is also located on the west side of the town.

Trafaria has a rich architectural heritage. Many of these buildings are in a bad state of conservation. Many of these have been passed from generation to generation, making it complicated to find their owners who are often not interested in rehabilitating their properties due to their state of decay.

The Presidio, where the NOVA IA&T will be located, is a building with a long and important history for the village and Lisbon at large. The space where the presidio is located used to be the Lazareto building, possibly the first building in Trafaria. It was built in 1565 to quarantine ships to prevent the spread of plagues in the city. In 1683, a fort was built next to the Lazareto to complement the defence of the capital on the Tagus South bank. By the year 1751 the fort was turned into a prison, a function that the building kept for some years before entering a period when it served different functions such as a dry cod factory and a theatre. In the early 1900s with the end of the Portuguese monarchy, most of the structures of the fort were demolished and a prison, known as the Presidio, was built. With the start of the republic, the prison started to receive civilian prisoners accused of political crimes. This status was consolidated with the dictatorship, the Estado Novo, when opponents to the regime were incarcerated in the Presidio. The building kept its military function until 1981. In the year 2000 the Municipality of Almada acquired the building. After several attempts of appropriation by civil society groups, the space was finally inaugurated as a cultural space.

Today, the Presidio is composed of seven buildings, and it occupies a space of 1,200 square feet. It is a symbol of the military architecture of the coastal artillery regiment. After over 40 years of abandonment, the structure is now in ruins.

The NOVA IA&T project aims to transform the Presidio area **into a centre for arts, culture and creativity that is to become the main catalyst for new higher education, applied research and opportunities for enterprise.** The requalification project of the Presidio is part of the Almada’s development strategy, which aims to promote economic development, boost cultural activities, and stimulate a new strategy for the requalification of public space. The new

NOVA IA&T will create **a cluster for the concentration and development of qualified businesses in the region that is to become a reference in arts and technology education at the local, national, and international scale**. On a local level, the NOVA IA&T is expected to become a driving force that brings local economic development to the town, contribute to the preservation of heritage, and develop educational programmes for the residents.

The idea of the NOVA IA&T is to create a centre for research, innovation, training, teaching and creation that enhances the connection between technology and the arts. To do so, the project brings together NOVA University's Faculty of Science and Technology (FCT) and the School of Social Sciences and Humanities (FCSH) to foster greater collaboration and research in the arts and technology, creating knowledge and value with a commitment to sustainability, impact in the local community and Portugal, and becoming a reference in the arts and technology education domestically and internationally. The two faculties currently have a total of 6,000 students and over 100 staff and researchers.

The NOVA IA&T educational programme will combine continuous MSc, PhD, and post-graduation programs, as well as short professional certification and skills development programs for executives, arts events and residencies and labs. On a more corporate level, the NOVA IA&T will have programmes for project prototyping and applied R&D, innovation, joint research projects between corporations and NOVA IA&TIAT@T fostering pathways to commercialisation, and a start-up accelerator and an incubator. In addition to this, the NOVA IA&T will also count on community impact projects. These include collaborations between local corporations and the local community to promote economic development and cultural activities and Street Labs for local residents to access the school facilities and training as well as many other activities and programs yet to be developed.

4.1.1. Issues

Several key issues are to be addressed within the Trafaria regeneration area. In this section, these issues are elaborated in order of importance, and related to the 'impact domains' identified within the evaluation framework of T-Factor.

Building Communities

Trafaria is currently very insular regarding the rest of the Lisbon metropolitan area. Struggling with unemployment, lack of public infrastructure and resources and education. As a higher educational institution, it is NOVA's responsibility to break this cycle, through IAT, but at this stage of regeneration it is primordial to involve the community and engage them with the regeneration process. Building communities is therefore getting the NOVA community together with the local community, through the planned activities, providing them with awareness of development proposals and the opportunity to have a say.

Cultivating innovation

IAT will provide training opportunities to the local community, particularly to the younger population, through the permanent Street Lab and Fab Lab. These initiatives will enable the community to develop new skills and give them the opportunity to have access to equipment and infrastructure that will enable them to build new businesses and make

Trafaria more self-sufficient economically.

4.1.2. Challenges and Opportunities

Key challenges and opportunities to be addressed within the Trafaria regeneration area are described below in order of priority, most relevant challenge/opportunity first.

Challenge 1 – Engagement & Communication

Communicate the project: One of our biggest challenges is how we can communicate the project to the local population in the most engaging way, keeping them informed of what the masterplan means and the impact in their community and lives.

Challenge 2 – Reciprocal Engagement & Trust

Enhance participation to leverage residents' contribution and interests: Engaging the local residents and interests in IAT's and Trafaria's regeneration process in a way that they feel that they are actually contributing and have a say on what is being done in the Fort and surrounding areas.

Challenge 3 – Space Availability and Accessibility

One of the biggest challenges regarding temporary uses of the space is the fact that during the construction works we won't be able to use the space as freely as we would wish to, we've faced many challenges regarding access to the building and infrastructures that we would have expected to have by now (e.g., access to restrooms).

Opportunity 1 – Activities That Bring Awareness and Participatory Engagement

The T-Factor activities enable us to communicate in an informal way with the local community, whether through local associations or/and the residents in Trafaria, enabling a form of communication that is closer and more inclusive (connected to the local reality) and engaging with populations from the projects nearby, bridging the gap between NOVA's project, T-Factor's goals and IAT's.

Opportunity 2 – Engaging the Population in the Transformation of the Area

The T-Factor meanwhile space opportunity enables the local population to live and experience the building that has been abandoned for over 40 years. Whether for short periods of time or for more permanent uses during the renovation works.

Opportunity 3 – Nomadic Approach to Meanwhile

During the period characterised by a limited access to the building, NOVA has been able to find other neighbouring locations to enable the activities and have more exposure.

4.1.3. Needs

Active Engagement

Engage and establish direct relations with key stakeholders around the regeneration project. Define an activation and engagement process that can involve different audiences and publics and better unveil the potential of the project.

Governance

Governance of collaborations and partnerships: better understand how we can establish a collaborative environment (especially with local actors at this stage) and nurture trust and commitment to shared objectives.

Communicating the Masterplan

Set up and sustain a diversified and engaging communication strategy presenting the masterplan to the local as well as to a wider national and international audience.

Addressing Education Needs of the Local Population

Design and test innovative curricula & training path: design and deliver innovative training and educational opportunities that also leverage existing skills and knowledge.

4.2. MEANWHILE SPACES AND USES

The map below shows the location of existing, planned, and potential meanwhile spaces and uses within the Trafaria regeneration area over the period of the T-Factor project.

4.2.1. Existing Meanwhile Spaces and Uses

Trafaria Fort

Trafaria fort is an ex-military facility within the Trafaria complex of buildings. Inside the fort there's a garden and a former chapel, and a new building that belongs to the municipality. It is accessible by road from the village. It is adjacent to the ferry, and it is at the end of the Trafaria village, facing the Tagus River and up south it is surrounded by a hill with trees. NOVA has a lease agreement with the municipality and have been given access to the new building within the complex. The fort provides co-working space, a makerspace, ateliers, and studios. The space will host small events, artist residencies, and co-working.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Military building
Type of meanwhile use	Education & training; Research;
Stakeholders involved and roles	The key players in this meanwhile use of the space include EDA, NOVA (researchers and grantees) and visiting artists. EDA has been in the premises for a very long time, and they are very committed to developing activities to support the community. NOVA has an agreement with EDA to use NOVA facilities (chapel and garden). NOVA has an agreement with the municipality to use their facilities (new building/restrooms/rooms), the municipality manages and decides who uses the space.
Target groups	UNL's team and other stakeholders including Researchers & Academics, Artists & Creatives, Makers & Artisans with a particular focus on young people.
Temporality	June 2020-2024 – Stable Use
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	It is hoped that the space will help UNL to become more closely connected to the local community and engage more closely with the local traditions and lifestyles. The space will also enable the community to visit and engage with the transformation process. High levels of engagement for the participants, they're either part of NOVA and will be integrating IAT or are working with the researchers at NOVA if not staff. The activities are promoted locally through posters and flyers, as well as promotion through NOVA's communication channels, website and social media, as well as the schools'. NOVA is constantly engaging with the actors that can help fund the space, namely with the municipality, once COVID restrictions are lifted we can chase other opportunities. The municipality is funding the maintenance and management of the space and uses. The buildings where IAT will exist were leased by NOVA, but don't have yet conditions to be fully used for activities, however, there is an adjacent new building within the complex that is brand new with bathrooms, space, and elevators. This building was rebuilt to host different arts and local associations, and it was due to the existing partnership between NOVA

	and the municipality that we were able to guarantee the usage of part of the complex (two rooms).
Relation to T-Factor	Planned. All Exploring and Inquiring activities will at some point take place in or around the fort, whether before or after the building's renovation.

Casino da Trafaria

Casino da Trafaria is a cultural space, formerly a casino. The space hosts many different events. The casino is in the centre of Trafaria, a few blocks away from the future IAT's location.

<https://rdtcasino.pt/>

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Cultural.
Type of meanwhile use	Poetry Slam competition hosted in the space. The space is managed by the Casino and the activities delivered in the space are managed by NOVA. Temporary rental – we rented the space for a few hours; it is rented as an event space by the ones exploring the space.
Stakeholders involved and roles	NOVA professors and researchers – production Artists – workshop development Local community – participation and engagement
Target groups	Artists & Creatives; Young People
Temporality	July 2021 – Prompt Use
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	The poetry slam is an activity that proved being useful to engage with the local community, both in the development of activity and in the performative act.
Relation to T-Factor	Past activity funded by T-Factor. The activity planners were looking for an events space, due to the proximity to the Fort and community environment, the organizers chose this location.

Casa da Cerca

Casa da Cerca is an exhibition space in the old part of the city of Almada, it is approximately a 10 minute drive from Trafaria and it hosts multiple cultural events. The space is managed and maintained by the Municipality. The space hosted a photo Exhibition integrated in a T-Factor activity.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Former Military Space.
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Type of meanwhile use	Exhibition.
Stakeholders involved and roles	Almada's municipality cultural department and artists
Target groups	Artists & Creatives; Young People
Temporality	July 2021 – Prompt Use
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	The activity has been useful to give exposure to the T-Factor project outside Trafaria. The municipality promoted the event in their communication channels (website and social media) and sent out an email to a mailing list. On NOVA's side, we've promoted the event through NOVA's and the school's website and social media channels. The future opportunity is to promote in this space artists production developed within the program.
Relation to T-Factor	The space was suggested by the Municipality's art curator.

4.2.2. Planned Meanwhile Spaces and Uses

Trafaria's Streets

Trafaria is a relatively small village with limited traffic. There's a main square and a river boardwalk where street engagement happens.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Streets and squares.
Type of meanwhile use	We are planning on using the public space in Trafaria for "taking over" the streets of Trafaria, by activating temporary street occupations including guerrilla actions, public performances, and a digital arts festival.
Stakeholders involved and roles	Trafaria municipality: to engage and support the promotion of these activities within the community.
Target groups	Artists & Creatives Young People
Temporality	From 2022 – Regular Use
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring	The Exploration and Inquiring activities enable the T-Factor team to assess the needs and issues of the local population and their concerns regarding the masterplan, therefore directing us in the definition for future activities.
Relation to T-Factor	Directly activated and funded through T-Factor.

4.3. ENGAGEMENT, EXPLORING AND INQUIRING, SUPPORT ACTIVITIES

This section describes engagement, exploring and inquiring, and support activities currently ongoing, recently delivered or planned for the near future. More in detail, content is articulated into the following sub-sections:

- **‘Existing & Planned Engagement Activities’** describes both existing and planned engagement activities in the area that are **not initiated or directly supported by T-Factor**.
- **‘Exploring & Inquiring Activities’** describes local exploration activities run by the Local Coalition **in the context of T-Factor**.
- **‘Support Activities & T-Labs Probes’** describes supporting activities that are developed by the Local Coalition in close collaboration **with Agency members and relevant T-Labs**.
- Lastly, the section provides a general overview of the **relational ecosystem of stakeholders** that characterises the pilot at the time of writing this report (November 2021).

4.3.1. Existing and Planned Engagement Activities

Open House Lisbon

Open House Lisboa is known for opening doors to private houses and flats, reserved or technical areas in museums and theatres, among other contemporary buildings with different uses, and in 2021 the doors are opened to a whole new territory: Almada. With an area of 71 km², Almada comes out on the itinerary for this unique weekend to celebrate architecture, through a protocol signed between the Lisbon Triennale and the City Council of Almada. Open House Lisboa celebrates its 10th edition by uniting the two cities over the Tagus river, and invests in a territorial expansion to join the two river banks in an accessible event that reaches the general public. Scheduled for 25-26 September 2021, the motivation for this extension is based on the interest in diversifying and expanding the spatial itinerary, to reveal the peculiarities of the architectural works in this municipality together with those in the city of Lisbon.

<i>Highlights of the activity</i>	
Stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open house Lisbon organizers • Municipality of Almada 	Relation to T-Factor Engaged
Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities As part of the Architectural Lisbon Triennial (https://www.trienaldelisboa.com/ohl/), the Trafaria Fort was integrated in 2021's program. Within the Lisbon Open house program there was a 2 day open house on the 25 th and 26 th September event at the Fort with the presence of guides and volunteers, providing a guided tour of the fort and surrounding buildings that belong to the	

city of Almada. This activity enables local residents to visit and learn about the space, enabling engagement with the local and nearby community. **Give visibility to the Fort and reach a larger part of the population.**

4.3.2. T-Factor Exploring and Inquiring Activities

Timeline

Web of Stories

Web of stories is a **platform for documenting community narratives and knowledge**. It provides support for multiple projects related to the community. It includes the server/database side and a prototype access interface. This interface uses mobile devices for user access and participation, opening the system to contributions by the local population and other interested people.

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Building Communities</i> • <i>Cultivating innovation</i>
Activity Objectives	By collecting local stories, we hope to help to keep Trafaria’s memories and stories alive and connected to each other. Keeping the memories of

	the area safe and shareable. This is important to address the fear of memory loss due to the region's transformation.
When/Where	Starting September 2021, in Trafaria
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	NOVA is the leader of the project and will award grants to two students to deliver the activity.
Participants & Beneficiaries	The population of Trafaria, general public, researchers. It is both a content database and applications for remote/web and local access. Several roles are planned as it will be possible to access existing content or provide additional content, such as interest points, stories about those points and pathways through the physical locations and associated digital content.
Insights	<p>This is an ongoing activity where the technology is being built and content is gathered – through several activities such as the bottom-up museum, walkscapes and the guerrilla action. By making accessible content provided by the community with a distributed participation and curation model, this project intends to challenge and discuss questions of ownership and meaning. It will research if people are willing to contribute and share, in which ways, and what is the value that this sharing and participation has – both for the contributors and for other interested participants. There are similarities with some of the questions raised by participation in social networks but here the issues addressed, triggered by stories about a specific location, have a local and territory-based dimension that is distinct and needs further research.</p> <p>Similarly, to the activity on digital documentation there is the background of prototyping future practices of the IAT and its relation to the community where it is being implemented. We hope that this experiment will provide insights for the institutional agenda of the IAT and its relationship with Trafaria.</p>
Outputs	A digital platform comprising a content repository – text, images, video, 360 video – and clients for web and mobile access. This work started in November 2021 and is currently in the stage of ideation and design while implementing some technological proofs of concept. The goal is to have preliminary prototypes as early as possible (end of 2021) so that these developments could be presented and improved based on external feedback. Further phases include completing the development and iterative evaluation cycles in the user experience design process. As the technological development progresses, gathering content (e.g., from the Bottom Up Museum Activity) will be carried out so that when the platform is made available it will have a rich set of interconnected assets.
Outcomes	The activity will be developed through time and expected outcomes are:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Through technology and content development support building a community and understanding value in content access and contribution. Establish a collaboration between researchers of different areas and people from Trafaria. - Develop working practices that could provide insights for other projects. Make accessible stories and less known information that could be further repurposed in future projects. Obtain results on how digital technology could mediate and alter notions of value and trust. - Align the institutional agenda of the IAT with artistic/technological practices that involve local participation.
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Digital Documentation and Virtual Visit

The project will provide a detailed **3D reconstruction of the environment and its changes over time**. It will focus mainly on the Presidio Building, but adjacent areas will also be considered.

Impact domain(s)	<i>Building Communities</i> <i>Cultivating innovation</i>
Activity Objectives	Track the changes in the building and surrounding areas during renovations to address the need to keep the memory alive and to share it with the community and other stakeholders.
When/Where	Ongoing. A preliminary prototype is available and was used in project presentations and awareness activities. A release of the project is planned for March 2022, making it available for experimentation and enrichment until the end of T-Factor and beyond.
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	NOVA is the leader of the project and awarded grants to two students to deliver the activity and will also be working with technology companies.
Participants & Beneficiaries	The digital documentation system provides a way to view the transformation in the Presidio Building over time along with the historical documentation that relates to it. It is developed by a team of researchers including students in a way that foresees future work of the Institute of Arts and Technology. Meanwhile it is being used to demonstrate the project to key stakeholders that visited the place – the Ministry of Science, Technology and Higher Education, the Ministry of Culture, the Ministry of Territorial Cohesion, and the mayor of Almada. Further planned uses include making it available to students, researchers, and the general public to foster participation and develop collaborative development practices.
Insights	A prototype is in development since April 2021 but the historical documentation is still scarce. By integrating this information, we intend

	<p>to provide connections with researchers and stakeholders in the project. It will hold part of the memory of the previous uses of the IAT building to preserve that memory and build trust for future uses and functions. Showing the prototype helps to trigger discussions about the territory, its transformation, and the history of the place. Similarly, to the activity on the web of stories there is a background of prototyping future practices of the IAT, in this case participatory documentation applications. We foresee that this experiment will provide insights for the institutional agenda of the IAT and its activities regarding heritage and documentation.</p>
Outputs	<p>The main output will be a 3D navigation system combining game-like interaction with digital documentation. It will gather information to be reused in other projects and will prototype heritage documentation practices. It is a software application with a game-like interface for exploring the physical space and its associated documentation.</p>
Outcomes	<p>Expected and current outcomes include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - By showing the existing building, historical documentation and the relation with the transformation process we intend to contribute to better explain the project and its qualities. - Develop a living documentation system of the building and its surroundings. Make accessible historical documentation and relate it with the Presidio building. - Experiment development models for the future IAT, involving the student community to address local issues. Use the system to foster awareness and engage stakeholders such as the several political actors that could contribute to the region development process and resource allocation.

Digital Arts Festival

The festival is **a platform that allows people in this area to present work and projects, but also collaborate, cross ideas, experiment and discuss projects at the intersection of art and technology**. An essential component for creating these conditions is the international Open Call of the festival. The Open Call is open to all students and artists working in this area and it will address site specific topics. Exhibition and interaction spaces will be as much as possible distributed in the territory. Digital art has gained traction in recent years and will be a key area to be developed at IAT. It opens interaction and dialogue possibilities that bring together different stakeholders. In this scope having a site-specific set of artistic contributions fosters interaction between the different communities and fosters future IAT practices. There is a need to engage with the residents in creating a space for identity construction and negotiation, develop relationships and networks among the different Trafaria's communities.

Impact domain(s)	<i>Building Communities</i> <i>Cultivating innovation</i>
Activity Objectives	The festival aims to integrate artistic and academic/scientific participants, creating an informal space for ongoing dialogue and interaction between artists, their work and the public. The festival intends to present to the broadest possible audience, projects and works that merge and intersect art and technology through exhibitions, workshops, talks and round tables. It will target emerging areas that combine digital and analogue technologies in artistic experimentation, and it will have a site specific call that will address issues that are relevant for Trafaria and the future IAT.
When/Where	November 2022 and April 2024, Trafaria
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	NOVA through its Digital Media Program, including FCT and FCSH, will be leading this effort with its researchers and students, Nuno Correia, Teresa Romão, digital media Phd students, other participants include local communities, artists, students, and the general public.
Participants & Beneficiaries	<p>This activity is planned for November 2022 and April 2024 in two editions. Insights that are expected include a better understanding of the relation of digital art with the environment, physical/virtual art, and the perception of value, and establishing relationships among participants. It is also an opportunity to contribute to the international nature of the IAT and how that will impact Trafaria. Although limited in time and scope, international artists and students will be able to submit and will be invited to present and discuss their work at the festival.</p> <p>The activity builds on previous work in Digital Media and Digital Art carried out in the FuturePlaces, Plunc and Reboot festivals organized by Digital Media faculty and students. These initiatives included work regarding the relation of the digital with the space, the physical aspects of digital art and the open and participatory nature of most artistic work today – we expect that further insights will be revealed by pursuing this line of activity and further reinforcing it in Trafaria and in the path to build the Institute of Art and Technology.</p>
Outputs	Digital art installations and exhibitions, workshops, and talks.
Outcomes	This activity is planned for November 2022 and April 2024 in two editions. Insights that are expected include a better understanding of the relation of digital art with the environment, physical/virtual art and the perception of value, and establishing relationships among participants. It is also an opportunity to contribute to the international nature of the IAT and how that will impact Trafaria. Although limited in time and

scope, international artists and students will be able to submit and will be invited to present and discuss their work at the festival.

The activity builds on previous work in Digital Media and Digital Art carried out in the FuturePlaces, Plunc and Reboot festivals organized by Digital Media faculty and students. These initiatives included work regarding the relation of the digital with the space, the physical aspects of digital art and the open and participatory nature of most artistic work today – we expect that further insights will be revealed by pursuing this line of activity and further reinforcing it in Trafaria and in the path to build the Institute of Art and Technology.

Bottom-up Museum

Creation of a bottom-up museum, whose collection will be made of objects and stories chosen and created by Trafaria's communities. Participants will be invited to choose an object for the museum, to associate stories to that object, and to interview each other about the choosing, collection and selection of their objects. The new Institute of Arts & Technology at Trafaria (IAT@T) in the deactivated prison may keep the collection, functioning as the bottom-up museum, but other alternatives (virtual museum) can be further explored.

Impact domain(s)	<i>Building Communities</i>
Activity Objectives	<p>The museum intends to be a place of collective memory and cultural expression, contributing to the development of new relationships and collaborations that are intended to promote agency, decision-making and real participation in community's affairs.</p> <p>We are aiming that residents will develop a sense of belonging and empowerment through the construction and negotiation of a common ground and engaging residents in creating a space for identity construction and negotiation, developing relationships and networks among the different Trafaria's communities, activating and preserving communities' cultural heritage.</p>
When/Where	on-going Trafaria
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	NOVA will lead this activity through its Department of Conservation and Restoration, Department of Computer Science, with NOVA researchers as well as conservation students and the local community.
Participants & Beneficiaries	Trafaria residents NOVA researchers and students
Insights	Currently, we are in the process of analysing the material EDA has already collected. At the same time, we organized both formal and

	<p>informal meetings with representatives of other local associations and members of the local community.</p> <p>We have started collaborations with many different local institutions, representing the different communities composing Trafaria. Trafaria can roughly be divided into three main areas: historical centre, Il Torrão and Cova do Vapor. Hence, we chose local associations and representatives of these three main areas, to ensure an inclusive collaboration with all of them. Namely, the local representatives of the central area of Trafaria involved for now are the local association of the firemen, commission Faber, the local library, the Archaeological Centre of Almada, the Musical association of Trafaria, the Casino association, the association Age em Rede, owners of local restaurants, bars and cafés. In what concerns Il Torrão area, currently the representatives involved are Canto do Curió and the Association of the inhabitants of Il Torrão. Finally, the association of the inhabitants of Cova do Vapor and the association Margem de Coragem, associated with the local Cova do Vapor library.</p> <p>The activity has stressed the diversity present in Trafaria, in terms of racial and gender disparities, but also regarding age gaps and social classes differences. Although disparities and differences often emerge during both formal and informal meetings with the participants involved, most of the time people feel the need to define elements in common between them, all related to the belonging to the place where they all live: Trafaria.</p> <p>The activity has been helping the members of the community to discover more about the intangible cultural heritage of the area and the history of the place itself. The activity also enables the involved actors to discuss commonalities and differences among Trafaria's different areas and neighbourhoods. Potentially, this could lead to the creation of networks and collaborations between local actors who have not been in touch until now. By creating a common definition of the elements that compose the local cultural heritage, the idea is to connect people to their past and, most importantly, to common elements in which all the people recognise themselves as part of their identities. At the same time, the academic actors involved must think about ways in which this heritage can be preserved and displayed.</p>
Outputs	Workshops, reports, interviews, stories, social media videos and photos, both a physical and a virtual museum.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing shared value, developing relationships and networks among the communities. • Preservation of communities' intangible cultural heritage, dissolving the walls between academia and communities. • Expanding notions of cultural heritage by creating alternatives to the authorized heritage discourse (AHD); create opportunities for conservation students, and professionals to observe the

fundamental role that Conservation can play in social sustainability.

Critical Futures Program and Seminars

Critical Futures is a four-year-long series of seminars and workshops in synergy with the Trafaria Biennial, the FCSH Ph.D. Program on Art Studies as well as to other UNL graduate and post-graduate programs (further developments are envisaged in other relevant academic domains, namely on Communication Sciences, Sociology, Geography and Anthropology). In its 2021 edition Critical Futures offered two 12 hours seminars, taught by UAL Professors Paul Goodwin and Basia Sliwinska. The seminars were part of the Art Studies PhD program (specifically, the seminar on “Advanced Themes in Art Studies”). 10 students participated in the seminar sessions.

Impact domain(s)	<i>Building Communities</i> <i>Cultivating innovation</i>
Activity Objectives	Focusing on the intersection of the arts, critical theories, and political ecologies, it will bring together invited scholars, researchers, artists, filmmakers, post-graduate students, as well as non-specialist audiences and the interested public of local communities, bringing academic knowledge to the local community and provide awareness to IAT's program
When/Where	4 events, started May 2021 Trafaria/Online/FCSH
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	NOVA will lead this activity with NOVA professors and guests with the local community, students and public in general.
Participants & Beneficiaries	In this first (and experimental) edition, Critical Futures was mainly a NOVA activity, centred on the Art Studies program and students. In that restricted sense, we consider it a success, marking the first attempt to inscribe the T-Factor community, objectives and mode of operation in a NOVA academic program. The two subjects taught were: New Grammars in Global Art (Paul Goodwin) and Dialogues and Exercises in Communal Freedoms (Basia Sliwinska). The participants wrote an ensemble of papers, from where they were graded.
Insights	The participants had the opportunity to discuss an ensemble of topics considered relevant to their PhDs, as well as to the future of IAT research agenda. The most important of these topics had to do with communal art and creativity, its dimension, power, political implications, and idiomatic qualities. These aspects will be of extreme relevance for the success of the future synergy between Trafaria community and IAT development, particularly in what concerns gentrification processes,

	<p>their dangers, and the role that local art and strategies can play as a resilient mechanism against the procedures and effects of that gentrification.</p> <p>For that objective, the seminars explored extensively, and among others, the concepts of “care space” and “fugitive practices”, seeking to define an ethos marked by the conscience of “place” and “belonging” in art practice and art-based research.</p> <p>In terms of “Challenges”, we sought to activate “natural” empathy mechanisms between the academic community and Trafaria regeneration process, trying to make comprehensible by the group of students the need to mobilize scientific concepts, theories, and mediations to activate practical solutions for the empowerment of Trafaria community.</p>
Outputs	These outputs were practical – materialized in the papers produced and delivered by the students at the end of the seminars. The seminar sessions were a “test bed” for future explorations to prepare the methodological foundations for a healthy interaction between the future of IAT project and Trafaria social fabric.
Outcomes	One particular outcome is the establishment of certain procedures to align the academic agenda with IAT development processes and its involvement with the Trafaria community.

Photo Impulse Action

This activity is a creative residency, with two local activists creating an anti-colonial fanzine and T-shirts in a workshop titled “Community Anti colonial Fanzine” at local association Canto do Curió, integrating another workshop on Emotional Borders - walking and building temporary landmarks.

Impact domain(s)	Building Communities
Activity Objectives	The activity searches for emancipatory anti-colonial identities and engages the local population for 2º Torrão, an extremely poor project in Trafaria, bringing IAT’s vision and knowledge bearers exchanges with the local associations (Canto do Curió), and connecting the academic community with local associations and residents.
When/Where	Started September 2021
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	NOVA is leading the activity in partnership with the local association Canto do Curió and Junta de Freguesia da Trafaria.

<p>Participants & Beneficiaries</p>	<p>The creative residency has been structured around a series of meetings where the images are being investigated by the research project Photo Impulse (images from colonial scientific missions, namely border delimitation and anthropological missions) are viewed, discussed, selected, manipulated, and graphically intervened upon. These meetings have benefited from other people coming and contributing to the discussions, these other “informal” participants are invited by any of the three and have been either researchers or collaborators in other activities led by Canto do Curió.</p>
<p>Insights</p>	<p>All participants were wary at the beginning of the meetings. Photo Impulse participants were aware of their institutional position and agenda, not wanting to impose their academic views or methods. On the side of Canto do Curió, as mediators of the future workshop involving the community, felt they should be well prepared and firmly positioned before assuming an action involving the themes of racism and colonialism.</p> <p>The participants were facilitated access to the archives of the IICT (in study by Photo Impulse project and including images and reports from the scientific missions to the former colonies).</p> <p>It is worthy to note that the initial proposal was completely different: the idea proposed to Canto do Curió at the first meeting involved the construction and poetic reinterpretation of a geodesic tower, based on an image of one of those towers from a 1909 border delimitation mission. This initial intention was discussed and rejected as the building of a tower in a neighbourhood such as 2º Torrão (and the inevitable contextualization of this construction in colonial intentions) was deemed potentially offensive and conducive to misinterpretation. The desire to make a magazine and the t-shirts, was manifested by Sessa Kperrom and João Cão, as they considered it useful to spend time with the images, to consciously position themselves with the themes in the archive. A second aspect considered interesting in the magazine and t-shirts vs. the construction of a tower was the horizontal, democratic aspect of this type of production (printmaking) including the possibility of spreading the work vs. the vertical ideological substrate of building something monumental like a tower.</p> <p>This community-based process of decision was very interesting as it demonstrated how the “institutional agenda” can be contrary to the interest of those on the ground and the possibility to completely change the initial plan to meet that interest was very productive and positive.</p>

Photo credits: NOVA University

Outputs	Anticolonial/Antiracist zine(s) + T-shirt production Workshop
Outcomes	The meetings (6 to date) have evolved from timid discussions of the images into a fuller, more open discussion of the themes of racism, colonialism, and the complexities of the postcolonial situation, both on a broader, political or economic level and on a more personal level, including the way it affects the lives of those living in the 2º Torrão.

Nomadic Territories

Nomadic Territories is a cycle of walksapes that aims to contribute to the understanding of Trafaria through a direct involvement with the place and its various communities. In this sense and based on routes defined by invited artists and artistic collectives, Trafaria is to be crossed by, based on different perspectives and approached not only as a territory with specific geographic and physical features, but also as a place that embodies stories and memories and as a political and social space.

Impact domain(s)	Building Communities
Activity Objectives	This activity promotes new forms of sociality around walking to discover the region.
When/Where	June 26th and October 10th 2021 at Trafaria

<p>Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved</p>	<p>Curator: Joana Braga Professor Margarida Brito Alves Professor Margarida Medeiros Ana Catarina Miranda - Researcher Francisco Silva - Historian</p>
<p>Participants & Beneficiaries</p>	<p>Until this moment, two walks have taken place, the first led by Francisco Pinheiro, a visual artist (28 people joined), and the second one by Flora Paim and Jessica Lundin, from Arteria (19 people joined). The beneficiaries are people coming from Lisbon and from the local community.</p>
<p>Insights</p>	<p>As curators of the Nomadic Territories, we were concerned with inviting artists whose work is characterized by a strong situated approach. In that sense, we invited authors who, from an artistic research perspective and from diverse standpoints, could address Trafaria - an area in the suburb of Lisbon, close to the city centre but little known to many from a social, ethnic and cultural point of view. Each time a walk takes place, Nomadic Territories constitutes a temporary community that relates to the complexity and to the multiple layers of this territory, its diverse and often conflicting memories and stories, enabling contact with new stakeholders who might be involved in activities in the future.</p> <p>Privileging a relational and experiential dimension, the activity establishes a direct connection with the context. To that extent, Nomadic Territories contribute to the gathering of information and different forms of knowledge that stem from local resources.</p> <p><i>Photo credits: NOVA University</i></p>

Outputs	Pictures
Outcomes	One of the main contributions of Nomadic Territories is to confront the tensions between the social, political and ethical dimensions that define the site. The activity reveals the intrinsic complexities of the institutional agendas and hopefully will contribute to attune some of the local social, political and economic challenges.

Poetry Slam

Generate Trafaria's community interest towards this expression form, **inviting slam artists to showcase their work and teach the fundamental relations between words, voice, and body.**

Impact domain(s)	Building Communities
Activity Objectives	Create engagement with the local young community, through the introduction of creative processes, while keeping a language that is relevant to the community, communicating the and bringing awareness to the T-Factor project and IAT to the local community.
When/Where	June 2021 and June 2022 Trafaria
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	The NOVA team (Professors Paulo Monteiro and Carla Fernandes, together with a PhD grantee student), Slam poetry trainers and EDA led this event. The local population participated in the workshops and competitions.
Participants & Beneficiaries	There were participants between the age of 12 up to 70 years old across all social classes, from Trafaria and all over the country. On the first day of the slam (19/20 June 2020), on the second day (June 26th) there were 11 participants and 40 people in the audience. On the final day, there were 16 participants and an audience of 60 people.

Photo credits: NOVA University Lisbon

Insights	The activity revealed that there are organizations that are interested in promoting cultural events in the Trafaria Community, and also demonstrated pro-activity in contributing to the success of the project.
Outputs	2 local events
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing relationships and networks among the communities • Expanding notions of cultural heritage by creating alternatives to the authorized heritage discourse (AHD).

Optical Fiber Spider Web

TEIA is the name of an artistic installation: **a giant Spider Web made of luminescent fiber to be installed on the external walls of Trafaria’s prison during T-Factor’s period, and then on top of the roof of IAT.** This installation is to be visible from the North bank of the Tagus river and to be complemented with the development of an App (in collaboration with MA and/or Ph.D. students, as well as with MAAT, a recent museum of Architecture, Art & Technology) to allow digital access by its users to: the working and family history of the local Trafaria fishermen; their sea routes map and their fishnets ancestral crafts; the history of the prison (and of the political prisoners) until its closure in 1981; and the content of the “Web of Stories” activity, with which we will collaborate for sound and image content collection.

Impact domain(s)	Building Communities Cultivating innovation Making places
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<p>Activity Objectives</p>	<p>Creating bridges between the local population of Trafaria and its visitors, especially from the other bank of the Tagus River. Drawing attention and spreading the word concerning the future Institute for Art & Technology in Trafaria. With this in mind, we have imagined building an artistic installation that could be visible from far, especially at night. TEIA (meaning both a spider web and woven threads, in Portuguese) will constitute a large-scale art work designed to activate the powerful metaphor of the infinite connections between the past, the present and the future: the local inhabitants of Trafaria and their past generations, the fishing nets woven and mended by the fishermen and fisherwomen, the old memories of the prisoners inside the fortress, the fishing routes that are in risk of loss and their corresponding memories, the anticipated fear of loss of the ancient craft of fishing. What motivated the artist for this activity was the fact that the old Trafaria prison, currently in a derelict condition (therefore full of real living spider webs), is indeed a strong symbol of the connections between the initial military prisoners quarantined there since the 18th century, and the local fishermen, both at that time and nowadays, where fewer and fewer fishermen are still alive.</p> <p>By building this huge but fragile spider web, we would like to represent the real and imaginary routes that Trafaria's oldest fishermen would do in their trajectories to the fishing areas, thus enabling the local population to engage with the actual construction of the luminescent spider web, whether physically or by offering their stories and memories to future dedicated "webs". By developing a complementary digital (and metaphorical as well, in fact) App, we intend to map the connections between the oldest fishermen families in the village, their younger generations and the always more numerous incoming visitors, we hope to mainly offer a clearer and brighter vision to the local residents of what is upcoming in the prison. Simultaneously, this large-scale work of art, to be installed on the future IAT building's roof and over a part of the external wall of the fortress, will signal and draw attention to the river's North bank (Lisbon) about the upcoming IAT to be born there, as if turning on a subtle luminescent light during the night, and hopefully fostering awareness to T-Factor and NOVA's future Institute of Art & Technology.</p>
<p>When/Where</p>	<p>November 2021: concrete start of TEIA's design in a 3D environment. April 2022: Testing Phase: development of a physical maquette to test the materials to be used for the final spider web's construction, as well as their resistance to winds and climate aggression (in collaboration with engineers working with the artist).</p> <p>During the construction of this maquette, Victor Gama will regularly invite local students to accompany his work-in-progress in the prison's Chapel, and we would also like to organize a public launching day when it's ready to be placed outside for the testing phase.</p>

	June to September 2023: conclusion of the artistic work and respective installation in situ (provisional date to be confirmed according to the end of the building's restoration works) over the walls of Presídio da Trafaria.
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	The artist Victor Gama will lead this project working with the NOVA Professors (Carla Fernandes, curator of the activity and content aggregator of audio-visual local memories for the App) and Nuno Correia (for supervision of the computer science grantee students who will help the artist developing the App), together with EDA and the local fishermen community.
Participants & Beneficiaries	<p>Participants: an invited contemporary musician, instruments designer and media artist; NOVA Professors; EDA; local youngsters; local fishermen; expert engineers in site-specific sculpture, hired by Victor Gama to build and install the actual spider web.</p> <p>Beneficiaries: local population and schools; local economy in general when visitors will come to see the installation.</p>
Insights	Not yet applicable, as this activity is just starting. However, we have by now been able to identify several positive aspects, such as the curiosity from the Torrão secondary school, as well as the cultural and sports associations regarding what the future IAT will be and the expectable consequences (both positive and negative) for their social and economic tissues. We have also witnessed the interest shown by restaurants and shop owners as to what they may gain by the increasing number of visitors when they come to see the spider web dynamic sculpture.
Outputs	<p>Design of the generic proposal with images and respective outlays for presentation (available on our project Drive dedicated to visual outputs). NOVA's Lisbon Pilot Day online event (04th May 2021) with the presence of the artist and Carla Fernandes, this activity's curator, as well as of other NOVA colleagues.</p> <p>Planned for April 2022: Testing Phase (in collaboration with engineers working with the artist) with development of a physical maquette to test the materials to be used for the final spider web's construction.</p>

Fadiagens

Impact domain(s)	Building Communities <i>Making places</i>
Activity Objectives	The project aims to unlock the transformative potential for urban regeneration of the temporary use of cultural heritage places, as well as to involve the local population in the emblematic sites representing Trafaria's history.

Activity Description	This was a mixed and itinerant public event-show (of course, offered for free, there was no entrance fee at all) including: Fado singers from Trafaria; performers to interact with the local people in the streets during the day before and some hours before the actual show in order to attract people and spread the word about the event and the respective locations.
When/Where	Trafaria: 31st. October 2021 - 16h30 to 20h30 This itinerant event took place in 3 key-places of meeting points for the population: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the "Verbena" (Trafaria's Musical Society); • the "Cortiço" (laid-back Café, owned by Zeca, a charismatic person in the village); • the "Club" (Trafaria's football club).
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	Artistic proposal: Marta Miranda and Carla Fernandes Owners/managers of the 3 local places mentioned above.
Participants & Beneficiaries	Audience: over 50 people, from local population to foreigners passing by, from youngsters to elderly people.
Outputs	Recordings of the event.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing relationships and networks among the communities, as well as a larger awareness regarding contemporary and site-specific collaborative artistic practices. • Preservation of communities' intangible cultural heritage, dissolving the walls between academia and communities.

4.3.3. Exploring and Inquiring Support Activities and T-Lab Probes

Grand Tour Roundtable

The Grand Tour is an activity to share with citizens the history of neighbourhoods surrounding the regeneration area. It is a way to engage different publics in the discovery of the neighbourhood, and to connect the area under regeneration to the wider surrounding areas. Moreover, the activity promotes new forms of sociality around the use of bikes as a way to discover the city. The support activity is an exchange with similar activities from other cases (Florence, Lodz) to inspire the "Walkscapes" cycles that had been already planned in Trafaria.

Impact domain(s)	Building Communities Cultivating innovation
Activity Objectives	The roundtable supported the "Nomadic Territories" walkscapes cycle organised by NOVA, with the aim of inspiring with different examples

	<p>from Florence - Manifattura Tabacchi and Lodz - EC1, but also the wider city projects of mapping industrial heritage.</p> <p>The exchange has mainly been about the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to create a living archive by digital means such as an App • How to measure the impact of activities, the outcomes of the stories collected, the building of collective memory.
When/Where	Roundtable on the 7th October Online
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	Lama; City of Lodz; EC1; NOVA; University of Dortmund; Associazione dei Desideri; Topografie
Participants & Beneficiaries	10 persons representing the above-mentioned organisations
Insights	The roundtable has been an activity showing the different approaches in the three cities and creating some useful linkages to generate an embryonic community of practice within T-Factor related to walkscapes experiences.
Outputs	Collection of stories and memories to inspire the Walkscapes in Trafaria.
Outcomes	Support on Collaboration and Governance domain

Data Campfire (T-Lab Probe)

Taking inspiration from data feminism and Afro-American data activism, we have developed a "data campfire" where local community representatives are called to bring their knowledge about Trafaria. By looking at the past and the present of Trafaria, citizens can situate themselves in a larger story, take ownership of it and imagine a different future.

Impact domain(s)	<p>Improving Quality of Life</p> <p>Building Communities</p> <p>Cultivating innovation</p>
Activity Objectives	<p>Community organisations and informal leaders are living sensors of the local population's evolution, needs and challenges. This knowledge base needs to stay relevant in the regeneration process as much as "official" dataflows from technological sensors and public authorities sources. Indeed, historical reality and desired reality are disconnected. Historical data perpetuate inequalities: data about disadvantaged groups embed and perpetuate their historical disadvantage but tell little about their everyday lives and desires.</p>
Activity Description	<p>Participants have been divided in three groups, representing 3 different areas of Trafaria. They responded to a set of questions about both the specificities and communalities of the areas they represented. The progress</p>

	of the activity showed how official data about Trafaria is scarce and does not represent people's lives in the present.
When/Where	October 21 st 2021 Trafaria Fort
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	T-Lab 3 – Knowledge Bearer NOVA researchers and students Stakeholders – Trafaria community representatives.
Participants	19 Trafaria community representatives, including cultural, social, and sports associations' leaders and local business owners (restaurants, bakery)
Insights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders seemed to be curious about the meeting and the project. Engagement was difficult at the beginning, becoming more intense towards the end. The activity exposed some disconnection among stakeholders or even a little sense of community. They mentioned some communalities related to the neighbourhoods where they live but claimed not to know much about other neighbourhoods e.g., people living in one neighbourhood claimed to ignore other neighbourhoods' features and behaviours. • In general, stakeholders have shown they are willing to create more connection among themselves and engage in common activities. • This and other activities that are part of T-Factor Program and have been taking place at Trafaria seem to be creating some curiosity and attention, which helps to address the need to build and engage community.

	<i>Photo Credits: Marta Arniani</i>
Outputs	Map of community formal and informal datasets that can be used in future engagement activities. Proposals for the accessibility of datasets for the community, from which engagement activities can spur
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The activity was an enabler of relationship development among Trafaria’s communities. It also contributed to a steadier relationship between academia and residents. Stakeholders became more engaged in discussing communalities and expressed desire to continue this endeavour. • The activity has shown that shared memories about places and activities no longer exist are probably the most important commonality among the stakeholders. A sense of collective nostalgia is a strong connector and an important tool to use to build community. • It contributed to identify the more active leaders of the different communities and to understand that they belong to an age group that does not include young people and is composed of a large majority of white men and women.

4.3.4. Overview of Stakeholders

Both the Science and Humanities and Social Sciences Schools NOVA have been very actively involved in this project, comprising over 20 people across the schools in the development of all activities. We have also engaged a postdoc and three master grantees to support the engagement with the community and the activities’ efforts. On top of it we have been working closely with the local stakeholders such as EDA, the band O’questrada, Casa da Cerca (a local exhibition space run by the municipality) and, the association Canto do Curió, and the local events space Casino da Trafaria. Through the work we are developing with the Bottom Up Museum and the outcomes from the Data Camp Fire Probe we are actively identifying other relevant players and stakeholders, that will play a relevant role in the transformation process, particularly those related to the municipality and local associations.

The Kumu map of all stakeholders is provided in the Figure below and it can be accessed [here](#) in its dynamic fashion.

Missing Stakeholders

The local council, public library, 2º torrão association, local music school, haven't been engaged yet, but we are willing to start working with them. By developing activities in the area, the different stakeholders become more aware of IAT and T-Factor and we hope that it will result in higher engagement and participation.

4.4. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

The activities that we've developed so far enabled us to better understand the needs and concerns of the local population and plan future activities and actions accordingly.

Due to the fact that the works for IAT will start in June 2022 and won't be finished until July 2023 we will have limited access to the area where the transformation will actually happen, but we are confident that with the support of the local municipality we will be able to find other spaces surrounding the Fort. In which concerns other stakeholders, we are in active conversations with the local municipality in order for them to become more involved and give

us more support, whether it is through the use of their locations or furniture. We are looking to diversify the funding opportunities, but it has been challenging and we are relying heavily on the T-Factor funding. This can be an issue in the future as we don't rely on volunteer work and the academic staff involved in the project is not being paid to develop the activities.

Regarding key conclusions, the overarching conclusion since we've started this project and the initial report is that there is a lack of visibility in Trafaria on what is happening next and that these activities we've developed so far showed how relevant it is for the locals to know what is going on and to have a say on how they want to be involved.

The team involved in this phase will remain the same throughout the rest of the project, or at least that is so far the plan, however as the pandemic situation is stable now, we will be able to start engaging different stakeholders that so far were unable to participate due to lack of in person meetings and difficulty to connect on digital platforms. We are planning to host large in person meetings with the different stakeholders to generate more interaction and participation opportunities.

LONDON EUSTON

5. LONDON EUSTON

5.1. PILOT STARTING CONTEXT AND PRIORITIES

Introduction

With an area covering 60Ha in the heart of London, the area of Euston is currently predominantly known as a main transport hub for London. Surrounding the station to the East and West are densely populated residential areas, with a high percentage of social housing in areas such as Somers Town to the East and Regents Park Estate and Cumberland Market to the West. Along key routes in close proximity to the station such as Drummond Street and Chalton Street are shops and restaurants, businesses and various cultural establishments. To the South of the station across Euston Road is Bloomsbury and various institutions such as University College London and the Wellcome Collection. To the East is another large transport hub, Kings Cross & St Pancras, which is also a recently regenerated area housing Central Saint Martins College, University of the Arts London, many technology focussed businesses and high end shops, and to the West is Regents Park. Euston is already a built-up area that is currently defined by an intersection of routes that are busy and often difficult to navigate, especially East to West where the current station design creates a large barrier between neighbourhoods.

Social Context

Euston and its surrounding neighbourhoods are marked by distinct contrasts. Despite its proximity to the centre of London and being one of the busiest transport hubs in London surrounded by commercial, cultural and educational centres, the residents of Euston continue to face many social, economic, environmental, health and educational barriers. A high proportion of residents are economically inactive compared with the Camden and London averages, and household income is approximately £20,000 lower than in Camden as a whole. Whilst there are 8,200 jobs in Euston, representing 3.1 jobs per capita of working age residents, these jobs are often not filled by Euston residents. There is a very strong sense of community, especially within neighbourhood pockets, and there are also many local organisations working to highlight and alleviate specific issues in the short and long term, alongside Camden Council.

The regeneration of Euston is multifaceted and includes many different regeneration stakeholders making it a highly complex Pilot. The vast infrastructure works for the construction of the High Speed Rail (HS2) which will have a main terminus at Euston Station are at the heart of the project. Connected with this is the Over Station Development being overseen by Lendlease as 'Master Development Partner' (MDP) who are developing a masterplan for the area above the new infrastructure of tracks. National Rail and Transport for London are also making changes to the existing station, the station area and connected transport infrastructure such as CrossRail 2. Alongside this, the London Borough of Camden are updating the Euston Area Plan (EAP) to ensure that policies in the plan reflect up to date information, constraints, opportunities and local priorities. The EAP provides guidance for the

overall regeneration project and will provide a basis for assessing the masterplan when it is submitted for planning.

Regeneration Stakeholders

As a requirement arising from the Oakervee Review, an independent review of HS2 in 2020, the project was obliged to set up a new governance system which provides a single entity to oversee all works - in response to this, The Euston Partnership was established in July 2020, sponsored by the Department for Transport, to actively promote and enable closer collaboration and joint working between all Partners working at Euston. The board consists of members from High Speed 2 Limited, the Department for Transport, London Borough of Camden, Lendlease, Transport for London, the Greater London Authority and Network Rail. The Euston Partnership aims to drive a singular focus on Euston, and achieve the benefits of integration across the three capital projects on the site.

Vision

A number of priorities have been identified by different regeneration stakeholders but in broad terms these are outlined below.

The new high-speed rail, HS2, with a main terminus at Euston will enable increased connectivity between London and the North of the UK. The ambition is for Euston to become a world class national transport interchange. Locally, the current design of Euston station creates a large East to West barrier in the area, cutting off sections of the city from one another and creating closed off neighbourhoods. The design of the proposed Over Station Development (OSD), above the tracks, will establish new links between these neighbourhoods with the provision of new routes and improved public realm. Whilst there was an original proposal for the OSD to be at the same level as the city this was deemed to be too expensive therefore the space above the tracks will be stepped and ramped. Alongside this, the OSD is aiming to provide between 2,800 and 3,800 additional homes, 180,000-280,000 sqm of new employment/economic floorspace (providing between 7,700 and 14,100 jobs), and in the region of 20,000sqm of retail floorspace focused around the station. There is also a need for education, health and other facilities to support new development, and the integration of existing and new communities. There are already a number of existing institutions in close proximity to Euston such as University College London, the University of the Arts London, Google, the Wellcome Collection and many others which are all members of the Knowledge Quarter (a knowledge cluster membership organisation). Therefore, there is a focus on building on the existing knowledge based, research and creative uses in the area in order to encourage and strengthen Euston's role as an internationally recognised knowledge and research hub. Alongside this, the regeneration stakeholders are looking at the STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Art & Design, Mathematics) agenda and how this can be integrated as a local strategy for the area with objectives including connecting schools to STEAM knowledge and resources within larger organisations in the surrounding area.

The provision of green space in Euston is an on-going issue, and one which has been worsened through the initial stages of the regeneration project. Recorded in 2010, just 8.7% of the land at Euston was public green open space, compared to Camden overall at 24.8%. Alongside this, public green space per capita is at 8.5sqm in Euston, compared to Camden overall at 24.59sqm per capita, and pollution in the area close to Euston Road caused by traffic continues to be a huge problem. Since HS2 was given the all clear to proceed in 2017 and construction works

started on site, this issue has been made worse and there has been a further loss of green spaces in the area, which has become a key area of dispute and disappointment for the local communities in Euston. Due to this and the pre-existing lack of green space, there is an ambition that Euston should be a place that is perceptibly green in all respects, integrating high environmental standards, active and sustainable travel, planting, biodiversity, and network of open spaces and green infrastructure.

The timeline for the regeneration project is currently thought to be around 20-30 years until completion. The development at Euston will emerge in stages over a long time period and will continue to evolve once structures are in place. There is an acknowledgement from the regeneration stakeholders that the development must ensure that local people are made part of Euston's growth, and there is an ambition to 'bring the benefits forward' for the existing residents and local businesses. However, the strategy of exactly how this will be achieved continues to emerge. There is support from the regeneration stakeholders for the provision of meanwhile uses and programmes in the area in order to support and build capacity within the existing social infrastructure. However, there is work to be done to align partner agendas and join-up partner resourcing via a strategy that all partners support. The recent creation of a Meanwhile Use Working Group, as part of the Place & Social Value panel, put together by The Euston Partnership, is working towards a mutually supported meanwhile strategy for the area.

Despite opposing HS2 for a number of years, Camden Council now have to ensure that re-development delivers the greatest possible benefit for their residents. Therefore, engagement and participation of residents has been central to Camden's strategy for the area. There has been substantial work done on forming resident groups, such as the Residents Advisory Group, that are representative of the diverse population of Euston and which enable local voices to be heard. Despite this, there is a lot of mistrust felt by the residents and local businesses towards the regeneration stakeholders due to the perception that resident views over key issues such as the provision of green space have been ignored. Despite wanting to engage in the conversation, a lot of 'engagement fatigue' is also reported by some residents and local businesses who feel they have been repeatedly questioned about their priorities, and yet do not see their contributions acted upon. Despite this there is also a keenness from many groups to have their voices heard and see their ideas materialised into tangible actions in the short term.

5.1.1. Issues

Engagement & Participation

Impact Domains

- *Building Communities*

Some specific groups of citizens in Euston have been engaged and consulted by a variety of stakeholders over many years linked to multiple regeneration initiatives and proposals. This has led to a feeling of 'consultation fatigue' for many living and working in the area as a result of similar questions being asked of them, and responses given, often without participants being able to see tangible outcomes from their input. Alongside this, participation can be hard work and requires time. Consequently, not everyone is interested or able to participate. There is also some difficulty in reaching certain voices and groups in the area which can lead to a lack

of participation and the exclusion of certain voices and perspectives. Both engagement fatigue and a lack of engagement can contribute to division and mistrust between some citizens and regeneration dutyholders. Whilst many local people and businesses want to input and have their voices heard, they also want to see what positive effects and tangible outcomes their contribution has in the short and medium term. Whilst there is a substantial amount of quantitative open data for the Euston area collated by Camden and available online (<https://opendata.camden.gov.uk/>) there is currently very limited qualitative data shared, including the results of past consultations. Making these data more easily accessible could help ensure that future consultation and engagement builds upon past findings and avoids repeating past questioning.

Green Space

Impact Domains

- *Improving Health & Wellbeing*
- *Attaining sustainability*

Before the regeneration project and HS2 proposals there were already many issues around access to green and open spaces in the Euston area. In 2010 before the regeneration started, just 8.7% of the land at Euston public green open space, compared to 24.8% in Camden overall. Public green space per capita was also at 8.5sqm in Euston, compared to 24.5 9sqm per capita in Camden overall. Since construction works started on site, this issue has been made worse and there has been a further loss of green spaces in the area HS2 had powers to claim certain sites surrounding the development site as part of initiating their construction site. The sites affected are Euston Square Gardens (outside Euston station), site of former St James Gardens (designated for housing), and the site of Hampstead Road open space (which has seen the closure of ball courts and playgrounds). This has become a key area of dispute and disappointment for the local communities in Euston. This issue has been raised by all residents and community groups interviewed so far and has also emerged from consultations in the area linked to mitigation initiatives such as Open Space Improvements, Greening Phoenix Road.

Youth Deprivation

Impact Domains

- *Building Communities*
- *Growing prosperity*

There are a considerable number of challenges affecting young people in the Euston area, particularly in the high-density social housing to the East and West of Euston station. It is felt by many residents in Euston that there are a lack of opportunities and positive role models, and factors such as this can lead to young people turning to crime, an ongoing issue in the area. Many young people living and working in Euston will be affected by the development for a prolonged period at a key time in their lives. Therefore, it is felt that there must be a focus on how to support young people in the area, providing more opportunities within education, skills development, employment, and also creative opportunities. There are several Voluntary and Community Sector (VCS) organisations such as Fitzrovia Youth in Action, West Euston Partnership and Somers Town Youth Centre (STCA), and schemes such as Kickstarter, which are leading the way on tackling these issues in the local area.

Environment

Impact Domains

- *Improving Health & Wellbeing*
- *Attaining sustainability*

To the South of Euston Station is Euston Road, one of the busiest roads in London and a key East/West route across, in and out, of London. Due to this there is a lot of pollution from cars in the form of emissions and noise affecting the environment and the health of those living and working in the area. Substantial issues around noise, vibrations, dust and pollution caused by construction impacts have also been reported in the areas surrounding Euston Station. This is felt acutely by residents who live closest to the current HS2 construction site to the West of the station stretching northwards, with some tenants having to be relocated due to the disruptions in extreme cases. Somers Town has also been affected by construction works at King's Cross since the early 2000's and this area will continue to be affected by construction works at Euston until the 2030's. These construction impacts affect the quality of life and the environment during the development phases. Alongside this, local businesses, especially those around Drummond Street, are affected by long-term and changeable road closures which make the routes from Euston station to these areas difficult to navigate leading to shops and restaurants losing business. There are also reports of ongoing issues around waste in the area such as overflowing bins on estates and in the street and difficulties with large bulky items left out in the street (in part due to the cost and difficulties associated with having it collected), and a lack of recycling facilities.

Covid Recovery

Impact Domains

- *Improving Health & Wellbeing*
- *Attaining sustainability*
- *Growing prosperity*

The effects of Covid-19 have been felt acutely in the local areas surrounding Euston station. Many local people have lost their jobs over the last 18 months as a direct result of Covid-19, and local businesses such as shops and restaurants have been severely affected by the lack of footfall and loss of customers in the area. There are local schemes such as Camden Renewal working on strategies such as 'We Make Camden' considering the possibilities for more resilient local communities arising from delivery of 'renewal missions' focused on four key areas including; Opportunities for young people, Sustainable communities, Access to food for all, Diversity in positions of power. Many people in Euston live in high-density buildings often with limited access to open spaces, and Covid-19 has laid bare the inequality of access to open and green spaces across Euston.

Crime, Anti-Social Behaviour & Safety

Impact Domains

- *Improving Health & Wellbeing*
- *Building Communities*

In many parts of Euston, it is felt that crime and anti-social behaviour heavily impact on health and wellbeing. Especially to the West of the station around Regents Parks Estate, Cumberland Market and the surrounding network of buildings and streets which are often difficult to navigate. As recently as August 2021 there was a shooting in Clarence Gardens leading to the hospitalisation of four people. The fear of crime also causes anxiety and a feeling of a lack of safety which contributes to social isolation for those less willing to leave their home.

Health & Wellbeing

Impact Domains

- *Improving Health & Wellbeing*
- *Building Communities*

There is a general consensus around Euston that more needs to be done to improve the health and wellbeing of residents who face multiple challenges relating to their environment, economic and social circumstances. Health & Wellbeing is a complex and multifaceted subject and there can be multiple factors affecting poor health & wellbeing. In 2018/19 there was a focus from regeneration stakeholders Camden & Lendlease on reducing social isolation and loneliness in the area. Lendlease are co-founders of an initiative called The Loneliness Lab (<https://www.lonelinesslab.org/>). Locally, one activity of the lab was a workshop 'Creating Connectedness' delivered in partnership with the Public Collaboration Lab at Central Saint Martins, University of the Arts London. In 2019 Lendlease also commissioned a piece of research by Publica to develop a 'Public Life Strategy' looking at the potential of the public realm to contribute to health & wellbeing in Euston.

Public Realm

Impact Domains

- *Making Places*
- *Attaining sustainability*

Whilst there are plans for regeneration of Euston station and the infrastructure required for HS2, National Rail and TfL, there also needs to be an emphasis on improving the fabric of the city and public realm that already exists around the station, which is in daily use by residents, local businesses and visitors to the area. There are currently many empty shops, and premises that are used infrequently leading to a feeling of abandonment in certain areas. There is a need to ensure that streets, particularly around the station, have active frontages so that they feel welcoming and safe. The barrier to East/West movement caused by Euston station has been exacerbated by the construction works and poor-quality wayfinding in the area. There is also a consensus from Camden Council that any proposed public realm in Euston must address equality and inclusion and provide a safe space for a diverse mix of uses by different local groups.

Cultural Expression

Impact Domains

- *Cultivating innovation*

It has been outlined by the Residents Advisory Group in Euston that there are currently limited opportunities for cultural expression in the area, and that there needs to be more support in the provision of cultural activities locally. The imposition of arts and cultural expression is also felt and there is a strong desire for community-led and co-created events. Running for 4 months, until the end of October 2021, Camden have been helping to organise a range of events under the bracket of Camden Together which was a programme aimed at celebrating Camden's rich, diverse and vibrant cultural landscape through music, dance and public art. These events all took place in local venues and were offered free to the public with an aim to support local trade and creativity. It has also been identified that the current night time economy in Euston is not accessible and inclusive to a range of different groups.

Food

Impact Domain

- *Improving Health & Wellbeing*

Food lies at the heart of Euston's diverse cultural and community life especially in the Drummond Street area. However, there is difficulty for residents in the Euston area in gaining access to affordable fresh food near where they live. To deliver the vision of a 15-minute neighbourhood for Euston affordable fresh food will need to be made more available locally.

5.1.2. Challenges and Opportunities

The following key challenges and opportunities will be addressed through the Euston Pilot within the regeneration area.

Challenge 1 - Reciprocal Engagement & Building Trust

Due to the engagement fatigue and mistrust felt by some Euston residents, there is a challenge is to consider how engagement can be delivered in more reciprocal ways in order to provide immediate benefits to residents and local groups. Some residents observe that for many years it has been usual for those asking the questions to be paid and those answering to not be paid. There is a desire to move away from extractive processes of research and 'consultation' and towards engagements that are more reciprocal in approach. It is necessary to define what motivates engagement and also what contributions can be made in return for residents' time – whilst vouchers are the most used way of rewarding residents, it is felt that this doesn't do enough to support residents. Other approaches such as payment (the London Living Wage), learning recognition, capacity building, support to find work and allocation of support services (e.g. help for those with caring responsibilities) need to be explored. If engagement can be done in more reciprocal ways where residents and local groups are given the chance to define the brief and influence and shape the outcomes in the area, then this could lead to building links and eventually trust between residents and regeneration stakeholders. This will also pave the way for strategies that prioritise community-led governance approaches. The approach to the communication of the regeneration project is also currently confusing and there needs to be an integrated approach across the regeneration stakeholders which is something currently being addressed by the Euston Partnership in establishing The *Discover Euston* website.

Challenge 2 - Provision of and Access to Green Space

The need for accessible green open space is felt urgently by residents, especially those who cannot easily reach Regents Park to the West of the site. Due to the loss of and lack of green spaces in the Euston area the challenge is how to find ways for residents and local organisations to connect to existing green spaces, and how to support on-going access to these green spaces. There is also a need to consider how to make existing infrastructure greener and how to provide green and open spaces in the short to medium term before the Over Station Development and associated public realm are complete in 20-30 + years.

Challenge 3 - Connecting with and Providing Opportunities for Local Youth

There are several VCS organisations and programs in the area that support young people, such as Fitzrovia Youth in Action, West Euston Partnership, Somers Town Youth Centre/STCA. Also, several work experience programmes, including those supported by the governments Kickstart scheme, and Lendlease's work through schools supporting the development and delivery of a STEAM curriculum. However, it is felt that there is more work to be done to alleviate problems of youth deprivation in the area and associated challenges such as grooming of young people and issues around drug dealing, and young people being coerced into crime. The regeneration project must prioritise the support of existing communities in the short to medium term to help alleviate these issues.

Opportunity 1 - Joining Up Engagement Activities & Outcomes

There is an opportunity to work together to survey the existing engagement landscape and join up engagement activities across Euston, with the aim of setting out an ambition for reciprocal working practices that can contribute towards and build capacity in local businesses, organisations, and people. This would contribute to operational & strategic infrastructuring and help to align agendas and combine resources locally towards collective impact. Something that continues to come up in the Euston Engagement Group meetings (convened by Camden and attended by all regenerations stakeholders involved in organising engagement activities in the area) is the need for a way to share engagement activities & findings in an accessible and easily editable format. There is an opportunity for T-Factor to bring capacity to this activity.

Opportunity 2 - Rethinking the Role of the Public Realm

HS2 have given Camden Council £2.7million in mitigation funding so that Camden can improve existing open spaces around Euston as part of their Open Space Improvements work. There is potential to connect T Factor activities with these projects being delivered across six sites in the Euston area. There is also potential to connect with Camden Partners Improvements programme, and the Council's Parks for Health work. There are also additional HS2 funding opportunities that could support local groups to improve biodiversity and green infrastructure in the Euston area.

Alongside the need to consider the provision of green spaces, there is also an opportunity to rethink the role of streets and squares, especially post Covid, to create thriving and inclusive neighbourhoods. If designed and programmed in the right way, public spaces have the capacity to address inclusivity and inequalities but key to this is an understanding of the needs of existing communities and how these spaces can become and remain accessible to them.

Due to the complexity of the current urban realm around Euston there is also an opportunity to improve foot and cycle connections over and around Euston Station and the railway track.

Opportunity 3 - Adaptability & Capacity Building of Existing SMEs

It is crucial that the development of Euston does not just concentrate on bringing new business and tenants to the area but also seizes the opportunity to support existing businesses and local organisations to adapt and build operational capacity. Locally this is something that is currently being worked on through the Camden Renewal project (<https://camdenrenewal.com/>), set up after the start of Covid-19 pandemic, and also through the High Streets For All scheme led by Camden Council and the GLA. Locally there is a substantial amount of work planned for Drummond Street in association with Camden Town Unlimited/Euston Business Improvement District. Despite Covid-19 severely impacting upon local retail and business in the area, it has also catalysed local businesses and VCS organisations to work together in collaborative ways that did not seem possible previously.

Core Challenge/Opportunity: Aligning and Leveraging Aims and Resourcing

There is a necessity to acknowledge the resources available through larger stakeholders in the area, both in the present (e.g. Lendlease, HS2, UAL, UCL, Camden Council, DfT) and into the future (businesses that will become new tenants within the 'Innovation Districts'), and understand how these can be leveraged to unlock opportunities and build capacities within existing local community groups, businesses and residents who live and work in the area. The Knowledge Quarter is a thriving cluster of institutions and organisations, located in a small area around King's Cross, the Euston Road and Bloomsbury. Currently the KQ is delivering an initiative called the People's Quarter which considers the civic role of KQ organisations and how they can increase the extent to which local communities' benefit from being located within an Innovation District. It is also important to consider what meaning and value 'innovation' holds for people that live and work in Euston and the potential for innovation districts to trigger preventative health, wellbeing and happiness. Coupled with this is the possibility to consider the provision of and access to Arts, Culture and Creativity to unlock new jobs and enterprise opportunities in the area, and how this can become a core aspect of the meanwhile strategy for the area. Discussions about how to bring resources to resident-led meanwhile uses are in progress through the Meanwhile Use Working Group, convened by the Euston Partnership as part of the Place & Social Value Panel.

Core Challenge/Opportunity: Bringing Benefits Forward

Due to the timescales of the regeneration, the residents and businesses of Euston must contend with major disruptions to their lives and work for the next 30 years. Due to this extended timescale, there is often talk from the regeneration stakeholders in the area about the need to 'bring the benefits of development forward' in the medium and short term to those already living and working in Euston. Whilst a clear strategy as to how best to do this is emerging, there are proposals such as those made by Camden Partners, a portfolio of seventeen potential meanwhile projects, looking at more immediate improvements to the public realm and explicitly about bringing benefits forward for residents.

One of the key recommendations from the Residents Advisory Group (RAG) was for Euston to remain a 'place' while development is underway. The RAG wants Euston's communities to be

able to carry on a good 'normal life' over the future decades of development. This means that people can live in their homes without worry, to access good quality open and green space, to stay healthy, and to be able to access the facilities and amenities that they need. They also need to be able to easily access information about what is happening, not just at an overall level, but at the scale of individual households. Stakeholders have identified that 'Meanwhile Uses' are likely to play a significant role here. T-Factor has the capacity to unlock the potential for meanwhile strategies to contribute to bringing the benefits of development forward in the short and medium term to those who already live and work in the area by working with the various stakeholders to propose a meaningful meanwhile strategy that addresses aims of residents, local business, cultural institutions and also the regeneration stakeholders. This also links in with T-Lab 1: Arts, Culture & Creativity, convened by UAL, and the potential to integrate local agendas such as STEAM (mentioned above) in preparing young people for future opportunities in the local area.

Core Opportunity: Interrelation Between the Meanwhile Strategy and the Masterplan

Within the current situation at Euston, there are seen to be limited options for physical space that could be used for meanwhile projects and programmes in the area. Whilst space is certainly limited a broader consideration of types of space that might be available and when may be beneficial. There is the possibility that spaces could become available at certain times of day such as offices and workspaces, retail shops, restaurants, university premises, and TRA halls. There is an opportunity to consider prompt, regular and stable meanwhile uses across the time and spaces of the development, also considering spaces that sit outside of the EAP and Masterplan boundaries. As well as spatial interventions, there are opportunities for meanwhile programmes that provide support and build capacity of residents and other stakeholders. Alongside this there is also the need to consider the longer-term potential for the meanwhile strategy to influence and contribute to aspects of the masterplan, both within the Euston Area Plan boundary by Camden Council and the Over Station Development boundary by Lendlease. There is an ambition that Lendlease will submit their Masterplan for Euston for planning in 2022 however, currently very little is publicly known about the Masterplan. There is also very limited information available for the phasing of the masterplan. If this information were more readily available, it would help to establish where and when specific spaces or buildings could become available for use at specific times. It is a goal of the Meanwhile Use Working Group to establish a clear relationship between the meanwhile strategy and the masterplan.

5.1.3. Needs

Green Space

There is a need to engage more diverse actors in green space activities in order to gain an understanding of how different actors experience their value. For example, is there a possibility for there to be layered activity with the same spaces being used, by different people, for different activities at different times? There is a need to understand what different groups would want to see in terms of activating green spaces in the area – for sports such as football or for allotments or for relaxation and meditation. Due to the complex nature of the streets and buildings to the West side of Euston station there is also potential to join up existing green space initiatives and think about where greening can be delivered in other ways e.g. green

routes and parklets such as the Greening Phoenix Road project in Somers Town. These interventions may be small-scale on their own but have the potential to create joined up areas of green corridors supported by signposting and wayfinding. A detailed mapping of the existing green space network in the area would be beneficial for this.

Equitable Access to Meanwhile

Working in collaborative ways with residents and local groups to define priorities and proposals for meanwhile projects together, leading to working together to deliver interventions that have immediate and tangible outcomes. It is not a simple equation of ‘matching’ people with space, and people who want space. What is needed is an integrated strategy providing different kinds of support necessary to help owners get spaces ‘meanwhile ready’, and potential meanwhile operators to get projects ‘meanwhile ready’. The Meanwhile Use Working Group, reporting to the Place & Social Value Panel formed by The Euston Partnership, is interested in the contribution that T-Factor can make to this, and have welcomed support to come up with a system that supports equitable and inclusive access to meanwhile spaces that address community priorities.

5.2. MEANWHILE SPACES AND USES

The map below shows the location of existing, planned and potential meanwhile spaces and uses within the Euston regeneration area over the period of the T-Factor project.

Link to the map [here](#).

5.2.1. Existing Meanwhile Spaces and Uses

The Story Garden

The site of [The Story Garden](#) is in Somers Town, with Euston station to the West and St Pancras to the East, neighbouring the Francis Crick Institute to the North and the British Library to the South. The site was opened in 2019 and is due to remain open until the redevelopment of the land by The British Library (dates tbc). The meanwhile use is Regular / Stable.

The Story Garden inhabits a previously disused and inaccessible piece of land which now houses a garden and a series of temporary buildings which are frequently open to the public. Since June 2019 Global Generation have been designing, developing and building the Story Garden through collaboration with local people including residents, families, children and young people, local workers, companies and institutions. To date they have designed and built the garden with over 650 adults and nearly 300 children and young people. It's important for GG that they foster collective ownership over the Story Garden as community space, and ensure local people have the power to influence and contribute to their local area. So far, the main ways in which they've been building the garden with the local community have been: Design and Build sessions for Children and Young People, Community Workshops, Collaborative Projects with Students & Others, Drop-in Volunteer Sessions, Organised Volunteering Days, and Construction support and collaboration from local companies.

The key objectives of the Story Garden are to provide a space that supports opportunities for local residents, school groups and others to gain access to green space and spaces for growing, with a strong aim to provide education around the natural world and creative workshop opportunities.

The British Library owns the land and has leased it to Global Generation for a number of years. Promotion is done through the Global Generation website and mailing lists, also word of mouth in the local area, and there are decorated hoardings and notice boards on site. The site is also frequently an openly accessible space for people walking past. Whilst the site is accessible to anyone, the educational aspect is focussed around working with young people, mostly from local schools who they have formed partnerships with. Global Generation are funded through charitable funding schemes and also through the developers they work alongside (Argent, Stanhope, Lendlease). The British Library approached Global Generation directly about the availability of the site, having seen the work they did for a few years in King's Cross with the Skip Garden. The site is overseen by staff of Global Generation, and also MAKE @ Story Garden (see below).

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Natural; Private or business buildings;
Type of meanwhile use	Education & training; Green & garden; Health spot;
Stakeholders involved and roles	Global Generation – charity who have worked in the area for approx. 15 years, previously on the Skip Garden at King's Cross. Leaseholders for the site, programme organisers. The British Library – landowners

	Stanhope – developers & funders Lendlease – developers & funders Local residents – users Local school children – users Your Bike Project – co-tenant MAKE – co-tenant / see below
Target groups	Children & Families, Young people
Temporality	The site was opened in 2019 and is due to remain open until the redevelopment of the land by The British Library (dates tbc). The Story Garden is a second iteration of the Skip Garden run by Global Generation in King's Cross for 10 years previously. The meanwhile use is Regular / Stable.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	The Story Garden and MAKE are written into funding opportunities/bids such as GLA Future Neighbourhoods projects. The operations of MAKE within the Story Garden are now being led and run by Somers Town Community Association who are a T Factor partner. MAKE is an accessible and bookable space with good facilities for making therefore can host activities for E&I. There is potential to connect The Story Garden and Global Generation with any E&I activities around the public realm, improving environment & biodiversity, and edible landscapes.
Relation to T-Factor	Informed; Engaged

MAKE @ The Story Garden

[MAKE @ Story Garden](#) is a public studio and maker space for creative collaboration with, and by, local communities within Somers Town and St Pancras in Camden. It is situated within the grounds of The Story Garden, and housed within a series of shipping containers connected by terraces and other outdoor spaces. MAKE @ Story Garden was initiated in 2019 and is due to continue until the development of the site by The British Library – see above. The project is a Regular/Stable use. The first phase of the MAKE @ Story Garden project between 2019 and 2021 was a collaboration between UAL-Central Saint Martins, Somers Town Community Association, Camden Council and Lendlease. The second phase of the project, from April 2021 onwards, is under the management and oversight of Somers Town Community Association/The Living Centre with UAL-Central Saint Martins as a lead partner.

The aim is to bring local people together with students and staff from UAL-Central Saint Martins around a programme of arts and creative activities, skills development and projects that address local and global issues. MAKE embraces the skills and talents of people who live and work in Somers Town and the wider Camden area to address local issues and social challenges and to help widen participation in arts and cultural experiences – from making clothes to tackling the climate emergency.

The British Library owns the land and they have leased it to Global Generation for an extendable term until construction works commence on the site (estimated end of 2022).

There are specific tenure arrangements between MAKE and Global Generation detailed within a Licence to Occupy. The space and its programmes are promoted through the MAKE social media accounts and mailing lists, also word of mouth in the local area, and there are decorated hoardings and notice boards on site. The site is often openly accessible to passers by, although some restrictions are applied linked to Covid and specific site activities. Between October 2019-March 2021 MAKE was funded by Camden Council, UAL and Lendlease. Now in its second phase it's core funding comes from STCA with a patchwork of other funders including Stanhope. Further funding comes from project funding for a program of activities that are delivered through MAKE. STCA currently oversees the MAKE site and activities and leads on the governance. The equipment, owned by UAL-CSM has been leased to STCA. The whole site is overseen by both staff of Global Generation and also MAKE.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Natural; Private or business buildings;
Type of meanwhile use	Workspace & co-working; Education & training and a Makerspace
Stakeholders involved and roles	<p>UAL-CSM – Co-Founder of MAKE at the Story Garden</p> <p>STCA – local community organisation who have taken over the operations of MAKE</p> <p>Staffing – from UAL-CSM, and others</p> <p>Stanhope – developer & funder</p> <p>Lendlease – developer & funder</p> <p>The British Library – landowner</p> <p>Local residents – users</p> <p>Local school children – users</p> <p>UAL-CSM Students & Staff – users</p> <p>Global Generation – charity. Leaseholders for and occupiers of the site</p>
Target groups	Artists & Creatives; Makers & Artisans; Children & Families, Young people; Students
Temporality	<p>The site was opened in 2019 and is due to remain open until the redevelopment of the land by The British Library (dates tbc). The Story Garden is a second iteration of the Skip Garden run by Global Generation in King's Cross for 10 years previously.</p> <p>The meanwhile use is Regular / Stable.</p>
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	<p>The STCA currently operate MAKE and are a third party partner on T-Factor. MAKE is frequently written into funding opportunities and bids such as GLA Future Neighbourhoods projects as a place to host activities. MAKE has been used to support a number of activities for E&I and will continue to support delivery of T-Factor through Scoping & Ideating and Prototyping stages. MAKE can act as a seeding ground for T Factor participatory meanwhile projects.</p>
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Public Studio – Mobile Makerspace

The Public Studio is a T-Factor partnership project, funded independently of T-Factor but supported by members of the T-Factor LC team alongside other local partners. It is explained in more detail within the Engagement Activities section below. Here we detail a specific Public Studio project that has been realised and built as a physical structure – the Mobile Makerspace for Cumberland Market in Regents Park Estate to the west of the Euston development site. The project is a Prompt/ Regular use. The Mobile Makerspace was delivered as one of the projects within the Access to Making cluster of the Public Studio. The focus of the ‘Access to Making’ Cluster was to explore how to widen the use and accessibility of MAKE @ Story Garden for fabrication of civic infrastructure in support of local community projects.

The ‘Mobile Maker Space’ is a public workbench at Cumberland market which aims to bring activities to people where they are, rather than them having to come to MAKE. The process includes using the data gathered through the existing workbench to redesign it to a scalable solution. An activation manual to support its use and assembly manual to enable more workbenches to be built for other sites in future.

The Mobile Maker Space concept was proposed by West Euston Partnership at a workshop in January 2020. It started as an MA Industrial Design group project at UAL-CSM, originally intended to be a way to bring MAKE @ Story Garden activities to other places and people, especially in Regents Park Estate, the other side of Euston Station. The Mobile Maker Space and its activation was further developed through the final project of one of the students that participated in the group project and implemented in collaboration with community and council partners through the Public Studio Mobile Maker Space project. Through Public Studio it has now evolved into a platform, with a focus on how it can be effectively activated. Residents can run art and making activities, share their own ideas and feedback for public realm improvement projects and request external providers to come in and run activities. The platform is also a way to connect residents to local organisations that can turn their ideas into council funded projects and/or connect residents to other projects in the community that they can support. The output is a community workbench installed in Cumberland Market, Regents Park Estate and coordinated by residents enrolled in Fitzrovia Youth In Action’s Community Champions programme.

The aims of the project were to develop and implement a local maker space for Cumberland Market, Regents Park Estate that will support community-led social action and creative collaboration.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Natural; Streets & squares;
Type of meanwhile use	Makerspace
Stakeholders involved and roles	Community Champions - Regent’s Park Estate Lead by Fitzrovia Youth in Action 8-10 Local Resident Collaborators Camden Council - Participation Team Camden Council - Green Space Team Bengali Workers Association

	Euston Citizen Social Scientists Camden Giving Make @ Story Garden Camden Green Gym Camden Think & Do Camden Canvas - Public Studio Project TrashCan LDN - Public Studio Project West Euston Partnership
Target Groups	Artists & Creatives; Makers & Artisans; Children & Families; Young people
Temporality	The Mobile Maker Space concept was proposed by West Euston Partnership at a workshop in January 2020. An initial intervention of table and chair was put in place in 2020 with the final prototype in place in August 2021. The meanwhile use is Prompt / Regular.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	<p>The mobile maker space continues to be in use and overseen by Fitzrovia Youth in Action and RPE Community Champions – this structure and the network can support T-Factor engagement.</p> <p>As part of E&I Activity ‘Transforming Open & Green Spaces in Euston’ the Regent’s Park Community Champions are working in collaboration with a UAL-CSM PhD student, a senior Urban Designer at Sustrans South, Fitzrovia Youth in Action and The Place Bureau. These ideation processes are fostering the development of creative processes and outputs which address local issues and support the existent socio-cultural fabric of the area. Importantly, the bottom-up activity serves as a ‘proof of concept’ for participatory meanwhile and has facilitate acceptance of urban interventions in the neighbourhood amongst the range of participating stakeholders.</p>
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

5.2.2. Planned Meanwhile Spaces and Uses

Euston Community Hub / Maria Fidelis Temporary Open Space

The Maria Fidelis site is located to the West side of Euston Station just North of Drummond Street. The site is in a predominantly residential area, though close to the shops and restaurants of Drummond Street, and it borders the current HS2 construction site. The site itself was formerly the site of the Maria Fidelis school which moved locations to the East side of the station in 2019. The site became vacant in 2019 after the school relocated to its new premises.

Planning consent was granted (subject to completion of Section 106⁹ agreement) in October 2020 for the mixed-use redevelopment of the former school building. The opening date has not been established yet however, the temporary use of the site is estimated to be 10 years from the date of occupation.

The [Euston Community Hub](#) is a proposal for a centralised hub for community consultation being planned by the Euston Partnership, with Lendlease as a partner and in collaboration with many other local stakeholders. The aim is to bring a physical presence to a complex project and could enable co-location of local organisations and their programmes, encouraging cross-fertilisation between groups which enables localised support structures to emerge and regenerate.

The site is currently occupied by a five-storey former school building, which was constructed in the interwar period, with a smaller building to the West and interconnected open space between which are currently car parks but planned as open green spaces, ecology areas and play space. (Stable Use). The proposal for the site is to use it for various temporary meanwhile uses, including a co-working space, a multi-use hall, an outdoor open space for socializing and playing. During HS2 construction two hectares of public open space will be lost – the size of two rugby pitches. However, due to the parliamentary process of the HS2 Act, Camden has secured assurances from HS2 Ltd to provide replacement open space during the construction phase. The Maria Fidelis site offers an opportunity to provide temporary open space close to the worst affected area.

The Maria Fidelis site on North Gower Street is jointly owned by the Council and London and Continental Railways (LCR). The project is currently promoted through the Euston Engagement Hub Commonplace website for engagement activities across Euston - <https://eustonengagementhub.commonplace.is/>. The engagement activities are currently funded through The Euston Partnership however it is yet to be established who will be paying for the capital works.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Other Public Building (School)
Type of meanwhile use	Workspace & co-working; Green & garden
Stakeholders involved and roles	The Euston Partnership (HS2, the Department for Transport, Camden Council, Lendlease, the Greater London Authority, Transport for London and Network Rail) Camden Council, land and building joint owner London & Continental Railway (LCR), land and building joint owner

⁹ A section 106 agreement is an agreement between a developer and a local planning authority about measures that the developer must take to reduce their impact on the community

Target groups	Startuppers and businesses, Children & Families, Young people, and Older people.
Temporality	<p>The site became vacant in 2019 after the school relocated to its new premises. Planning consent was granted (subject to completion of s.106 agreement) in October 2020 for the mixed-use redevelopment of the former school building. The opening date has not been established yet however, the temporary use of the site is estimated to be 10 years from the date of occupation.</p> <p>The project will become a Regular/Stable use.</p>
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	<p>Due to the long time scales and complex ownership and governance on the Maria Fidelis project, there are limited opportunities for integration with E&I activities however, this will be re-considered at Scoping & Ideating. As far as we are aware the groups currently agreeing proposals for the site are The Euston Partnership partners Camden, HS2 and LCR – the local T-Factor team is in conversation with these organisations individually and also through the Meanwhile Use Working Group.</p>
Relation to T-Factor	Informed

Euston Construction Skills Centre

The site is located in the northern part of the former Maria Fidelis Convent School in the London Borough of Camden, to the North side of the boundary of the Maria Fidelis School site described above. The site is currently vacant but had most recently been used as outdoor play space associated with the school and a two-storey ancillary school building, constructed in the 1990s, remains on site. The proposed building will have two-stories and will be a Stable Use for a period of 10 years from the date of occupation which is yet to be defined. The project will become a Regular/Stable use.

The existing King's Cross Construction Skills Centre is due to move from its current location in 2022 and it will become the Euston Construction Skills Centre. The creation of the King's Cross Construction Skills Centre (KXCSC) was a product of the planning agreement, known as Section 106, between the developer of King's Cross, Argent, and the local planning authority, Camden Council. The Section 106 agreement at King's Cross was attached to the planning permission and there are various duties that the developer, Argent, were obliged to agree to and carry out across the phasing of the development. The residential areas surrounding the King's Cross development site had suffered long term deprivation in terms of education, employment, health and other factors. Therefore, it was seen to be crucial that the construction of the project at King's Cross could directly benefit local residents in terms of education and employment. It was identified early on that the construction of the King's Cross development had the potential to provide training and jobs to local people. The plan to move the operations of the KXCSC over to Euston has been worked on for a few years so that it can perform a similar role in the Euston regeneration project.

The Euston site is jointly owned by the Council and London and Continental Railways (LCR) with the Euston Construction Skills Centre being managed and funded through various means. The KXCSC was supported through S106 by a combination of the capital building costs and a revenue stream - £3 million in revenue over 10 years and £2.7million for the build. They also had a contract with an Further Education (FE) partner which enabled them to bring their FE funding to the table, it also enabled them to bid for funding through the GLA's Mayor's Construction Academy programme, which they couldn't do if as a local authority. LB Camden have contributed, and LB Islington have contributed a small amount on an annual basis. They have also had funding from the European Social Fund, the Construction Industry Training Board, and the Department for Work & Pensions. The programme of activities that KXCSC undertaken are often guided by the type of funding they secure. The shift in revenue and capital funding to move across to Euston and become the ECSC is currently unknown.

The KXCSC do a lot of work with outreach in the local area by a range of means, including council publications, their website, social media, and engaging with candidates directly through text messaging. The team also does a lot of work in fast food chicken shops because that is where a lot of local young people go to buy food. They also work with community partners who go out and talk to groups of young people in youth centres, outreach facilities and other spaces. Word of mouth is seen to be one of the most successful means for sharing information but that goes both ways, it can also have negative effects. However, there is not currently a lot of publicly available information on the shift across to Euston except for the planning application accessible [here](#).

<https://constructionmanagemagazine.com/hs2-build-construction-skills-training-centre/>

<https://www.hs2.org.uk/in-your-area/local-community-webpages/hs2-in-camden/plans-for-the-former-maria-fidelis-school-site/>

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Other Public Building (School)
Type of meanwhile use	Education & training; with some space for Workspace & co-working (the ECSC is to share the space with HS2 contractors for the duration of the HS2 construction works)
Stakeholders involved and roles	King's Cross Construction Skills Centre – site user (to become Euston Construction Skills Centre) The Euston Partnership (HS2, the Department for Transport, Camden Council, Lendlease, the Greater London Authority, Transport for London and Network Rail) Camden Council – land and building joint owner, leading the Skills Centre organisation London & Continental Railway (LCR), land and building joint owner
Target groups	Young people, with an ambition to ensure that underrepresented groups are also given opportunities such as Migrants & Refugees, Women, Homeless people, Unemployed people, and People experiencing poverty.
Temporality	The existing King's Cross Construction Skills Centre is due to move from its current location in 2022 and it will become the Euston Construction

	Skills Centre. The proposed building will have two-stories and will be a Stable Use for a period of 10 years from the date of occupation which is yet to be defined. The project will become a Regular/Stable use.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Due to the long-time scales on the Euston Construction Skills Centre project, there are limited opportunities for integration with E&I activities however, this will be re-considered at Scoping & Ideating, and Prototyping. LB Camden is a member of the local T-Factor team and the lead partner on the ECSC therefore we will continue to assess possible integration between ECSC and other aspects of the project.
Relation to T-Factor	Informed

Public Studio – Parklets & Euston Canvas

The Public Studio is explained below in Engagement Activities. This section will go into more detail about two specific projects within the Public Studio, Parklets and Euston Canvas, which are due to be realised and built as meanwhile spaces/uses over the coming months. The projects will eventually become Regular use.

The Public Studio aims to support implementation of existing projects, developed by UAL-CSM students working in collaboration with council and community partners, that have potential to address challenges and opportunities linked to Covid and disruptive development. In this way it builds on the work of the Public Collaboration Lab and integrates with the work of the T-Factor project through exploring 'participatory meanwhile use'.

The Public Studio is funded by UAL with project implementation match-funded by council and community partners. For this reason, Public Studio projects must align with and support partners' existing project plans - bringing additional capacity to achieving partners' objectives.

Six projects have been delivered by the studio over six months between February - August 2021. Projects were grouped within Thematic Clusters – Access to Making, Access to Green Space and Access to Meanwhile. The two projects which are due to be realised as physical meanwhile spaces/uses are the Parklet (as part of the Access to Green Space cluster) and The Euston Canvas (as part of the Access to Meanwhile).

Cluster: Access to Green Space

Project: Parklets

The 'Greening' cluster of Public Studio saw the Parklets project develop:

- Service design and prototyping of a 'Parklet' (a public seating/green area in a former car parking space). Design completed by July 2021, construction and installation is expected to be completed by December 2021.
- Public facing guide to support a citizen-led approach and the devolved management and stewardship for future Parklets
- Explore other supporting public realm interventions and community engagement, such as hosting a series of half term workshops for children and young people in the area

The aims of the project are to address challenges and opportunities linked to Covid-19 and disruptive development in the area and develop projects and collaboration approaches that empower a range of stakeholders. Alongside supporting collaborators and local stakeholders to share, challenge and explore ideas around public space whilst improving local communities' access to greening - through immediate improvements and improved access to infrastructure.

The collaborative design process involved identifying project partners and the wider local community (workshops, on site activity, public sessions etc.), followed by collaborative design process with other ongoing Public Studio projects and structured learning and training programme for UAL- Central Saint Martins Spatial Practices students.

Cluster: Access to Meanwhile

Project: Euston Canvas

Over 2020-21 a class of 32 UAL Service Design Students partnered with residents, communities and artist groups in Camden to co-design concepts for meanwhile use, focussing on the Euston area and vacant spaces on Chalk Farm Road. The team applied a service design methodology to co-design 8 meanwhile propositions: 4 concepts addressed High Street renewal; 4 concepts looked at disruptive redevelopment in the Euston area. By testing the proposals with stakeholders the team identified a willingness towards using meanwhile for regeneration and community engagement. One of the projects addressing disruptive development, Euston Canvas, was selected for delivery through the Public Studio. The Euston Canvas project served as a pilot for the development of an Access to meanwhile service proposition.

The service takes a location-based approach, connecting meanwhile use opportunities - available to be activated - with the local community, local organisations and initiatives. The underpinning principles for this service, and the access it supports to meanwhile spaces, are that it must be inclusive, equitable and transparent. The service includes a toolkit to specify the typologies of the space/use, the objectives for the use, the time frame, any legal and regulatory requirements and a series of collaborative workshop activities to support the co-development process.

The meanwhile prototype (Euston Canvas) will provide access to hoardings around Euston for displaying artworks co-created by local artists and young residents. The co-design approach to artwork creation aims to empower communities and celebrate the diversity within them. It aims at building 'meanwhile ready' communities using an asset-based approach (keeping in mind that the people in the community are its greatest asset). The co-design and co-creation process applied here explores a way for residents to take ownership of meanwhile opportunities and make their identities and priorities visible during the development process.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	The Parklet will be positioned on a piece of land that was previously Streets & Squares . The Euston Canvas will be shown on hoardings on Streets & Squares .
Type of meanwhile use	The Parklet – Green & garden; Leisure & sport. The Euston Canvas doesn't clearly fit into options provided by the T-Factor typology of meanwhile uses although it may be considered as an Artistic residency of sorts, it will provide a backdrop to the streets and construction site.

Stakeholders involved and roles	<p>Parklets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UAL-Central Saint Martins ● Reclaim: Public Space ● Somers Town Space ● Camden Council Green Space Team ● UK Mexican Arts Society ● MAKE @ The Story Garden ● Somers Town Community Association <p>Euston Canvas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fitzrovia Youth in Action ● Local artists ● Euston Partnership ● MACE Dragados ● Camden Euston Team ● Camden High Streets Renewal Team ● Camden High Streets Action Group
Target groups	<p>The Parklet – Children & Families, Young people, Older people. The Euston Canvas – Artists & Creatives, Makers & Artisans, Children & Families, Young people.</p>
Temporality	<p>Six projects were delivered by Public Studio over six months between February - August 2021. The Parklet design was completed by July 2021, with the construction and installation expected to be completed by December 2021. The Euston Canvas is expected to be installed in December 2021.</p> <p>The project is a Prompt/Regular use.</p>
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	<p>The construction and installation of the first Parklet is expected to be completed by December 2021. This will be positioned outside of the new premises for the Somers Town History Club on Phoenix Road.</p> <p>As part of E&I Activity 'Gilbert Bayes Finials and The History of Somers Town: Digital and Material Reconstruction', UAL-CSM academics and students are working with the Somers Town History Club to explore the history of the intricate decorations created by Gilbert Bayes as part of the social housing estate infrastructure in Somers Town.</p> <p>As part of E&I Activity 'Transforming Open & Green Spaces in Euston' the Regent's Park Community Champions are working in collaboration with a UAL-CSM PHd student, a senior Urban Designer at Sustrans South, Fitzrovia Youth in Action and The Place Bureau. These ideation processes are fostering the development of creative processes and outputs which address local issues and support the existent socio-cultural fabric in the community. Importantly, the bottom-up activity can facilitate acceptance of urban interventions in the neighbourhood.</p>

Relation to T-Factor	Engaged
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Additional Opportunities for Meanwhile Uses

The regeneration area offers additional opportunities for meanwhile spaces and uses that are not yet planned.

Camden Partners Public Realm Improvements

The Camden Partners came together after a series of incidents in the housing estates West of Euston station. One of the contractors for HS2, Mace Dragados, did a series of engagement events in the area in April 2021 and so far there have been seventeen proposals for projects to make immediate improvements in the area. Whilst there is commitment from the duty holders involved that at least some of these proposals will be realised there is currently very little information available about which projects and when this will take place. For more information please see 'Camden Partners Public Realm Improvements' section within Engagement Activities and Stakeholders Involved (Non T-Factor) below.

British Library Extension

There is an extension to the British Library planned for the site (<https://blextension.co.uk/>) which is currently housing The Story Garden, MAKE & Your Bike Project. The project is a partnership between the British Library and SMLB Developments (a joint venture between Stanhope Plc and Mitsui Fudosan UK Ltd). The ambition is to open the British Library to the northeast and west with new publicly accessible spaces, squares and routes created to connect the Library to Somers Town and St Pancras. The aim is to create more capacity with The British Library for Camden residents, visitors, schoolchildren, students, researchers, workers and businesses as well as new spaces for exhibition galleries, an events space, and additional facilities for learning and business. Tying this in with the existing Knowledge Quarter network through leasing commercial space to businesses and communities in the Knowledge Quarter (KQ), joining other research-based institutions near the Library such as the Francis Crick Institute and The Alan Turing Institute. The site will also support the future creation of a new underground station for Crossrail 2 by connecting Euston and St Pancras.

Whilst there has been speculation on the ground floor uses being more community focussed there hasn't yet been a commitment by The British Library to lease these spaces to the existing tenants of the Story Garden site including Global Generation, MAKE & Your Bike Project. There may be an opportunity for T-Factor to support these organisations, and others such as the neighbouring STCA and Living Centre, to gain access and support within this major capital redevelopment project in Somers Town.

Network of Tenants & Residents Association Halls

There are many social housing estates around Euston, both to the west of the station at Regents Park Estate, Cumberland Market and Clarence Gardens, and also to the east of the station at Godwin Court, Ampthill Estate, Ossulston Estate and Oakshott Court. Many of these have communal spaces usually known as Tenants & Residents association (TRA) halls. These

are usually tenant and resident run community-focussed spaces that can be made accessible at a low price for a range of events such as meet-ups for local organisations, birthday parties and resident organised activities such as yoga or coffee mornings. Some of these TRA’s are more active than others and the range of spaces and facilities will vary dramatically between the estates. There is an opportunity to map these spaces across Euston out and consider them as potential venues for ongoing T-Factor activities. They offer a way to connect activities in with local communities – this has been the case with E&I activity ‘transforming open & green spaces’ which connects with Fitzrovia youth in action and the community champion network who are also residents from the west of Euston station – each week they meet at the Dick Collins Hall which is the Regent's Park Tenants Association.

5.3. ENGAGEMENT, EXPLORING & INQUIRING, SUPPORT ACTIVITIES

This section describes engagement, exploring and inquiring, and support activities currently ongoing, recently delivered or planned for the near future. More in detail:

- The section ‘Engagement Activities and Stakeholders involved’ describes both existing and planned engagement activities in the area that are not initiated or directly supported by T-Factor.
- The section ‘Exploring & Inquiring Activities’ describes local exploration activities run by the Local Coalition in the context of T-Factor.
- The section ‘Support Activities & Probes’ describes supporting activities that are developed by the Local Coalition in close collaboration with Agency members and relevant T-Labs.

Timeline

The timeline underneath demonstrates the existing and planned engagement activities and meanwhile uses within the regeneration area over the period of the T-Factor project.

	2021	2022	2023	2024
Existing				
Regents Park Community Champions	■	■	■	
Public Studio	■	■	■	■
Good Life Euston / Citizen Social Scientists	■	■	■	■
Planned				
Camden Partners Public Realm Improvements		■	■	■
Soundings Engagement on behalf	■	■	■	■

of Lendlease																				
GLA Future Neighbourhoods																				
National Lottery Bid – Climate Action Fund																				

5.3.1. Existing and Planned Engagement Activities

Regents Park Community Champions

Impact Domains

- *Building Communities*
- *Cultivating innovation*

The Regents Park Community Champions project is led by youth charity Fitzrovia Youth in Action. The “by the community, for the community” approach hopes to tackle the significant health and social inequalities across Camden that have been exacerbated by the pandemic. FYA are currently working with residents across Regents Park Estate, to the West of Euston Station, on projects that benefit fellow residents with a focus on health and wellbeing across the estate. As part of the project there are young people aged 11-24 and also community members who are 24+. The group currently meets every Wednesday in the local area to plan projects together which currently include organising: Scam Awareness Campaigns, Youth Led community events in Cumberland Market, Community Clean Up and Wellbeing Walks, Recycled Objects Projects, Noticeboard & Resident Communication, Mental Health First Aid, a Local sports facility improvement youth led campaign, Cumberland Community Workbench with UAL-CSM – see also ‘Public Studio’ Activity.

<http://www.fya.org.uk/regents-park-community-champions/>

<https://www.happinewss.com/post/community-champions>

<https://app.viima.com/mmspace/open-innovation/>

Challenges and Issues Addressed Through the Activity

Key issues and challenges addressed by these activities relate to the **strengthening of the local communities** through **engagement and participation** in the Euston area. The Community Champions bring together a diverse and talented group of local residents from the Regents Park Estate and surrounding areas, many who have faced, are currently facing or know of young people facing **youth deprivation**. Many residents do not have gardens and therefore the shared public realm and green spaces in the area are crucial, and this has only been exacerbated by Covid. The group is focussed on ways they can propose and contribute to projects that **improve their local environment** in and around Regents Park Estate, Cumberland Market and Clarence Gardens in order to **improve health & wellbeing** for all residents. The resident project proposals are currently being connected with local T-Factor E&I activities, in particular with UAL-CSM practitioners and students, enabling a connection with **cultural expression** as a shared working practice. Ideally this will lead to opportunities for local

youth and a **re-thinking of the role of public realm**, and provide **improvements to green spaces and access to green space in the future**.

<p>Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fitzrovia Youth in Action, youth led local charity • Residents of all ages 11+ across Regents Park Estate • Camden Council, Participation Team • HS2 Community Liaison Officer for Camden Council 	<p>Relation to T-Factor</p> <p>Engaged</p>
<p>Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities</p> <p>The T-Factor team at UAL-CSM are working with the Participation Team at Camden Council to introduce our E&I work on the Communities of Practice to this group of Community Champions in October 2021. They have been presented with projects that have been proposed by both the UAL-CSM Community of Practice (CoP) and Knowledge Quarter CoP – the Community Champions were invited to either Participate (join an existing activity/project), Collaborate (Contribute to shape an existing activity/project), or Initiate (propose a new activity/project). The Community Champions have several projects that they would like to develop in collaboration with the T-Factor LC CoP. Exploration of these projects is described below within the section ‘T-Factor Local Coalition Exploring & Inquiring Activities’.</p>	

Public Studio

Impact Domains

- *Building Communities*
- *Cultivating innovation*
- *Attaining sustainability*

The Public Studio aims to support implementation of existing projects, developed by UAL-CSM students working in collaboration with council and community partners, that have potential to address challenges and opportunities linked to Covid and disruptive development. In this way it builds on the work of the Public Collaboration Lab and integrates with the work of the T-Factor project through exploring ‘participatory meanwhile use’.

The Public Studio is funded by UAL with project implementation match-funded by council and community partners. For this reason, Public Studio projects must align with and support partners' existing project plans - bringing additional capacity to achieving partners' objectives.

Six projects have been delivered by the studio over six months between February - August 2021. Projects were grouped within Thematic Clusters – Access to Making, Access to Green Space and Access to Meanwhile (For more please see Part 4: Meanwhile Use). Each project has been delivered by a separate multi-partner project team, supported by Public Studio. Although the projects sit within different organisation clusters, the overlaps and connections between individual projects are celebrated through programmatic opportunities for collaboration and cross-pollination between clusters.

Access to Green Space

CLUSTER FOCUS: PUBLIC SPACE AND GREENING: The ‘Greening’ cluster of Public Studio saw the following two projects developed and delivered in harmony.

1. Service design and prototyping of a 'Parklet' (a public seating/green area in a former car parking space)
2. Public temporary history space for Somers Town Space

Access to Making

CLUSTER FOCUS: The focus of the 'Access to Making' Cluster is to explore how to widen the use and accessibility of MAKE @ Story Garden through the implementation of three projects. All three projects were developed by or in collaboration with members of the local community.

- 'TrashCanLDN' aims to teach young people to design and make products at MAKE, which they can then sell at a local market.
- 'Mobile Maker Space' is a public workbench at Cumberland market which aims to bring activities to people where they are, rather than them having to come to MAKE. The process includes using the data gathered through the existing workbench in order to redesign it to a scalable solution
- 'Community Bookshelf' was initiated by a Godwin Court resident in Somers Town. The team are re-designing the bookshelf to improve it's appearance, durability and usability. The fabrication took place as a public making course, open to all local residents. The designs are scalable which would allow another course to make more bookshelves for alternative locations.

Access to Meanwhile CLUSTER FOCUS: Over 2020-21 a class of 32 Service Design Students partnered with residents, communities and artist groups in Camden to co-design concepts for meanwhile use, focussing on the Euston area and vacant spaces on Chalk Farm Road. The team applied a service design methodology to co-design 8 meanwhile propositions: 4 concepts addressed High Street Renewal (a Covid Recovery scheme being led by Camden Council); 4 concepts looked at disruptive redevelopment in the Euston area. By testing the proposals with stakeholders the team identified a willingness towards using meanwhile for regeneration and community engagement. One of the projects addressing disruptive development, Euston Canvas, was greenlit and delivered through the Public Studio. The Euston Canvas project was a co-designed construction hoarding developed for the construction site at Euston and served as a pilot for the development of an Access to Meanwhile service proposition.

Challenges and Issues Addressed Through the Activity

Key issues and challenges addressed by these activities relate to the **strengthening of engagement and participation** in the Euston area. As a response to 'engagement fatigue' felt by many residents in the area, the Public Studio projects support the need to move away from 'consultation' and towards **types of engagement that are reciprocal and in turn lead to building trust** between local residents and VCS organisations, and UAL-CSM. Through the 'Access to Green Space' cluster and the prototyping of a 'Parklet' (a public seating/green area in a former car parking space), the project promotes **provision of and access to green space, re-thinking the role of the public realm** and **improving the environment**. With limited access to parks and green spaces in the area, the role of public realm has been made all the more clear in terms of the **Covid recovery** in the area. All project clusters: Access to Green Space, Access to Making and Access to Meanwhile support residents and local VCS organisations with **cultural expression**.

<p>Stakeholders</p> <p>The studio brings together UAL-CSM students and graduates to work with people from the local area supported by college, council and VCS staff. Students and graduates are paid via UAL internal programme funding. An earlier ambition to include local young people in the core team, funded by the UK Government’s Kickstart programme, did not happen due to the time it took for the Kickstart recruitment process (NB. within the Public Studio the Kickstart UK living wage was to be ‘topped up’ to London living wage).</p> <p>Each project was delivered by a project team including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UAL-CSM Student/Graduate Lead: responsible for day to day delivery of project • UAL-CSM Partner Lead: responsible for supporting project delivery from the partner perspective. Giving feedback on proposals, making introductions to relevant people and organisations. Connecting and coordinating with partner programmes through which projects will be implemented. • UAL-CSM Academic supervisor: responsible for supporting the graduate and project team in the delivery of the project. • VCS supervisor: responsible for hosting the local young person and supporting them and the project team in the delivery of the project. 	<p>Relation to T-Factor</p> <p>Engaged</p>
<p>Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities</p> <p>There are various ways in which the Public Studio activities will form a basis for on-going engagement for E&I activities. Many of the E&I activities will build on the work already done within the Public Studio – both through groups and individuals involved, the networks created and the physical infrastructure created by the project (bookcase, workbench, parklets) which can be used to support further engagement activities.</p>	

Good Life Euston & Citizen Social Scientists

Impact Domains

- *Improving Health & Wellbeing*
- *Building Communities*

The Good Life Index is a project initiated by The Institute for Global Prosperity (University College London) partnering with Camden Council and local charity Camden Giving as facilitators who are both well connected into the local networks, and Lendlease (developer at Euston) as funding partner. They are working together to understand the experiences of local communities most affected by the major regeneration project in the Euston area, and to develop a new prosperity and wellbeing index for Euston which is co-produced with local people and defined by their lived experiences. This involves teaching, training and designing curriculum, that in turn trains community members to become social citizen scientists. The initial process started in June 2020 and concluded in March 2021. Eventually a prosperity and wellbeing index for Euston will be developed using findings which will then measure the impacts of regeneration on local communities over the long-term to support decision making and investment based on resident-led priorities that benefit local communities.

Each stage of the process is co-led by the participants: this process is called Citizen Social Science, which builds on methods and approaches from ‘community based participatory research’. Citizen Science is defined as members of the public having a greater role within research and recognising the invaluable role they play in providing insights a researcher may not typically have. This is seen as a way to decolonize the research process, and instead of extractive models of research, the project is offering a skill in return and is co-produced with local participants at every step. In terms of choosing participants, the goal was to capture a majority of representations from the local area, whether it be gender, age, ethnicity, profession. The only common denominator between community members is that they have been living in the area for about eight years and that they are integrated in the community.

The latest ‘Good Life Euston Model’ findings were shared in October 2021. The main domains that were identified included: 1. Systemic Equity, 2. Secure Livelihoods, 3. Environmental Revitalisation, 4. Formal and Informal Learning, 5. Positive Connections, 6. Community Richness, Cultures & Identities 7. Our Spaces & Services 8. Positive State of Being. Each Domain has a description and four sub-domain categories. There will be a final round of validation before the Good Life Euston Model and metrics are finalised and baseline data collected in a household survey.

<https://www.ucl.ac.uk/bartlett/igp/news/2020/nov/euston-young-voices-citizen-led-research-shaping-regeneration>

<https://www.lendlease.com/euston/stay-up-to-date/wellbeing-index/>

Challenges and Issues Addressed Through the Activity

This activity is related to the issues of **engagement & participation** in Euston and the ‘consultation fatigue’ felt by many residents. It is responding to this by looking at ways that **engagement can be made more reciprocal and rewarding for residents** – each resident has been given the London Living Wage as remuneration for their involvement. This activity also addresses the need to **connect with and provide opportunities for local youth**. There is also the potential to **join up engagement activities and outcomes** with T-Factor E&I, subsequent S&I and prototyping activities. Many of the Good Life Euston Model research findings which have been categorised into domains and sub-domains by the Citizen Social Scientists have crossovers and similarities to the Issues, Challenges & Opportunities identified within the T-Factor Pilot so far.

Stakeholders	Relation to T-Factor
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Institute for Global Prosperity, University College London – researchers & organisation ● Lendlease, master development partner for Over Station Development at Euston – funders ● Camden Council, specifically the Participation Team – organisers ● Camden Giving – a local charity assisting with connecting with resident networks and payment system for residents 	<p>Engaged</p>

Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities

The results of the Good Life Euston and Citizen Social Scientists project were presented at a workshop/seminar at UCL in September 2021. Within the workshop the T-Factor project was also presented in three ways: an introduction to the project, through an invitation to get involved, and also through two presentations around meanwhile use projects run through Public Studio (the Community Bookshelf and the Mobile Makerspace) as a demonstration of the types of meanwhile projects emerging that the CSS cohort can become involved with in different ways. The Community Bookshelf project was already a collaboration between a UAL-CSM graduate and one of the Citizen Social Scientists. The CSS's were presented with projects that have been proposed by both the UAL-CSM CoP and Knowledge Quarter CoP – the CSS cohort will then get the chance to either Participate (join an existing activity/project), Collaborate (Contribute to shape an existing activity/project), or Initiate (propose a new activity/project). There is an opportunity where a CSS member has been piloting a cafe at Amptill Square Estate – this is currently being scoped out to connect with UAL-CSM MArch Spatial Practices students as an E&I activity and project to enable more to be done with the cafe including offering training to support local women, inclusion of a play area and a small garden and awning on the site.

Camden Partners – Public Realm Improvements

Impact Domains

- *Making Places*
- *Attaining sustainability*

The Camden Partners came together after a series of incidents in the housing estates West of Euston station. One of the contractors for HS2, Mace Dragados, did a series of engagement events in the area in April 2021 and so far there have been 17 proposals for projects to make immediate improvements in the area. These include:

- Making Euston a safe & secure place to live, work & visit
 - Hot Spot Management for addressing key local issues in the area and speeding up funding routes
 - Combating begging around the station
 - Safe Corridors and Green Routes whilst there are so many construction disruptions
- Making Euston an attractive and navigable place to live, work and visit
 - Improving community cohesion and engagement
 - Improving skills, education & employment
 - Supporting local shopping through 'Love Euston' loyalty scheme
 - George Mews Play area and café - with Euston BID team develop play area and café to discourage anti-social behaviour on Regents Park Estate
- Making Euston a greener and more sustainable area
 - The creation of moveable gardens to create gardens that can be moved to accommodate changes to site boundaries but maintain green spaces
 - Design Manual for green spaces - scoped and pre-agreed for use of community spaces and site boundary so can be implemented without seeking consent on a case-by-case basis

- o Community Nursery - to use green spaces and community gardens to grow trees/plants that will be used for Station Urban Realm

Although these activities have a lot of alignment with the Residents Advisory Group recommendations in the area, the project proposals did not emerge through an in depth engagement process. Camden Council and the RAG believe that it's essential to run these proposals by the RAG and other community groups before implementing so that they can express their views on their suitability. We are waiting for an update on which of these project proposals are going ahead and when. Camden Council believe that whilst the projects outlined above could help to deliver on lots of the RAG recommendations, the way that they are delivered and discussed with the community will be crucial to their success. One of the key things that was highlighted by the RAG (and other engagement) is that local communities want to be involved in what happens in their local area. Engagement was one of the top three recommendation areas for the RAG therefore they believe that ongoing engagement will be key. One of the big challenges for everyone at Euston, given the complexity of the situation, is how to communicate the ongoing work and provide the community with feedback when they raise issue(s).

Challenges and Issues Addressed Through the Activity

Key issues and challenges addressed by these activities relate to the need to **improve green spaces in the area** in order to make Euston a greener and more sustainable area. Through **improvement to the local environment** in and around Regents Park Estate, Cumberland Market and Clarence Gardens there is the capacity to **improve health & wellbeing** for all residents. The activities also seeks to address **crime, anti-social behaviour & safety** through crime hot spot management. There are many similarities between issues and challenges identified through Camden Partners seventeen project proposals and those identified through T-Factor research so far and there is the possibility to **align and leverage aims and resourcing** across regeneration stakeholders and local communities in the area.

<i>Highlights of the activity</i>	
<p>Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Camden Partners ● HS2 Community Liaison, Camden Council 	<p>Relation to T-Factor Mapped/informed</p>
<p>Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities</p> <p>There are multiple opportunities to integrate these activities and proposals listed above with E&I activities however, there is currently limited knowledge within the Euston LC about the status of these projects – which are going ahead and when. We believe there are possible funding streams in place for some of these projects to be realised and there are opportunities for us to bring expertise and capacity from our CoP projects, but also through engagement opportunities with the local groups we are working with.</p>	

Soundings Engagement for Lendlease on the Over Station Development

Impact Domains

- *Building Communities*

Lendlease was appointed 'Master Development Partner' (MDP) of the Euston OSD masterplan by the Secretary of State for Transport and Network Rail in 2018. As part of this role, Lendlease is responsible for delivering a programme of public consultation on the masterplan proposals before it can submit a planning application to the London Borough of Camden.

Lendlease has appointed Soundings, a specialist community and stakeholder consultation consultant, to carry out the public consultation. Soundings will carry out a comprehensive programme of consultation and engagement to ensure a constructive and meaningful dialogue is created with the community and that the outcomes of this feed directly into the master planning and design development process.

Soundings have been working as citizen participation consultants for developers Lendlease on the Euston project since July 2020. Their role was initially around the mapping of the existing context and stakeholders in order to understand what participation work had been done in the area already, and any work that was planned. Soundings have most recently been working on bringing together two Liaison Groups made up of local residents and specific local groups – this includes the continuation of the Residents Advisory Group (originally initiated by Camden Council as part of the Euston Area Plan updates consultation – see below) which will continue to be overseen by Camden, and a newly formed Community Interest Group overseen by Soundings and Lendlease. Both Covid and budget issues with the larger project have delayed their work however, they have been working on the ground to set up the groups since August 2021.

Lendlease will work in parallel with the CIG and the Resident Advisory Group (RAG) managed by the London Borough of Camden (LBC). Similar content will be shared with both groups across the same timeframes and there will be opportunities for both groups to come together and exchange. The RAG is composed of local residents selected by a sortition process to ensure representation across different geographies and demographics within the borough. Involving a similar number of participants to the CIG (30), the RAG will bring an overlapping but distinct perspective to the process focusing on the lived experience of individual residents. The CIG involves representatives from a variety of organisations in the Euston area representing a broad range of groups.

Together, these two groups (the RAG and CIG) will act as a sounding board, discussing matters relating to local dynamics, needs, and aspirations to inform the development of the masterplan. Each stage of consultation will be bookended by working sessions with both groups. This means that they will be involved in shaping the approach to consultation from the outset and then helping ensure that feedback from the wider community is reflected in the developing masterplan.

<https://eustonengagementhub.commonplace.is/proposals/residents-advisory-group>

Challenges and Issues Addressed Through the Activity

Key issues and challenges addressed by these activities relate to the **strengthening of engagement and participation** in the Euston area, ensuring that a wide variety of residents are represented and continue to be heard when assessing the appropriateness of the masterplan. The continued role of the Resident Advisory Group as part of the activity also contributes to **joining up engagement activities & outcomes** in the area. There is a key opportunity here to demonstrate a meanwhile strategy for Euston and understand how this

interacts with the master planning process organised by Lendlease leading to potential for an **interrelation between the meanwhile strategy and the masterplan.**

<i>Highlights of the activity</i>	
<p>Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lendlease, Master Development Partners in charge of the masterplan of the Over Station Development of Euston station • Soundings, citizen participation consultants • Residents Advisory Group • Community Interest Group 	<p>Relation to T-Factor</p> <p>Mapped/informed</p>
<p>Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities</p> <p>As far as we are aware the activity of 'Soundings Engagement for Lendlease on the Over Station Development' is currently on hold. The local T-Factor team is in contact with Lendlease through various forums and meetings in the area and will request and update in order to understand the opportunities for relation with E&I activities, and subsequent stages more closely.</p>	

Camden Six Sites / Open Space Improvements

Impact Domains

- *Improving Health & Wellbeing*
- *Building Communities*
- *Making Places*
- *Attaining sustainability*

HS2 are providing Camden Council with funding to improve six green spaces in the Euston area, in order to help reduce the local impacts of HS2 construction works and loss of public open space. The green spaces are: Munster Square, Clarence Gardens, Cumberland Market, Hope Gardens, Ampthill Square Estate and Churchway Estate.

Camden Council have been working with consultants Groundworks to carry out public engagement and put together proposals for designs. Groundworks began their engagement work with the public in late 2017, sketch designs were then shared in 2020 and residents given the chance to feedback in January 2021, with final designs shared in April 2021 [here](#). The construction works were due to start in September 2021 but these have been delayed, it is unknown when these works will go ahead.

<https://eustonengagementhub.commonplace.is/proposals/residents-advisory-group>

Challenges and Issues addressed through the activity

Key issues and challenges addressed by these activities relate to providing **improvements to green spaces and access to green space** in and around Euston. This activity has the capacity to contribute towards the **re-thinking of the role of public realm** in the short to medium term and also the long term. All six projects seek to **improve their local environment** in and around the designated sites which in turn should allow residents and local organisations to spend

better quality time outdoors in order to **improve health & wellbeing**. Simultaneously **safety should improve**, and **crime and anti-social behaviour reduce**.

<i>Highlights of the activity</i>	
<p>Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Camden Council – space owners and organisers ● Groundworks – public engagement and design consultants ● Residents of the areas surrounding the Six Sites 	<p>Relation to T-Factor</p> <p>Mapped/informed</p>
<p>Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities</p> <p>So far there are no direct links between the Camden Six Sites / Open Space Improvements Activity & T-Factor. There is however a crossover of working areas with T-Factor Local Coalition E&I Activity with the Community Champions ‘Transforming Open & Green Spaces’ at Cumberland Market and Clarence Gardens, and potential to connect in further stages of the project.</p>	

Planned Engagement Activities and Stakeholders Involved

Somers Town – GLA Future Neighbourhoods 2030

Impact Domains

- *Building Communities*
- *Making Places*
- *Attaining sustainability*
- *Cultivating innovation*

To help support a green recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic, the Greater London Authority (London’s Mayor) launched a new funding programme called Future Neighbourhoods 2030. It aims to tackle some of London’s defining environmental challenges, including the climate emergency and toxic air quality, whilst creating jobs, developing skills and supporting a just transition to a low carbon circular economy. Future Neighbourhoods will be located in London’s most disadvantaged and climate-vulnerable areas, or areas where residents have been most severely affected by the pandemic. £3million is being made available for the first phase of the programme, initially supporting three projects.¹⁰

A consortium of partners in Somers Town, including Camden Council, Somers Town Community Association, Somers Town Neighbourhood Forum with help from other support partners such as University of the Arts London-Central Saint Martins, were successful in their initial application to the GLA Future Neighbourhoods 2030 which shortlisted six projects. The final applications are due on 20 September 2021, and selected Future Neighbourhoods will be announced in October 2021 – three out of six projects will be allocated funding.

¹⁰ <https://www.london.gov.uk/what-we-do/funding/future-neighbourhoods-2030>

Within the Somers Town application there are ten projects. UAL-Central Saint Martins are involved, with T-Factor partner and community leaders Somers Town Community Association, in delivery teams on Project 2 - Greening Estates and Project 8 - Circular Economy on Chalton Street.

Green Estates

The Green Estates project addresses inequality in access to green space in Somers Town by supporting communities to improve and enhance open spaces on and around housing estates. The project will deliver a range of initiatives on council housing estates, building on existing grass-roots activity, responding to community needs, and informed by green infrastructure studies. It combines physical infrastructure investment with social capital investment to foster a sustainable approach to greening.

Somers Town has an under-provision of public open space (0.6ha against the Camden standard of 0.9ha per 1000 pop). Meanwhile, 79% of households do not have private or shared gardens, compared with 21% London average (and 12% UK average) (ONS, 2020). However, Somers Town contains high levels of largely underutilised housing estate land, with the potential to offer benefits to residents and the wider community.

The project will support local demand and interest in greening and gardening activities that has been highlighted by the Covid pandemic. It comprises three main strands: physical greening interventions, community support and training, and the piloting of an estate-based Mobile Maker Space. The project will deliver a series of estate-based physical improvements projects, including new food growing space to meet local demand, improved spaces for play and social interaction, and other green infrastructure interventions such as green walls or tree planting. These projects are driven by local demand but also reflect and deliver aspects of an estate-based green infrastructure study undertaken in 2018 which identified a range of interventions suitable across a number of sites to respond to environmental challenges.

Circular Economy Chalton Street market

A new Circular Chalton Street Market community will create new enterprise, training and employment experiences for residents. Existing local organisations and groups will collaborate to deliver an innovative range of circular ethical and charitable services for Somers Town centred on Chalton Street market but linking to local estates. The market arena will test and deliver circular growth and themes for achieving zero waste.

There are six layered strands for this proposal.

1. Stalls codesign – Central Saint Martins (CSM), Somers Town Community Association (STCA) and Little Village will collaborate to run a Makerspace with tools and equipment to design and build a range of flexible new stalls for use at Chalton Street market and on housing estates. A transferable pop-up maker space led by UAL-CSM and STCA on estates will include makers upcycling, repairs support and training experiences for residents. The collaboration will train residents, build skills and support circular economy participation groups to convert unwanted items ('waste') into new items which can then be sold at bookable stalls at Chalton Street market - transforming potential waste outputs from estates into products for local people.

2. Circular Economy Chalton Market- A six-to-nine-month circular economy street market project using the new stalls to include information sharing stalls, stalls for estate

reuse/upcycled produce, charity stalls, reuse and repair-it stalls, new eco- trader stalls. The strand would also include a series of themed event days promoting circular economy principles with the community. A small grant programme will support groups to run circular economy stalls.

3. Identifying zero waste streams - A survey will be delivered to analyse zero waste streams within the area with Camden, Veolia and Keep Britain Tidy Campaign. A Circular Economy Project Manager for 12 months will coordinate and deliver the bid components. Camden will identify local sheds, garages and voids for the storage of equipment for improved market facilitation.

4. Refill Station Camden Stalls - We will design and operate a new dry grains, spices and teas Camden Refill stall at Chalton Street allowing residents to buy by weight and bring along reusable jars and containers or bags for transferring produce home. The stall will provide local employment to 8 people 16-24 under the Kick Starter scheme. A series of seasonal Eco-festive Refill pop-up events will invite new eco- traders to run a market group on new days.

5. Tipp Tapp app - Tipp Tapp will pilot a social app linking residents, buyers and organisations to local green transport to redistribute reuse and upcycle unwanted home and business products. A multilingual marketing campaign will be developed to promote the app.

6. Circular Economy localised outreach and engagement model – Lifeafterhummus and Think & Do will build on their existing circular models of working with schools, residents and volunteers, estates to build on existing understanding and acceptance of sharing economy principles and reuse. An existing visitor centre hub in Phoenix Road in Somers Town will provide outreach to deliver other circular/ health and waste prevention activities, youth projects including Plot 10 and the Somers Town Youth Club, hands-on food waste cooking club socials, delivered by local trained residents.

<https://www.london.gov.uk/what-we-do/funding/future-neighbourhoods-2030>

Challenges and Issues Addressed Through the Activity

Key issues and challenges addressed by this grouping of activities relates to many of the challenges and issues identified. Firstly, there is a strong focus on providing **improvements to green spaces and access to green space** in and around Euston through supporting local demand and interest in greening and gardening activities that has been highlighted by the Covid pandemic, also connected with **Covid recovery**. This activity has the capacity to contribute towards the **re-thinking of the role of public realm** in Somers Town in the short to medium and also the long term. All projects are multi-stakeholder initiatives between Camden Council and local VCS organisation which seek to **improve engagement and participation** in the area through projects that allow for the promotion of **adaptability & capacity building of existing SMEs** through this process. With projects linked with UAL-CSM, there is also the potential for **cultural expression** and exploring projects through creative means.

Stakeholders

Somers Town Community Association, Somers Town Neighbourhood Forum, Camden Council, Greater London Authority, Central Saint Martins, Little Village, MAKE @ Story Garden, Lifeafterhummus, Think & Do, Plot 10, Somers Town Youth Club

Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities

Whilst there are multiple opportunities to integrate these activities and proposals listed above with E&I activities, the clearest way this has been carried out so far is with the T-Probe 'Thinking the Meanwhile Circularly & Collaboratively' co-organised by UAL-CS and the Open University of Catalonia. As part of this probe an online event was held in November 2021 'A Circular Economy for Somers Town' which focussed on showcasing and connecting Somers Town GLA Future Neighbourhood Partners and local projects with those in Barcelona through UoC, in particular the proposal for Chalton Street Circular Market.

Somers Town Community Climate Action Market – Climate Action Fund, The National Lottery Community Fund

Impact Domains

- *Building Communities*
- *Attaining sustainability*
- *Cultivating innovation*

Somers Town Community Association, as partnership lead, is applying for a development grant to create a community Climate Action Market based around the existing Chalton Street Market in Somers Town, Camden, with the following objectives:

- Providing climate action right at the heart of the community by making the Chalton Street Market the focal point for knowledge, advice, support, resources and practical projects to inspire and enable a lasting change around everyday consumption habits and reduced waste.
- Using the market to champion climate change by promoting re-use, challenging scepticism and changing attitudes. Examples include resistance to using second-hand items, a disconnect between local actions and global climate impact, lack of awareness/promotion of local initiatives and support.
- Unlocking the academic, student and professional resources in the area to empower, support and sustain community-led activities beyond the Climate Action Market.
- Providing opportunities for local traders and residents with skills and experience (e.g technicians, electricians, furniture repairers) to assist in achieving a community-led circular economy and create local jobs based around existing, enhanced and new projects.

The proposal is based on a powerful place-based alliance between the local community, voluntary and statutory sectors and a robust, nationally recognised academic and business sector. Partners include the Knowledge Quarter, UAL-Central Saint Martins, University of London, UCL, Little Village, the Somers Town Neighbourhood Forum and the Camden Climate Change Alliance.

The project proposes these interwoven activities:

1. Creating both pop-up and embedded climate action advice, support and practical projects on Chalton Street Market. Ideas include:

- A mending exchange, mobile re-use and repair hub; turning food waste into jewellery & bioplastic materials; making products from recycled materials; a refill station.

- A community auction at which material resources (e.g. IT, officeware, beds from student accommodation) of larger organisations in the area are recycled for the benefit of local residents and small businesses; and promotion of a community-facing warp-it recycling platform so that members of the community can request items they want/need. Items will be repaired, refurbished and delivered.
- A community, co-created recycling and waste reduction competition based on the University of London's successful Reduce the Juice campaign.
- Facilitating a community climate action assembly, and the creation of a community manifesto on climate action.

The local market is at the heart of the community and a familiar/trusted space with a deep community outreach. Programming of the climate action markets will be developed with, and by the local community, contributing to Chalton Street Market's future sustainability.

2. Building the capacity of local communities to sustain climate action activities. Partners will lead the creation of a pilot circular economy framework for re-cycling, re-use and waste reduction. It will link projects in the market with work by students and staff from UAL-CSM, UCL and UoL. This framework will have the potential for scaling up and replication with guidance, milestones and capacity building toolkits, e.g.

- a climate change playbook for communities to create their own climate action projects;
- work with Islington Council and communities around Caledonian Road, where there is the potential to immediately scale up and replicate, drawing on our existing strong connections with Islington.

3. Evaluation and dissemination: A combination of methodologies which measure: carbon emissions saved by extending the life cycle of materials; social value of reuse and recycling of materials within the community; behavioural change, and the potential for systemic change. Key roles include:

- Academic sector partners using carbon reporting, warp-it and other tools;
- STCA and partners around footfall, project engagement monitoring, case studies;
- Promoting the project widely and engaging additional businesses to connect with community initiatives.

These activities will complement and integrate with the Chalton Street Circular Market project funded as part of the GLA Future Neighbourhoods 2030 programme, as described above. The activities funded by the Climate Action Fund will provide further programme content for delivery through the market as described in the objectives above. The local market is at the heart of the community and a familiar/trusted space with a deep community outreach. Programming of the climate action markets will be developed with, and by the local community, contributing to Chalton Street Market's future sustainability.

<https://www.tnlcommunityfund.org.uk/funding/programmes/climate-action-fund-round-2>

Challenges and Issues Addressed Through the Activity

Key issues and challenges addressed by this grouping of activities relate to **improving engagement and participation** in the area through projects that are focussed around climate awareness and how this can be supported and made more accessible at a local level which in turn promotes **reciprocal engagement and building trust**. Through partnerships which

include larger institutions in the area such as Knowledge Quarter partners, University of London, University College London and Central Saint Martins there is also the opportunity to **align and leverage aims and resourcing** with local residents and VCS organisations in the area whilst also supporting the **adaptability & capacity building of existing SMEs** through this process. The Chalton Street market proposal also contributes towards the **re-thinking of the role of public realm** in Somers Town, alongside the GLA Future Neighbourhoods application, as described above. With projects linked with UAL-CSM, there is also the potential for **cultural expression** and exploring projects through creative means.

<p>Stakeholders Project Partners:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Somers Town Community Association ● Central Saint Martins (Programme Director, Jewellery, Textiles and Materials and acting Deputy Director of the Textile Future Research Centre) ● Knowledge Quarter ● University of London ● University College London ● Little Village ● Somers Town Neighbourhood Forum ● Camden Climate Change Alliance ● The National Lottery – funder
<p>Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities Whilst there have not been any opportunities to integrate these activities with E&I activities so far there is a clear link between the Somers Town Community Climate Action Market and the Somers Town GLA Future Neighbourhoods 2030 proposals which are both focussed around the future of Chalton Street Market. The integration of T-Factor with these projects through UAL-CSM and Camden Council is ongoing and will be further explored during Scoping & Ideating.</p>

5.3.2. T-Factor Exploring and Inquiring Activities

Gilbert Bayes Finials & The History of Somers Town: Digital and Material Reconstruction

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Building Communities ● Making Places ● Cultivating innovation
Activity Objectives	To create a framework of egalitarian archiving and activation, supporting the community to direct the reconstruction process, mode of refabricating and the decisions for making the project publicly visible. This project has the potential to have both a digital and physical staging. For the digital staging adequate equipment, including storing drives are necessary.
Activity Description	The project proposes to work with a Space for Us and the Somers Town History Club using 3D modelling and 3D reconstruction to remake the

	<p>lost Gilbert Bayes finial sculptures that were mounted on the communal washing line poles located within the social housing estates in Somers town during the social housing reform in the 1920's and 1930's. The collaboration would develop a working methodology supporting their community history work by introducing open source 3D scanning of the sites where the washing lines were originally located. The second stage would involve the 3D digital fabrication of the sculptures by working from existing photographs, oral history and community knowledge</p>
When/Where	October 2021 to March 2022. Somers Town – A Space for Us
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Knowledge bearer: UAL-CSM BA Fine Art ● Knowledge bearer: Somers Town History Club – A Space for Us ● Provider: UAL-CSM BA Fine Art ● Provider: Somers Town History Club – A Space for Us
Participants & Beneficiaries	<p>As the project develops in various stages, it includes diverse participants and groups of beneficiaries in each stage. Within the current first stage of development, the project's participants include local adults with long term engagement with the Somers Town history club and its public, comprised mainly of long standing local residents of diverse ages. It also includes young locals interested in both the specific Bayes subject and the digital skills development component.</p> <p>In subsequent stages of development (2022) the project engages children from local schools through afterschool and/or half-term activities in collaboration with local primary and/or secondary schools, particularly history and computer science teachers. In the first stage the project involves groups of up to 15 people at any one workshop. In the second stage and depending on school groups, this number might (or not) increase.</p> <p>The beneficiaries of this project comprise groups at many levels, from the local level - the residents of Somers Town who would participate in the capturing, archiving and reconstructing of lost and/or damaged legacy, to the general public who will be able to learn and enjoy the often overlooked stories and histories which have shaped the locality.</p> <p>The project also has the potential to serve as a model for open source archival projects aimed at preserving significant heritage, especially in the context of rapid urban renewal.</p>
Insights	<p>Process: The story so far:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Preparatory meetings have been held with the knowledge bearers during the month of October. These have consisted of lengthy discussions about how to best support the interests and needs of the community, and how to translate these into impactful and long lasting actions while building from their existing knowledge and activism preserving the localities

history and valued/valuable Bayes sites. These meetings/discussions have been held on 06, 07, 21 and 29 OCT 2021.

2. Bayes Sites recognition walk with Elizabeth Wright and the Somers Town History Club on 12 NOV 2021. This in order to better envision the design and dynamics of the first workshop on digital reconstruction.
3. First Bayes Scanathon Workshop on 20 NOV 2021. It will be based at the newly opened space for the History Museum A Space for Us on Phoenix Road and local Bayes sites. The workshop was a complete success in offering the community skills, techniques and perspectives on how to carry their work on historic preservation and communication of the locality's heritage using new digital tools for the construction and dissemination of archives, for example.

*Participants capturing the airing court at St Mary's Flats, Drummond Street.
Photo Credit: Adriana Cobo-Corey*

In the words of Elizabeth Wright, project lead: "The workshop was successful in introducing to the group through their own active capture some of the possibilities of digital 3D modelling. They particularly liked the AR and we had a rich discussion about how they might incorporate the digital workflow into the museum. Most of all we all had a lot of fun, great shared conversations and wonderful to meet residents who played as children in the air courts and to hear from another resident about his role as social housing officer and how other participant gathers knowledge of Bayes through oral history interviews".

Key insights

So far, the project has revealed the potential of techniques such as photogrammetry, to expand understanding about how to archive historical material as part of the history museum, beyond the specific scanning of lost/damaged finials for the exclusive purpose of reconstruction. In line with this, 3D scanning activities, as proposed by the project, also have the capacity to engage diverse members of the locality as agents in the process of creating digital databases comprising sites, objects and local experiences, to be part of the forthcoming History Museum-A Space for Us archives.

In the eyes of the History Museum – A Space for Us, the project represents an opportunity to achieve a long standing goal of reconstructing key public realm sites via recovering and consolidating lost legacy. It also offers the possibility to initiate a longer lasting collaboration aimed at exploring 3D archival methodologies.

From the point of view of the BA fine Art practitioners, the project represents an opportunity to offer and test a methodology that enhances the ways in which the Community museum may be developed over time, and one which would support local residents to construct and communicate their local histories and knowledge in the longer term.

Project Precedents

Existing bayes sites in Somers Town, London: Archive and preservation work by The Somers Town History Club

<https://aspaceforus.club/artineverydaylife/>

Project References

Photogrammetry archival work / Crumbles Castle Centre, Islington-London.

By Elizabeth Wright / Digital Markers

The abandoned Crumbles Castle Centre in Islington, London, is the pilot location for Digital Markers - a prototype initiative within the Horizon 2020 Designscape funded project. A call for contributions of photographs, newsletters and artworks from families past and present, play leaders and social workers, unearthed a collection of material related to their individual and shared experiences of the adventure playground project.

<https://digitalmarkers.net/crumbles-castle/>

Relational and operational insights: The activity has so far revealed potential to further partnerships with organisations such as Stanhope, and expert practitioners such as archaeologists and ceramicists from UAL, around the shared interest on using heritage preservation and legacy reconstruction as a pathway into community building and support for the creation and maintenance of the public realm.

Outputs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 3D Skills workshops on photogrammetry and making digital data bases 2. Workshops on digital objects and sites reconstruction 3. Ceramic and 3D Printing workshops towards objects re-interpretation and re-construction. <p>See also <i>Process: The Story so Far</i>, see above.</p>
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Relational: Through its collaboration with the Somers Town History Club and local residents, aimed at contributing towards constructing the new community museum A Space for Us, the project is expected to help to build trust, shared value, relationships and networks between stakeholders in relation to the two main challenges it addresses: Cultural expression and Public Realm. ● Operational: The project is aimed at building methodological capabilities and capacities of stakeholders in relation to their long standing work on establishing a community-led museum for the area. This, especially in the context of forthcoming large scale urban regeneration projects that threaten the locality with further disappearance of significant heritage. The project helps with learning, teaching and accessing 3D and digital knowledge and resources, not used or thought of as relevant for the history project so far. ● Strategic: the project has the potential to help align institutional agendas in relation to the value of cultural expression and its significance in the construction, maintenance and enjoyment of the local public realm.

Transforming Open & Green Spaces in London Euston

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Improving Health & Wellbeing ● Building Communities ● Making Places ● Cultivating Innovation
Activity Objectives	<p>The project engages with community members in Regents Park Estate, with co-design workshops, aimed at tackling local issues identified by residents and at revitalising negatively perceived sites within the neighbourhood. This, by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Co-designing specific interventions for the Prince of Wales Passage, an agreed site of great interests and potential and currently a 'gateway' into Regents Park Estate as construction works limit access from other routes

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Recording and translating local resident's stories into iconic outcomes as part of the locality's public realm 3. Promoting recycling to reduce fly-tipping through dedicated interventions on the subject in relevant sites.
<p>Activity Description</p>	<p>The community members have deep understanding of local problems and multiple ideas about how to address them, which are now in need of design expertise to support their delivery as tangible and significant interventions. This activity contributes towards fulfilling this need, with co-discovery and co-design workshops where design practitioners support the ideation process by supporting residents to capture, visualise and present ideas in form of mapping and referencing activities, as well as prototyping proposals.</p> <p>Environment and green space: The project proposes activities and workshops that can contribute to alleviate environmental impacts of construction, improve the local environment and tackle issues with rubbish and pollution. Overall, the activities at the heart of the project contribute towards improving Quality of Life in the area.</p> <p>The project crucially asks: <i>How can we use different 'arts of noticing' to engage with and be more attentive to the environment?</i></p> <p>Public Realm: The project addresses the current poor quality wayfinding in the area, and contributes with a co-design approach which in turn, helps building Communities. The following questions motivate the project: <i>How can we rethink the role of streets and squares post Covid to create thriving and inclusive neighbourhoods?, How can public space address inequalities?, How can streets stay accessible to whole communities?</i></p> <p>Cultural Expression: Following from the above, the project addresses limited opportunities for cultural expression by supporting storytelling lead by residents and translating these into creative interventions for the public realm. It asks: <i>How can we leverage Arts, Culture and Creativity to support local identity?</i></p> <p>Working together with Regent's Park Community Champions in collaborative ideation processes will foster the development of creative means which address local issues and support the existent socio-cultural fabric in the community. Importantly, the bottom-up activity can facilitate acceptance of urban interventions in the neighbourhood.</p>
<p>When/Where</p>	<p>October/November 2021. Across Euston, and in and around the Regents Park Estate</p>

<p>Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved</p>	<p>Knowledge bearers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PhD candidate, DACRC UAL-CSM - Senior Urban Designer Sustrans South and DACRC, UAL-CSM - The Place Bureau - Youth Leadership and Regents Park Community Champions Manager, Fitzrovia Youth in Action <p>Providers: UAL-CSM</p>
<p>Participants & Beneficiaries</p>	<p>The Regents Park Estate community group <i>Community Champions</i>, are the main participants and direct beneficiaries of this project. However, the project's impact extends beyond this group to the community at large as well as to London citizens. Euston is a transport, labour and cultural hub integral to London, and this project seeks to highlight its importance, and that of the lived experience of its local residents, to transform its open spaces and spatial links with nearby localities and the city at large.</p> <p>The Community Champions live in Regents Park Estate/Euston and are familiar with its urban environment. They are able and generous to share first-hand experiences of common concerns about the locality, describe the origins of contentious issues and propose opportunities for interventions.</p>
<p>Insights</p>	<p>Process: The story so far</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Preparatory meetings with the practitioners/knowledge bearers involved, have been held on 29 SEP, 13 and 19 OCT 2021. First preparatory meeting with Community Champions/Participants on 06 OCT 2021. These meetings were held to sketch out common themes and aims driving the collaboration. 2. First meeting CoP + Community Champions 20 OCT 2021. Ongoing discussions about shared concerns have been an essential part of the project's development. These discussions have revealed the origin of local problems and what factors (urban development, persistent lack of cleanliness, sense of dismissal or neglect by local governmental institutions) further contribute to those problems. Thoughts around mapping 'anti-social rubbish spots', creating locations for furniture exchange or developing creative and playful ways of recycling, emphasised shared values around sustainability and reusing materials for example. Storytelling has also played a significant role in promoting the socio-cultural value of the neighbourhood to both residents and visitors. <p>Overall, the participants have expressed a collective motivation to improve their neighbourhood by undertaking initiatives for creating</p>

moments of delight, discovery and celebration, which the project aims to contribute to materialise.

In a brief walk through the locality, the Prince of Wales Passage/Everton Mews collectively identified as a relevant site for transformative interventions.

*West of Passage Towards Hampstead Road – Most Problematic Stretch.
Photo Credit: Adriana Cobo-Corey*

Our fist mapping exercise was carried out to locate the three key themes identified in previous meeting within maps of the locality.

These themes are: 1) Passageways in need of transformation, 2) Story trails offering opportunities to celebrate and commemorate local histories and re-use and 3) Recycling habits and sites in need for care. (See above under Activities Objectives and Aims)

The maps produced will be used to visualise overlaps, relevant spots and links between the identified key themes. Our first discussion over the material produced, suggested, follow-up mapping workshops, where maps are produced collectively on a bigger scale of approximately 1:750 and 1:400, and using materials such as cardboard boxes and plywood. These exercises could lead to deeper mapping of significant sites, personal stories and relevant locations with an expanded group of participants, and to temporary, pop-up participatory installations for specific sites within the public realm.

More specifically, the material produced suggested developing potential projects on the themes of: 1) Remembrance and Hope Trail – Commemorating the lives of those killed in episodes of street violence which have shaken local residents who experience ongoing grief and wish for a better future for their young. 2) Public + Private Trail – overcoming psychological barriers by which some locations such as Regents Place are perceived as too corporate, shiny and overtly invigilated by private security by incorporating these sites into a wider trail that bridges the residential and the corporate realms 3) Healthy Trails: Outlining a sequence of accessible green and non-polluted spaces to support existing programmes whereby groups of residents gather together to walk through the locality. These walks could in turn link to 4) Safety Trails – identifying routes through the neighbourhood that are well maintained and well-lit with the possibility of identifying/providing ‘safe havens’ for those that experience anti-social behaviour or violence. 5) Bridging routes – Devising alternative, meanwhile routes to link Euston with Somers Town while construction work for HS2 is under way.

Participant Mapping of the Euston Area – Regents Park Estate locality / Bridges across wards, Rubbish sites, Green spots

Key Insights

Although the participants have ideas for addressing shared issues, ongoing discussions have revealed that design expertise is now required towards accomplishing the realisation of those ideas. The presence of design practitioners supported the project, by providing examples of existent urban and social interventions as well as by sharing relevant knowledge and experience. The sketching and mapping of thoughts, for example, has fostered an engaging presentation. Sharing knowledge of existing networks and associations in the neighbourhood (e.g. schools and theatre associations) between community members has expanded

the remit of the project, opening opportunities for wider communal collaboration.

One of the ideas that the Community Champions are working on - and we are helping them to develop - is that of a 'story trail' - a walking route that links locations within the estate that are meaningful for residents - green spaces (including Clarence Gardens, Cumberland Market etc) also, sites of 'bottom up' regeneration - community-led projects that are turning nasty corners of the estate into places residents want to be and use. This group are all too aware of some of the community safety challenges in their area - from youth safety to drug use and ASB - some of which they understand to be displaced into their neighbourhood from Euston development - public urination/defecation (including taxi drivers that toss away bottles of urine as there are no public toilets they can easily use), the perennials of dog poo and fly tipping, and a general increase in littering, in part as a consequence of all the bins being removed ("by the council").

Project references/precedents

An important reference for this project is a crime prevention initiative delivered in a neighbourhood of Seoul in South Korea, led by the Design Policy Department of Seoul Metropolitan Government and catalysed by the Mayor of Seoul, Park Won Soon. This initiative is analysed at length in the article:

Walking with Park: Exploring the 'reframing' and integration of CPTED principles in neighbourhood regeneration in Seoul, South Korea

Adam Thorpe* and Lorraine Gamman

Design Against Crime Research Centre, University of the Arts London, London, UK.

*Corresponding author.

Here, the Salt Way project is described as a part of the case study. The project provides useful example of how community safety interventions are combined with health and fitness interventions. This multiple driver approach may provide inspiration to Community Champions and partners seeking to combine Community Safety and locally defined 'heritage/identity' in the form of the 'story trail'.

User-Oriented Design Created by Repeated Design Prototyping. Photo Source: <http://sampartners.co.kr/en/portfolio-item/design-for-crime-prevention/?ckattempt=>

<p>Outputs</p>	<p>Follow-up workshops in November and December as described above.</p>
<p>Outcomes</p>	<p>The activity fostered the exchange of experiences between community members and facilitated a collective goal to improve current conditions in a creative way, with themes around sustainability and storytelling emerging. It built trust between community members and design practitioners that will support collaborative working in the future. It surfaced resident concerns that align with the programmes of other local stakeholders, identifying opportunities to combine resources and efforts towards collective impact as regards improvements to the public realm that contribute to positive identity and community safety.</p>
<p>Next Steps</p>	<p>In Summary, these workshops entail:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping exercises to identify spots for storytelling, activities for recycling and the revitalisation of urban spaces • Planning a consultation process with the wider community around the ideas generated by previous meetings and exercises • Prototyping workshops for co-designing future urban interventions <p>The workshops will continue to work on the three main themes that have emerged from our fortnightly meetings with the Community Champions, which are interconnected and provide a template moving forwards:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Passageways - transforming a negatively perceived spaces into a positive one through way finding exercises and prototyping.

<p>2. Story trails - joining significant sites within the locality for creating public events that commemorate and recognise local histories.</p> <p>3. Re-Use and Recycling - identifying current negative habits and un-attended 'dumping' sites towards transforming these into more formal and sustainable opportunities that contribute to the community's well-being.</p> <p>This work will also explore the potential to integrate several parallel work streams that are currently separate including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plans to improve wayfinding in the area as part of public realm improvements led by Camden Council's Green and Open spaces team and funded by HS2 mitigation funding. • Plans to implement a Community Guardianship programme led by Community Safety and Youth Support teams within the Council <p>By bringing these initiatives together with the work of the Community Champions described above these dutyholder-led interventions have potential to become more community-led, which in turn may bring more resources (and capital funding) to the delivery of the Community Champions' projects described above.</p>	<p>2. Story trails - joining significant sites within the locality for creating public events that commemorate and recognise local histories.</p> <p>3. Re-Use and Recycling - identifying current negative habits and un-attended 'dumping' sites towards transforming these into more formal and sustainable opportunities that contribute to the community's well-being.</p> <p>This work will also explore the potential to integrate several parallel work streams that are currently separate including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plans to improve wayfinding in the area as part of public realm improvements led by Camden Council's Green and Open spaces team and funded by HS2 mitigation funding. • Plans to implement a Community Guardianship programme led by Community Safety and Youth Support teams within the Council <p>By bringing these initiatives together with the work of the Community Champions described above these dutyholder-led interventions have potential to become more community-led, which in turn may bring more resources (and capital funding) to the delivery of the Community Champions' projects described above.</p>
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Demystifying Research

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building Communities • Making Places • Cultivating innovation
Activity Objectives	<p>The project aims to communicate diverse methodologies for conducting research, including those involving non-academics as researchers. It focuses on and highlights the local knowledge embedded within communities and local residents, which are at the heart of co-design and collaborative practices in research. The project requires a sustained programme that encourages knowledge exchange between different research communities within the area, which is currently in its initial stages.</p>
Activity Description	<p>The project will unfold as a collaboration between a group of students from the Master programme in Culture, Curation and Criticism MA CCC at UAL-Central Saint Martin's, who are currently curating an exhibition of PhD student research at The Lethaby Gallery (Nov-Jan 2021) in Kings Cross, and the Citizen Social Scientist CSS group, working on the project Good Life in Euston with UCL and Camden Council. The exhibition addresses issues surrounding access to higher education, placing the will for demystifying the processes of PhD research at the forefront of</p>

	<p>shared concerns to open critical work towards broader audiences. They hope that they can make creative practice more accessible and approachable to the universities' local community through transparency and openness.</p> <p>Incorporating elements of the exhibition into public events within Granary Square and outreach events where we reach out towards Euston communities, rather than the other way around. We could develop a participatory activity with one of the exhibiting artists – several of whom already have existing partnerships with stakeholders like We Are Aging Better Together, Saint Pancras and Somers Town, and the Saint Pancras Community Association SPCA.</p>
When/Where	October to December 2021. Lethaby Gallery, Central Saint Martin's - UAL
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	<p>Knowledge bearers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course Leader MA CCC / Culture & Enterprise, UAL-CSM • Executive Lead, Prosperity Co-Lab UK (ProCol UK) and Principal Research Fellow, Institute for Global Prosperity UCL <p>Providers: UAL-CSM</p>
Participants & Beneficiaries	MA CCC students, Citizen Social Scientists/CSS research group members
Outputs	Follow-up workshops in November and December as described above.
Outcomes	Public engagement programmes in the form of outreach events such as dedicated gallery visits, research readings and/or curatorial workshops/seminars.

Digital Storytelling & Collective Poetry Making

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving Health & Wellbeing • Building Communities • Cultivating Innovation
Activity Objectives	<p>The project will deliver digital storytelling projects with vulnerable groups with strategies including citizen film making for consultation techniques with Euston residents.</p> <p>Stretch charity, directed by Carlotta Allum, has been delivering digital storytelling projects with vulnerable groups for 9 years. The charity has</p>

	<p>worker with Mind in Camden, a charity focused on caring for mental health citizens well-being in the area.</p> <p>Poet and the City is an independent charity dedicated to help people and places tell their stories. Based in Camden's Knowledge Quarter, Poet and the city has raised funds to run workshops and diverse public events to train and encourage young people to read and write poetry for more than 20 years.</p>
Activity Description	The project provides a platform to translate resident's concerns and views into creative forms of expression, and to amplify their voices through varied public stages, digital and otherwise.
When/Where	The project will take the form of a series of four to six weekly workshops, occurring on Wednesdays 10:30 am to 1:00 pm, from 12 JAN 2022.
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	<p>Knowledge bearers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PhD Candidate UAL-CSM (+ artist, storyteller, Stretch charity director) ● Camden resident (artist and Stretch storyteller) ● Camden Mind ● Producer, Poet in the City ● Poet, Poet in the City <p>Providers: UAL-CSM, Mind in Camden, Stretch Charity, Poet in the City</p>
Participants & Beneficiaries	Local Residents, experienced storytellers and a poet. The residents are mainly a group from the organisation MIND in Camden, we are envisioning a group of around 15 participants per session. Participants may vary from session to session, so the total number across the four to six weeks of workshops might end up being higher.
Insights	<p>Process: The story so far</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A Series of preparatory meetings have been held throughout the months of October and November, leading towards building up a community group to work with., as well as for connecting the charities Stretch, Mind in Camden and Poet in the City to join efforts in amplifying diverse resident group's voices. 2. A joint presentation to the participant's group about the workshop will be delivered by Stretch, Poet in the City and T-Factor, in the context of a coffee morning at MIND in Camden, on 01 DEC 2021 3. Workshops to commence 12 JAN 2022. <p>Project Precedents</p> <p>Stretch Charity has delivered numerous digital story telling workshops with groups of prisoners, for example.</p>

Through the making of Poetry, Poet in the City organises and participates in large events gathering diverse forms of expression from poetry to DJing, and engaging a wide range of audiences of different ages and backgrounds.

Poet in the City Events. Images <https://www.poetinthe.city.co.uk>. Photo Credit: Poet in the City

<p>Outputs</p>	<p>Outputs (anticipated): A series of workshops and public events to co-create stories around residents responses to the upcoming redevelopment.</p>
<p>Outcomes</p>	<p>Outcomes (anticipated): A series of photographic and text based stories including poetry, digital essays and short films. Temporary displays of outcomes across the area both digitally (websites, social media) as well as hardbound (billboards, plaques)</p>

Timeline

The below timeline shows when the E&I support activities implemented during the E&I stage.

D5.1 Stakeholder Reports: Exploring and Inquiring

KNOWLEDGE BEARER	AGENCY ACTIVITIES	Jul21	Aug21	Sep21	Oct21	Nov21	Dec21	Jan22	Feb22	Mar21
UAL-CSM	Access to Meanwhile Workshop									
Defining the role of London Euston LC Co-Leaders										
Local Coalition engagement, planning and design of sessions. Integration with Meanwhile Use Working Group as part of the Place and Social Value Panel (TEP).										
Access to Meanwhile Workshop with members of MUWG										
UAL-CSM	Participation in Social Action									
Workshop design and planning. Engagement of LC in conversation										
Brief writing for MA Industrial Design students at UAL-CSM										
Engagement of local residents, community groups and VCS organisations in an event / workshop										
Production and testing of workshop										
KNOWLEDGE BEARER	T-LAB PROBES	Jul21	Aug21	Sep21	Oct21	Nov21	Dec21	Jan22	Feb22	Mar21
UAL-CSM / T-LAB 1	Community of Practice									
Knowledge Quarter CoP Presentation - 18th August										
Presentation of UAL-CSM CoP and KQ CoP projects to CSS cohort – 22nd September										
Presentation of UAL-CSM CoP and KQ CoP projects to Community Champions – TBC (Oct)										
On-going E&I Activities related to the CoP										
UOC / T-LAB 5	Thinking the Meanwhile in Circular & Collaborative Terms									

Workshop design and planning									
'A Circular Economy for Somers Town', online talks and discussion – 16 November									

5.3.3. Exploring and Inquiring Support Activities and T-Lab Probes

Access to Meanwhile Workshop

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Building Communities</i> ○ <i>Cultivating innovation</i> ○ <i>Growing prosperity</i> ○ <i>Making places</i> ○ <i>Improving Health & Wellbeing</i>
Activity Objectives	<p>Meanwhile uses are recognised by Euston dutyholders (represented within the Euston Partnership) as integral to delivering on their social value aims, including ‘bringing the benefits of regeneration forward’ for Euston residents and stakeholders during the construction period. The importance of meanwhile uses to overall project success, and the need for partnership working to deliver meanwhile uses, is recognised within both The Strategic Plan for One Euston and the HS2 Assurances that the secretary of State provided to LB Camden as part of parliamentary process in relation to redevelopment at Euston.</p> <p>The Project Objectives within The Strategic Plan for One Euston include two specific references to meanwhile uses as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deliver Comprehensive Development Fit for the Future <i>The One Euston design will prioritise a balance of uses, and create the critical mass and concentration of activity necessary to create a new piece of city. We will address the priorities that matter most to local people, working with young people and delivering meanwhile-use projects that illustrate, and will help deliver, Euston’s potential. The long term economic and social resilience of One Euston depends heavily on creating a truly diverse and mixed-use place that is flexible and adaptable to market shifts.</i> ● Optimise Construction Phasing <i>...Given the long timescales involved the project must embrace opportunities to deliver meanwhile uses across the site, and support and empower local communities/businesses to co-create these. These meanwhile uses offer the opportunity to test out creative concepts and uses utilising local skills and knowledge which could inform the final development.</i>

HS2 Assurances include specific assurances that require the 'Nominated Undertaker' (i.e. Euston Partners) to:

- *use reasonable endeavours to engage with the London Borough of Camden throughout detailed design and construction to identify opportunities for possible meanwhile uses for vacant or blighted buildings resulting from HS2 works in the London Borough of Camden area...*
- *liaise with LB Camden throughout the design and construction of the authorised works with a view to identifying opportunities on land within the Nominated Undertakers control for, and implementing the provision of, temporary open space during the authorised works...*

In response to these requirements Euston Partnership has convened the Meanwhile Use Working Group (MUWG) which reports into the Place and Social Value Panel according to the organisational structure below.

The MUWG has a clearly defined set of tasks, fulfilment of which will enable it to support delivery of a portfolio of meanwhile projects in Euston that deliver on the following (draft) objectives:

- Delivering community priorities;
- Delivering social value (as defined by the Place and Social Value Panel)
- Mitigating the impacts of construction work;
- A positive experience of Euston for residents, businesses and travellers;
- Euston as a place is celebrated positively;
- Realising early benefits of the legacy aims of the scheme;
- Embracing the scope to test uses,

- Testing creative approaches to place creation and future uses for the Euston Campus;
- Embracing the opportunity of transition to test new ways of doing things and share this learning widely, for example changes to the highway network necessitated by construction should be used to test longer-term opportunities); and
- Build confidence in the delivery partners to deliver and to work with communities

As can be seen from the above, the objectives of the MUWG closely align with those of the T-Factor project linked to “unlocking the transformative potential of meanwhile in urban regeneration” through the exploration of “participatory meanwhile” approaches.

The objectives of the **Access to Meanwhile Workshop**, and the related activities that preceded the workshop, are to support the T-Factor team in understanding more about the local context in relation to meanwhile uses, in preparation for engagement with the MUWG and to support the MUWG in developing an inclusive and equitable approach to meanwhile allocation and support for providers. In doing so, the activities hope to contribute a first step in helping to address the following challenges and opportunities identified within the Euston regeneration area through T-Factor research to date (as described above):

- **Reciprocal Engagement & Building Trust and Capacity amongst residents and other stakeholders** – community-led meanwhile activities and associated support can reciprocate contributions made by residents and community groups participating in consultation and engagement activities linked to regeneration.
- **Joining Up Engagement Activities & Outcomes** – meanwhile projects can contribute to respond to concerns raised through consultation/engagement activities in the short to medium term demonstrating that contributions to consultation/engagement are listened to and acted upon.
- **Aligning and Leveraging Aims and Resources** of stakeholders towards collective impact in relation to local priorities – can be exemplified by partnership working supporting delivery of meanwhile projects that address local priorities.
- **‘Bringing Benefits Forward’** for residents and other stakeholders during the regeneration process through meanwhile delivery that addresses resident priorities and demonstrates how regeneration can help to meet their needs.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interrelation Between the Meanwhile Strategy and the Masterplan – supporting meanwhile experimentation as a means of ‘prototyping permanence’ and informing future provision.
Activity Description	<p>The <i>Access to Meanwhile Workshop</i> is the third of three phases of work exploring access to meanwhile in Euston that has spanned 12 months.</p> <p>Phase 1. Access to Meanwhile student project with MA Service Design, UAL-London College of Communication.</p> <p>Phase 2. Public Studio Euston Canvas project and High Streets Renewal Access to meanwhile service proposition.</p> <p>Phase 3. Meanwhile Use Working Group Access to Meanwhile Workshop</p> <p>Phase 1 engaged thirty-five UAL MA Service Design students in a project exploring meanwhile uses in the parallel contexts of <i>High Streets Renewal post-Covid</i> (focused on Chalk Farm High Street in Camden) and <i>Disruptive Development</i> (focused on Euston). The project was supported by Euston Partnership and Camden Council’s Euston and High Streets Renewal teams. The project engaged businesses and community groups in the two locations and produced eight meanwhile proposals that addressed the concerns and opportunities identified by the stakeholders. The co-design of the meanwhile project proposals built shared understandings around the potential of meanwhile uses amongst stakeholders and developed networks and partnerships that have supported further work, including the co-delivery of Phase 2 of the activity.</p> <p>Phase 2 co-developed and co-delivered one of the meanwhile propositions for Euston - the Euston Canvas. This project is described above in section 5.2.2. above. The Euston Canvas project, led by staff and students from the MA Service Design cohort that delivered Phase 1, brought together local artists, youth group Fitzrovia Youth in Action and Euston Partnership partners to co-design and co-deliver two community artworks that are being produced for display on the Euston hoardings. The Euston Canvas project explored, through collaborative practice, what it takes to enable local residents to deliver a meanwhile project. The project revealed that inclusive and equitable access to meanwhile opportunities requires more than a match-making process. Considerable effort and resources were required to coordinate and support the co-creation of the meanwhile project and its implementation. This insight has been useful in helping the T-Factor team to understand what it takes for partnership working in delivery of community-led meanwhile to succeed. The project has supported the development of operational understandings as well as building relationships between delivery partners that are contributing to the development of further meanwhile project proposals (see <i>Transforming</i></p>

	<p><i>Open and Green Spaces in Euston in T-Factor Local Coalition Exploring & Inquiring activities).</i></p> <p>Phase 3 of the Access to Meanwhile Activity is the core activity described here. It concerns the planning, co-design and delivery of the Access to Meanwhile Workshop, an online workshop with members of the Meanwhile Use Working Group.</p> <p>The purpose of the two-hour workshop was to support the group in exploring the tasks set out in their draft terms of reference. Specifically, the workshop invited participants to share their knowledge, perspectives and ideas in response to a series of open questions, concerning meanwhile spaces and projects, as a first step towards devising a support plan for inclusive and equitable meanwhile uses in the Euston regeneration area.</p> <p>The workshop was delivered online using Miro and MS Teams. Participants made contributions in open discussion, via the chat function and directly onto the miro board. The T-Factor team supported the entry of data to the miro.</p> <p>The questions were presented on a series of canvases accompanied by relevant resources and reference materials including maps, policy documents and information relating to stakeholder priorities as identified by previous public consultation and engagement in the area. Each canvas explored a different aspect of meanwhile access and operation including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identifying sites for meanwhile uses ● Criteria and priorities for meanwhile uses ● Applications for meanwhile use ● Identifying meanwhile projects/Calls for meanwhile use proposals ● Assessment and decision making ● Supporting meanwhile uses ● Evaluation and reporting ● Legacy
When/Where	23rd November 2021: Online – Phase 3 Access to Meanwhile workshop with the MUWG
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	<p>Phase 3. Meanwhile Use Working Group Access to meanwhile workshop:</p> <p>Knowledge bearer: UAL-CSM</p> <p>Providers: UAL-CSM</p>

	<p>Co-Providers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Camden Council, Euston Area Plan Team • The Euston Partnership
Participants & Beneficiaries	<p>Phase 3: Meanwhile Use Working Group Access to meanwhile workshop, seventeen participants in total from the following organisations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Camden Council, Euston Area Plan Team • Camden Council, Participation Team • Camden Council, HS2 Community Liaison • The Euston Partnership – Governance for One Euston • HS2 • Mace Dragados – Contractors • SCS Railways – Contractors • Network Rail – Landowners, Network Operators • Lendlease – OSD / Masterplan • Department for Transport – Central Government Dept. overseeing HS2 works • UAL-CSM
Insights	<p>At this link is a synthesis of the data collected. Insights are arranged by canvas theme. Each theme has a series of sub questions that were asked to the whole group of participants at the same time. Responses were recorded on Miro, in the Teams chat, and the video was also transcribed after the activity. These data have been synthesised thematically in order to provide insights, and made anonymous for this report. Any commercially or politically sensitive information has also been removed.</p> <p>The workshop activity contributed to support partnership working across MUWG members. It highlighted the need for support for local organisations to develop meanwhile use proposals to foster equitable meanwhile uses that are inclusive of community-led operators.</p> <p>The MUWG is the operational lead for meanwhile uses within the Euston regeneration area and as such it is essential that T-Factor's Euston Pilot is integrated into MUWG activities. T-Factors methodology for Scoping and Ideating meanwhile use and evaluating meanwhile uses is being shared with the MUWG to see if/how it can contribute to the goals of the group. The aims of the T-Factor project are closely aligned to the strategic objectives of the MUWG and the Place and Social Value Group to which the MUWG reports. This presents opportunities for alignment of T-Factor resources with those of the MUWG to enable collective impact in relation to experimentation in</p>

	supporting participatory meanwhile uses within the Euston regeneration.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Miro Tool / Canvas that can be used to structure conversations about meanwhile use in other pilots • Report summarising information shared and next steps to be circulated to MUWG in December 2021.
Outcomes	T- Factor has been recognised as useful and welcomed by the MUWG. The group welcomed the resources and recommendations that the focused questions surfaced. There is interest for another workshop to consider the remaining Miro Canvas questions together, and possibly future sessions. Partners are keen for the workshop findings to contribute to actionable outcomes for the MUWG.

Participation in Social Action

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Improving Health & Wellbeing</i> ○ <i>Building Communities</i> ○ <i>Cultivating Innovation</i>
Activity Objectives	<p>Participation in social action and civic activity can be hard work and require time and commitment. Also, the impacts of participation are not always evident to participants. Consequently, not everyone is interested or able to participate. This is especially true in and around Euston where residents of Somers Town and Regents Park Estate have been subjected to engagement and consultation for many years linked to multiple regeneration initiatives and proposals. Scoping research in the Euston area has identified that whilst there is a desire amongst residents, businesses and organisations to influence the Euston regeneration there is also 'consultation fatigue'. Residents report frustration at being repeatedly asked for their views but not seeing evidence of action or benefit arising from their participation. A lack of participation can contribute to exclusion of certain voices and perspectives and can foster division and mistrust between citizens and regeneration dutyholders.</p> <p>This scenario is also significant for the T-Factor Pilot in Euston. To support equitable and inclusive 'participatory meanwhile' residents and other stakeholders need to be willing and able to participate.</p> <p>This Activity set out to explore how citizen engagement can be acknowledged and rewarded so as to become less extractive and more reciprocal. In the earliest stages of engagement with partners and participants it became obvious that the framing needed to be broadened to consider 'how to support all those that wish to participate</p>

	<p>in Social Action to do so?'. Also, 'how to encourage and support those that do not currently participate in Social Action to do so?'. </p> <p>The objectives of the activity were to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understand different types of participation in Social Action ● Understand the circumstances, perceptions and motivations of different residents in relation to participation in Social Action ● Understand the barriers to participation in Social Action experienced by residents ● Understand the support and inducements provided to promote participation in Social Action ● Identify new approaches to supporting participation in Social Action
Activity Description	<p>The Participation in Social Action Activity took the form of a ten weeks student project delivered by a team of ten MA Industrial Designers supported by members of the T- Factor Pilot Local Coalition, including UAL researchers, Camden's Participation Team and Somers Town Community Association.</p> <p>The activity was delivered in four stages:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Desk research to understand the state of the art as regards support for participation in Social Action 2. Expert interviews with representatives of organisations with experience of inviting and supporting participation in Social Action and consultation and engagement activities. 3. On street engagement using Participation Probes - tools designed specifically to engage those who do not usually participate in consultation or Social Action. 4. A workshop to share, validate and iterate insights and make proposals for supporting participation in Social Action, including T-Factor participatory meanwhile projects. <p>Expert interviews</p> <p>The team conducted twelve expert interviews to establish:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The different kinds of Social Action residents are invited to participate in ● The different kinds of support and inducements provide to residents for participation in different scenarios ● The barriers to participation in social action experienced by citizens. <p>Interviews were transcribed and findings clustered and categorised.</p>

Participation probes

To engage citizens that do not typically participate in Social Action so as to understand their perceptions and experiences the team designed a series of 'participation probes' - tools and activities that supported conversations about the barriers and enablers for participation in Social Action. The 'participation probes' built upon the insights derived from the expert interviews, seeking to validate findings and fill gaps in knowledge identified by the experts. The 'participation probes' were implemented in Chalton Street, a market street in Somers Town (within the re-development area) and in Swiss Cottage open space – an outdoor civic space to the north of the development area. Each probe applied a different strategy to explore different perspectives of participation in ways that might appeal to different groups.

Probe 1. Time travelling archaeologists

The Time Travelling Archaeologists. Photo Credit: MA Industrial Design, CSM

In this interactive performance time travelling archaeologists have returned to the present from the year 2050 in which a number of poor design decisions have been implemented. The activity is staged beneath a banner that reads “All it takes for a bad idea to prevail, is for a good idea not to be shared”. The dysfunctional designs that have been brought back from the future include train tracks that run through houses and backpacks that carry a personal ‘green space’ to make up for the green spaces lost to development. Participants are asked to share their ideas

for supporting people to participate in Social Action so as to avoid the dystopia that they have observed in 2050.

Probe 2. Camden Queendom

Camden Queendom - Quests and Rewards. Photo Credit: MA Industrial Design, CSM

An interactive performance in which a 'servant' must find a citizen to complete a 'quest' for the 'Queen of Camden'. Citizens are stopped and asked to help. They are shown a map of the area and asked what challenge their 'quest' would address and where in the area it would be located. The choice of challenges is derived from the issues and activities that were revealed through the expert interviews. Citizens are then asked what kind of reward they would want for completing the 'quest'. The chosen challenges and rewards are recorded and the citizen is engaged in a discussion around what support they might need to enable them to complete the challenge successfully. This information is also recorded by a 'scribe'.

Probe 3. Participation ball game

stickers that are relevant to their experiences and perceptions of participation in Social Action. The selected stickers are placed on the 'participation post'. The stickers are placed in the orange section of the post if they are perceived as barriers and in the green section if they are perceived as enablers. Further stickers are added if other citizens identify the same barriers or enablers. Citizens are engaged in a discussion about their choices and the results are recorded.

The results from all four Participation Probes were combined with those of the Expert Interviews. Findings were synthesised into:

- Types of participation, according to; issues addressed, type of activity, commitment required of participants
- Motivations for participation
- Barriers to participation
- Enablers for participation

Workshop exploring participation in Social Action

The student team designed and delivered a 1.5hr workshop to share the findings of the research with regeneration stakeholders.

The findings of the research informed the development of a set of workshop resources including:

- A set of six 'participation personas' – characters that are representative of citizens' different circumstances, perceptions and values relating to participation in Social Action.
- A set of 'activity cards' – arranged according to the typology of participation described above.
- A set of 'motivation cards' sharing the motivations for participation in Social Action identified by the preceding research.
- A set of 'barrier cards' sharing the barriers to participation in Social Action identified by the preceding research.
- A set of 'enabler' cards sharing the enablers for participation in Social Action identified by the preceding research.
- A 'participation journey canvas' to be used by workshop participants to map out participation scenarios for each persona.

The workshop methodology structures a process by which workshop participants were invited to work together in teams to:

1. Choose a persona that they are familiar with.
2. Choose an 'activity card' that represents an activity that the team think will appeal to the persona.
3. Choose the 'motivation cards' that the team consider might encourage the persona to participate in the activity.
4. Choose the 'barrier cards' that describe the barriers that the team think might prevent the persona from participating in the activity.
5. Choose the 'enabler cards' that describe the support that the team think might enable the persona to participate in the activity.

6. Propose any additional support that the team think the persona may require to enable them to participate in the activity.

Workshop Exploring Participation in Social Action. Photo Credit: Adam Thorpe

The team were invited to repeat this process three times – starting with an activity that they thought the persona was most likely to participate in (now), then focusing on an activity that the team thought may be of interest to the persona but may be more challenging for the persona to participate in (near), and finally to work through an activity that the team thought may be most difficult for the persona to participate in (next). Finally, the teams were brought together to reflect on their work and discuss what support might be necessary to support participation in Social Action and how this support might be provided.

<p>When/Where</p>	<p>Expert interviews were delivered online between 20th October and 5th November.</p> <p>Participation probes were implemented in Chalton Street Market and Swiss Cottage open space between between 3rd -13th November.</p> <p>Workshop exploring participation in Social Action was held at Central Saint Martins College on 25th November 2021.</p>
<p>Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved</p>	<p>Knowledge bearer – UAL T-Factor team</p> <p>Providers – UAL-CSM MA Industrial Design students and UAL T-Factor team</p> <p>Co-Providers - Camden Council Participation Team, Somers Town Community Association (STCA)</p>
<p>Participants & Beneficiaries</p>	<p>Expert interviews included representatives of the following organisations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Camden Council: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Euston team re. Euston Area Plan and Residents Advisory Group ○ Participation team ○ Green space team

- Somers Town Community Association
- Somers Town Youth Centre
- Lendlease
- HS2
- MACE Dragados
- Walls on Walls

Participation Probes engaged 70 citizens.

Workshop included representatives of the following organisations:

- Camden Council Participation Team
- Somers Town Neighbourhood Forum
- Regents Park Estate Community Champions
- Citizen Social Scientists

Insights

The activities identified motivations, barriers and enablers of citizens in relation to participation in Social Action as illustrated below.

Barriers

Barriers

Barriers to participation in social action.

The activity revealed that some citizens that had participated in the past, felt that their contributions had not made a difference to the outcome. This has led them to feel that their contributions are not valued by dutyholders.

Amongst citizens that had not participated in Social Action, lack of time, unwillingness or inability to commit to participation, and the belief that

participation ‘would not change anything’ were amongst the most common reasons given for not participating.

Common barriers to participation also included a lack of confidence amongst participants about the participation activity and their capacity or ability to contribute to it.

Motivations and Enablers

Enablers

Enablers to participation in social action.

Amongst younger citizens interested or active in participation in Social Action a common motivation was the opportunity to learn new skills and expand their networks.

Amongst those with caring responsibilities the opportunity to involve their children in ways that they would enjoy was an important motivation as was the offer of childcare provided alongside participation in activities.

Time and commitment featured as a common concern amongst ‘would be’ participants, with ‘flexibility’ in terms of timing and ways of participating seen as an enabler.

The opportunity to participate alongside friends was seen as an important way to overcome lack of confidence.

Activities led by peers/neighbours/fellow citizens were found to be more likely to foster participation than those delivered by consultants and dutyholders according to some respondents.

	<p>Payments for participation were considered important when higher levels of commitment and longer periods of time were required for participation. Also, when participation required people to contribute their professional skills outside of the workplace.</p> <p>Existing approaches to support</p> <p>Research into existing approaches to supporting participation revealed that it is typical for dutyholders inviting participation to offer different levels of support and inducement/reward depending on the level of commitment required.</p> <p>Inducements and rewards included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Competitions and prizes (for participation in surveys) ● Shopping vouchers (for participation in workshops, focus groups) ● Training and skills development (linked to participation in workshops, research activities, and advisory groups e.g. Citizen Social Scientists, Community Champions) ● Payments @ London Living Wage (for participation in activities that require higher levels of commitment e.g. meetings, conferences, focus groups and/or preparatory work, research activities, advisory groups) <p>Processes of reward and recognition need to be clear and transparent. Good practice is to develop a specific 'reward and recognition' policy for each project. Participants should be given clear advice on the potential financial implications of being paid to participate e.g. on benefits and tax.</p> <p>Support opportunities</p> <p>There is no 'one size fits all' when it comes to supporting participation in Social Action. A range of support should be offered to potential participants so it can be tailored to a participant's needs. There is a resource implication for tailoring support that should be considered when planning approaches to inviting and supporting participation in Social Action. There is an opportunity to explore learning recognition for participants who develop skills and competencies through participation in Social Action.</p>
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Four participation probes. ● Six participation personas. ● A workshop design and resources for diagnosing support for participation in Social Action.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Potential to develop and test a support plan approach for participation in Social Action through the Euston pilot. ● Potential to explore learning recognition for participants in social action through the Euston pilot.

Thinking the Meanwhile Circularly & Collaboratively

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Cultivating innovation</i> ○ <i>Attaining sustainability</i> ○ <i>Growing prosperity</i>
Activity Objectives	<p>The aim of this probe was to support and accompany the Euston Local Coalition in thinking about the inclusion of circular and collaborative economy practices into the design of meanwhile uses. The Circular Economy can be applied to different processes in urban regeneration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● First, a regeneration process opens many opportunities as it generates a lot of waste and materials that can be recycled and also urban regeneration practices can include circular economy principles in the use, recycling and reuse of some resources (examples of Sustainable Urban Drainage systems, rainwater harvesting/greywater reuse, etc.). ● Second, the circular economy can be enacted and enhanced through collaborative economy approaches that involve grassroots and community collectives in making more sustainable spaces and communities. ● And third, meanwhile spaces - built with the principles of circular economy - may emerge as interesting spaces to promote and showcase collaborative economy practices. <p>Co-organised by T Lab 6 partner, the Open University of Catalonia, the probe connected UoC's network of experts in circular and collaborative economies in Europe to different actors in the Euston Local Coalition. This was initiated in order to generate a common ground on what the circular and collaborative economies are, how this common understanding aligns with the different interests and policies of the Euston Local Coalition members, and to assess how circular economy principles could guide the process of rethinking the role of streets & squares in the covid aftermath to produce thriving and inclusive neighbourhoods.</p> <p>It was decided that a local 'home' was required for the Probe so that the work could connect in with a specific Euston area and associated network, and a local project with the principles of the Circular and Collaborative Economy at its core. The theme of the Probe ties in with Euston Local Coalition partners, Somers Town Community Association and Camden Council's, successful application to the GLA Future Neighbourhoods 2030 commission.</p> <p>To help support a green recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic, the Greater London Authority (London's Mayor) launched a new funding programme called Future Neighbourhoods 2030. It aims to tackle some of London's defining environmental challenges, including the climate</p>

emergency and toxic air quality, whilst creating jobs, developing skills and supporting a just transition to a low carbon circular economy. Somers Town was chosen as one of two sites to be funded across London – Somers Town represents one of London’s most disadvantaged and climate-vulnerable areas, and an area where residents have been most severely affected by the pandemic. £3million is being made available for the first phase of the programme, initially supporting two projects, Somers Town is one of them.

A consortium of partners in Somers Town, including Camden Council, Somers Town Community Association, Somers Town Neighbourhood Forum with help from other support partners such as Central Saint Martins, were successful in their initial application to the GLA Future Neighbourhoods 2030 which shortlisted six projects. Within the Somers Town application there are ten projects. T-Factor LC partners Central Saint Martins are involved in delivery teams on Project 2 - Greening Estates and Project 8 - Circular Economy on Chalton Street. All activities associated with the application need to be delivered by March 2022.

Chalton Street Market is a pre-existing market located in Somers Town, between Euston Station and the British Library, just off Euston Road. Whilst it has been in operation since 1795 with over 300 market pitches, the market has not been thriving for a number of years and currently only operates on Fridays from 10:30 am to 3pm with a small number of stalls selling clothing, household goods, and fresh food. Despite this, there is a strong feeling in the surrounding communities that the market could offer much more than it currently does and needs to offer something different to draw people away from the commercial centres of King’s Cross and Euston.

As part of the GLA application, Camden Council and other partners have proposed a *Circular Chalton Street Market*. This would be a re-imagining of what Chalton Street Market could offer with a focus on how the principles of the Circular Economy could frame the market. The ambition is for this proposal to create new enterprise, training and employment experiences for residents. Existing local organisations and groups would collaborate to deliver an innovative range of circular ethical and charitable services for Somers Town centred on Chalton Street market but linking to local neighbouring estates. The market arena will test and deliver circular growth and themes for achieving zero waste. The Circular Economy Chalton Market would be a six-to-nine-month circular economy street market project using the new stalls to include information sharing stalls, stalls for estate reuse/upcycled produce, charity stalls, reuse and repair-it stalls, new eco- trader stalls, including:

- 1. Co-Designed Market Stalls
- 2. Identifying Zero Waste Streams
- 3. Refill Station, for eco home products

- 4. Tipp Tapp App, a social app linking residents, buyers and organisations to local green transport to redistribute reuse and upcycle unwanted home and business products.
- 5. Localised Outreach and Engagement Model

In connecting the Thinking the Meanwhile Circularly & Collaboratively Probe with a pre-existing project and associated network local to Euston the Probe hopes to contribute in helping to address the following challenges and opportunities identified within the Euston regeneration area through T-Factor research to date and described above:

- **Reciprocal Engagement & Building Trust and Capacity** amongst residents and other stakeholders – community-led projects local to the Euston area, some of these ‘meanwhile’, are forefronted during the event as the Circular and Collaborative Economy already in Action. This enables a sharing and support network amongst local stakeholders with institutional stakeholders in the area.
- **Aligning and Leveraging Aims and Resources** of stakeholders towards collective impact in relation to local priorities – can be exemplified by partnership working supporting delivery of meanwhile projects that address local priorities.
- **Bringing Benefits Forward** for residents and other stakeholders during the regeneration process through meanwhile delivery that addresses resident priorities and demonstrates how regeneration can help to address them.

Activity Description

‘**A Circular Economy for Somers Town**’ event on 16th November 2021 was co-organised and hosted online by UoC (BCN), UAL-CSM and STCA (London). It was a two hour event exploring the Circular and Collaborative Economy within urban regeneration processes and through pre-existing local projects.

The event formed part of the COP26 climate awareness programme of events run by Euston LC T-Factor partner STCA. It also celebrated the success of the Somers Town application to the GLA’s Future Neighbourhoods 2030 fund. The workshop was focussed around the potential of the **Chalton Street Circular Market**, which formed one part of the application to the GLA.

The event was in four parts, and the choices of speakers for Parts 2 & 3 were focussed around the themes of circular food systems, open source tool making for agriculture, sustainable transport, and also implementing circular economy policies within the public administration as these were topics considered most important in facing current challenges in Somers Town, when hosting initial planning meetings for the event.

Event Programme:

1. Initially introducing **T-Factor, STCA, the Somers Town GLA Future Neighbourhoods application, and Circular Economy principles (UoC)**, focussing around different understandings and visions of the circular economy and the potential of the urban scale as the scale for implementation
2. **Case study examples from Somers Town**, hearing from three local projects which are already implementing Circular & Collaborative Economy principles
 - a. **Your Bike Project:** Social enterprise specialising in up-cycling and cycle maintenance for all young people in the Euston area
 - b. **Camden Mobile Foodbank:** Food supplies & re-distribution to address food poverty on local estates in Somers Town
 - c. **Re-Fill Stall, Camden Council:** Camden Re-Fill market stall proposal promoting no packaging and eco items for the home
3. **Case study examples from in and around Barcelona**, hearing from four projects which are already implementing Circular & Collaborative Economy principles.
 - a. **Cuchara:** An initiative that uses food as an engine for social and cultural emancipation using cooking and eating together as a form of activism
 - b. **Espigoladors:** A non-profit organisation which fights against food waste and losses using the process of 'gleaning' food left over in fields
 - c. **Tzoumakers:** Is an open lab to cooperatively design and manufacture tools for small-scale agricultural production
 - d. **Diputació de Barcelona:** Involved in the drafting of Diputació de Barcelona's Green and Circular economy at the local scale, implementing circular economy policies within the public administration
4. **Workshop:** Topics for discussion included:
 - i. Mapping out other existing circular activities in Somers Town, and beyond
 - ii. Sharing ideas for other and new circular projects
 - iii. See if and how these project ideas could be supported by and connect with the GLA Chalton Street Circular Market project

Despite being planned for the last 20 mins of the event the workshop element was cut short due to speakers over-running; however the Miro, link below, could be used for another follow up session with some of the speakers and participants.

When/Where	16th November 2020: Talks & Workshop Online – ‘A Circular Economy for Somers Town’
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	<p>Knowledge bearer – UAL-CSM</p> <p>Providers – Open University of Catalunya</p> <p>Co-Providers – STCA, Camden Council</p>
Participants & Beneficiaries	<p>There were approximately 35-40 people at the online event 16th November.</p> <p>Hosts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UAL-CSM, UoC <p>Speakers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Somers Town Community Association, Camden Council, Your Bike Workshop, Camden Mobile Food Bank, Various Speakers from Open University of Catalonia (BCN), Cuchara (BCN), Espigoladors (BCN), Disputacio de Barcelona (BCN) <p>Attendees:</p> <p>Crick Institute, British Library, Knowledge Quarter, Global Generation, Greater London Authority, Think & Do Camden, Little Villages, Somers Town Neighbourhood Forum, The Living Centre, Students and staff from UAL-CSM + Others</p>
Insights	<p>STCA is a T-Factor Euston LC partner. Their role in the activity was local ‘hosting’ – the activity was originally planned to take place both online and in person at their project premises The Living Centre in Somers Town. The event was also planned to coincide with STCA’s pre-existing COP26 event schedule for 1st – 16th November 2021. Despite not taking place at the Living Centre in the end due to logistical difficulties, STCA helped us to ensure that the event was approachable to their networks, and they also spoke at the event, introducing Somers Town and specifically some of the challenges faced in the area around food, transport and the local environment. Together we identified local speakers who were already putting circular and collaborative economy principles into action and STCA played a crucial role in putting us in touch with local speakers.</p> <p>The activity revealed the role of Camden Council in bringing partners together to put together a strong bid for the Somers Town GLA Future Neighbourhoods 2030 application which was eventually successful. Camden Council will be working closely with local partners until March</p>

2022 when all activities must be delivered by. T-Factor has the capacity to provide continued support to this work.

The Open University of Catalonia were able to co-organise and host the Probe, bringing their extensive network and expertise of the Circular and Collaborative Economy from multiple perspectives including: small social enterprises putting principles into action, the role of the CE in the public administration and how the CE is being viewed from an academic perspective.

In **Relational** terms, it became clear through conversations between UoC/UAL-CSM and STCA that there is a need to demystify terms like the Circular and Collaborative Economy as they are deemed inaccessible to many residents and local organisations in the area. Despite already working in these ways, many do not engage with these terms themselves as it is difficult to understand how they are relevant to the everyday challenges felt on the ground such as food poverty and multiple environmental issues such as pollution, traffic and construction noise and dust. This realisation guided the decision to showcase local organisations already putting the principles into practice, tackling issues and challenges felt on the ground in a more accessible way.

In **Operational** terms, the Probe revealed that YourBike Workshop, one of the speakers at the event, had been running the social enterprise bike fixing project on and off for over 10 years. The Probe revealed that there were multiple operational struggles that his business has and continues to face including: a resilient business case including access to consistent funding, struggles to find meanwhile or permanent space both for bike storage and workshops (two of their previous sites had been earmarked for redevelopment forcing them to leave, and their current site at the Story Garden is also only temporary until the extension to the British Library begins). This story is not uncommon for projects such as this and reveals the precarity that many are facing day to day despite creating a huge amount of social value for the area.

In **Strategic** terms, the Probe revealed that there is a strong alignment between the GLA Future Neighbourhood 2030 priorities, Camden Council priorities, local priorities as defined through STCA and other local partners, and also with the Euston Pilot challenges and opportunities identified within T-Factor. All institutions involved are working on specific aspects of the Circular Economy principles of re-use, repair, recycling and zero waste in different ways and the Probe acted as a platform to share these agendas and reveal points of interest which could aid further collaboration into the future. The invitation to the event which was sent to many local networks also revealed that the KQ is currently working with UCL students as part of a Climate Action Fund project to map circular economy activity in the Knowledge Quarter and

	Somers Town – there is need to understand this in more detail and see how it could link to the Probe in the future.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event invitation / flyer • Event itself • Miro board (this did not get used in the end but will could form part of a workshop for a follow up event) • All presentations given on the day have been stored on the T-Factor G Drive • A video recording of the event, both a full length video, but also a video which has been cut down into individual speakers elements Google Form Feedback Questionnaire
Outcomes	<p>In terms of relational infrastructure the Probe helped to build trust and relationships between the stakeholders involved. The focus of the Probe enabled the shared priorities of the Circular and Collaborative Economy to be revealed between all partners involved in the event, and also with the attendees. There is now an opportunity for the T-Factor probe to become an available resource for actions around the Chalton Street Circular Market, addressing local challenges and priorities, going forward.</p> <p>In terms of operational infrastructure it must be considered that there is often an imbalance in terms of those that are able to give their time and expertise for free to speak at events – whilst it is easier for those in academia and larger businesses as they are paid a wage, it is often a stretch for smaller business especially those reliant on inconsistent funding, often volunteering their time in order to promote their project/practice.</p>

Building a Community of Practice

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Building Communities</i> ○ <i>Cultivating innovation</i> ○ <i>Growing prosperity</i>
Activity Objectives	<p>Activities attached to the Communities of Practice both at UAL-CSM and KQ are necessary to advance the exploring and inquiry phase of the project, crucially involving local residents through collaborations with different actors from the institutional and cultural sectors within the locality. In this way, cross-sector working gets embedded within the local context from the outset, and potentially opens opportunities to carry activities forward into the project's next phases.</p>

	<p>The activity responds to eight main challenges/opportunities identified by prior public consultation and engagement in the area:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - furthering and addressing diverse cultural expression, - tackling anti-social behaviour, - understanding accessibility and use of green and public spaces, - improving health and well-being, - furthering awareness about environmental issues, - providing opportunities for young people, and - increasing access to local food supplies. <p>The Probe is aimed at continuing to build the Community of Practice (CoP) in the London Euston area, drawing from the communities of the pilot and its key institutions and stakeholders. The Probe continues to build on the UAL-CSM CoP and the KQ CoP work done at London Euston to date.</p> <p>Locally the work done on the UAL-CSM CoP and KQ CoP is now being shared with residents, resident groups, local VCS organisations (such as the Citizen Social Scientists and Community Champions) and others in order to work towards and support the exploration of multi-stakeholder meanwhile use projects as part of E&I Activities in October and November 2021.</p>
Activity Description	<p>How Euston CoP was developed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UAL-CSM Interviews <p>An interview canvas was developed for mapping the UAL-CSM CoP. It explored the community of participatory arts and design practitioners at UAL-CSM and their participatory practices. The interviews were recorded and are in the process of being transcribed onto a Miro Board. This process was launched with a presentation at the beginning of T-Factor. After the interviews had been conducted there was an event on 30 April 2021 which presented the next steps of the CoPs engagement activities. There was a call for Expressions of Interest toward developing activities.</p> ● KQ Interviews <p>The Knowledge Quarter adopted the same interview canvas with some modifications to adapt it to its community. They also used the same process, recording interviews, transcribing onto Miro board as with the UAL-CSM CoP. Approximately 60 interviews have been made to date. On 18 August 2021 The KQ ran an event that mirrored the UAL-CSM CoP April event to launch the next steps and the call for Expressions of Interest.</p>

- UAL-CSM CoP workshop

UAL-CSM interview participants were assembled and the synthesised findings of the interviews shared. The results of the Euston Pilot report research were shared to familiarise the UAL-CSM CoP with the Euston context. The workshop participants were invited to make Expressions of Interest to deliver Exploring and Inquiring activities.

- Shared Findings: the expressions of interest submitted all share a desire and motivation to engage with existing local communities, build upon works they have developed and contribute towards translating residents' concerns, insights and local knowledges into diverse outputs such as film, digital archives, participation in exhibitions and poetry, for example.
- Expressions of Interest; there was enthusiastic response from the CoP as social and spatial justice are embedded within the UAL-CSM teaching, learning and research practices at various levels, as the list of submitted projects below shows.
- Projects Submitted: Projects submitted by the community of practice are divided into two basic timelines: Those to be developed between October and December 2021, and those with a longer time frame to be developed from January onwards. Some overlaps are to be expected, as projects initiated in October develop pace and evolve into more consolidated potential activities which can be integral to the project's next phase.

For the first timeline, projects submitted were:

- Gilbert Bayes Finials and the History of Somers Town: Digital and Material reconstructions (please see detailed report above)
- Open and Green Spaces: an exploration into wayfinding, story trails, reuse and recycling throughout the Regent Park Estate (See above),
- Demystifying Research: developing curatorial strategies to communicate research and widen its audiences and impact (see above)
- Digital storytelling and collective poetry with residents with different kinds of learning disabilities (See above).

For the second timeline, projects submitted were:

- An investigation into the night-time economy within the Euston Area, focused on service provision for night-time workers

- An exploration into mobility futures within the context of the new train station and HS2 developments in the area in connexion with sustainable transport alternatives
- The development of a virtual hair salon as a community space for young groups to develop new skills and shared local life experiences.

Projects submitted involve course leaders, PhD researchers and MA students and alumni from different courses and departments within UAL-CSM.

KQ CoP workshop: Shared Findings: although the initial interview phase highlighted existing research fatigue amongst residents due to extensive consultation projects which, often, did not show desired and/or responsive outcomes, it was stressed that, in its capacity as an arts school UAL-CSM could contribute by building from existing concerns and initiatives, rather than extending consultation processes locally.

Expressions of Interest: By the end of the workshop, an open call was made for the KQ Community of practice to submit expressions of interest, and a brief description of projects submitted by the UAL-CSM Community of Practice was given.

Projects submitted; two proposals were put forward:

- Poet in the City, which offered their expertise on working with collective poetry making with local groups,
- British library which in more general terms, mentioned their own expertise in community engagement and particular interest on projects involving upskilling for groups of young people.

T-Factor matchmaking – UAL-CSM x KQ: Matchmaking has been done through two channels. First, by identifying common practices, such as that of digital storytelling and collective poetry making. Common interest in translating local everyday experiences and insight into audio visual/artistic content allowed a natural match between UAL-CSM CoP and KQ CoP for the delivery of one of the proposed projects. Second, reaching out to established resident communities directly, listening to their ideas and local concerns to then match these with proposed projects, for example around positively transforming open and green spaces around the Regents Park Estate, and Euston at large.

This second channel for matchmaking was supported by STCA & Camden Participation Team are supporting development of a strategy for matchmaking with local organisations and residents and extending citizen involvement.

When/Where	<p>April 2021: Online – UAL-CSM CoP event</p> <p>August 2021: Online – KQ CoP event</p> <p>September 2021: In person – offer made to Citizen Social Scientist cohort as part of full day workshop</p> <p>October 2021: In person – offer to Regents Parks Estate Community Champions with Fitzrovia Youth in Action</p> <p>In person - offer to Somers Town History Club</p> <p>In person – UAL-CSM meetings with CoP proponents</p> <p>November 2021:</p> <p>In person - Mapping Exercise Community Champions Mapping exercise</p> <p>In person - recognition walk over area CoP + Somers Town History Club</p> <p>In person - Bayes Scanathon Workshop</p> <p>In person - Dedicated Exhibition Tour to CSS</p> <p>In person - Research Reading on hidden histories of Somers Town at Jellicoe Hall</p> <p>December 2021:</p> <p>In person - Mapping workshops with Community Champions + Ideas Swop</p> <p>In person: - Coffee morning at MIND in Camden</p> <p>Gallery Take Over by CSS - TBC</p>
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	<p>UAL-CSM</p> <p>Co-Providers: Knowledge Quarter - organising the KQ CoP with their own networks</p>
Participants & Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Citizen Social Scientists, as part of the Good Life Euston Project (alongside Camden Participation Team, Institute for Global Prosperity and Lendlease). ● Regents Park Community Champions: This is a group of approximately 20 people, with embedded connections with the larger community in the area. They convene for activities in different configurations with approximately ten to twelve people attending each meeting. For specific workshops and activities they can assemble the larger community. ● Somers Town Neighbourhood Forum / Drummond Street Neighbourhood Forum ● Mind in Camden, is a local charity providing services to support people's mental health. A group of approximately fifteen members of Mind are expected to participate in a weekly series of workshops. ● Somers Town History Club, as a long-standing local initiative led by two residents. Through their ongoing programme of events they have a strong capacity to convene local residents, with groups varying between ten to thirty people at a time, around activities designed to care for and disseminate the area's historic

	<p>heritage. Proposed projects are designed to support and enhance these programmes.</p>
Insights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Insight from UAL-CSM event: Generally, socially engaged practice by now is embedded within the community of practice at UAL-CSM, in different programmes and with initiatives led by a variety of members: PhD researchers, course leaders, associate lectures, etc. More specifically, proposed projects work better when linked with existing elements of curricula or ongoing research topics. This allows post-graduate students to get directly involved, which in turn provides more capacity for project delivery. Perhaps a direct call to research degrees, appealing to PhD students across UAL-CSM could allow for even more diverse proposals and matchmaking. ● Insights from KQ event: The KQ event summarised members experiences of public engagement with local stakeholders. There was a general understanding that residents have consultation fatigue. This insight proved useful for focusing projects and activities on specific actions, interventions, and physical contributions to the built environment, rather than extending consultation-type modes of engaging. In terms of proposals received, they were not many, perhaps due to the pandemic context which finds KQ members busy finding ways to reboot community engagement after Covid 19 prolonged lockdowns. <p>Relational: the activities undertaken so far confirm that projects work better when there is an existing trustful relationship with specific communities. Alternatively, if such trust is starting to emerge, it is key to develop a feedback loop by which weekly or fortnightly contact is put in place, so trust builds up and projects develop on the basis of common interests, continuous presence and reciprocal input.</p> <p>Operational: Generally activities develop at their own pace, and the CoP needs to be open to make adjustments and adapt to new input from the various participants. Also to be prepared to adapt their schedules and availability. Although this at times might delay action, ultimately, adapting and being flexible is key to build trust and keep activities improving and growing.</p> <p>Strategic: All projects initiated for the exploring and Inquiring phase have great potential to develop into the next phase of the project. This requires a strategic resourcing, programming and designing of the next phase to keep up with the participant communities' expectations, the CoP capacities and the T-Factor project aims.</p>

Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CoP Methodology ● Interview Canvases UAL-CSM ● UAL-CSM Report ● Interview Canvases KQ ● KQ Report ● Workshops: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ April 2021: Online – UAL-CSM CoP event ○ August 2021: Online – KQ CoP event ○ September 2021: In person – offer made to Citizen Social Scientist cohort as part of full day workshop <p>October 2021: In person – offer to Regents Parks Estate Community Champions with Fitzrovia Youth in Action</p>
Outcomes	<p>Zad Cafe – CSS: a connection match was made between Zad Cafe manager, Camden Council and UAL-CSM MArch Architecture Students to carry out design improvements for the cafe forwards. This is an important community hub, focused on women and young families, in need of care and support. This work could contribute towards the cafe programme of events, engagement capacity and long lasting presence in the area.</p> <p>Your Bike Workshop – contribution to Circular Workshop, looking at ways to reciprocate with links to free bikes in the area.</p>

5.3.4. Overview of Stakeholders

Below we provide a **preliminary** map of stakeholders and initiatives as it emerges from exploring and inquiring activities. This map is continuously evolving in sync with the progress of the activities at pilot site. The link below shall provide a dynamic overview of the evolution of the pilot as it progresses over time.

The Kumu map of all stakeholders is provided in the Figure below and it can be accessed [here](#) in its dynamic fashion.

Missing Stakeholders

Below is a list of local stakeholders that are not yet engaged in activities relating to the regeneration process or meanwhile uses. During October & November we will consider why these stakeholders are not engaged, what would motivate them to engage, and how E&I activities can help to engage them.

- Faith Groups such as:
 - Quakers Friends
 - Shahjalal Mosque
 - St. Pancras New Church
 - St. Mary's Church
 - Al Rahman Mosque

- St Aloysius Church
- Somers Town Islamic Cultural & Education Centre
- St. Mary Magdalen Church, Regents Park Estate
- Schools such as:
 - St Mary St Pancras Primary School
 - Netley Primary School
 - Maria Fidelis Catholic School
 - Regent High School
 - Christ Church Primary School
 - Regents Park Children's Centre
 - Edith Neville Primary School & Family Centre
- Business Groups in the area such as:
 - Euston & Somers Town Association of Businesses
 - Stephenson Way Group Members
 - The Wesley Group
 - Urban Partners
 - Drummond Street Traders Association
 - Local Globe
 - Euston Town BID
 - KQ
- Hard to Reach / Transient Groups:
 - Hard to Reach residents
 - Station Users
 - Visitors
 - The Homeless

5.4. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

Assembling Communities of Practice & Concern

The Exploring and Inquiring (E&I) phase in Euston has contributed to assembling 'Communities of Practice' – bringing together local organisations and residents around practices of interest – including digital model making, sketching and mapping spaces and places, and sharing stories through different media. These activities have also contributed to assembling 'Communities of Concern' or 'Publics', as different practices were applied to the exploration of different contextual issues and challenges in the regeneration area - ownership and preservation of history and heritage, recognising and supporting circular behaviours and practices, amplifying ownership and identity of public spaces. The work gave practical opportunities for the T-Factor LC to work together with residents and stakeholder organisations and demonstrate the ways that our collaboration can deliver tangible outputs that can contribute to bring benefits forward within the meanwhile of the regeneration area.

Creating Enabling Conditions for Meanwhile Missions

This phase of work also contributed towards fostering enabling conditions for the 'participatory meanwhile' activities to follow in the next phases of the Euston Pilot. Agency activities focused

on exploring *Access to Meanwhile* and *Supporting Participation in Social Action* surfaced insights and infrastructures that can support equitable and inclusive access to the spaces necessary for future meanwhile missions, as well as the support required to ensure that all those that wish to participate in meanwhile missions are able to do so whilst those that do not typically participate in such processes are encouraged and supported to join in.

Aligning Meanwhile Aims & Resourcing

The Euston Partnership and Meanwhile Use Working Group (as part of the Place & Social Value panel) is crucial for the alignment of meanwhile aims across the regeneration dutyholders. These dutyholders have the power to unlock spaces, resources and capital investments to support a participatory citizen-led meanwhile strategy in Euston. Whilst the formation of the group, which meets once a month, has drafted a Terms of Reference (to be finalised), work continues on alignment and commitment to common goals. The T Factor Activity *Access to Meanwhile Workshop* was well received by project partners, and a number of useful insights have been recorded and shared back with the group. There is scope to book in 1-2 hours with the same participants to finish the workshop in either December 2021 or January 2022.

After the Knowledge Quarter's (KQ) Community of Practice event in August there was a limited response from their members to get involved with T Factor E&I Activities (only two organisations sent through proposals). The KQ represents a large network of institutions with knowledge and resources to contribute towards citizen-led 'meanwhile missions' in the Euston Pilot. As a member of the Euston LC, it is important that the Knowledge Quarter is kept up to date with developments, both linked to the E&I activities, and also when moving into planning the S&I phase of work. It is hoped that the E&I activities can make the project more tangible to KQ members and that the active involvement of community groups in these activities can demonstrate the value of T-Factor engagement for supporting KQ organisations public engagement objectives.

Role of the Neighbourhood Forums

The two neighbourhood forums, in Somers Town and Drummond Street, are well established within their networks of both residents and organisations on either side of Euston Station. These forums can guide us to consider how we continue to try and connect with those we have not yet managed to include such as the many faith groups in the area, schools, business groups, and hard to reach and transient groups and individuals.

Collaboration with Social Action Organisations

E&I activities have enabled the T-Factor LC to engage more meaningfully with both the Community Champions of Regents Park Estate and the Euston Citizen Social Scientists, both of which are already active in Social Action and Community organising in the regeneration area. These groups are already actively identifying projects that respond to resident priorities and it is key that T-Factor continues to find ways to support implementation of these existing proposals and contributes to 'join up' efforts to bring resources of regeneration dutyholders and KQ partners to them. The Community Champions are particularly keen to widen their engagement activities to involve more of the wider Community in defining and delivering projects and T-Factor has a role to play in helping them to achieve this.

Next Steps

Scoping & Ideating

The next phase of the project, Scoping & Ideating, needs to be considered in and organised with the Euston LC with input from Agency partners in December 2021, and carried out in January & February 2022. It is still to be decided whether the S&I phase will be delivered as one large event that brings together the stakeholders engaged via E&I with CSM-UAL, Camden, STCA, KQ and Lendlease or in smaller groups linked to existing E&I clusters. The core tools that we will be using are those provided by the T-Factor Agency: a set of **forty Meanwhile Activity Cards**, two **Theory of Change Canvases**, an array of **ideation methods** selected from consolidated co-creative participatory approaches. and an.

During December it is essential that T-Factor LC (including Camden's Participation Team, Somers Town Community Association, KQ and Lendlease) work closely with the actors described above, including the Neighbourhood Forums and Social Action organisations and the Euston Partnership partners to validate and, if necessary, adapt the proposed methodology so that it can be integrated into existing approaches to meanwhile project development.

To begin with there will be a need to share the results of E&I with the Euston LC, as well as a synthesis of the insights of all previous events organised by both T-Labs and the Local Coalition. The focus of the Scoping & Ideating workshops will be to co-create an **Activity Portfolio** - including a range of prompt, regular and permanent meanwhile activities. It is crucial that we find a way to do this in person as the Euston LC has not yet met as a single group in one space, due in part to the impact of Covid on the willingness of participants to engage in group face-to-face activities as well as the volume of activities to which residents are invited to contribute as we emerged from Covid restrictions over the autumn.

Co-development of S&I activities with all LC members is essential to align S&I with other local engagement activities and avoid expecting too much citizen participation in the area.

Alignment & Integration of Ongoing Activities & T-Factor Methodology

The Activities initiated within E&I are programmed to continue until March 2021 including:

- Gilbert Bayes Finials & The History of Somers Town: Digital and Material Reconstruction
- Transforming Open & Green Spaces in London Euston
- Demystifying Research
- Digital Storytelling & Collective Poetry Making

The T-Factor LC recognises the open-ended and emergent nature of these infrastructuring activities and will work with the E&I CoP leads and partners to find ways to ensure continuity and coherence for participants as we seek to introduce them to the Scoping and Ideating phase of the project.

MILAN MIND

6. MILAN MIND

6.1. PILOT STARTING CONTEXT AND PRIORITIES

MIND is located in a suburban environment at the north-west periphery, right on the border delimited by Milan's outer ring road and connected to the city centre by tube and train. It is also located at the convergence of two main typologies of suburban space, namely small sized urban sprawls and a formerly industrialised area, which has undergone a process of deindustrialisation and is now looking for a new identity.

The regeneration project foresees the development of 480,000 sqm of public uses:

- students' accommodation, social housing and leisure, sports and cultural activities;
- 205,000 sqm will host the Public Anchors headquarters:

The Galeazzi research hospital will be completed by 2022, and will host around 9,000 staff, mainly dedicated to orthopaedics and cardiology. The Human Technopole, an international Hub connecting Universities, Research Institutes and Hospitals to develop personalized medicine and nutrition to tackle cancer and neurodegenerative diseases by means of genomics, big data analysis, will host 1,000 researchers and 500 administrative and technical staff. The scientific campus of the University of Milan Statale will host around 18,000 students and 2,000 staff. 480,000 sqm of private uses: commercial uses and offices, residential, retail, light industry and hospitality, a hotel, labs, culture and sport-related uses. At completion, in 2031 the district will host around 60,000 people a day.

MIND aims to be **an engine of economic and technological growth as well as of inclusion and sustainability, to increase the well-being of both people and the planet** by leveraging on a critical mass of public and private stakeholders committed to advance research and accelerate innovation by working together, pairing world-class know-how in specialized, high-growth potential areas and an open-innovation, cross-sectoral, multi-disciplinary approach.

MIND is being built around two main clusters:

City of the Future - a large-scale demonstrator proving a strong community can already be totally carbon neutral and soon carbon negative. MIND partners are developing the new district with a view of turning it into a living-lab where new technologies, products, services, processes and projects aimed at improving human wellbeing and sustainable practices can be tested and scaled. Since December 2019 Lendlease has further developed the masterplan and defined their Carbon targets:

- o Net Zero Carbon Scope by 2025 (net zero – means with compensation)
- o Absolute Carbon Zero by 2040 ('Absolute zero' means no compensation in any of the 3 Scopes).

Life Science - an extensive network of research-intensive companies, multinationals, SMEs, start-ups, top international researchers, professors, doctors, and patients for experimenting and testing

innovative solutions, all in one place. The three main strands are: from patient to citizen journey; digitization and digitalization of the health sector, Technology Transfer and Open Innovation.

The Masterplan promotes the priorities of walkability and innovative mobility to enhance its environment and the well-being of its population. A mix between functions through a common ground will ensure outdoor working areas to boost creativity; a character of residential courtyards applied to the main public area such as the Decumano; a clear view of nature for each resident by the creation of continuous green infrastructures, public spaces with a feeling of intimacy fostering people's gathering, and an easy access to water.

6.1.1. Issues

A number of key issues are to be addressed within the regeneration area, centred around its geographical position and the nature of the development itself.

Accessibility (MIND as a distant and difficult area to reach)

Impact Domains

- Making Places

MIND is perceived, and to a certain extent rightly so, a distant and uneasy area to reach. From a Milan-centered perspective, MIND is located at the outskirts of the city, and it is not considered part of it, despite the fact that it takes 10 minutes by regional train from Milan Central train station and about 40 minutes by tube. As for the surrounding municipalities (such as Rho, Baranzate, Pero, Gallarate) MIND is in fact, an uneasy area to reach without a car. Despite Expo 2015 attracting more than 150.000 visitors every day, mobility has not improved and connections within the local suburban areas are still lacking or insufficient. Furthermore, the massive presence of the railway and highway infrastructures together with abandoned brownfields and small rural areas around the site represent important physical barriers to the area generating an "island effect" which need to be addressed. Finally, as of today, there is only one semi-public access to the site, which is from "Cargo 6". This restricts the engagement opportunities for the surrounding neighbours.

Perceived Exclusiveness (Make MIND a place for everyone)

Impact Domains

- Building Communities
- Making Places

MIND is the first innovation district of this scale in Italy focusing on life sciences and the design of the city of the future. It has been designed to attract an extensive network of research-intensive companies, multinationals, SMEs, start-ups, top international researchers, and academics, which will be all in one place for experimenting and testing innovative solutions. For that reason MIND can appear as an exclusive destination. However, first and foremost, MIND aspires to become a lively city district ahead-of-the-times lifestyles to create social, cultural and economic growth and to serve people's well-being. This is an issue to be addressed and a threat to be mitigated.

6.1.2. Challenges and Opportunities

Challenge 1 - What is MIND? Develop a Glocal Identity.

MIND is the Milan Innovation District of Milan but very few know what it means, except for those companies who have been already engaged. For many, especially the general public, it is not clear what MIND is and what it will become, how it will generate new opportunities for the inhabitants of Milan as well as for the surrounding communities. There is the need to communicate and present MIND as well as creating a new glocal identity.

Challenge 2 - Change People's Perception on Accessibility

MIND's accessibility is and will be until the completion of the regeneration project one of the major challenges. Physical barriers exist and the lack of transport solutions, less to say green solutions, to access the site from the immediate surroundings is a well-known issue. Nonetheless, alternatives exist but people's perception is still hard to overcome. There is the need to work on MIND's porosity.

Challenge 3 - Building Trust

While the EXPO2015 strongly contributed to raise the visibility of the City of Milan, the surrounding municipalities and communities did not benefit as much from the success of the international exhibition. This is still a complex and challenging sub-urban area, mainly because of its spatial and socio-economic fragmentation (high youth unemployment rates, former industrial workers struggle to cope with rising property prices, Bollate prison at the north edge of MIND). On the other hand Bollate and Rho are very active municipalities, initiating a number of activities. From a local point of view, MIND represents both an opportunity - the chance to improve and develop trustworthy relationships with its neighbours and revitalize the whole area - and a threat - attracting only external highly specialised jobs while further contributing to gentrification phenomena. There is the need to work towards an open dialogue and an engagement becoming more reciprocal in approach.

Challenge 4 - Manage Expectations

EXPO2015 legacy with regards to local engagement is unfortunately not one of positive take-aways. Ensuring continuity and managing expectations remain key challenges to the successful re-development of the area. Once trust is gained, and a communication channel is established, as it starts to happen with the activities of Fondazione Triulza and the educational project of Arexpo, as well as the interactions among the developer and the future tenants, it is important not to let down people's expectations.

Challenge 5 - Administrative Limitations for Temporary Spaces

The regulation for temporary use of spaces by the Municipality of Milan differs based on the duration of the use: below 24hrs, a self-declaration to the Municipality is enough to organize the activity; between 1 and 90 days, for public venues under 200 people, the applicant must submit, within 12 days before the event, an application; above 90 days a proper building permit or change in use procedures is required. Consequently, temporary activities and installations should be perceived as such and cannot last more than 6 months in total according to the

municipality regulation. That sets the baseline for the use of construction materials. For example, timber and cardboard should be chosen upon concrete or drywall, even if only used for a temporary installation and define the type of installations and furniture, which should be always movable. There is need to plan meanwhile uses to follow these administrative guidelines, which would entail for example moveable installations and pop-up interventions or start a co-creating approach with the Municipality to adopt sandboxes.

Challenge 6 - Funding

The funding ecosystem in Milan and Lombardy provides ample options within the domain of arts, culture and urban developments. However, there are not a lot of budgets allocated specifically to meanwhile uses and precisely the initiatives that are in need of additional funds, do not always have enough capacity to dedicate to the complex web of funding options - which amplifies the need for a distinctive funding strategy and program.

Challenge 8 - Adaptability of Meanwhile Activities

MIND is a worksite in continuous development. Thus, meanwhile spaces and activities should be foreseen as adaptable and flexible to the worksite development.

Opportunity 1 - Mending the Territory, Fostering Local Competences, and Attracting New Ones

Small local businesses might not be prepared to respond to such an innovative and ambitious project. It is crucial that the development of MIND does not only concentrate on bringing new businesses and tenants to the area, but it also seizes the opportunity to support existing entrepreneurial networks (e.g. foster adaptability and support capacity building in their operations) and create new opportunities, from jobs to training. MIND should aim at leveraging on, and valorising, the competences, and activities already in the area, combining them with new ones. MIND could work together with local community organisations to co-create a space of reconciliation becoming a collector of international excellence and local expertise. Another opportunity is represented by the numerous local associations and by the two active municipalities of Bollate and Rho. A lot of social capital and transversal competences are already available in the area.

Opportunity 2 - Turn the Physical Barriers into Connective Fringes

MIND is located within the Milanese greenbelt and represents a cornerstone in the connection between the Parco Agricolo Sud and the Parco delle Groane. It gives continuity to the park system of western Milan. The waterways of the site are part of a set of interventions aimed at improving the landscape and the environment of the Naviglio Grande's open spaces. The site benefits from a unique network of connections with the rest of the city but these must be improved. The construction of canals reached Milan in 1258 and was made navigable by 1272. Initially intended for irrigation, it quickly developed for goods transportation upriver to Lake Maggiore and Switzerland and back. The canal was also used for transporting the marble for the Duomo when construction began in 1386. It is believed that Leonardo da Vinci was commissioned by the City to review the canal system and proposed improvements to the docks. To provide the Expo construction site and Expo Exhibition with water supply, the 'Via D'Acqua project' was proposed aiming at connecting Villoresi canal to Naviglio Grande canal

for irrigation purposes to provide 2.0 m³/s during irrigation season to agricultural areas to the southwest of Milan. The “Via D’Acqua” project should have been completed for the EXPO 2015, but the south branch was not completed, and the Municipality of Milan has suspended the project for the completion of the missing section for various reasons. The park, green areas and the water canal circling MIND secure a natural and immediate connection with the surrounding municipalities and should be further exploited to establish and foster relationships and opportunities in/out MIND.

Opportunity 3 - Attract a Diverse Audience and Create Opportunities for Vulnerable Groups

At completion, in 2031, the district will host around 60,000 people a day: the Galeazzi research hospital will host around 9,000 staff, mainly dedicated to orthopaedics and cardiology; the Human Technopole 1,000 researchers and almost 500 administrative and technical staff; finally, the scientific campus of the University of Milan Statale which will be completed in 2026 and will host around 18,000 students and 2,000 staff. Besides researchers and workers, MIND will offer residential, retail, light industry and hospitality, hotel, labs, culture and sport-related premises and uses, which means MIND will offer an array of opportunities targeting a diversified audience: children and families, young people, high schools’ students and students from other universities, start-ups and local community organisations and SMEs. As already explored and successfully demonstrated by 2 community projects - MIND Education by Arexpo, and the Social Innovation Academy by Fondazione Triulza- T-Factor can contribute to boost the engagement with the communities of young entrepreneurs and young people, especially NEETs, vulnerable groups and minorities.

Opportunity 4 - Research & Innovation Dissemination and Citizens Science initiatives

Ahead-of-the-times research, innovation and experimentation will characterise MIND before the completion of the regeneration project. For the developer as well as for the anchors and tenants it is imperative that the knowledge and expertise produced in MIND becomes accessible to the wider public, which includes policymakers. This offers unique opportunities to develop ways to not only share content but to design tools and approaches to establish a dialogue to inform, co-create and share knowledge.

Opportunity 5 - Strong Commitment and Support from the Developer and Anchors

Both MIND private developer, LendLease, and public Anchors, UniMi, Galeazzi and Human Technopole, are engaged and committed in supporting the design and development of meanwhile uses and engagement activities that would support the creation of a MIND community that not only include the community of companies and researchers on site but reach out MIND’s boundaries. In fact, the Village has been designed since the beginning in the masterplan with a meanwhile function; and MIND Education, entering its 5th season has been involving students from local schools (including some at regional level) in co-creation activities for the future of MIND. We can rely on diverse and capable stakeholders.

6.1.3. Needs

Accessibility and Attractivity of the Area

At this stage of the regeneration project, accessibility to the site and the capability to attract a diverse target audience are key to the success. The masterplan will improve the access routes, improving connections with existing cycle paths, planning new bus stops and offering green mobility solutions to circulate on site from the main entry points, both train and metro station and car parks. In the meantime, there is the need to facilitate access to the site and despite the construction site, offer a seamless and enjoyable experience to those who come to visit MIND. Not only is it important to offer adequate mobility services, likewise it is working to change the general perception on accessibility. From the EXPO2015 experience and other mainstream events which took place at MIND after the EXPO (X-Factor, many concerts) it is fair to say that the type of content offered, and the audience targeted could make people overcome the difficulty of accessing the site. Meanwhile uses, and later community activities on site would need to respond to the needs of the citizens, of those living and working in MIND, as well as offering unique content.

Meanwhile Uses to Include Different Target Audiences

MIND needs to become a destination not only for high-specialised researchers and big companies, but also and especially for the larger community starting from the immediate surroundings. There is a need to engage more diverse actors in order to gain an understanding of how they see value in the project. There is a need to understand what different groups would want to see in terms of activating the area – not only in terms of green and open spaces for sports or outdoor educational activities, but also looking ahead at ways to collaborate and start a dialogue with the network of actors that would populate MIND.

Green Spaces to Promote Innovation and Serve People's Wellbeing

Green and open spaces represent the immediate and tangible point of contact with the local communities (residents and business) and MIND. Once the masterplan is completed, green areas in MIND will cover more than 50% of the whole area. Such an important presence of greenery offers diverse opportunities to carry out educational programmes as well as recreational activities supporting the promotion of more healthy lifestyles, one of the core missions of MIND. How working on green spaces activities can be used to start and enable a trustworthy relationship and open collaboration with the surrounding communities?

Reducing Distance between University / Private Sector / Decision-makers / Civil Society

There is the need to create a common ground between the research and private sector, the decision-makers and the civil society. MIND could offer the perfect setting to explore new ways to collaborate as well as matching bottom-up capacity building.

6.2. MEANWHILE SPACES AND USES

The map below shows the location of existing, planned and potential meanwhile spaces and uses within the MIND regeneration area over the period of the T-Factor project.

6.2.1. Existing Meanwhile Spaces and Uses

In MIND there are a few existing spaces that have been already used for meanwhile activities despite not being designed as proper meanwhile spaces.

Cascina Triulza

Cascina Triulza is mentioned for the first time, as "Cascina Triulza", in a document of 1346. As part of the division of the Milanese territory into parishes, it belonged to the Pieve di Trenno. It is part of the important historical, architectural and environmental heritage of Milan's farmsteads, traditional rural buildings in Milan and Lombardy, covering an area of 7,900 square metres. After extensive renovation, Cascina Triulza in 2015 hosted the first Civil Society Pavilion in the history of Universal Expositions, with over 1500 events, shows and workshops. It is located in the "Municipio 8" of the city of Milan. The ground floor is used for events and meetings, while the second floor hosts the operational headquarters of Triulza Foundation. The external facade is made in glass so that it is possible to see what is happening inside also from people outside. Since that time, it has been managed by Triulza Foundation, a group of 70 organisations of national and international importance, in collaboration with Arexpo S.p.A. Triulza Foundation intends to be the privileged place to represent the requests and proposals of Civil Society and Third Sector organizations, favor the encounter between different cultures, and to welcome and include various social subjects starting with the most disadvantaged. It encourages the active participation of citizens, especially young generations, and carries out educational events, workshops, and debates on the UN SGDs.

Cascina Triulza is located on the west side of Decumano in MIND, in front of the actual offices of Arexpo and Lendlease.

<https://fondazionetriulza.org/cose-cascina-triulza/>

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Private building
Type of meanwhile use	Workspace & co-working; Education & training; Organized Civil society aggregation point
Stakeholders involved and roles	Fondazione Triulza: owner and manager of the place Stripes Digitus Lab : International Centre for Research and Innovation on educational robotics and digital technologies. The activities of Stripes involve primary and secondary school students, teachers, educational professionals, adults. Pedagogy and technology meet and give life to courses, workshops and campuses to develop new ideas, approaches and tools.
Target groups	Children & Families, Young people and Students;; NGOs; Local and National associations.
Temporality	Stable - since 2015. After extensive renovation, Cascina Triulza in 2015 hosted the first Civil Society Pavilion in the history of Universal Expositions, with over 1500 events, shows and workshops.
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	Shared interest on the issues of sustainability, nature, community offers opportunity for co-organising public events, such as walks, tours and workshops. Organisations of the Fondazione Triulza network have been involved in the Ecosystem Mapping carried out in September and October.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

The HIVE

The Hive is a polyfunctional place of more than 300 sqm organised on two floors: ground floor dedicated to a public space (114 sqm) and multifunctional (59 sqm) equipped with almost 50 seats and big screens for events and workshops; the second floor is mainly dedicated to offices and co-working space. The co-working desks can be used prior booking on “Hosts” platform owned and managed by CBRE - community manager- and available by any MIND guest. More in detail, the Hive is organised in flexible spaces: the Arena, the MIND Hub, the Atelier, the Theatre, and the Garden. The Hive welcomes visitors and gives primary information of the site and its rules. The Hive has been conceived to respond to modern need and thus, as modular and flexible, adaptable not only to the succession of numerous start-ups and professionals who will animate the offices, but also to the different working methods of the contemporary scenario. Moreover, the Biophilic design of the Hive aims to incorporate natural stimuli into the artificial environment to restore and enhance mental and physical well-being. Indeed, a specific botanical bio-filtration system will improve air quality (that is why the Hive is also named “the Air Factory”) and the simple exposure to indoor greenery and the smart use of plants will have a positive impact on creative performance and people’s wellbeing.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Private space
Type of meanwhile use	Reception; Workspace & co-working; Training and Workshops
Stakeholders involved and roles	<p>Lendlease- owner of the space</p> <p>Lombardini22: Designer of the space (Landscape and Urban architecture)</p> <p>DDLab: Digital Design Lab, part of Lombardini22</p> <p>FUD Factory: Communication and Design company, part of Lombardini22</p> <p>CBRE: Community and Property Manager. Its role is to support start-ups and companies located at the MIND Village with logistics and red tape, programmes, as well as providing information related to real estate.</p> <p>Start-ups, Students, and professionals - beneficiaries of the space</p> <p>Civil Society - beneficiary of the space</p>
Target groups	Startuppers and businesses, Researchers & Academics, Artists & Creatives, Students and Civil Society
Temporality	From March/ April 2022, Stable
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	<p>Meanwhile initiatives might be included in the program of the Hive managed by the community manager: CBRE.</p> <p>CBRE can support the project in organising events involving the tenants of the village due to the shared interest of activating the community.</p>
Relation to T-Factor	Informed/ possibly Engaged in the future (CBRE is engaged in TF activities)

6.2.2. Planned Meanwhile Spaces and Uses

Planned meanwhile spaces in MIND so far are represented by open space, such as the Park and the Decumano. However, since MIND is in constant change and the availability of spaces is not guaranteed, the possibility of building temporary and moveable spaces for meanwhile activities has emerged. T-Factor Local Coalition has been considering this option for meanwhile activities to be developed during the project.

Park (“Parco del Cibo e della Salute”)

The park of Food and Health (Parco del Cibo e della Salute) is a 35,000 smq area currently used as a car park. It is located in the northern side of Decumano, right behind the Cascina Triulza and in front of the MIND Village. The landowner is Arexpo, who granted a concession to Lendlease for the management of that area. The design and planning of new green areas/spaces requires the engagement of the municipalities: the municipality of Milan and Rho have been involved in the early planning phase of that area and, specifically, with regard to a

section of the park that will remain a property of the City of Milan while managed by Leandlease. The park is linked to the opening of the Westgate, set for the second half of 2024. Nevertheless a section will be temporarily open from April 2022, with the opening of the MIND Village. In the Masterplan, the Park will also serve workers willing to work in the open air, disposing of various benches and seats.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Prior to becoming a park, the area was partly used as a car park and just a small section of the land was dedicated to green wild areas.
Type of meanwhile use	Green & garden; Health / sport; Food & drink; Leisure
Stakeholders involved and roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arexpo - owner of the space • Lendlease - private developer and manager • Milan Municipality - future owner of a portion of the land • Fondazione Triulza: it is committed to carry out some engagement activities with the civil society in the park. So far, they won a call by Fondazione Nord Milano to study models of governance for green urban areas and parks. • LAND - it is planning the infrastructures (benches, tables, ...) for the temporary use of the park in 2022 and 2023.
Target groups	Startuppers and businesses, Researchers & Academics, Artists & Creatives, Makers & Artisans, Civil Society
Temporality	From March/April 2022. Stable
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	One of the T-Probes in MIND focuses on Health, Environment and Sustainability. The park will be an interesting place for T-Factor activities to be used in the next months, especially if organised in partnership with Fondazione Triulza.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Decumano

The Decumanus ("Decumano") is the main axis of MIND that crosses the entire site from east to west. It is a very long (1.5 Km) and wide (50 mt) road that divides MIND North-South. The Decumano has not changed neither its function nor the name after Expo2015. Indeed, it originally divided the north pavilions from the south ones, helping visitors to find their way around the area among experiences, events and exhibitions. As in ancient Rome, together with the Cardo, the Decumano divided a camp into various square lots that were assigned to individual settlers. During the Expo 2015 the road was mainly pedestrian, as no cars were allowed. Today, 10 meters in width are dedicated to pedestrians, while the remaining are used for the transit of electric small buses, owned by MIND. In 2022, part of the Decumano will be

incorporated into the Park, “Parco del Cibo e della Salute”, becoming the perfect place to organise temporary events for young people and families.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Decumano was (and still is) a street that crosses and connects the site from east to west. It is a transition space. While during Expo only people could trample the road, surrounded by the 139 international pavilions and greenery, with the advent of MIND the road was opened to cars, and small electric buses, and people have a dedicated sidewalk.
Type of meanwhile use	Open area; Street
Stakeholders involved and roles	The Decumano is owned by Arexpo and managed by Lendlease. LAND- working on the installations, especially on the benches and seats <u>Mario Cucinella Architects</u> - working on the installations
Target groups	Everyone who is allowed to enter the site
Temporality	2015 Prompt and Regular
Opportunities for Exploring and Inquiring activities	The Decumano is the main asset for temporary activities being an open air and large space which is not under construction so far. The main idea is to transform its primary function, transition, into an experience for the visitors. Supported by the WayFinding Strategy of Migliore & Servetto, the Decumano might become the opportunity to take a journey, explore new meanings, and make a new experience. So doing, the road is transformed: from a mere infrastructure connecting two spots, it becomes an experimental journey. The street painting by Andreco and possible related activities of community engagement will take place on the Decumano.
Relation to T-Factor	Engaged

Hortus

The Hortus was named as such during Expo 2015. It is now the portion of land in between the two buildings called “Stecche”. The area will be mainly dedicated to sport and leisure activities.

Type of space (prior to meanwhile use)	Prior to the advent of MIND, that stretch of land did not have a specific function.
Type of meanwhile use	Open area; Green; Sport and Leisure.
Stakeholders involved and roles	Arexpo - Owner of the area Lendlease - manager of the area
Target groups	Everyone who is allowed to enter the site

Planned												
Sports and Wellness activities - Workout w/ Nike trainer												
Street Painting												
Dynamic Wayfinding & Urban (Artistic) Installations												
Innovation Talks												

*light blue: not officially defined yet

Existing Engagement Activities

Tenant Symposium

Impact Domain

- Building community

The activity started in May 2021 and is organised by Lendlease. The aim of the tenant symposium meetings is to initiate the people who will be the first to work on the site, the so-called Village tenants, to the complexity of the ecosystem and to its broader mission. Operatively, Tenants Symposium comprises a series of meetings, so far only virtual due to Covid restrictions, in which different actors already working in MIND were invited both to describe the history of MIND, its mission and their role within the ecosystem, as well as to talk about relevant topics for the future of the site, such as the importance of the EU funding opportunities; PNRR, what is Federated Innovation and who is part of it, etc.

Highlights of the activity	
Stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MIND Village tenant - primary beneficiaries of the activity. • Lendlease - organiser and manager of the activity • Arexpo, HT, Fondazione Triulza, Galeazzi Hospital, Cariplo Factory and other partners of the activity 	Relation to T-Factor Engaged
Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities PlusValue and PoliMi organised a workshop with the Village Tenants to explore the opportunities and resources that these stakeholders are bringing at MIND. The workshop coincides with an activity of Exploring and inquiring of T-Factor.	

Social Innovation Academy and Campus

Impact Domains

- Building Community
- Cultivating Innovation

The Social Innovation Academy was officially inaugurated in 2018 by Triulza Foundation. Its scope is to test and develop new training and design proposals in all areas of social innovation and sustainable development and to stimulate contamination between knowledge and actors in the territory. The Social Innovation Academy is in fact a space for co-design and collaboration open to the wider community: Third Sector and Civil Economy organisations, Philanthropic Organisations, Universities and Research Centres, Public Institutions, Finance and Companies interested in promoting innovation and social impact. Since 2019, the Academy promotes the Social Innovation Campus, the annual event (February) on social innovation held by Fondazione Triulza for students. The campus is based on two trends: the interest of the young generations in supporting or choosing businesses that have a positive impact on society and the real difficulties encountered in Italy and Europe in getting DSI (Digital Social Innovation) projects and organisations off the ground. It includes activities such as hackathon, contests, debates, interactive labs, thematic workshops, international testimonials.

Technology is changing the way we live and work. Young generations, but not only, need to be guided through the jobs of the future. The Campus offers the opportunity to discover these new jobs directly from the voice of those who work in innovative sectors, from university til big multinational. Indeed, the Innovation Campus hosts international testimonials promoting moments and opportunities for contamination and co-design among generations and provides the occasion to different worlds to pursue together the 17 sustainability objectives of the 2030 Agenda in the concrete context of MIND.

Link: <https://www.sicampus.org/sicampus-2021/programma-culturale/>

<i>Highlights of the activity</i>	
<p>Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Triulza Foundation - promoter and organiser • Milanese Universities - partner • Third Sector associations (such as Caritas, Banco Alimentare), Philanthropic organisations such as Bank Foundations, and NGOs - partner • Private companies (such as Intesa San Paolo, Unicredit)- partner • Students - final beneficiaries 	<p>Relation to T-Factor</p> <p>Engaged</p>
<p>Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities</p> <p>Fondazione Triulza showed wide interest in taking part in T-Factor activities, willing to be an active subject from the beginning and complementing its activities with T-Factor. Fondazione Triulza has been involved in the Exploring and Inquiring activities organised so far, both as a gatekeeper and a participant. In the next phases of the project, Fondazione Triulza will be kept involved and possibly engaged in other co-creative activities.</p>	

MIND Education

Impact Domains

- *Cultivating Innovation*
- *Building Communities*

Mind Education is the annual program that involves students in the creation of innovative and original projects for the Milan Innovation District. MIND Education started in 2018. Since its first edition, it involved almost 5.000 students (primary, secondary, high schools, and university) both from the Municipalities around MIND and the Municipality of Milan. Previous editions explored projects such as the creation of the MIND brand licensing strategy, Data collection and storage in MIND, as well as imaging the city of the future and jobs of the future. At the end of every year, a final event where projects' outputs are presented, and a winner is awarded is organised. A cash prize is provided for the winners. The programme stimulates young generations to “think big” and to learn about jobs of the future, overcoming for example gender stereotypes. Moreover, this program helps the young generation to get in contact with MIND as a new part of the city, as a place of the future.

<i>Highlights of the activity</i>	
<p>Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arexpo: Initiator and Coordinator • Fondazione Triulza: Initiator and partner • Lendlease: Partner and contributor • Human Technopole Foundation: Partner and contributor • Galeazzi Hospital: Partner and contributor • University of Milan: Partner and contributor • Joint Research Center (EU): Partner • Students from primary, secondary and high schools, as well as university. They are the: first beneficiaries of the educational programme. • Università Bocconi: Partner • NABA- Nuova Accademia delle Belle Arti: Partner • Università VITA San Raffaele: Partner 	<p>Relation to T-Factor Engaged</p>
<p>Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities</p> <p>The MIND Education “Call for Ideas” to be launched in November 2021 will concern the MIND Park and green spaces in MIND. Students will be involved in piloting new ideas for the Park. Moreover, in this year’s edition the challenge for university students addresses the topic of Meanwhile Uses. Arexpo, which has been involved in the T-Factor mapping analysis as one of the main stakeholder, suggested to include meanwhile uses as part of the programme event. Within that context, the Local Coalition will be open to analyse together with Arexpo and Lendlease future “meanwhile” participatory ideas for the community carried out by students.</p>	

Open House Milano (OHM)

Impact Domain

- *Building Communities*

The event takes place yearly all over Milan since 2015. The city has been divided according to the ancient criterion of the Sestieri: 6 areas that develop along the lines of the historic gates, from the centre to the suburbs, to discover the urban (sustainable) development of the city. During OHM it is possible to visit buildings that are normally not accessible to the public, in order to get to know and rediscover Milan's modern and contemporary architectural heritage, the transformation that the city is undergoing and the artistic and cultural wealth that has characterized it since ancient times. The event promotes the concept of citizens participation to encourage dialogue between public and private, between citizenship and business and

increase the sense of belonging to the city. Lendlease participates in the 6th edition of OHM (25-26 of September 2021) presenting its offices in Moscova, Palazzo Montecatini, designed by the popular architect Gio Ponti in 1963, and touring around MIND with a close group of citizens. It is the first time that a group of visitors, fully external to MIND, make a (guided) tour in MIND.

The Open House event organised by Lendlease in MIND aims at gradually opening MIND to a wider community. Indeed, for the first time MIND will open its doors to the citizens of Milan and the municipalities around which are interested to discover more about the new-born area. The scope of that kind of event is to start communicating MIND, avoiding becoming an isolated place or to be communicated prejudicially. MIND wants indeed to become a new area of the city of Milan, capturing the attention of new partners and future investors and attracting people that will populate the area in the next months.

Highlights of the activity	
<p>Stakeholders</p> <p>The event is organised by the Open House Milano Association, under the patronage of Milan Municipality, Lombardy Region, Senato della Repubblica, Chamber of Architects, and Idealista as the main partner. Every year public bodies and associations as well as private companies and organisations can apply to participate by opening their spaces and venues to the wider public. In 2021 joined Open House Lendlease for the first time.</p>	<p>Relation to T-Factor</p> <p>Mapped</p>
<p>Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities</p> <p>OHM was an interesting opportunity for the E&I phase because it paved the way to the Guided Tour that the Local Coalition is organising in MIND the 4th of November 2021. The guided tour organised by the Local Coalition is an exclusive tour of the MIND site that sees key representatives for each anchor explaining the mission, the history and the future of their organisation. It is open first, to the Village tenants, Third Sector and institutional players, then to the general public. The main scope is to give a sort of “preview” of the area before the formal opening in March/April 2022. Local coalition coordinator exchanged with the person in MIND who developed the tour for OHM to better organise T-Factor’s Guided Tour. If the initiative is well received by the public, it should be discussed with Lendlease and Arexpo about the possibility to reproduce it as a more regular event in the next months.</p>	

Planned Engagement Activities

Workout Sessions with a Nike trainer

Impact Domain

- Improving Health & Wellbeing

Lendlease is about to launch a series of workout activities held in the Media Hall of MIND once a week from December 2021. The courses are carried out by a popular Nike trainer, Paolo Zotta, and are open to employees of the Anchors of MIND. Starting from January 2022, training sessions will be held twice a week with the opportunity to also practice a YOGA course. The Media Hall is not set up for sports activities, but to date it is the only space accessible to everyone that is not an office. People working in MIND expressed the need for training after

work. Working sessions as well as being a sports moment for personal well-being, are a moment of aggregation and therefore an activity for community development and activation.

<p>Stakeholders Lendlease, Arexpo, Human Technopole, Galeazzi employees - beneficiaries</p>
<p>Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities During the first Ecosystem Mapping activity (part of E&I) carried out with the Third Sector associations, sport associations, namely US (Unione Sportiva) ACLI and CSI (“Centro Sportivo Italiano) took part to the round table and expressed their interest in taking part to likely future activities to be developed on site involving their target groups, and expressly youngsters, who have suffered the most from isolation because of the Covid pandemic.</p>

Dynamic wayfinding & Urban (Artistic) Installations

Impact Domain

- Making Places

Lendlease commissioned Migliore Servetto to design the wayfinding strategy for the Village area and the Decumano. Dynamic wayfinding is a technique that allows dynamically referring to people in an area, by targeting information and responding to current situations such as events, activities or diversions. It is “dynamic” as it can change over time. The strategy responds to the necessity to guide the first batch of visitors through the complexity of such a dispersive area like MIND today. Having clear directions to reach specific buildings or plazas can help the visitor to fully experience the area, without wasting energy to check the correct route on the map, for example. A good wayfinding experience is then reflected in the final perception of the visitor in the area. The strength of dynamic wayfinding in a regeneration project of such big dimensions is that it can continuously change depending on the development of the site. In some ways, it can also be fun for the visitor to experience the site differently each time, as long as the wayfinding is explanatory and accompanies the visitor along the route in an optimal way.

<p>Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migliore Servetto - developer of the strategy. Independent global design firm based in Milan • Lendlease - owner and final decision maker • MIND Visitors - final beneficiaries
<p>Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities During the Exploring and Inquiring phase carried out by the Local Coalition from January 2022, the dynamic wayfinding strategy can be designed and tested. Officially, the strategy and its related ideas will be released at the end of March with the MIND Village opening.</p>

Street Painting

Impact Domain

- Building Communities

Street Painting is part of the artistic activation strategy of the area. The idea was launched by Lendlease to illustrate the 1.5 km of Decumano. The Decumano is a long road that people are obliged to travel through if they want to reach the MIND Village area and the entire site from west to east. So, to overcome the temporarily lack of retail services and attractions along that stretch of road, the strategy is to create artistic and creative spots on the ground, perhaps accompanied by exhibition boards or virtual experiences. The biggest challenge is to define the strategy that accompanies the visitor along the journey, pausing for a moment and living the experience. Conversations between Lendlease and a popular artist, Andreco, who already worked on a site specific painting in Manifattura Tabacchi, Florence, in June 2020, are ongoing. Andreco's artistic research is focused on the relation between humans and nature and between the built environment and the natural landscape. For that reason, one valuable idea is to provoke visitors with a global issue, such as climate change. What's more, reflecting the mission of the site of absolute zero carbon, Andreco does not use chemical colors in his artistic performances. The activity will take place in conjunction with the opening of the Village area, possibly April 2022.

Stakeholders

- Lendlease - manager
- Migliore Servetto- LL consultant for activation strategy
- Andrea Conte aka Andreco + other 10 popular artist(s)- participant of the activity as performers

Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities

Street Painting is a very good engagement activity that can be used also for future E&I activities. Street painting targets mainly a specific group of stakeholders: youngsters, but the whole performance might engage a wider population. On the one hand, from January to March 2022, T-Factor may support Lendlease to organize this activity as a participatory occasion. On the other hand, the LC can think of a similar activity, such as a wall painting contest dedicated to youngsters, exploiting empty spaces and streets on a dedicated part of the Decumano and exploring the identity of the place.

Innovation Talks

Impact Domain: Building Communities

Innovation Talks are informal gatherings among people from different backgrounds aimed at opening up discussions and debates on actual and relevant innovative themes, mainly related with Life Science; Health; Technology and Innovation. These gatherings take the form of informal aperitifs where, after a speech of some relevant national or international actors on diverse topics, people can relax and chat. Indeed, it is proved that innovation is quite often the result of informal gatherings, in which the share of information is higher and more fluid than in official meetings. People feel free to express their identity and speak up. This sometimes opens up new opportunities to be explored. MIND is a large innovation district populated in the next months by many people from different educational, cultural and working backgrounds. Being such a big place, makes new encounters difficult. The challenge thus is creating new opportunities for innovation, that comes from the encounter of different disciplines and ideas. Thus, nudging researchers, doctors, professors, entrepreneurs, to meet

in a relaxing environment all in one place once a month, can be a good trigger for future cooperation and co-production in the District.

<p>Stakeholders Anchors - promoter and organizers and beneficiaries, Researchers, Students; Employees from the Anchors</p>
<p>Opportunities for Exploring & Inquiring Activities These gatherings might be a regular activity for MIND, aimed at monitoring interests of the stakeholders and opening up high level debates at the level of the internal community of MIND.</p>

6.3.2. T-Factor Exploring and Inquiring Activities

To date, the only exploring and inquiring activities pursued by the T-Factor Local Coalition are those of the Exploring and Inquiring station. Other engagement activities aimed at getting a better understanding of the community and its needs have been developed by other stakeholders, such as Lendlease, are described in the “Planned/Existing Engagement Activities and Stakeholders Involved” chapter.

6.3.3. Exploring and Inquiring Support Activities and T-Labs Probes

This section describes the Activities (supported by Agency partners) and Probes (supported by T-Labs) implemented within the Exploring and Inquiring stage of the MIND Pilot.

Timeline

KNOWLEDGE BEARER	ACTIVITIES	Jul21	Aug21	Sep21	Oct21	Nov21	Dec21	Jan22	Feb22	Mar22
POLIMI	Ecosystem Mapping									
	Pre-mapping and design of the exploration sessions									
	Stakeholders’ engagement, planning and realization of sessions									
	Map finalization and definition of the Meanwhile Community of Practice									
POLIMI	Guided Tours									
	Tour design and planning									
	Engagement of guides and communication to audience									
	Tour production and realization									

LAND	Alternative Mapping									
Itinerary planning and approval by MIND's LC and Lendlease										
Engagement of local associations and target stakeholders and communication										
Implementation of the walks/rides										
Postproducing and mapping activity										

Ecosystem Mapping

Impact domain(s)	Building Communities
Activity Objectives & related needs	As one of the main challenges is to convey MIND's identity as an inclusive area for the surrounding communities, businesses and institutions, this activity aims to identify and potentially involve MIND's internal and external stakeholders to activate the broader communities in the development of meanwhile activities.
Activity Description	<p>Starting from a preliminary framework realized thanks to information collected during previous exploratory activities, data gathering was done through the organization of 2 listening sessions with key actors of the LC and other external actors identified by them as potential stakeholders or beneficiaries of MIND meanwhile uses.</p> <p>Each session lasted 3 hours and involved from 10 to 15 actors clustered per organization type. One session involved MIND tenants and SMEs from the surrounding area, while the other one involved third sector organizations and communities operating in the neighbouring municipalities. Each session aimed at investigating the (potential) role of participants as actors at MIND, relationships (already active or to be activated) with other actors of the ecosystem or to be involved into the ecosystem, needs and interests toward the topics addressed by meanwhile uses (wellbeing, prevention, sustainability, healthy habits, ...) and possible participation in meanwhile activities.</p>
When/Where	<p>Pre-mapping and design of the listening sessions > Jul-Aug 2021</p> <p>Stakeholders' engagement, planning and realization of the sessions > September 2021 and beginning October 2021</p> <p>Map finalization and definition of the Mind Meanwhile Community of Practice > October 2021</p>

	Where > Media Hall at MIND
Activity Providers	Each session was facilitated by 2/3 researchers from Polimi with the support of 2 consultants from PlusValue as Pilot Coordinator.
Participants & Beneficiaries	<p>The activity allowed getting in contact with 2 different groups of stakeholders as potential enablers or beneficiaries of meanwhile uses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Local gatekeepers from the third sector, such as foundations, sport associations, cooperatives, etc. As gatekeepers they have been selected to open the ecosystem to a wider network of stakeholders, since they can provide a wider picture of the local context, especially from a social and cultural point of view. 2. Local representatives/gatekeepers of small and medium enterprises and startups as well as stakeholders that will first arrive on site: the Village tenants. <p>Session 1 - September 23 at MIND Media Hall Fondazione Comunitaria Nord Milano Consorzio Cooperho Altomilanese Cascina Bollate UNIONE sportiva ACLI CSI Comitato di Milano LegaCoop Lombardia Confcooperative Lombardia Fondazione Triulza</p> <p>Session 2 - October 13 at MIND Media Hall Distretto 33 Parolo Group (member of Distretto 33) Fervo (member of Distretto 33) Assolombarda Rold (MIND Tenant) Bio4dreams (MIND Tenant) Tim (MIND Tenant and member of Federated Innovation) CBRE (MIND Village community manager) Cariplo factory (Federated Innovation Catalyst)</p> <p>Individual online session - October 18 Esselunga (MIND Tenant and member of Federated Innovation)</p> <p>Individual online session - October 21 Valore Italia (MIND Tenant)</p>
Insights	In summary, conversations with participants have highlighted that actors from the Third Sector are mainly interested in answering to the needs of local communities from the surroundings through a connection between MIND and social projects already present and

active in the territory. On the one hand, the Third Sector showed concerns regarding the possibility to move specific community services to MIND, mainly due to the lack of accessibility. On the other hand, they have shown particular interest in the need to gather more concrete details to carry out meanwhile activities, such as those related to location and financial aspects. Participants of the first session found it hard to imagine what kind of relationships they could establish with MIND once the site will open. Nonetheless they see opportunities in the participation to meanwhile initiatives in the future.

Most of the participants in the second session were tenants who will start settling in the MIND Village from January or April 2022. Many of them are also members of the Federated Innovation™. Being part of the internal community of MIND they showed high interest in the success of the site activation, including for meanwhile uses. Participants not belonging to the internal community also expressed their interest in getting involved with meanwhile uses at Mind, in continuity with what they already do with other companies in the area.

With relation to the challenges identified by previous exploring and inquiring activities, and in particular that concerning the issue of accessibility to the site, both groups confirmed that MIND currently appears to be a site with significant accessibility problems, especially because at the moment only one access gate has been activated, isolating the area from most of the municipalities surrounding the site. This strongly relates to the need for attractiveness of the area, also highlighted in previous E&I activities. According to participants, working on **attractiveness** could help overcome the problem of accessibility to the site (based on EXPO2015 experience), and they consider meanwhile activities as an opportunity to create a sense of belonging to the site.

The session with tenants and companies revealed interesting projects and contents to be put in place to support the future community of MIND. Some of the companies are supported by strong territorial business ties, while it was revealed that the relations with municipalities other than Milan are quite absent. However, the third sector has a very close network with the surrounding municipalities and with the territory in general with associations and other organizations present in the area.

As for opportunities, what clearly emerged from the 2 sessions is that tenants and companies are willing to put in place their contents to build a wider community at MIND, also sharing the link with their business networks, while those operating in the third sectors represent the key to get access to external subjects and communities. Establishing a connection with these 2 worlds would be thus very much needed to

build a cohesive community of practice that would see them both involved in the planning and deployment of meanwhile uses.

Outputs
 The first activity of each session focused on exploring relationships among participants and other internal and external actors of the MIND ecosystem. What emerged is that the main link of third sector organizations with MIND occurs through Fondazione Triulza and that such organizations are very much connected among them and with the territory in a network that also includes municipalities.

Conversely, many tenants and companies have already activated several relationships within MIND through the Federated Innovation™ initiatives. The companies at the table share the mission and values of MIND and they are very enthusiastic to be part of it. They have high expectations from being part of the area and with respect to the possible activities put into play to activate the internal community and engage the external one. In fact, many of the companies participating in the session declared to have content and experience, especially related to training, that they could share with other actors, not only inside the MIND ecosystem but also with an external audience.

Ecosystem Map Before the Sessions:

Ecosystem Map After the Sessions:

The second activity of each session focused on the exploration of potential meanwhile initiatives, already planned by the participants' organizations or that they could propose at MIND, according to their interests and resources, and of the networks of stakeholders necessary to enact them. In summary, proposals emerging from the two sessions can be clustered under the following categories: health and wellbeing, education and training, environment and biodiversity, agrifood, mobility and sustainability, identity and inclusion. Among them, it can be said that most proposals belong to the education and training category, including ideas that address both to the internal community of

	<p>companies and students, as well as to outside communities of the territory. Also proposals concerning environment and sustainability were numerous, confirming that the area is acknowledged as a field of experimentation and innovation around these topics.</p> <p>In addition to the above-mentioned proposals, some of the participants highlighted possible resources for meanwhile initiatives in terms of thematic contents, spaces, expertise, etc. During the two sessions, participants also identified possible networks of local stakeholders and projects that could be involved for the development of the activity plan.</p> <p>Regarding the involvement of young people in potential activities related to sport, training or education, the participants indicated as actors to be involved: the network of neighbouring oratories, youth centres, training centres and sports centres, but also national associations with which some companies have already done projects (such as Save the Children).</p> <p>Concerning the topic of prevention and health, healthcare centres but also associations carrying out health services in the surrounding area were mentioned.</p>
Outcomes	<p>This activity allowed to start engaging and work with the potential MIND Meanwhile Community of Practice, i.e. the community of actors that could actively participate in the design and implementation of meanwhile spaces and uses. The activity was useful to map the relationships -and consequently the missing connections- between the actors inside and outside the current MIND ecosystem. Overall, the two activity sessions achieved their intended exploration objective. Many new stakeholders were identified and will be involved in the process of designing and co-designing the meanwhile-uses activity plan.</p> <p>In addition, the themes proposed for meanwhile uses were considered interesting by most stakeholders, who in some cases already have potential resources to deploy or networks of other actors to be involved in the following stages of the process.</p> <p>It remains to be understood how the preliminary ideas that emerged from the two sessions can work synergistically to solve the challenges identified by the local coalition and how these issues can be addressed by meanwhile uses in relation to the project objectives.</p>

Guided Tours

Impact domain(s)	<i>Building Communities</i>
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<p>Activity Objectives & related needs</p>	<p>The activity is useful when an industrial area has been closed for many years to the general public, and there is the risk for it to be perceived as an exclusive rather than inclusive area. It tries to involve actors who can help the LC achieve this purpose, while at the same time presenting the future destination of use of the area as well as the masterplan.</p>
<p>Activity Description, including key moments</p>	<p>During E&I station, guided tours were proposed to groups of actors involved in 'Ecosystem Mapping' and extended to their networks up to the organization of one exemplary tour. The tour required registration through an online platform (23 registrations were recorded) and involved approximately 13 people.</p> <p>The tour focused on illustrating the history of the site and the future scenario envisaged by the masterplan, and on introducing key stakeholders of the area, who had the chance to present themselves at dedicated tour stops, guiding visitors into their headquarters (where possible). To do so, such key stakeholders have been actively involved in the production of tour contents. Based on this first experience, other tours, eventually revolving around thematic contents, could then be planned throughout the entire pilot period and constitute prompt meanwhile uses.</p> <p>The Tour Map. Presentations and Canvases Related to this Activity are Attached in "GuidedTour_6.4.2" pdfs.</p>
<p>When/Where</p>	<p>Tour design and planning > September-October 2021 Engagement of guides and communication to audience > October 2021</p>

	<p>Tour production and realization > November 2021 Where > On pilot site</p>
<p>Activity Providers</p>	<p>The tour was designed and organized by the Polimi team, in the role of bridge from the T-Agency, with the support of consultants from PlusValue as Pilot Coordinator. The organization was also supported by Lendlease and MIND anchors (Arexpo, Galeazzi Hospital, Human Technopole and Unimi) in the role of content providers and guides of the different tour stops.</p>
<p>Participants & Beneficiaries</p>	<p>The participants of the ecosystem mapping sessions were first invited to this activity and then the initiative was opened to a larger audience thanks to dedicated communication from Plusvalue, Lendlease and the anchors.</p> <p>The registration form to be filled out for taking part in the tour recorded 23 submissions, 8 from participants of the Ecosystem Mapping sessions or Alternative Mapping activity and 15 from new actors. Among them, 13 actually took part in the tour on November 4th, 2021.</p>
<p>Insights</p>	<p>The activity was useful for consolidating the participants' knowledge and trust in relation to the Local Coalition and for involving new actors, such as "Planet Idea", which showed interest in learning about and possibly contributing to the project.</p> <p>Several actors, who could play the role of gatekeepers for external target groups, found the activity useful to the point of asking if it would be possible to export the format and to propose it to some of their networks in the territory, for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Mayors belonging to the "North West Mayors"; -Cascina Merlata community; -Companies in the D33 network.
<p>Outputs</p>	<p>The activity contributed to weaving together past history and future visions for the site, creating a shared narrative around the site heritage and communicating core values. Also, the active support from the Anchors in the tour helped create a first occasion of exchange between internal and external stakeholders toward the creation of a new perception of MIND, as an open and inclusive area.</p>

Photo credit: Polimi

During the tour participants demonstrated a lot of interest in the proposed contents. They asked several questions during the tour to the representatives of the anchors.

The citizens were glad to have the opportunity to see the site again after Expo and asked many questions about how their development projects will relate to the surrounding area. It was also an opportunity for them to understand what is happening "inside" the area that is not yet perceived from "outside".

Some of the participants working on the territory around MIND, such as representatives of District 33 or Fondazione Housing Sociale, who already took part in Ecosystem Mapping, found the contents of the tour original and very useful to understand the complexity of MIND.

They really appreciated the possibility to meet the representatives of the Anchors and to know in detail the projects and their progress. This finally helped them to perceive the concreteness of the regeneration project.

Moreover, thanks to a final informal networking moment, it was possible to collect expectations and impressions of participants related both to the Guided Tour and regarding ideas for the regeneration of the area through meanwhile initiatives.

In summary, they have suggested to replicate the tour for different target, but also to involve citizens through cycles of events, festivals, "mini-EXPOs", social gatherings, in-depth meetings on urban regeneration issues or on the Anchors' projects, or again, to establish at MIND a place for the third sector (a sort of house of associations) as well as to create a hub for local craft realities.

Outcomes

This activity was an opportunity to directly engage each of the individual actors and their role as part of the ecosystem within MIND. The activity was also effective in terms of engagement, it could be replicated with other target groups.

Alternative Mapping (Probe)

Impact domain(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Building Communities</i> • <i>Making Places</i>
Activity Objectives & related needs	<p>This activity aims at building a shared and alternative mapping of MIND, involving storytelling and community perspectives e.g. about perception and subjective attractiveness of green areas, new uses, accessibility of and to the area, wilderness. Perception by different stakeholders and target groups is especially meaningful when researching in an area where there is not a proper community on site and when the masterplan is changing fast. A community walk and bike ride provide various insights and contribute to start a process of engaging surrounding communities.</p> <p>MIND is perceived as a difficult area to reach by foot or by bike. The purpose of this activity is generating awareness among the neighbouring municipalities regarding the accessibility to the MIND area. The challenge is to perceive and understand the complexity and richness of that territory, exploring vulnerable topics especially about the relation between nature and infrastructure. The objective is to collect impressions, key words, emotions, and feelings of first “pioneers” reaching MIND by foot and bike in order to include multiple perspectives beyond ‘usual suspects’; this data will be expressed in an alternative mapping designed by LAND and used as a community-building tool and as a compass to orienteer possible meanwhile uses on the area.</p>
Activity Description	<p>Both a walk from the city of Rho and a bike ride mainly along the so-called ‘LET 1 e Via d’acqua’ from Garbagnate have been implemented. Walking methodologies help participants to become more aware about places. These methods also strengthen the interpersonal and relational aspects between participants, while helping researchers to better understand citizens’ experience by collecting more information rather than with an interview. A series of stops (stations) and small tasks have been planned according to highlights and important elements to give the group the time to reflect and acknowledge specific topics and to write them on cards. Impressions, information, expectations, feelings, visions and needs collected during the walk/ride are being represented in the alternative mapping outputs, consisting of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. “Placemaking compass”, a visual tool recording the routes, and all the highlights raised by participants for each stop during the walk and ride. All collected datas have been processed by clustering them under relevant topics. 2. Development of an alternative map through the different perspectives of the site from non-mainstreaming stakeholders, which will work as an open canvas informing the possible definition of an online open source platform to be developed during the next stages of TLabs’ activities .

When/Where	<p>Engagement of local associations and target stakeholders > Jul-Sept 2021</p> <p>Implementation of the walks/rides > Sept 25th 2021</p> <p>Postproduction > Oct-Dec 2021</p> <p>Urban Walk: from the city of Rho to MIND (7 Km, around 3 hours).</p> <p>Bike trip: from Garbagnate Groane railway station via Villa Arconati in Bollate and along the Waterway to MIND area (11 Km, around 2,5 hours). This trip is one of the 4 LET (Landscape Expo Tours www.let-milano.com/it/) planned and partially realized to raise awareness about local natural and cultural heritage and to reconnect municipalities surrounding EXPO 2015 with slow mobility routes.</p>
Activity Providers & Stakeholders involved	<p>LAND created the concept of participative site visits, providing methods and tools for people engagement, took care of inviting participants through local associations and public stakeholders within its network. Lendlease was involved in the organization to provide access on the site and took part to the activity. Participants were invited to co-guide the visit themselves to empower their knowledge of places.</p>
Participants & Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adults and young adults • Local residents of the surrounding areas • Milanese residents • Members of local associations • Representative of local institutional public bodies and municipalities
Insights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The activity revealed a high historical value of the path and of the landscape to access MIND and especially the potential of valorizing the memory of the place. Many participants acknowledge the importance of knowing the history in order to better understand the landscape and reading the territory in another way. • Some participants found it very interesting exploring an urban landscape and going in depth on the relation between nature and infrastructure, showing good capabilities of using all the 5 senses to perceive and describe the landscape. This capability can be very important in peer-to-peer education. • A challenge has surely been to walk through and to look at the “bad” or “hugly” parts of the path. Many statements are addressing the topic with a complaining approach. Some of them are, instead, seeing in these areas a potential and writing vision-oriented statements. • Another challenge is the Decumano, defined by participants as a “white canvas” for new public open spaces: concrete, space and huge dimensions are ingredients for thinking of something new.

- The urban ride provides less statements belonging to the cluster “vision”, so it was not possible to order some suggestions in the 3 time horizons. This is linked to the speed of the movement: by cycling our brain is less stimulated than by walking in seeing details or exploring the place itself, because cycling is the main action, and the landscape is perceived more as a whole.

Outputs

- Ongoing stakeholder map: in order to organise the T-Probes and to get to know more the territory, LAND produced a Stakeholder Map later also used for inviting people to the urban walk and the bike-ride. This map is a live working tool.

- Excel sheets managing all the data of the collected opinions written on cards by participants.
- Visual elaboration of these data explaining the main characteristics of each stop on the route, through a clustering process of all the given statements in 6 main clusters.

PARTICIPANTS RESPONSES EXPRESSED THROUGH CLUSTERS - VIEW PER EACH STOP without Emotion / Impression (in absolute numbers)

PARTICIPANTS RESPONSES EXPRESSED THROUGH CLUSTERS PER EACH STOP without cluster EMOTION / IMPRESSION (in absolute numbers)

The “Placemaking compass” as visual tool to support future decisions on meanwhile uses. This image shows: the route and the stops, the main character of each stop, some key words for each stop, and some actions organized by 3 different time horizons suggested by participants.

Urban Walk - Placemaking Compass

Urban ride - Placemaking Compass.

Outcomes

- Networking and territorial cooperation - The activity was a networking opportunity for some stakeholders, showing interest in proposing the same activity for their own community (e.g. Fondazione Housing Sociale) or in proposing new collaborations like some Municipalities or other institutional actors joining specific projects on historical topics (E-Pic Land Project financed by Regional government).
- Suggestion of meanwhile uses - The successful reception by participants showed that urban walks and rides can be a good option of meanwhile use in the future.
- Awareness of places - Citizens have been motivated to learn more about landscape potential in their area and informed about preferred accessibility routes to get to MIND; moreover MIND's stakeholders have become aware of the strengths and weaknesses of local communities by direct experience of **their everyday places**.
- Engagement of stakeholders - The landscape perception and active participation revealed an effective approach to make people think

The Kumu map of all stakeholders is provided in the Figure below and it can be accessed [here](#) in its dynamic fashion.

Missing Stakeholders

As the strategic and practical decision was made to create a first contact point with those local organisations that we consider intermediaries, the net of local stakeholders is still large to explore. This includes smaller local community organisations and volunteer groups, schools and residents.

6.4. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

A number of new insights were gained during the E&I trajectory while others were confirmed from our initial analysis, which underscore our core conclusions below and at the same time allow us to narrow it down our ideation and prototyping trajectory. Generally, MIND Pilot has a clear vision on establishing a meanwhile strategy leveraging on physical and content-based connections with the local area to enhance the development and positive outcomes of the regeneration project.

New Insights Emerged from E&I Activities:

- During the Stakeholder Mapping workshops, three areas of work were explicitly identified which narrows down and provides a clear context for the local coalition's development of meanwhile uses and engagement with local stakeholders :
 - **green, wellbeing and inclusion:** those topics were presented as potential areas of work for meanwhile uses activities and were positively accepted as priorities by the actors involved.
 - **knowledge creation, capacity building and training opportunities,** which includes new skills support to job creation: this targets not only NEETS and young people as identified priority in the local community but also the existing network of SMEs and entrepreneurs.
 - **Innovation and research:** cornerstone of MIND identity and development there is the intention and potential of incredible knowledge sharing across diverse groups.
- A new topic which would connect MIND with the outside (both Milan and the smaller municipalities) is Art and Culture, as found out by informal discussions with stakeholders involved in the Ecosystem Mapping.
- NEETs and young students (from primary school to university) emerged at the convergence of these two areas of work. During the Stakeholders mapping workshops all actors involved agreed on the importance of including and addressing this specific audience as a priority responding to the community's need.
- When planning the Stakeholders mapping workshops, the strategic and practical decision was made to establish a first contact with those local organisations who could act as gatekeeper of a larger network of organisations and groups. The full potential of the MIND stakeholder ecosystem is yet to be explored but that initial mapping exercise allowed to define key entry points, to activate in accordance with the area of work that the local coalition intends to explore for meanwhile uses (eg. sports, art and cultural activities, entrepreneurship and innovation) as well as specific target audience to include.

- As both the Guided Tour and the Alternative Mapping activities were very successful, the MIND Local Coalition is considering implementing them as regular events from spring 2022, prior to MIND Anchors' approval.

General Challenges

- All local stakeholders engaged - both public and private, already or newly engaged, working in the same field of MIND and completely external to it - have demonstrated to share a strong motivation to be part of MIND engagement and meanwhile uses activities. The Ecosystem Mapping sessions highlighted the urgency to leverage this incredible opportunity that the regeneration project will offer not only in the long run but starting from today.
- A strong motivation comes especially from the public stakeholders (municipalities) who experienced negative or irrelevant outcomes from past large scale development projects. Local stakeholders aspire to be a central part in the conversation to maximise the value and impact that MIND will bring to the local communities.
- MIND is still poorly known outside its perimeter and its potential is even less clear to local residents in the surrounding municipalities (Rho, Arese, Bollate).
- The masterplan is still very much evolving which means that confirmation on the specific venues that would become available to run meanwhile activities is still missing or not clear. The local coalition will have to adapt or design activities that could easily change.
- MIND is still very much a construction site with limited or restricted access, which could hamper the development and planning of meanwhile activities. Besides there is very little to show in terms of new buildings, which means we will have to find new and inclusive ways to show what experiencing MIND will look like.
- A number of engagement/meanwhile uses activities already exists or are planned and are for most of them part of a preliminary strategy initiated by Lendlease with the support of T-Factor project. Lendlease is planning a number of activities that will mainly serve the first inhabitants of the Village to create a nicer work environment (street paintings, furniture and leisure areas) but without specifically addressing the community strategy yet. Lendlease is closely working with the Local Coalition to develop it.
- This year MIND Education challenge for university students focus on meanwhile uses, this is to be considered a very positive and successful result of the work done so far in collaboration with local Anchors.
- Engagement strategies, mechanisms, and tools to deliver meanwhile and co-creative and collaborative engagement activities will be clarified and designed in the next weeks.

Next Steps

- As part of the Scoping and Ideating phase a workshop will take place by the end of November with a selection of stakeholders who took part in the ecosystem mapping in the Exploring and Ideation phase. The actors involved will be selected based on their relevance, experience and work in the topics aligned with the directions identified by the Local Coalition.

- T-Factor may contribute to define and test a regulatory sandbox for temporary uses in the city of Milan. Exploring this opportunity during the activation of the site, and taking the issue to the attention of the institutions, is deemed key in order to be able to support both existing and new temporary initiatives, and allow them to develop in a clear, accountable and favourable legal and regulatory environment.
- A first selection of spaces (venues could potentially change during the course of the regeneration or activities will have to be moved because of the regulatory limitations by Milan Municipality on temporary uses) within MIND construction site will have to be identified to plan activities.
- Availability of spaces and timing will have to be confirmed by the developer.
- A funding strategy needs to be defined, together with Lendlease, as well as the identification of relevant partners and sponsors for meanwhile activities.
- The ongoing engagement of actors and stakeholders to be involved in the next months will have to be detailed and structured with the support of the developer, Lendlease, who has a complete overview of the entire regeneration project.

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